

MEMBROS

Manifestação e divulgação do trabalho encetado através da sua apresentação em conferências, congressos e seminários, com consequente publicação dos artigos e indexação a bases de dados acessíveis

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MEMBROS
3

Tese de Doutoramento apresentada à Faculdade de Arquitectura da Universidade do Porto com vista à obtenção do grau de Doutor em Arquitectura com Menção Europeia

PEDRO FONSECA JORGE

Arquitecto, licenciado pela Faculdade de Arquitectura da Universidade do Porto, Mestre em Intervenção no Património Arquitectónico, Doutorando em 'A célula mínima na experiência da habitação de custos controlados', pela mesma instituição.

A CÉLULA MÍNIMA NA EXPERIÊNCIA DA HABITAÇÃO DE CUSTOS CONTROLADOS

Orientação do Professor Associado Doutor Francisco Barata Fernandes

Com os apoios da Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia e da Fundação Luso-Americana

MEMBROS

Manifestação e divulgação do trabalho encetado através da sua apresentação em conferências, congressos e seminários, com consequente publicação dos artigos e indexação a bases de dados acessíveis

1_Curriculum Vitae

2_reHabitat [8] abandono y oportunidad

HABITAR – grupo de investigation de professors/investigadores
Departamento de Proyectos Arquitectónicos
Universidade Politécnica de Cataluña, UPC

Exposição (15 de Junho/29 de Setembro): Sala de la Arqueria de Nuevos Ministerios, Paseo de La Castellana 67, Madrid

3_reHabitat [7] entrar por el balcón

HABITAR – grupo de investigation de professors/investigadores
Departamento de Proyectos Arquitectónicos
Universidade Politécnica de Cataluña, UPC

Exposição (15 de Junho/29 de Setembro): Sala de la Arqueria de Nuevos Ministerios, Paseo de La Castellana 67, Madrid

4_‘The idea of the City in the Social Housing experience throughout the past century: scale, shape and extent’

ENHR 2011 ‘Mixité’: an urban and housing issue?

Toulouse, França, 5 a 8 de Julho de 2011

5_‘The Minimum Cell as a House: ideas and forms in social housing in search of a Home’

NHR Day *Journée Jeunes Chercheurs, New Housing Researchers’ Day*

Toulouse, França, 4 a 5 de Julho de 2011

6_‘O Mínimo como Dinâmico’

1.º CIHEL *Congresso Internacional (da) Habitação no Espaço Lusófono*

Lisboa, Portugal, Setembro de 2010

7_‘The Minimum Cell: Family and households in new housing proposals’

ENHR 2010 *Urban Dynamics & Housing Change*

Istambul, Turquia, Julho de 2010

8_‘The Minimum Cell: criteria for minimum housing studies’

NHR *New Housing Researchers 2010 Colloquium*

Istambul, Turquia, Julho de 2010

9_‘History is not just stories: a proposal for an operative use of popular architectural heritage’

Heritage 2010 *Greenlines Institute*

Évora, Portugal, Junho de 2010

10_ ‘The Minimum Cell – minimum housing standards: Minimum as Maximum’

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ARTS AND SCIENCES *International Conference for Academic Disciplines*

Orlando, Florida, Estados Unidos, Março de 2010

11_ ‘The Minimum Cell – minimum housing standards: Minimum as Maximum’

INTERDISCIPLINARY THEMES

Vancouver, Canadá, Novembro de 2009

CURRICULUM VITAE

PEDRO
FONSECA
JORGE
Arquitecto

Informação pessoal

Pedro FONSECA JORGE

Avenida da Igreja, n.º 32, 1.º andar, 2475-100 Benedita, Portugal

+351 91 873 30 99

egrojordep@gmail.com

www.pfj-arq.blogspot.com

Nacionalidade Portuguesa

Nascido a 05/01/1977

Formação académica e profissional

1 de Outubro / 30 de Novembro de 2011

Nome e tipo da organização de ensino
ou formação

Orientação

Competências profissionais

Local de Internet

Estagiário de Doutoramento

Colaboração no Grupo de Investigação '**Proyecto, Progreso y Arquitectura**'

Investigador no âmbito da execução da Tese de Doutoramento: '**A célula mínima na experiência da habitação de custos controlados**'

Escola Superior Técnica Superior de Arquitectura, Universidad de Sevilla, Reina Mercedes, 2. 41012 Sevilla

Doutora Arquitecta Rosa Añon Abajas (Escola Superior Técnica Superior de Arquitectura)

Investigador no âmbito da publicação de arquitectura de artigos revistos por comité científico 'Proyecto, Progreso y Arquitectura, número 6. montajes habitados: vivienda, prefabricación e intención / inhabited ready-mades: housing, prefab and aim'

<http://www.proyectoprogresoarquitectura.com/>

1 de Abril de 2011 / 30 de Junho de 2011

Nome e tipo da organização de ensino
ou formação

Orientação

Competências profissionais

Local de Internet

Designação da qualificação atribuída

Estagiário de Doutoramento Europeu

Colaboração no Grupo de Investigação '**Habitar**'

Investigador no âmbito da execução da Tese de Doutoramento: '**A célula mínima na experiência da habitação de custos controlados**'

Escola Superior Técnica d'Arquitectura del Vallès, Universidad Politècnica de Catalunya, Sant Cugat del Vallès, Edifici SC2. C/ Pere Serra, 1-15. 08173 Sant Cugat del Vallès

Professora Jubilada Doutora Magda Mària (Escola Superior Técnica d'Arquitectura del Vallès)

Investigador no âmbito do projecto 'reHabitat', exposições [7]: 'entrar por el balcón', e [8]: 'abandono y oportunidad' (abertura dia 6 de Julho na Sala Arquería de Nuevos Ministerios ,Madrid)

Ministerios ,Madrid)

<http://www.rehabitar.blogspot.com/>

Título de Doutoramento Europeu (no final do projecto de investigação – 2011)

Janeiro de 2008 até à presente data

Doutorando em Arquitectura

Tese de Doutoramento: '**A célula mínima na experiência da habitação de custos controlados**'

PEDRO
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JORGE
Arquitecto

Nome e tipo da organização de ensino ou formação

Orientação

Competências profissionais

Designação da qualificação atribuída

Setembro de 2003 a Novembro de 2005

Nome e tipo da organização de ensino ou formação

Orientação

Competências profissionais

Designação da qualificação atribuída

Classificação obtida

Setembro de 1995 a Setembro de 2001

Nome e tipo da organização de ensino ou formação

Competências profissionais

Designação da qualificação atribuída

Classificação obtida

Faculdade de Arquitectura da Universidade do Porto (FAUP), Via Panorâmica S/N, 4150-755 Porto

Doutor Francisco Barata Fernandes (Faculdade de Arquitectura da Universidade do Porto) Investigador/Especialista no ramo do Espaço Habitável em Habitação Social ou de Custos Controlados

Doutor Arquitecto (no final do projecto de investigação – 2011)

Mestre em Metodologias de Intervenção no Património Arquitectónico

Dissertação de Mestrado: **'A casa rural no Concelho de Alcobaça em 1961: da teorização Erudita à prática Popular'**

Faculdade de Arquitectura da Universidade do Porto (FAUP), Via Panorâmica S/N, 4150-755 Porto

Doutora Marieta Dá Mesquita (Faculdade de Arquitectura da Universidade Técnica de Lisboa) Investigador/Especialista no ramo da Intervenção/Recuperação do Património Arquitectónico Mestre Arquitecto

Muito Bom

Licenciado em Arquitectura

Prova Final de Conclusão de Licenciatura: **'Alguns dos Processos de Transformação da Casa Rural da Região de Alcobaça'**

Faculdade de Arquitectura da Universidade do Porto (FAUP), Via Panorâmica S/N, 4150-755 Porto

Prática profissional no Domínio da Arquitectura e Urbanismo; Especialista/Investigador no campo da Habitação Rural Unifamiliar

Arquitecto

16 (Licenciatura)

18 (Prova Final); orientação: Doutor Francisco Barata Fernandes, Faculdade de Arquitectura da Universidade do Porto

Associações Profissionais

OASRS – Ordem dos Arquitectos, Secção Regional Sul, Travessa do Carvalho, 23, 1249-003 Lisboa
Membro número 11229, desde 2001

European Network for Housing Research, OTB Research Institute for the Built Environment, Technical University Delft, P.O. Box 5030, 2600 GA Delft, The Netherlands (<http://www.enhr.net/>)
Membro desde 2010

Experiência no Domínio Teórico Arquitectónico

Caleidoscópio- Edição e Artes Gráficas, SA, Rua de Estrasburgo, 26, R/C Direito, 2605-756, Casal de Cambra

Editora de Publicações de Arquitectura

Crítico/Teórico de Arquitectura

Desenvolvimento de textos de Opinião e Crítica de Arquitectura, a saber:

'Á saúde de Celestino de Castro', periódico 'Arquitectura Ibérica n.º 28 - Saúde', Setembro de 2008, ISBN: 978-989-8129-75-8

'Uso, desuso, com algum abuso incluso', livro 'Anuário de Arquitectura XI', 2008, ISBN: 978-

Nome e endereço do empregador

Tipo de empresa ou sector

Função ou cargo ocupado

Principais actividades e responsabilidades

[RE] HABITAR
[RE] HABITAR
#020

PEDRO
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Arquitecto

Ilustração em 'A profissão do Arquitecto'

Arq.º Camillo Botticini e a sua equipa

989-8129-63-5

'**Arquitectura é paisagem**', livro 'Anuário de Arquitectura XI', 2008, ISBN: 978-989-8129-63-5

'**A História não são estórias**', periódico '**Arquitectura Ibérica n.º 27 - Habitar**', Setembro de 2008, ISBN: 978-989-8129-66-6

'**O Alibi**', livro '**Casas Recuperadas II**', 2008, ISBN: 978-989-8129-46-8

'**A profissão do Arquitecto**', periódico '**Arquitectura Ibérica n.º 23 - Equipamento**', Dezembro de 2007, ISBN: 978-989-8129-28-4

'**O Novo Passado**', periódico '**Arquitectura Ibérica n.º 20 – Re-habitar**', Maio 2007, ISBN: 978-989-8011-??-?

'**Função e representação**', livro '**24 casas**', 2006, ISBN: 978-989-8010-39-1

'**O espectador na Arquitectura**', periódico '**Arquitectura Ibérica n.º 16 – Habitar**', Outubro de 2006, ISBN: 978-989-8010-33-9

Revisão da tradução portuguesa da entrevista realizada por Stefano Ferracini ao arquitecto Camillo Botticini (disponível em: www.vitruvius.com.br/entrevista/botticini)

Colaboração, sob a coordenação do Arq. Eurico Salgado dos Santos, na **execução de artigos relativos a monografias de arquitectos**, para a **DICIOPÉDIA**, edição de 2003, da Porto Editora.

Participação em Conferências e Seminários

Artigo

Entidade Organizadora

23rd ENHR Conference 2011 - 'Mixité' : an urban and housing issue ?

Toulouse, França, 5 a 8 de Julho de 2011

<http://www.enhr2011.com>

'**The idea of the City in the Social Housing experience throughout the past century: scale, shape and extent**'

ENHR - European Network for Housing Research, OTB Research Institute for the Built Environment, Technical University Delft, P.O. Box 5030, 2600 GA Delft, The Netherlands
LISST (Interdisciplinary Laboratory on Solidarities Societies Territories), National Center for Scientific Research (CNRS) and the University of Toulouse-Le Mirail

Artigo

Entidade Organizadora

Journée Jeunes Chercheurs, New Housing Researchers' Day (NHR Day)

Toulouse, França, 4 de Julho de 2011

<http://www.enhr2011.com/node/38>

'**The Minimum Cell as a House: ideas and forms in social housing in search of a Home**'

ENHR - European Network for Housing Research, OTB Research Institute for the Built Environment, Technical University Delft, P.O. Box 5030, 2600 GA Delft, The Netherlands
LISST (Interdisciplinary Laboratory on Solidarities Societies Territories), National Center for Scientific Research (CNRS) and the University of Toulouse-Le Mirail

Artigo

Entidade Organizadora

1.º CIHEL – Congresso Internacional (da) Habitação no Espaço Lusófono,

Lisboa, Portugal, Setembro de 2010

<http://cihel01.wordpress.com/about/>

'**O Mínimo como Dinâmico**'

1º CIHEL ISCTE-IUL, Av. das Forças Armadas, Ala Autónoma, Sala 335 1649-026 Lisboa
<http://cihel01.wordpress.com/>

Urban Dynamics & Housing Change, ENHR 2010, 22nd Conference,

Istanbul, Turquia, Julho de 2010

<http://www.enhr2010.com/>

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Artigo

'The Minimum Cell: Family and households in new housing proposals'

(http://enhr2010.com/fileadmin/templates/ENHR2010_papers_web/papers_web/WS06/WS06_375_Jorge.pdf)

Entidade Organizadora

ENHR - European Network for Housing Research, Institute for Housing and Urban Research Uppsala University, P.O. Box 785, SE-801 29 GÄVLE, Sweden
<http://www.enhr.ibf.uu.se/index.html>

NHR2010
COLLOQUIUM
ISTANBUL
2-3 JULY 2010

Artigo

NHR - New Housing Researchers 2010 Colloquium, Istanbul, Turquia, Julho de 2010

<http://www.nhr2010.com/index.html>

Entidade Organizadora

'The Minimum Cell: criteria for minimum housing studies'

ENHR - European Network for Housing Research, Institute for Housing and Urban Research Uppsala University, P.O. Box 785, SE-801 29 GÄVLE, Sweden
<http://www.enhr.ibf.uu.se/index.html>

Artigo

Heritage 2010, Évora, Portugal, Junho de 2010

<http://heritage2010.greenlines-institute.org/H2010website/home.html>

Entidade Organizadora

'History is not just stories: a proposal for an operative use of

popular architectural heritage', publicado em: Lira, Sérgio; Amoêda, Rogério; Pinheiro, Cristina (Editors); 2010, **'Heritage 2010 – Heritage and Sustainable Development – Vol. 2'**, pages 1373-1382, Green Lines Institute for Sustainable Development, ISBN 978-989-95671-3-9

Green Lines Institute for Sustainable Development, Av. Alcaldes de Faria, 377 S.12 4750-106 Barcelos, Portugal

http://www.greenlines-institute.org/greenlines-institute/pt/pt_home.html

Artigo

International Conference for Academic Disciplines, Orlando, Florida, Estados Unidos, Março de 2010

<http://www.internationaljournal.org/orlando.html>

Entidade Organizadora

'The Minimum Cell – minimum housing standards: Minimum as

Maximum', vencedor do **'Best Paper Award'**, atribuído pela entidade organizadora (disponível em: http://openaccesslibrary.org/images/RLN165_Pedro_Fonseca_Jorge.pdf)

International Journal of Arts and Sciences, 99 Sleepy Hollow Drive, Cumberland, RI 02864-3236, USA

<http://www.internationaljournal.org/>

Apoios

FLAD – Fundação Luso-Americana para o Desenvolvimento, Rua Sacramento à Lapa, 21 1249-090 Lisboa, Portugal
www.flad.pt

Artigo

'Interdisciplinary Themes – The City: Culture, Society, Technology',

Vancouver, British Columbia, Canadá, Novembro de 2009

<http://www.interdisciplinarythemes.org/journal/index.php/itj/index>

Entidade Organizadora

'Mending the City Fabric', ISSN: 1920-3241

(disponível em: <http://www.interdisciplinarythemes.org/journal/index.php/itj/issue/current>)

Interdisciplinary Themes Journal, P.O. Box 33045, Cathedral Post Office, Regina, SK, Canada

<http://www.interdisciplinarythemes.org/journal/index.php/itj/index>

Artigo

'Seminário de Estudos Urbanos – Vazios Úteis', Lisboa, Setembro 2007

<http://seu2007.saau.iscte.pt/>

'Cezir a Cidade'

(disponível em: http://seu2007.saau.iscte.pt/Actas/Actas_SEU2007.html)

PEDRO
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Arquitecto

Entidade Organizadora

Departamento de Arquitectura e Urbanismo, ISCTE – Instituto Superior de Ciências do Trabalho e da Empresa, Av. das Forças Armadas, 1649-026 Lisboa, Portugal
<http://iscte.pt/>

Ano Lectivo 2000/2001
Nome e endereço do empregador
Tipo de empresa ou sector
Função ou cargo ocupado
Principais actividades e responsabilidades

Experiência Pedagógica Profissional

Monitor da Disciplina de Projecto II

Faculdade de Arquitectura da Universidade do Porto (FAUP)

Estabelecimento Público de Ensino

Monitor

Acompanhamento do desenvolvimento dos trabalhos de Projecto II a nível de concepção e apoio técnico de alunos do curso de Arquitectura

Outubro de 2003 até à presente data
Nome e endereço
Tipo de empresa ou sector
Função ou cargo ocupado
Principais actividades e responsabilidades

Gabinete Particular de Arquitectura

Pedro Fonseca Jorge, Arquitecto, Av.ª da Igreja, n.º 32, 1.º andar, 2474-100, Benedita

Gabinete de Projectos de Arquitectura e Urbanismo

Projectista

Concepção/ elaboração de projectos de arquitectura e urbanismo nas suas diversas fases, a saber:

Casa na Cruz de Oliveira, (ampliação), Benedita
Estudo Prévio; Licenciamento

Casa no Baleal, Peniche
Estudo Prévio

Casas no Baleal, Loteamento e Arquitectura, Peniche
Estudo Prévio

Casas no Figueiral, Loteamento e Arquitectura, Benedita
Estudo Prévio

Casas na Avenida, Loteamento e Arquitectura, Benedita
Estudo Prévio

Casa no Taveiro, Benedita
Estudo Prévio; Licenciamento; Projecto de Execução; Acompanhamento de Obra; Construída

Casa n' A-da-Gorda, (reconstrução e ampliação), A-da-Gorda, Óbidos
Estudo Prévio; Licenciamento; Projecto de Execução; Acompanhamento de Obra; Construída

Casa em Gouveva, Gaia
Estudo Prévio; Licenciamento; Projecto de Execução; Acompanhamento de Obra; Construída

Bungalow Effort, sistemas de pré-fabricação em Betão e Fibra de Vidro
Estudo Prévio; Projecto de Execução

Quinta Nova, (reconstrução e ampliação - turismo rural e eventos), Benedita
Estudo Prévio

Casa na Cruz de Oliveira – Moradia Evolutiva, Benedita
Estudo Prévio; Licenciamento; Projecto de Execução; Acompanhamento de Obra; Construída

(Publicada na revista 'New Generation: Arquitectos - Architetti under 40, Porto (Portugal) / Pisa (Italia)', n.º 2/2008, da colecção "Biblioteca Architetture" da editora 'Edizioni ETS')

Casa no Taveiro

Casa n'A-da-Gorda

Casa em Gouveva

Casa na Cruz de Oliveira

PEDRO
FONSECA
JORGE
Arquitecto

Casa no Figueiral

Casa Evolutiva n.º 2

Casa Evolutiva n.º 1

Edifício de Habitação Plurifamiliar na Rua dos Machados

Participação em Concursos de Arquitectura

'Unbuilt Architecture'

Prémios

'Lancia PI (3.14)'; exposição em Turim

Janeiro de 2011 até Agosto 2011
Nome e endereço do empregador
Tipo de empresa ou sector
Função ou cargo ocupado

PEDRO
FONSECA
JORGE
Arquitecto

Casa no Figueiral, Benedita

Estudo Prévio; Licenciamento; Projecto de Execução; Acompanhamento de Obra; Construída

(Publicada no n.º 23 da revista 'Arquitectura Ibérica', Dezembro de 2007 - ISBN: 978-989-8129-28-4 - no texto 'A profissão do Arquitecto')

Casa no Algarão, Benedita

Estudo Prévio; Licenciamento; Projecto de Execução; Acompanhamento de Obra; Construída

Herdade de Montalto, (reconstrução e ampliação - turismo rural e eventos), Castelo Branco

Estudo Prévio

Edifício Hoechst (renovação de interiores), Porto

Estudo Prévio

Casa Evolutiva n.º 2 – Moradia Evolutiva

Estudo Tipológico de cariz teórico-prático

Casa Evolutiva n.º 1 – Moradia Evolutiva

Estudo Tipológico de cariz teórico-prático

Módulo de Topo – Edifício de Habitação Colectiva

Estudo Tipológico de cariz teórico-prático

Edifício de Habitação Plurifamiliar na Rua 8/6, Benedita

Estudo Prévio

Edifício de Habitação Plurifamiliar na Rua dos Machados, Benedita

Estudo Prévio; Licenciamento; Projecto de Execução

'Unbuilt Architecture' (projectos de arquitectura não construídos ou teórico-práticos de reflexão), Boston Society of Architects; Projecto: 'Band-Aid Building'

'Primeiro Concurso Arkinka de Habitação' (Novas Soluções para a Habitação Social), Arkinka – Revista de Arquitectura, Peru

'Concurso de Ideias para a Reabilitação do Mercado Municipal de Cascais', (reabilitação/ampliação com novos usos), Câmara Municipal de Cascais

'Concurso Público para a Elaboração do Projecto de Remodelação do Edifício Sede da Delegação do Algarve da Ordem dos Arquitectos em Faro' (reabilitação/ampliação de edifício existente)

'Europar 7, o Desafio das Periferias – Tercena, Oeiras' (reabilitação/adaptação a novos usos e projecto complementar de habitação colectiva)

'Best Paper Award', atribuído pela International Journal of Arts and Sciences, no âmbito da International Conference for Academic Disciplines, Março de 2010

Menção Honrosa no Concurso 'My Renault', no âmbito da Experimenta Design, em outubro de 2003, com o projecto 'Renault Twingo'

Prémio de Melhor Interior, da Associação de Design Italiana (ADI), no concurso para Jovem Designer, promovido pela Associação Nacional de Fabricantes Italianos de Automóveis, na edição de 2002, com o projecto 'Lancia PI (3.14)'

Experiência profissional

Colaborador

Hélia Pires e Valeria Merola, Alcobça

Gabinete de Projectos de Arquitectura e Urbanismo

Colaborador

Principais actividades e responsabilidades

Casa em Lameira

Julho de 2006 até à presente data

Nome e endereço do empregador

Tipo de empresa ou sector

Função ou cargo ocupado

Principais actividades e responsabilidades

Loteamento de St.ª Rufina

Outubro de 2003 a Dezembro de 2004

Nome e endereço do empregador

Tipo de empresa ou sector

Função ou cargo ocupado

Principais actividades e responsabilidades

Jazigo de Família em Cortegaça

Fevereiro 2000 a Agosto 2000

Setembro 2000 a Março de 2001

Abril de 2001 a Setembro de 2003

Nome e endereço do empregador

Tipo de empresa ou sector

PEDRO
FONSECA
JORGE
Arquitecto

Responsável pelo Acompanhamento de Obra

Casa em Lameira, Alcobça
Acompanhamento de Obra

Colaborador a tempo parcial

Rita Zina, Arquitecta, A-da-Gorda, Óbidos

Gabinete de Projectos de Arquitectura e Urbanismo

Colaborador/Projectista

Concepção/ elaboração de projectos de arquitectura e urbanismo nas suas diversas fases, a saber:

Casa Paulo Félix, Óbidos

Estudo Prévio

Casa Rita Zina, A-da-Gorda, Óbidos

Estudo Prévio

Loteamento de St.ª Rufina – Projectos de Arquitectura, Arelho, Óbidos

Estudo Prévio; Licenciamento; Projecto de Execução

Colaborador a tempo parcial

Homevision – Arquitectura e Design, Lda., Av.º 8, 1054, Espinho

Gabinete de Projectos de Arquitectura e Urbanismo

Colaborador/Projectista

Concepção/ elaboração de projectos de arquitectura e urbanismo nas suas diversas fases, a saber:

Joalheria 'Cleópatra', (projecto de interiores), Suil Park, S. João de Ver

Projecto de Execução; Construída

'Homevision 2', (projecto de interiores), Porto

Estudo Prévio; Projecto de Execução; Acompanhamento de Obra; Construída;
Desenvolvimento da Linha Gráfica

Restaurante 'Temperos', (projecto de interiores), Espinho

Estudo Prévio; Projecto de Execução; Construído; Desenho do Logótipo

Jazigo de Família, Cortegaça

Estudo Prévio; Projecto de Execução; Construído

Edifício de Habitação Plurifamiliar na Rua 33, Espinho

Estudo Prévio

Salão de Festas, Grijó, Porto

Estudo Prévio

Edifício de Habitação Plurifamiliar na Rua 12, Espinho

Estudo Prévio

Colaborador a tempo parcial

Estágio Curricular

Colaborador a tempo inteiro

Francisco Barata Fernandes & Madalena Pinto da Silva, Arquitectura Lda.,
Praça da Corujeira, n.º 54, 4300-144 Porto

Gabinete de Projectos de Arquitectura e Urbanismo

Função ou cargo ocupado
Principais actividades e responsabilidades

Casa Paulo Gonçalves

Quinta da Carreira

Quinta Marques Gomes, GaiaPolis

Castelo da Feira – Torre de menagem

Colaborador/Projectista

Concepção/ elaboração de projectos de arquitectura e urbanismo nas suas diversas fases, a saber:

Quinta do Sameiro (recuperação e ampliação), Guimarães
Estudo Prévio; Licenciamento

Casa Madeira Campos (reconstrução e ampliação), Porto
Revisão de Licenciamento; Projecto de Execução

Casa Madeira Campos – Anexo, Porto
Estudo Prévio; Licenciamento; Projecto de Execução

Casa António Paiva, Gaia
Projecto de Execução

Casa Paulo Gonçalves - Piscina Coberta, Vizela
Aditamento ao Licenciamento; Revisão do Projecto de Execução; Acompanhamento de Obra; Construída

Casa Paulo Gonçalves (recuperação e ampliação), Vizela
Revisão do Projecto de Execução; Acompanhamento de Obra; Construída
(Publicada na 3ª edição da Revista 'Páginas Brancas', 2009, Publicações FAUP, pág. 80-81)

Edifício de Habitação Colectiva I, Vila das Aves
Estudo Prévio; Pedido de Informação Prévia

Edifício de Habitação Colectiva II, Vila das Aves
Estudo Prévio; Pedido de Informação Prévia

Edifício de Habitação Colectiva III, Vila das Aves
Estudo Prévio; Pedido de Informação Prévia

Quinta da Carreira – Casa Principal (reconstrução e ampliação), Vizela
Projecto de Execução; Acompanhamento de Obra; Construída

Quinta da Carreira – Anexos (Piscina Coberta, Cozinha Exterior, Sequeiro)
Estudo Prévio; Projecto de Execução; Acompanhamento de Obra; Construídos

Gaiapólis: Concurso para a Concepção do Plano de Pormenor para a área de S. Paio e Canidelo, Gaia

Porto 2001: Projecto de Requalificação Urbana da Rua do Almada, Praça Filipa de Lencastre, Rua de Ceuta e Envolvente da Cadeia da Relação
Fase Final do Projecto de Execução; Construído

Casa Crisóstomo, Pombal
Fase Final do Projecto de Execução; Construída

Castelo da Feira, Santa Maria da Feira – Requalificação da Torre de Menagem
Fase Final do Projecto de Execução; Construída

Praça Sandeman, Gaia
Fase Final do Projecto de Execução; Construída

reHabitat [8] abandono y oportunidad

**HABITAR – grupo de investigation de
professors/investigadores
Departamento de Proyectos Arquitectónicos
Universidade Politècnica de Catalunya, UPC**

Exposição (15 de Junho/29 de Setembro)

<http://www.rehabitar.blogspot.com/>

rehabitar

abandono y oportunidad [8]

Este episodio se propone observar los edificios desocupados y en estado de abandono como oportunidades que permitan revitalizar la ciudad desde su interior, ensayando alternativas al derribo e incorporando nuevos usos, como la vivienda, para lo cual se cuestionan las operaciones necesarias para reactivarlos.

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Ministro de Fomento

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Cristina Thomas Hernández

Directora General de Arquitectura y Política de Vivienda

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En portada: Casa-estudio en un almacén transformado (Londres, 1994).

Adam Caruso y Peter St. John, arquitectos.

Imagen: Hélène Binet

En su continua transformación y expansión, las ciudades dejan en su interior un conjunto heterogéneo de edificaciones que no mantienen el ritmo vital del tejido del que forman parte. En algunos casos, se trata de situaciones aisladas fruto de condiciones muy particulares. En otros casos, sin embargo, estas condiciones afectan a un ámbito urbano en el que los cambios económicos o sociales han dejado numerosos edificios en desuso. Con el final brusco del último ciclo de la construcción, se han sumado a éstas otras situaciones de abandono de edificios todavía inacabados que deberían ser, por sí mismas, motivo de una reflexión en profundidad, como la que incita la mirada crítica del fotógrafo Stanley Wong en la serie *Lan Wei* (2006), que podríamos traducir como ‘inacabados’.

Disponibilidad

Es difícil establecer una estadística clara de edificios en desuso, a no ser que se trate de una situación especialmente relevante, como la que vive el área metropolitana de Barcelona, con un 14% de los edificios de oficinas vacíos en 2011, lo que equivale a unos 820.000 metros cuadrados¹. Es también el caso de Lisboa, con unos 4.000 inmuebles de

1. Pellicer, L.: “Barcelona acumula más de 820.000 metros cuadrados de oficinas vacías”. *El País*, 19 de enero de 2011.

"Fly Away". Fotografía de la serie *Lan Wei (Inacabado)*, de Stanley Wong (2006).
Destilería abandonada.(www.abandonalia.com)

vivienda abandonados –más de un 7%– resultado de una disminución significativa de su población².

En otras muchas situaciones, se trata de equipamientos desmantelados; edificios de oficinas, hoteles o centros sanitarios obsoletos; estructuras agrícolas abandonadas; cárceles, construcciones escolares y religiosas cerradas; instalaciones militares trasladadas; infraestructuras para el transporte o antiguas fábricas y almacenes engullidos por el crecimiento urbano sobre los que no siempre se dispone de cifras absolutas.

2. Datos de 2008, publicados en Relea, F.: “Lisboa, la capital del vacío”. *El País*, 1 de agosto de 2010.

Transformación de la nave Boetticher, Madrid, según propuesta de José María Churtichaga y Joaquín Lizasoain de 2006, en construcción.

Naves 8 y 9 del antiguo Matadero municipal, Madrid, transformadas por Arturo Franco y Juan Arregui, 2008.
www.mataderomadrid.org

Algunas redes sociales y sitios web ven en ellos paisajes postindustriales que se prestan a ser retratados en su desolación, lo que permite hacerse una idea de la cantidad y variedad de edificios que se encuentran en esa misma situación³. Sin embargo, nuestro punto de vista está cambiando y comenzamos a observar estos casos como oportunidades.

De entre todos estos edificios, la ciudad recupera una parte para instalar nuevos equipamientos, con usos mayoritariamente culturales. Como dato revelador, de las 100 actuaciones urbanas destacadas por el Ayuntamiento de Barcelona en 2011, 17 se sitúan en edificios transformados y, de éstos, 13 corresponden a instituciones culturales, 3 a la educación y uno solo a vivienda pública⁴.

En casos concretos, la administración desarrolla incluso programas a medida de la singularidad del edificio, como sucede en Madrid con la antigua nave Boetticher, en la que actualmente se construye un centro de nuevas tecnologías TIC o, anteriormente, con el Matadero municipal, reconvertido en un espacio para la creación artística contemporánea (2008), a imagen de otros muchos complejos industriales en toda Europa. En estos casos, la disponibilidad es el desencadenante del proceso.

3. Sitios como www.abandonalia.blogspot.com en España o www.telefunkner.be en el ámbito europeo.

4. Exposición *Barcelona Direccions*, junio de 2011. (www.bcn.cat/barcelonadireccions).

Robert Motherwell en su barracón *Quonset* adaptado en Long Island (1946).

Fotografía de Hans Namuth, 1950.

Aristide Antonas, albergue móvil, 2009.

www.aristideantonas.com

Aprovechamiento

A la vista de estos y otros ejemplos, puede argumentarse una cierta cultura del aprovechamiento que vincula la necesidad de nuevos equipamientos con la existencia de edificios en desuso y de interés arquitectónico o histórico, normalmente incluidos en el catálogo del patrimonio. Sin embargo, también puede interpretarse como una evidencia de la escasez de otros programas distintos al equipamiento y de la falta de iniciativas para reutilizar los edificios comunes que no forman parte del conjunto de bienes protegidos. Sólo cuando se cumplan ambas condiciones tendrá pleno sentido hablar de una cultura del aprovechamiento.

En este sentido, la vivienda-estudio habilitada por Pierre Chareau para el pintor Robert Motherwell en el interior de un barracón militar del tipo *Quonset* (Long Island, 1946) o el albergue móvil proyectado por el arquitecto ateniense Aristide Antonas en un autobús de dos pisos

Imágenes del libro *Small buildings and other informal structures underneath Tokyo railway viaducts*.

Tiendas bajo el viaducto de la Avenida Daumesnil en París y en Savignyplatz, Berlín.

(2009) son ejemplos muy diversos de aprovechamiento capaces de dar con una solución atractiva a partir de un material corriente que se halla disponible.

Es lo que sucede en muchas ciudades en las que existe un viaducto u otra infraestructura comparable. Ejemplos como Tokio, París, Berlín o Évora en Portugal, por citar tan sólo algunos casos, ofrecen imágenes de cómo aprovechar estas infraestructuras para dar cobijo a usos diversos, desde la vivienda hasta el almacén, la tienda y las combinaciones entre ellos. El viaducto aporta estabilidad estructural, además de la cubierta y algunas paredes, de modo que la construcción *huésped* tan sólo debe subdividir la altura y cerrar las fachadas.

Apartamentos en un antiguo almacén en Shepherdess Walk, Londres, de Buschow Henley + Partners.

Quaderns d'arquitectura i urbanisme. nº 227, 2000

Edificio de oficinas (Yves Lion, 1994-96) reciclado en vivienda.

Imágenes: Jean-Marie Monthiers, *AV Monografías*. nº 67, 1997.

Aún hoy, existe la creencia que derribar y construir de nuevo es más económico y proporciona mejores resultados que aprovechar. En términos de huella de carbono es más que discutible. Si reúnen unas mínimas condiciones, “la reutilización de edificios existentes es en sí misma una estrategia sostenible en la conservación de la energía incorporada en la fábrica construida”, tal como sostienen los arquitectos Buschow Henley, autores de algunas obras de reciclaje que agrupan bajo el lema de *Adaptive Reuse* (<http://www.hhbr.co.uk>).

Otro modo de uso

La clave para rehabilitar edificios vacíos u obsoletos se encuentra en la manera de usarlos de nuevo. No se trata simplemente de utilizar su estructura o sus cerramientos como base para una nueva actuación, sino de concebir una habitabilidad distinta que incida sobre las nociones de confort, gestione adecuadamente sus limitaciones y permita cuestionar ciertos aspectos de la normativa general en esta materia.

Rehabilitar estos edificios significa descubrir y potenciar sus cualidades intrínsecas –aquéllas que dependen de las características materiales, espaciales y perceptivas del edificio– y poder asignar esas cualidades a nuevos usos que sean reflejo de la complejidad de la propia sociedad: programas que contemplan la vivienda, o que la mezclan con el trabajo, en sus más variadas

Una fiesta en *The Silver Factory*, con
Andy Warhol al fondo.
Imagen: Jon Naar, 1965.

Primera planta del *loft* de Donald Judd
en el 101 de Spring Street, Nueva York.
Imagen: Todd Eberle

facetas; otras fórmulas de habitar como residencias y hoteles o bien propuestas que intercalan programas distintos en las plantas bajas y en las cubiertas.

En la historia doméstica del siglo XX, el *loft* ha demostrado que es posible replantear la forma de habitar un espacio, cuando las características de partida no son las de una vivienda convencional. Con este término, se designa la mínima adecuación de un espacio, normalmente industrial, para ser habitado en un sentido amplio. Podemos encontrar ejemplos de *lofts* en el barrio berlinés de Kreuzberg en los años 60 y 70, ocupados por

comunidades de jóvenes, o bien en Nueva York, en esa misma época, donde artistas como Andy Warhol o Donald Judd trasladan su actividad creativa y social. A ellos se sumarán, a finales de los 70, numerosos artistas organizados entorno a Gordon Matta-Clark, transformando la zona industrial del SoHo, entonces prácticamente abandonada, en un centro de experimentación artística.

El interés de estos ejemplos reside en la fórmula utilizada para ocupar de nuevo sus espacios. Por una parte, no se pretende eliminar las huellas del paso del tiempo. Por otra, el nuevo uso no impone esquemas preestablecidos, sino que reconoce en esos espacios fabriles desocupados un potencial para plantear otros modos de vida y, con ellos, otras maneras de materializarlos que no serían posibles en circunstancias distintas. Es justamente ese potencial, y no su aspecto, lo que nos interesa de estos espacios.

Dos arquitectos tan distantes como Josef Frank y Kees Christiaanse coinciden en plantear cuestiones similares. En un texto de 2001, titulado significativamente “Fuck the programme?”⁵, Christiaanse afirma que “un nuevo edificio proyectado de acuerdo con un programa cuidadosamente preparado nunca podría alcanzar un carácter y

5. Christiaanse, K.: “Fuck the programme?”. *Quaderns d'arquitectura i urbanisme*, nº 230, 2001.

una calidad comparables” a los que puede ofrecer el edificio reciclado; una aplicación del concepto de *reparación como mejora* que desarrolla el episodio 7 de *rehabitar*. Para ello, debe existir cierta compatibilidad entre la construcción existente y el nuevo programa como condición necesaria para que la primera sobreviva a la transformación sin que sea preciso invertir una cantidad excesiva de energía para lograrlo.

En otro contexto, Frank asegura que “la casa moderna tiene su origen en los *ateliers* bohemios bajo las mansardas. Estos espacios bajo cubierta, declarados inhabitables y poco higiénicos por los arquitectos [...] y por la autoridad, y arrebatados a la especulación y a la ambigüedad de las leyes, edificados casi por casualidad, tienen aquella vitalidad que buscamos en vano en las viviendas de los pisos inferiores, organizados según criterios más racionales”⁶. Frank atribuye a estos espacios destartalados la capacidad de impregnar a la nueva arquitectura doméstica.

En relación a la reutilización, esta cita permite señalar el potencial que puede tener una arquitectura *reparada* como revulsivo y como modelo a seguir en el planteamiento de nuevas obras. Tan sólo exige que observemos la realidad con una actitud interrogante y

6. Frank, J.: “Das haus als weg und platz”. *Der Baumeister*, nº 29, 1931.

Edificios catalogados en el barrio del Poble Nou, Barcelona.

atenta, fijándonos en aquellos casos que, por unas u otras circunstancias, se apartan de lo convencional.

Oportunidades

Se propone observar esos casos como oportunidades y no como obstáculos y de reconocer –también desde la normativa– lo singular de cada situación respecto al estándar.

Podemos interpretar en este sentido el planeamiento para la transformación del barrio barcelonés del Poblenou en un distrito de actividades tecnológicas⁷. De su pasado industrial, perduran numerosos edificios construidos desde mediados del siglo XIX hasta finales de la década de 1970. La presión ciudadana y los nuevos criterios de inclusión han motivado la catalogación de 68 de esos edificios –hasta un total de 114– como parte del patrimonio.

Este incremento significativo de bienes protegidos ha provocado que el plan incentive su reconversión en vivienda –que se define como ‘tipológicamente no convencional’– consciente de que la ciudad no puede absorber una cantidad de edificaciones tan considerable como nuevos equipamientos. Sin embargo, al limitar la fórmula a los edificios

7. “Modificación del PGM para la renovación de las áreas industriales del Poblenou. Distrito de actividades 22@BCN”, Barcelona, septiembre de 2000.

Placa **RH**.

Allan Wexler: *Crate House* (1991). Encargo de Herter Gallery, University of Massachusetts. Colección de Karl Osthaus Museum, Hagen, Alemania.

catalogados, el propio plan impide que otras construcciones en buen estado puedan ser aprovechadas del mismo modo. La expresión 'no convencional' hace referencia a la ya conocida fórmula del *loft*, pero con el inconveniente de que esas viviendas deben regirse por la normativa de habitabilidad convencional. ¿No sería más apropiado explorar condiciones distintas a las habituales, capaces de sacar mayor provecho a lo singular de esos espacios; de permitir una relación más distendida con las diversas fórmulas de trabajo compatibles con la casa o de mezclar los espacios habitables con otros usos, mejorando su relación con la ciudad?

Los vehículos clasificados como históricos se identifican con una H que precede a la numeración de la matrícula. Con ello, se distinguen del resto pero, sobre todo, se rigen por una normativa propia

que fija unas condiciones distintas –incluso un tipo de seguro propio– consciente del material con el que trata. Un distintivo parecido (las siglas RH, por ejemplo) podría servir para identificar edificios históricos rehabilitados. Producen espacios habitables, pero no necesariamente viviendas, y para ello, precisan de una reglamentación no convencional que incida sobre las acciones más que sobre los espacios. Se puede cocinar, pero no hay cocina en sentido estricto.

Ocupar el espacio

Un modo de habitar estos espacios es su simple colonización. No se interviene directamente sobre el edificio, sino que su interior se hace más habitable por la incorporación de determinados dispositivos. Las intervenciones artísticas de

Una habitación *NoHotel* instalada en una nave desocupada (2004).
T. Lehmann y F. Schiferli, arquitectos.
www.nohotel.info

Allan Wexler, muy cercanas a la arquitectura, pueden ser entendidas en este sentido. La *Casa contenedor*, de 1991, está formada por cuatro armarios móviles que clasifican todo lo necesario para comer, dormir, ducharse y descansar, de modo que, al desplegarse en un determinado espacio, son capaces de aglutinar a su alrededor las actividades básicas que lo hacen habitable.

De manera comparable, las habitaciones transportables que proponen los arquitectos Tobias Lehmann y Floris Schiferli con el lema *NoHotel* convierten el interior vacío e inhóspito de una nave industrial en un refugio provisional para trabajar y pasar la noche confortablemente, sabiendo que, en pocos días, la habitación vuelve al interior del baúl con el que se traslada sin que el edificio haya sido alterado. Con esta habitación provisional, es posible plantear que las condiciones de confort –especialmente las térmicas– no tienen porque ser uniformes en todo el espacio interior, intensificándose tan sólo en los ámbitos más sensibles, como forma de racionalizar el consumo.

Construidas de manera más permanente, aunque con un uso igualmente temporal, las cápsulas *Sleepbox* (2009) de los arquitectos A. Goryainov y M. Krymov, ofrecen en 3,75 m² unas condiciones de habitabilidad para trabajar y dormir que los grandes espacios de un aeropuerto o una estación –para los que están pensadas– no pueden procurar. No son dormitorios ni despachos,

Cápsula *Sleepbox* seccionada (2009). A. Goryainov y M. Krymov.
www.arch-group.org

Una cama con dosel en un grabado de Jan van der Straet (ca. 1590).
The British Museum, Londres

sino ámbitos en las que esas actividades se producen durante unas horas, como actualización de las antiguas camas con dosel contenidas, a su vez, en habitaciones de mayor envergadura. Como en el caso del *NoHotel*, la creación de las condiciones de confort corresponde a cada cápsula y no al espacio que las contiene.

En estos casos es imprescindible la yuxtaposición del gran espacio inalterado y del pequeño ámbito equipado, como muestra de la capacidad de éste para abastecer el espacio interior por la vía de aglutinar ciertas actividades. Este planteamiento recuerda la imagen descrita por el crítico Reyner Banham cuando se refería al potencial del motor fueraborda, que permite

“convertir prácticamente cualquier objeto flotante en una embarcación capaz de navegar”⁸.

En 1971, el diseñador italiano Joe Colombo concibe el equipamiento de la casa en estos términos.

La *Total Furnishing Unit* es, en cierto modo, una versión comercializable de la *Casa contenedor* de Wexler que trata de ser la condición suficiente para producir habitabilidad a su entorno. Se trata de un módulo compacto, dotado de cierto movimiento, que incorpora el equipo de cocina, armarios, cama y baño, de manera que los habitantes puedan configurar su uso en cada momento. El espacio resultante se

8. Banham, Reyner: “A Clip-on Architecture”, *Design Quarterly*, nº 63, 1965.

Total Furnishing Unit (1971-72)
de Joe Colombo. Ignazia Favata
Studio, Milán.

Planta y detalle de las viviendas
en un edificio mixto. I. Ábalos y
J. Herreros, concurso *Hábitat y
Ciudad*, Barcelona (1990).

aleja de la casa compartimentada en habitaciones y, quizás por ello, era necesario encontrar una definición alternativa. En 1972, el Museo de Arte Moderno de Nueva York (MoMA), incluyó este experimento en la exposición “Nuevo paisaje doméstico”; un título que pretende dar con una imagen más apropiada: el interior entendido como paisaje en el que algunos episodios marcan su geografía a partir de las actividades que son capaces de generar.

Las viviendas propuestas por Iñaki Ábalos y Juan Herreros para el concurso *Hábitat y Ciudad*, en Barcelona (1990) actualizan estas experiencias, acercando la casa al modelo de la oficina. El espacio diáfano se distribuye en unidades paralelas, con doble ventilación, separadas por franjas de armarios. El resto de elementos de la casa son configurables, desplegándose a partir de dos columnas de servicios que equipan la vivienda. El sistema puede ser trasladado a la rehabilitación de edificios en tanto que no predetermina la manera de usar la casa, sino que ofrece los mecanismos para que el habitante pueda hacerlo en el tiempo.

Atributos

Las situaciones descritas ponen de manifiesto una gran disparidad en las características de estos edificios. Sus estándares difieren de los inmuebles de vivienda concebidos inicialmente para tal fin. Tienen mayor altura libre o profundidad edificable; sus

Almacén frigorífico de bacalao frente al Duero en Oporto, obra de F. Yglesias d'Oliveira (1937-39), transformado en viviendas. Estado inicial y modificado. 2007, Carlos Prata, Gabinete de Arquitectura.

estructuras pueden llegar a resistir mayores cargas o pueden tener más distancia entre pilares; las fuentes de luz natural pueden provenir de la cubierta, de fachadas más vidriadas o ser menos abundantes; las dimensiones y el volumen de sus espacios pueden ser mucho mayores que en un edificio de viviendas y pueden disponer de sistemas de acceso poco convencionales, como rampas o grandes montacargas.

Pero también pueden destacar por sus carencias en relación a los nuevos programas, como el control del consumo energético, que reclama soluciones ingeniosas –tal vez mediante el uso de espacios intermedios o de transición–; o como la accesibilidad adaptada que cumpla con los criterios actuales. Es necesario reconocer las limitaciones y plantear soluciones de forma individual, a partir de lo peculiar de cada situación y no de un único criterio general, inevitablemente reduccionista.

En algunos casos, su aprovechamiento es todo un reto, como sucede con antiguos depósitos, gasómetros o silos, cuyo atributo común es la falta de ventanas. Sirva de ejemplo la reciente reconversión en viviendas y comercios de un almacén frigorífico de bacalao en Oporto, construido en 1939. En cada módulo estructural encaja una vivienda orientada al río y dos plazas de aparcamiento en la cara más próxima a la pendiente del terreno, de modo que es posible aparcar en la misma planta en la que se habita, algo que no se hubiese planteado en otras circunstancias. No obstante, para hacer posible la operación, ha sido necesario transformar

Estación abandonada
de Príncipe Pío, Madrid.
abandonalia.blogspot.com

Hospital abandonado
en Italia.
Imagen: Alex Vetri

Antiguo hospital
del Tórax, Terrassa,
Barcelona.

Imagen: Joaquim Sierra

Clínica infantil
desocupada en Alemania.
www.flickr.com/earthmagnified

Acción reivindicativa
en la antigua cárcel de
Carabanchel, Madrid, poco
antes de su derribo, 2008.

Silos reconvertidos en apartamentos, Copenhague
(MVRDV y JJW Arkitekter, 2002-05).

Los silos de la harinera Magro en el barrio de San Blas
de Alicante, antes de su derribo en 2011.

Imagen: Jorge Barreno.

sus fachadas ciegas sin sobrepasar el límite de lo constructivamente razonable, y aquí es donde un proyecto de esta naturaleza encuentra su mayor dificultad.

Un caso comparable podría ser el de los silos que se construyeron en España, a partir 1937, para la Red Nacional del SENPA, hoy abandonados en su mayoría (www.silosygraneros.es). Si bien existen, en otros países, precedentes de reciclaje en residencias, hoteles o apartamentos, aquí no se ha planteado el futuro de estas infraestructuras, a pesar de una cierta toma de consciencia al respecto. Prueba de ello es la demolición en Alicante de los silos de la harinera Magro (1951) el pasado mes de mayo de 2011, entre la indiferencia y la aprobación de unos y la reivindicación de otros que proponían su reutilización, apoyados por plataformas como *ecosistemaurbano.org*.

La altura interior es un valor propio de algunos de estos espacios no domésticos. Podría decirse que se miden en metros cúbicos, más que en metros cuadrados, de modo que a igual superficie, ofrecen una cualidad distintiva. En algunos casos, esta altura puede permitir la creación de entreplantas que desdoblén parcialmente su superficie, aportando un punto de vista distinto sobre el espacio interior. La denominada *Naked House* (2000), del arquitecto japonés Shigeru Ban, no es un edificio reutilizado, pero ilustra el aprovechamiento de este rasgo distintivo. La altura del espacio permite disponer un cierto número de cubículos móviles dotados de techo propio, que puede ser accesible. Cada cubículo está concebido

Interior de la *Naked House*, obra de Shigeru Ban.
Saitama, Japón, 2000.

Locales de alquiler en la última planta del edificio
David, Barcelona (Ignasi Mas i Morell, 1929-31), a
los que se puede llegar en coche.

como espacio de la privacidad, mientras que el espacio que los contiene adquiere un carácter colectivo –es el lugar de la sociabilidad– lo que hace verosímil el uso de esos techos como punto de observación.

Como en otros casos, se trata de saber aprovechar las particularidades que los definen. Incluso situaciones como la existencia de rampas y montacargas para vehículos en un edificio industrial en altura pueden convertirse en oportunidades para plantear soluciones poco frecuentes.

El antiguo depósito de taxis *David* en Barcelona (Ignasi Mas, 1929-31) es un ejemplo de cómo un edificio urbano dotado de una estructura versátil, rampa y montacargas ha sabido adaptarse a los cambios, sacando partido de esos atributos. Hoy en día, alberga un aparcamiento, un supermercado, un gimnasio, una galería comercial y locales de alquiler, accesibles en vehículo, en la última planta. Todo ello sin más modificaciones que las particiones interiores y el equipamiento de cada actividad.

En 1983 se plantea un concurso para la remodelación de la fábrica Fiat en Turín, conocida como *Lingotto*, obra de Giacomo Matte' Trucco (1915-23). La propuesta de Richard Meier contempla que las 500 nuevas viviendas puedan ser accesibles desde el coche, dando sentido a la rampa que asciende hasta la cubierta del edificio, antigua pista de pruebas de la marca. Ahora, con un escenario próximo de vehículos no contaminantes, tiene sentido

Vista de la calle interior del *Lingotto*, Turín (G. Matte' Trucco, 1915-23), en la propuesta de concurso de Richard Meier (1983).

Instalación *Living 1990*, de Archigram, por encargo del *Weekend Telegraph* y los almacenes Harrods, Londres 1967.

redimensionar y replantear la relación de éstos con nuestra actividad diaria.

La imagen de un artilugio eléctrico como la *hoverchair*, que proponía en 1967 el grupo inglés Archigram en su instalación doméstica *Living 1990* vuelve a suscitar interés. Se trataba de un asiento desplazable, más que de un coche en sentido estricto, supuestamente capaz de modificar la pequeña movilidad urbana. En el contexto del aprovechamiento, un cambio de esta naturaleza podría subvertir el papel que hemos asignado al vehículo, desplazándolo de nuevo hacia el interior de algunos edificios y acortando distancias entre usos diversos, como la vivienda y el trabajo.

Normativas

En base al conocimiento de los edificios que se hallan desocupados y que todavía permiten ser rehabilitados, debería ser posible establecer un protocolo de actuación capaz de orientar, más que determinar, las posibles vías de intervención.

Para ello, sería necesario aislar sus atributos –sus características espaciales y constructivas o su relación con el entorno, entre otros– y hacer lo propio con los nuevos requerimientos para conocer la compatibilidad entre el soporte y la actividad. Sólo de este modo es posible reactivar estos edificios con garantías de supervivencia.

Consciente de estar trabajando con un material que se comporta de modo particular, la normativa debería adaptarse con la misma flexibilidad que los nuevos usos y las estrategias de intervención, gestionando la habitabilidad a partir de parámetros menos convencionales. Si asociamos lo flexible a programas culturales y a edificios como las naves industriales es, seguramente, porque la normativa no permite que las viviendas lo sean en igual medida.

Regulamos sobre los espacios de la casa y eso tiene como consecuencia su uniformidad. Sin embargo, cuando la base no ha sido concebida originalmente para tal propósito, este grado de uniformidad no es posible ni deseable sin tomar riesgos innecesarios con los que el edificio puede sucumbir.

Es entonces cuando conviene plantearse si la flexibilidad no debería estar en el habitante, en lugar de exigirla al soporte de la actividad. Adaptarse depende de uno mismo y rehabilitar un edificio industrial, de oficinas, sanitario, escolar, militar o agrícola, reclama una actitud distinta hacia ese soporte, capaz de ver como una oportunidad aquello que el edificio puede ofrecer y resolviendo las presuntas incomodidades que pueda generar.

En la página siguiente:
[hospital abandonado en Alemania.](#)
www.telefunke.be

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rehabitar

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**HABITAR – grupo de investigation de
professors/investigadores
Departamento de Proyectos Arquitectónicos
Universidade Politècnica de Catalunya, UPC**

Exposição (15 de Junho/29 de Setembro)

<http://www.rehabitar.blogspot.com/>

rehabitar

entrar por el balcón [7]

Durante los últimos años, una parte del parque de viviendas en nuestras ciudades se ha ido dotando de ascensores para mejorar su accesibilidad. En el contexto de estas obras de reparación es donde nos gustaría hacer algunas observaciones que pueden servir para ver el problema inicial –no disponer de ascensor– como una oportunidad.

José Blanco López

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En portada: Fotograma de *Mon Oncle* de Jacques Tati (Francia, 1958)

Reparar como forma de mejora

En su libro *El artesano*¹ Richard Sennett realiza algunas interesantes observaciones sobre la idea de reparación, ampliando el concepto y dilatándolo hasta ver en él un modo de operar sobre los objetos y los conceptos. El hecho de reparar es entendido como una prolongación natural de los objetos a partir de la crítica que su uso inevitablemente conlleva. La reparación que sugiere Sennett se convierte en un atractivo repaso de la cultura material y una invitación a ver los objetos como el resultado de su incesante uso y adiestramiento, que es el que provoca la reparación. Sennett también habla del papel de la contingencia en la arquitectura y decanta sus observaciones hacia aquellas obras cuyo interés y belleza provienen del hecho de incorporar las dificultades, e incluso las equivocaciones, en el proceso de diseño.

A partir de este razonamiento, el episodio de dotar de ascensores a las viviendas que no los tenían, nos lleva hacia un lugar especialmente atractivo: que el objeto reparado sea mejor, tenga más prestaciones, que el objeto inicial, e incluso que supere aquéllos que ya han subsanado el problema en origen.

1. Sennett, Richard: *El Artesano*. Barcelona, Anagrama, 2008.

SOLUCIONES

Instalar un ascensor en la fachada

La instalación de un edificio y sistema de ascensor garantiza un alto rendimiento energético y la máxima eficiencia que consigue el Ayuntamiento de Madrid.

■ Instalación

El edificio garantiza a vivienda un elevado nivel de confort por su capacidad de aislamiento térmico y acústico, y el uso eficiente de la energía.

■ Estado anterior

La instalación de ascensor en el edificio de forma exterior garantiza un elevado nivel de confort por su capacidad de aislamiento térmico y acústico, y el uso eficiente de la energía.

■ Características técnicas específicas de

El edificio garantiza a vivienda un elevado nivel de confort por su capacidad de aislamiento térmico y acústico, y el uso eficiente de la energía.

El edificio garantiza a vivienda un elevado nivel de confort por su capacidad de aislamiento térmico y acústico, y el uso eficiente de la energía.

Foto: José Antonio / G. P. A. Ciudad de Madrid

Un ascensor en la fachada

El Ayuntamiento de Madrid permite esta posibilidad desde diciembre.

Desde esta necesidad de proporcionar de un edificio de un sistema. También es necesario que se le permita una instalación que permita la instalación de un ascensor en la fachada exterior del edificio. Este requisito de la ley establece que el Ayuntamiento de Madrid (Ayuntamiento de Madrid) permita esta posibilidad desde diciembre.

El punto 12 de la ley establece que el Ayuntamiento de Madrid permita esta posibilidad desde diciembre. Este requisito de la ley establece que el Ayuntamiento de Madrid (Ayuntamiento de Madrid) permita esta posibilidad desde diciembre.

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Solo se instalará la colocación en fachada cuando sea la única alternativa viable para subsanar la carencia de ascensor

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El País, viernes 16 de enero de 2009

¿Sólo se trata de poner un ascensor?

En algunos edificios, colocar un ascensor ha supuesto utilizar el espacio existente en el hueco de la escalera o en un patio adyacente. En estos casos, la reparación ha mejorado las prestaciones de la escalera, por expresarlo de alguna manera, añadiéndole un sistema mecánico. Sin embargo, esta clase de reparación no ha supuesto cambio alguno en la estructura de accesos del inmueble.

En otros casos, esta operación se ha abordado de una forma drástica: el ascensor no ha tenido más opción que colocarse en alguna de las fachadas del edificio. Ésta es una situación habitual en muchos polígonos construidos en España a partir de los años 50 y 60 del siglo pasado. Se trata de conjuntos formados en gran parte por bloques laminares; edificios de crujía estrecha y viviendas con dos caras de ventilación y asoleo. Son bloques que forman barras en las que podemos contar las unidades que contienen a través de las cajas de escalera, que generalmente dan acceso a dos viviendas por rellano.

El ascensor en la fachada

En estos bloques, los ascensores han modificado la fachada y también, en buena parte, el espacio público, ya que su caja se ha construido sobre la acera o sobre el espacio libre entre edificios. No puede dejar de recordarse el ejemplo del Centro Nacional de Arte Reina Sofía de Madrid, cuando hace más de 20 años se colocaron en

Ascensores instalados en
el barrio de La Trinitat,
Barcelona (2008)

El Centro Nacional de
Arte Reina Sofía, Madrid
(1986).

Imagen: www.es.wikipedia.org

la fachada dos torres de ascensores de cristal, que hoy pueden considerarse como un caso pionero entre los que aquí nos ocupan. Estos ejemplos u otros similares representan, a nuestro juicio, la mejor ocasión para realizar las observaciones a las que antes nos referíamos. En particular, podemos distinguir dos formas de intervención.

En la primera de ellas, cuando los ascensores ‘no han tenido más remedio’ que ubicarse en la fachada –puesto que en la escalera no cabían– lo han hecho como prolongación del descansillo de la escalera hacia el exterior, ocupando una parte del espacio público. En esta situación, está claro que se han mejorado las prestaciones de la escalera, con una mínima intervención y una mejora de accesibilidad notable. Sin embargo, resulta interesante observar que en algunas reparaciones en las que se ha procedido así, los vecinos finalmente han expresado su disconformidad ya que, de este modo, al realizar el desembarco en el descansillo de la escalera, tienen que acabar por subir o bajar media planta. A raíz de estas opiniones, se han desarrollado soluciones constructivas ingeniosas para sustituir las escaleras existentes por otras de un solo tramo –normalmente construidas en taller con perfiles de acero– que permiten situar el ascensor a nivel de planta, proyectándose aún más sobre la calle.

La segunda forma de intervención –que a nuestro juicio posee las condiciones más extremas– es aquélla en que los ascensores exteriores se han dotado de un sistema de balcones para poder acceder directamente a las viviendas por la sala de estar o por alguna de las habitaciones.

Ejemplo de colocación de un ascensor y balcones en fachada.

Tarta *Tatin*.

Queremos referirnos a estos casos. En los bloques reparados de este modo aparecen unas estructuras hiperestáticas, de acero en su mayor parte, que no modifican la estructura del edificio y que se superponen a las fachadas distinguiéndose en ellas las cajas de los ascensores y los nuevos balcones. Algunos de estos casos son, sin duda, ejemplares y pueden considerarse una mejora evidente del conjunto del edificio.

Entrar por la sala, entrar al revés

Los casos en los que el acceso se realiza directamente por la sala de estar son los que encarnan el problema de forma más clara, ya que las viviendas resultantes tienen un doble acceso y, además, uno de ellos es, por así decirlo, inconveniente.

Estos ejemplos nos permiten volver a las observaciones de Richard Sennett sobre la reparación y nos traen a la memoria el caso de la tarta *tatin*; una conocida tarta de manzana ‘inventada’ por las hermanas Tatin por error, para aprovechar una tarta quemada. Se trata de una reparación en toda regla. La tarta es aquí oportuna ya que es una tarta al revés, puesto que se cocina en el horno con la manzana hacia abajo, sobre caramelo, y cubierta por la pasta y se invierte al sacarla del horno. Aquí, en estas viviendas reparadas por necesidad, también se da la vuelta al acceso. De lo que se trata ahora es de aprovechar las virtudes de esta inversión inconveniente del uso.

Vivienda de fin de semana, de los arquitectos Guérin y Herbulot.

Architecture d'Aujourd'hui, nº 2. Paris, 1935

Entrar por la sala es habitual en muchas viviendas de verano.

Es inconveniente porque se entra por un sitio que no es habitual en una vivienda urbana: por la sala de estar. A esta anomalía se le suma el hecho de que mantiene otro acceso por un recibidor vinculado a una escalera y, probablemente, cercano a la cocina. Este hecho representa para nosotros una oportunidad. Por su parte, la sala resulta ser también un distribuidor, adquiriendo un papel más práctico, alterando los recorridos en la vivienda y abriendo algunas posibilidades de cierto interés al poder usar el recibidor ‘canónico’ de nuevas maneras y, en algunos casos, extendiendo la cocina hacia él. Resulta también inconveniente ya que los criterios de algunos promotores de viviendas públicas, como es el caso de los que rigen el diseño de viviendas en el área metropolitana de Barcelona, regulan el número de puertas que deben dar a la sala de estar, ya que se trata de evitar lo que se denomina una ‘sala de estar pasante’. Sin embargo, este tipo de salas –que podemos asimilar al *hall* en la terminología anglosajona– poseen la cualidad de ser el centro de actividad de la casa y de concentrar buena parte de los accesos al resto de piezas. De este modo, aceptar un segundo acceso por la sala de estar, implica una excepción a la normativa. Como tal, debería estudiarse si esto supone una cualidad a imitar en las nuevas viviendas.

El mejor mecanismo para poder realizar este acceso es, sin duda, a través de un balcón en la fachada. Por tanto la vivienda, si no lo tenía, deberá incluirlo o modificar el que existe. Podríamos decir que a partir de este caso invitamos a proyectar las nuevas viviendas como si fueran unas viviendas reparadas.

El balcón y el acceso

Entrar por el balcón como resultado de la implantación de los ascensores en la fachada y por tanto en la calle, supone ocupar el espacio público (aunque sea transitoriamente), lo que representa una oportunidad para ver balcones y ascensores como una prolongación de la calle, pero también como una extensión de lo privado a la esfera pública. Esta transitoriedad es la que ha sido regulada a través de normativas específicas que pretenden ordenar este uso de la calle en distintas ciudades de España, pero al mismo tiempo, incentivar y ordenar la colocación de ascensores en los edificios que carecen de ellos.

Todo ello debería ser motivo de una reflexión, ya que al colocar ascensores se puede estar añadiendo a la vivienda un elemento igualmente valioso: el balcón. En algunos casos, el balcón se convierte en un factor de tanto peso como el ascensor mismo y constituye un argumento convincente a la hora de colocar ascensores en la fachada en bloques de pocas viviendas, en los que es importante el reparto de la inversión entre todos los vecinos. En estos casos, la experiencia enseña que los inquilinos de las primeras plantas aceptan la instalación del ascensor gracias al balcón y, aunque muchos podrían seguir subiendo a su vivienda a pie, no dispondrían de un nuevo espacio exterior. En esta misma línea, algunas de las normativas, como la de Sevilla, obligan a prever una parada del ascensor en la cubierta, para facilitar el acceso a todos los vecinos, haciendo

aún más convincente la colocación del ascensor para aquéllos que viven en las primeras plantas.

Según esta experiencia, pensar en la colocación de ascensores en la fachada principal supone también agregar balcones a dicha fachada. Nos preguntamos cómo deberían resolverse estos casos a partir de tomar conciencia de la importancia del balcón y poder así formular el problema de otro modo. ¿Debemos, pues, plantearnos cómo añadir un ascensor en la fachada dotado de pasarelas de acceso que usamos como balcón? O bien ¿debemos añadir balcones que contengan un ascensor? Pensamos que este matiz es significativo, puesto que lleva a diseñar el balcón pensando en que su uso sea relevante. El balcón ha sido tradicionalmente un espacio ‘terminal’ en la vivienda, es decir, el último punto del recorrido que hemos iniciado al entrar en casa. Si fuera, por el contrario, el primer punto de este recorrido, ¿cambiaría entonces su uso en la vivienda?

En el contexto del replanteo de la casa que supone esta alteración de los accesos, es posible realizar algunas especulaciones a partir de este uso indebido del balcón. Esto tiene que ver –una vez admitido que el acceso alterará la estructura habitual de una vivienda– con la cocina y el balcón. En nuestro país hay muchas situaciones geográficas que permiten un uso más familiar y distendido del balcón durante gran parte del año, rescatándolo de un uso puramente ocasional al vincularlo a una actividad cotidiana como

Barbacoa portátil *BBQ Bruce* para balcón.

www.swiss-miss.com

Portal del Palazzo Zuccari, Roma.

Rasmussen, Steen E.: *Experiencia de la arquitectura*. Barcelona: Reverté, 1962

Pfleifer y Kuhn, viviendas en Basilea.

Werk, Bauen + Wohnen, nº 5. Mayo 1996

la que hacemos en la cocina. Las barbacoas portátiles de balcón, a las que nos hemos referido en otros episodios, nos ponen en la pista de esta utilización inconveniente de balcones y terrazas, añadiendo a la vivienda en altura algunas de las cualidades de la casa aislada. Al ver algunas fachadas de viejos palacios tenemos la absoluta certeza de que muchos balcones fueron en su origen la simple protección mediante una barandilla del espacio de la cornisa. Hoy, además de salir a ver la calle, podemos añadir funciones más propiamente domésticas a esta pieza.

Todo ello debería ser motivo de otra reflexión sobre la separación entre la escalera y el ascensor y sobre la elección de cada uno de ellos en relación a la parte de la casa a la que dan acceso directo. ¿Se trata del mismo caso que las pasarelas de acceso comunitarias que muchas veces se han visto como un elemento de desprestigio vinculado a las viviendas más económicas? O, por el contrario, ¿el balcón con ascensor abre la puerta a una comprensión y a un uso de la vivienda distinto? Un ejemplo no tan lejano

Balcón plegable *Bloomframe*, de los arquitectos holandeses Hofman Dujardin (2007).
www.bloomframe.nl

El País, domingo 7 de julio de 1996.

LOS ARQUITECTOS Y LA CIUDAD

Enric Tallas — "La ciudad es el desafío importante para después a los arquitectos".

La pérdida de los balcones es una muestra de la disfunción arquitectónica, explica Ramon Folch

En el artículo publicado en esta edición de la revista "El arquitecto y la ciudad" se analiza el fenómeno de la pérdida de balcones en las ciudades de la costa catalana. El autor es el arquitecto Enric Tallas.

El artículo también está incluido dentro del programa de la CITA. En la misma revista, editada por "El arquitecto y la ciudad", se publican los artículos de Enric Tallas, José María Rodríguez Domínguez y Ramon Folch.

En el artículo de Ramon Folch se analiza el fenómeno de la pérdida de balcones en las ciudades de la costa catalana. El autor es el arquitecto Enric Tallas.

Ramon Folch, según se dice en el programa de actividades de la CITA, es un arquitecto y un urbanista que ha trabajado en Barcelona desde 1960 hasta el momento de su muerte en 1984. Folch, un arquitecto que ha trabajado en Barcelona desde 1960 hasta el momento de su muerte en 1984. Folch, un arquitecto que ha trabajado en Barcelona desde 1960 hasta el momento de su muerte en 1984.

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En un momento de la plaza de la Generalitat

En un momento de la plaza de la Generalitat, se puede apreciar la arquitectura clásica de la ciudad. El arquitecto Ramon Folch, quien ha trabajado en Barcelona desde 1960 hasta el momento de su muerte en 1984, ha diseñado edificios que reflejan esta tradición arquitectónica.

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es el de las viviendas de los arquitectos Pfeifer y Kuhn en Basilea, cuya escalera exterior de acceso se prolonga lateralmente en un balcón ligado a la cocina. La ambigüedad de esta solución, a medio camino entre una terraza y una escalera, nos mueve a fijarnos de nuevo en ella en este contexto.

Dentro de la misma línea argumental, conviene recordar la proliferación en Europa, en estos últimos años, de balcones prefabricados pensados especialmente para adosarse a fachadas que

Javier Mariscal, *El balcón comestible*.
Campaña del Ayuntamiento de Barcelona (2000)

carecían de ellos. Estos balcones, concebidos como un accesorio de la ventana, alteran profundamente las fachadas de los edificios y la relación de éstos con la calle. En algunos casos, esta condición de accesorio queda subrayada por el hecho de tratarse de balcones plegables mediante un mecanismo equiparable al de una persiana. Hace ya algunos años que el biólogo Ramon Folch invitaba a valorar la pérdida de los balcones como un ejemplo de disfunción arquitectónica, al definirlos como una zona de transición entre el interior y el exterior de las viviendas en las ciudades mediterráneas. Más tarde han aparecido, cada vez con mayor insistencia, distintas soluciones y productos para convertir el balcón en un huerto urbano de consumo doméstico. Basta cruzar todos estos datos para obtener un dispositivo que puede modificar el uso de la sala de estar adyacente, incorporando al balcón el papel de zaguán, huerto o cocina, que por extensión, puede llevar a un uso distinto de la casa.

Normativas

La incorporación de ascensores en las fachadas ha dado lugar a un nuevo tipo de problemas que son motivo de reglamentación en nuestro país. En ciudades como Madrid, Sevilla, Salamanca, Getxo o Avilés se han desarrollado normativas que pueden interpretarse como el instrumento que trata de comprender este fenómeno creciente. Se regula la instalación de

Escaleras de incendios en un edificio de viviendas, Nueva York.
Sert, J. L.: *Can our cities survive?*. Harvard University Press, 1942

Loft de Donald Judd en el 101 de Spring St., Nueva York (1968).
Imagen: Todd Eberle, 1993

estos elevadores en el hueco de la escalera o bien en los patios de luces y de manzana. Pero lo más interesante de estas normativas es que admiten la colocación de los nuevos ascensores en la fachada principal –y por tanto en el espacio público– cuando no hay más remedio, y siempre mediante un informe que demuestre la imposibilidad de actuar de otro modo. El hecho de que diversos municipios, como Bilbao o Barcelona, contemplen la necesidad de un plan urbanístico para su instalación, deja clara la vinculación entre estos edificios reparados y la ciudad, tal vez de la manera más explícita posible.

La normativa sale al paso de la colocación de ascensores en las aceras, regulando las condiciones de ocupación de la vía pública, lo que supone un interesante caso que deberá hacer pensar en las relaciones entre el espacio público y el espacio doméstico en el futuro, aunque la colocación de ascensores en la calle y por la fachada sea algo provisional. En algunos casos, como en Madrid por ejemplo, se fija el período de ocupación del espacio público en 75 años.

Las escaleras de incendios, un antecedente

El hecho de que la fachada de un inmueble urbano contenga elementos de acceso a las viviendas no es nuevo. En nuestro país, los casos de escaleras de incendio en las fachadas no son frecuentes en edificios de viviendas pero sí en edificios industriales en altura.

Angels flight. Óleo sobre lienzo de Millard Sheets, 1931.

Los Angeles County Museum of Art

Planta de vivienda del tipo *rabo de bacalaho* en la calle São Ciro, Lisboa.

Imagen: Carlos Dias Coelho, Universidade Técnica de Lisboa

A menudo observamos estas escaleras en la fachada como algo añadido, como una prótesis correctora. El decoro y la composición de las fachadas parecen haber sido los argumentos que han llevado a descartar una solución que, en otras ciudades, se popularizó en distintas épocas. De estos casos nos interesa el hecho de que las escaleras puedan usarse, no tanto como evacuación, sino como un acceso duplicado. La entrada por una zona de la casa que no está pensada para ello los hace especialmente atractivos.

Un caso interesante de reseñar es el de Lisboa. Una parte de esta ciudad posee una tipología edificatoria conocida popularmente como *rabo de bacalaho* debido a la forma de la planta de estos inmuebles urbanos. Las parejas de viviendas de estos edificios se estrechan hacia la parte trasera, hasta acabar en las cocinas, afilando aún más su extremo con un balcón o una galería desde la que acceder a una escalera de incendios que evacua al patio interior de manzana. Esta escalera, situada en la fachada posterior, hace que el corredor de estas viviendas tenga una utilidad mayor al conducir a esta segunda salida. Ésta se convierte además, por pura lógica del aprovechamiento, en una entrada de servicio para la casa, lugar de encuentro con los vecinos y espacio de improvisadas actividades al exterior.

Casos de inmuebles de todas las épocas y lugares, como los de Nueva York, Rotterdam o

Viviendas de Mogens Lassen. Copenhague. 1937.

Fuertes, P., Monteys, X.: *Casa Collage*. Barcelona, Gustavo Gili, 2001

Immeubles Villas en la Ciudad Contemporánea.

Le Corbusier: *Urbanisme*, 1925

Copenhague, contemplan habitualmente este acceso posterior, vinculado a la cocina. Nos interesan porque en ellos existe una separación entre el ascensor y la escalera –o bien una segunda escalera– que permite desdoblarse la entrada a las viviendas y, en algunos casos, forzar la presencia de un balcón que da acceso a la cocina.

Ya hemos podido ver en el episodio 2 de Rehabilitar cómo estos accesos pueden asociarse también a las habitaciones de servicio y, por tanto, ser considerados como el germen de lo que denominamos ‘habitaciones satélite’. Ahora se trata de verlo desde otra óptica y observar estos accesos secundarios como una invitación a alterar la jerarquía de la casa en su conjunto, de modo comparable al uso inadecuado de un objeto.

Accesos y ascensores en la calle

Los llamados *Immeubles Villas* de la Ciudad Contemporánea, proyectada en 1925 por Le Corbusier, muestran un bloque doble que incorpora la calle como una infraestructura, conteniendo el acceso a los ascensores junto a las paradas de autobuses y tranvías. Esta exhibición organizativa en la que el medio de acceso mecanizado se integra en la calle, como lo hacen los servicios de abastecimiento, no puede dejar de entenderse como el resultado de concebir las viviendas ligadas a la ciudad.

Fotograma de *Mon Oncle* de Jacques Tati (Francia, 1958)

Las viviendas y, por extensión, el bloque que las contiene, son parte misma de la ciudad al ser precisamente la calle su columna vertebral. En esta ciudad, Le Corbusier concibe el espacio libre como algo contemplativo; una especie de espectáculo natural que se ofrece a las terrazas jardín de estos *Immeubles Villas*. Por la posición de los accesos mecánicos, puede decirse que la ciudad no se organiza en grandes manzanas con viviendas que contienen un espacio verde en el interior, sino en bloques dobles que contienen la calle.

Resulta curioso ver, contrapuesta a este proyecto, una escena de la película *Mon Oncle* de Jacques Tati (1958), que discurre en un viejo inmueble amenazado por la piqueta mientras la ciudad moderna se abre paso a su alrededor. En la escena, se hace una reivindicación de la incomodidad y de una especie de organización de la contingencia que se ilustra con el recorrido, aparentemente errático, de acceso a una vivienda de la última planta. Una secuencia que culmina inesperadamente con la entrada al apartamento a través de un balcón y que podemos contraponer a la organización impecable de la Ciudad Contemporánea. Los dos casos comparten la misma 'anomalía' que supone entrar por la fachada y ambos funcionan. Sin embargo, mientras uno lo hace de manera planificada y sistemática, el otro se muestra vital y espontáneo, como resultado de la contingencia.

Estado inicial

Modificaciones en la fachada

Se añade el ascensor

Se incorporan los balcones

Edificio rehabilitado

Ejemplos de una oportunidad

Tratando de unir estas observaciones, se recogen aquí algunos ejemplos de lo que podría ser un conjunto de soluciones para la vivienda, partiendo sencillamente de su reparación. Estos ejemplos están dispersos por la geografía española: Bilbao, Alicante, Ferrol, Barcelona, Madrid y Sevilla.

En todos ellos se han escogido tipos de bloques diversos con viviendas distribuidas de maneras distintas, para poder ensayar un conjunto heterogéneo de soluciones. Se ha representado gráficamente la planta en su estado original y se ha dibujado una nueva planta a partir de lo que supondría colocar un ascensor en la fachada.

Es necesario observar que, al margen de la mejora que implica colocar el ascensor, la casa modifica su organización y la forma de habitar sus distintas piezas. Estas hipótesis de transformación de las viviendas gracias a la incorporación de un ascensor y de una galería o balcón de acceso, son una invitación a ir más allá de la simple resolución de los problemas técnicos, para convertir toda la actuación en una mejora de la organización de la casa.

Imagen: Google Earth

Estado actual

Propuesta

Imagen: Philidel77, Flickr

Casas baratas del barrio de la Cruz

Bilbao

Enrique Epalza, 1909-12

El barrio de la Cruz se compone de cinco bloques lineales separados por pasajes. Este caso nos permite ensayar la construcción de un ascensor con servicio a ambos lados de la calle y a cotas de planta diferentes. Todos los edificios tienen la misma orientación, por lo tanto los nuevos accesos afectan a las viviendas de cada bloque manera diferente.

En los edificios situados en la cota inferior, el ascensor desembarca en las galerías ensanchadas para acomodar más usos, como un comedor o una salita. También se aprovecha la operación para mejorar el infradotado baño existente. Los edificios del lado opuesto del pasaje alcanzan el ascensor con una nueva galería que les permite reubicar la cocina y ganar una pieza más.

Imagen: Google Earth

Estado actual

Propuesta

Imagen: Centro de formación, innovación y recursos educativos, Elda

Grupo San Francisco de Sales

Elda, Alicante

Juan Antonio García Solera, 1956-68

Los bloques de este polígono disponen de terrazas y habitaciones bien dimensionadas. Aquí el nuevo acceso abre la oportunidad de agregar la habitación menor a la cocina para ensancharla e integrar el comedor. La entrada principal se realiza desde el núcleo central de la casa: la cocina-comedor.

La habitación contigua a la entrada desde la escalera se convierte en un caso ejemplar de estancia independiente. El conjunto reparado dispone de tres espacios: el propio de la habitación, un vestíbulo relacionado con ésta a partir de una puerta de mayores dimensiones y el antiguo baño de servicio. Además, su relación con el resto de la vivienda se establece a través de dos puertas, una directamente a la cocina-comedor y otra al salón.

Imagen: Google Earth

Estado actual

Propuesta

Imagen: Concello de Ferrol

Barrio de Recimil

Ferrol, A Coruña

Santiago Rey Pedreira, 1929/1944-48

El nuevo acceso a la vivienda del grupo Recimil se efectúa a través de una galería acristalada que recubre toda la fachada. La distribución existente se vertebra de nuevo a partir de una estancia central en relación con la cocina y la nueva galería. Las dos habitaciones de mayor dimensión acompañan a este espacio y se relacionan con puertas de mayores dimensiones. De este modo, la sala central puede funcionar conjuntamente con alguna de estas habitaciones adyacentes a modo de binomio comedor-sala, sala-estudio o sala-antecámara.

Imagen: Google Earth

Estado actual

Propuesta

Imagen:
Associació de
Veïns de Bellvitge

Polígono de Bellvitge

L'Hospitalet de Llobregat, Barcelona

Antonio Perpiñá Sebría, Xavier Busquets

Sindreu, 1968 (planeamiento)-1980

El nuevo acceso a los bloques se realiza por la fachada sur, añadiendo una terraza para cada pareja de pisos, que no disponían de ningún ámbito exterior. Cada extremo de la terraza se cierra con una tribuna que aumenta la superficie de las dos habitaciones menores. El antiguo recibidor puede agregarse a la cocina.

La tribuna y el trazado de nuevas instalaciones a través de la torre permiten también un cambio más ambicioso: desplazar la cocina a la habitación central utilizando la nueva tribuna como comedor. Con este cambio, la antigua cocina se convierte en una habitación con acceso directo desde las escaleras. La vivienda se dota de una pequeña habitación con acceso independiente.

Imagen: Google Earth

Estado actual

Propuesta

Imagen: Juan V. Fernández, Panoramio

Barriada El Tardón

Sevilla

Viviendas tipo 2, 1952-55

A los bloques de este polígono sevillano se les añade una terraza parcialmente acristalada para el desembarco del ascensor, que actúa también como extensión de la cocina actual. La estructura de la distribución de estas viviendas –basada en una sala central acompañada de habitaciones a ambos lados– se vería potenciada y mejorada. La nueva tribuna prolonga la crujía central, habilitando un espacio para una mesa, bien sea en ampliación o en el ensanchamiento entre la nueva cocina y la sala existente.

Imagen: Google Earth

Estado actual

Propuesta

Imagen: Docomomo Ibérico

Poblado dirigido de Caño Roto

Madrid

Fase 1, viviendas tipo 1.

José Luís Iñiguez Onzoño, Antonio Vázquez de Castro,
1957-59

El nuevo acceso en ascensor dota a los pisos de Caño Roto de una larga terraza con entrada a la cocina-comedor. La modularidad con la que se proyectó la planta permite aprovechar esta ocasión para disolver la sala de estar convencional en una sucesión de espacios con su centro de gravedad en el antiguo recibidor y con salida a ambas fachadas.

En la página siguiente:
Ascensor *Katarina*, Estocolmo,
fotografiado en 1941.
Imagen: www.commonswikimedia.org

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ENHR 2011 *'Mixité' : an urban and housing issue ?*

***'The idea of the City in the Social Housing experience
throughout the past century: scale, shape and extent'***

Toulouse, França, 5 a 8 de Julho de 2011

<http://www.enhr2011.com>

The idea of the City in the Social Housing experience throughout the past century: scale, shape and extent

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Abstract

We can say that social housing was a big part of all the architectural experience of the last century, since it had the responsibility of partially or totally (according to some) solve a housing problem that, more than physical, was also social and political.

Architects and Urban planners work hardly in the search of solutions that would face the pre-existing problems of housing in the traditional city, as the result of an uncontrollable industrial growth, among others. Their solutions varied according to their intentions and their ideological purposes, and different proposals were made in order to solve the same problem: to dignify the urban living of the lower classes, the ones that most suffered from housing shortage and speculation.

Although different and specific, we can gather most of the experiences in three categories, the first two attempting to overcome the traditional city by a) creating a disperse organism according to a scale and spatial solutions dear to previous urban settlements, or b) inventing a condensed city as part of an infinite modern system. Finally, the last group includes c) the rehabilitation of the traditional city fabric by surgical or large interventions.

The idea of the paper is not to offer a critical review of the different ‘cities’, or even to make a choice, among them, of the perfect settlement, but just to present different solutions supported by various case-studies, pointing flaws and successes, demystifying misconceived ideas or supporting others. Here, more than answers will be offered tools of evaluation for present and future proposal of architects and urban planners.

Keywords: Social Housing, city, dwelling, housing.

Introduction

The present article is inserted in a more extended investigation that uses the ‘minimum cell’ as an alibi to study the evolution of the idea and the shape of social housing in Europe during the XX century. Several scales have been studied in previous articles presented in other conferences (and inserted in a Thesis: ‘The Minimum Cell’): the unit, the house, the building, the neighbourhood, and now, the city.

In this study, therefore, it will be made an evaluation of the different urban structures according the built and human surroundings and how they were adequate (or not) to people’s needs, and it’s relation with the ‘housing cell’, the basis of most architectural thinking of the evaluated period.

The Condensed City

Some of the first humanitarian movements who tried to improve labourers’ living conditions proposed models that were still based in the urban fabric, like Henry Roberts (1803-1876) and his ‘Streatham Building (1948). Other went further ahead rethinking the entire urban context, instead of ‘solving it’ locally.

Workshop 05 – Large Housing Estates

Long before the Russian ‘Dom-kommunas’, the ‘Phalanstère’ was an idea of Charles Fourier (1772-1837) who dreamed with a new social order that would abolish the Industrial Revolution’s prevailing materialism. Agriculture would be the main economical support of a four-storey building where all social and domestic life would take place.

There were three communal spaces, one destined to dining rooms, libraries and offices, other to work and other ‘noisy’ activities, and finally ballrooms and meeting rooms for people outside the Phalanstère. The private apartments were based in a new family structure where the privacy of each household member was praised.

Followers started to appear since 1820 and the first building of this kind was built in Conde-sur-Verge (1833-1836), supported by the local bourgeoisie. A lot of supporters were found in the United States where the abolitionist ideals were well sustained by Fourier’s liberal ideas about women’s liberation. It was not a successful enterprise, as the America Phalanstères lasted an average of 2 years.

Figure 1: The ‘Phalanstère’ in Fourier’s writings and a model built in the United States

The ‘Familistère’ was conceived by a ‘disciple’ of Fourier, Jean-Baptiste Godin (1817-1888) who even financed the unsuccessful American experience of ‘La Reunion’ phalanstère. However he saw the new social order as a basis of industrial development, instead of Fourier’s ‘agricultural’ ideas. His ‘Familistère’ was therefore built near his stove factory, which had recently moved from the inner city to the Guise suburb (has it needed more room to expand his growing business).

The building’s physical formula was maintained, with three volumes joined through its corners, with communal services like daycares, schools, laundries, etc. The ensemble was idealized to be a city within a city, since its autonomy didn’t exclude its interaction with same kind buildings.

Figure 2: the ‘Familistère’ in its context (near the factory) and views of the inner courtyard and from the outside.

The extended Condensed City

The year of 1925 was considered as the apogee of the Russian Constructivism, a precise, mathematical and functional architectural response to society's problems. As a political statement, the 'individual' was diluted for a greater cause, the Community. Any similarity with previous architectural styles, connoted with the bourgeoisie, was avoided, the family structure included. Workers needed a new housing space where one's isolation was promoted: like in the previous 'Phalanstère' each had its own space, with communal services, and children were even raised in day-care facilities where they slept. The idea was to promote social contact, instead of personal one, and its most well-known built manifestation was the 'Dom-komuna' Narkomfin (1928), an example of the 'Social Condenser', who received obvious popular resistance to the living model.

Figure 3: 'Dom-komuna' Narkomfin

The new urban model that supported this structure refused the traditional city for the same reasons that were being acknowledged throughout Europe (overcrowding, poor hygiene, expensive leases). As a building, it was a sum of independent cells, the only space for the manifestation of the 'individual'. These cells were disposed successively and accessed by a shared corridor, intended to be a 'inner' street, more comfortable than an outside one. To the main building would be adjoined smaller buildings destined to be the communal and social spaces.

As this ensemble would (supposedly) support urban life, the city would become a succession of Dom-komunas with exceptional elements like Worker's Clubs, who had services not included in the main buildings. As a quick and efficient way to house workers, the main efforts and means would be applied in the industry sector that jointly would create the 'General Condenser', the city.

Figure 4: urban insertion of the Narkomfin, who remained a single example in its context

The Dom-komuna failed at many levels, since the living unit to the city model, as the family and vicinity relations remained the basis of the soviet society. The Narkomfin, despite being conceived as a transition model (with apartments for families, for instance) remains the example of the model's failure: nowadays a decrepit structure inserted in the surroundings of pre-revolutionary neoclassical buildings.

The London Isokon Flats (1934)¹ tried to apply the model in England, but its 'customers' were far away from the working class, like Agatha Christie, Marcel Breuer, Laszlo Moholy-Nagy e Walter Gropius, a more 'open-minded' clientele that accepted easily the minimum cell, its modern furnishing or even the communal services.

The Condensed City as a Unit

Post-war urban models are personified by Le Corbusier (1887-1965), according to the ideas he presented in the CIAM reunions ('Congrès International d'Architecture Moderne'). From its 4th reunion was born the Athen's Chart where it is written that the new urban solutions needed to be constructed from zero, and not over the old structure that was the traditional city. Hygiene, health, clean air and green spaces were incompatible with its 'horizontal' density, as the 'promiscuity' of its functions: housing, work and leisure.

The new city would be born in a blank sheet where each function had its separated place. Blocks became one single building with numerous floors (to spare ground space) accessed by inner galleries that gave access to apartment doors and some commerce and leisure spaces: these galleries intended to be streets, a place where people would get together and enjoy urban life... As buildings were vertical units, there was enough space among them for green and healthy spaces. There are obvious similarities with the Russian Constructivism, as Le Corbusier and Moisei Ginzburg (Narkomfin's author - 1892-1946) corresponded regularly.

The physical manifestation of Le Corbusier's theories is well-known: mainly the 'Unité d'Habitation de Marseille', but there were others in Nantes, Berlin or Briey-la-Forêt. Both formally and ideologically there are differences between both proposals, as Le Corbusier tends to be apolitical and, despite all, more cautious: there were shared facilities like the day-cares, gymnasium and such, but families were not 'destructured', although idealized as a 'nuclear' one: parents with two children.

Figure 5: The 'Unité d'Habitation de Marseille': its urban context and façade

¹ Authors: Isokon Studio, Wells Coates (1895 – 1958) and Jack Pritchard (1899 – 1992)

Le Corbusier's 'whole' city was never built and its concept 'suffered' from the necessary adaptations to the surrounding's reality: after Marseille the units became smaller, Nantes and Berlin lack the communal services (whose maintenance was very expensive for dwellers) and in Briey shops are in the ground-floor, a more effective, and traditional, solution.

Various factors lead to the concept's deviation: these super-blocks had to be distant from the pre-existing city, but were unable to create its own centric magnet, as housing supporting services were the first to be sacrificed as money ran scarce. Therefore, rather than being independent from the traditional cities, these units and their heirs became totally subordinate to them. Housing speculation caused the increase of building density, depriving buildings from sun or green spaces, resulting all in an urban suburb far from the intended self-supporting city.

Failure and Redemption

The Pruitt-Igoe complex is an example that deserves some attention, given the consequences, both to the buildings and to Modernism. Minoru Yamasaki (1912-1986) designed in the 1950's 33 housing blocks with 11 storeys according to Modernist ideals, although the initial plan intended to have also medium and low rising buildings. The involved costs condemned this proposal, and the final project had more density than the Saint Louis slums. The high rising building dwellings were accessed by galleries, who became a place for robbers, since the most of its population were black, poor and unemployed (as segregation still took place).

Nevertheless 60% of the buildings remained unassigned and were illegally occupied. For all these reasons the whole complex was demolished, starting in March 16th, 1972, the day Modernism died, according to Charles Jencks². The project is generally considered a pure architectural failure, but we must take into account that numerous alterations were made to the original plan. Even the surrounding public spaces were never made, as for leisure and working infrastructures, the whole complex becoming isolated. As the Missouri State ended with Social Housing in 1956, the complex went for rental, but, considering the circumstances, it was considered as the last resort for home-seekers (which explains the partial occupation of the buildings).

Figure 6: The Pruitt-Igoe complex in 1955, shortly after being built

² Jencks, Charles (1984). 'The Language of Post-Modern Architecture', pág. 9 New York: Rizzoli. ISBN 0847805719, ISBN 9780847805716, (quoted in: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pruitt%E2%80%93Igoe#cite_ref-5, [01.2011])

However its dwellers considered the units ‘well designed’³, but as an urban proposal it failed. But we must take into account that this is not an example upon we can make a correct evaluation of Modern urban planning, since its original plan was, as said above, hugely perverted, in its shape and in its social scheme. Even if Modern detractors argue that the Carr Village complex nearby, a low density estate, never had the same problems despite being occupied by the same social stratus.

Figure 7: The second building’s demolition of Pruitt-Igoe broadcasted live in April 1972

Review, Continuity and Immutability

Even before the death of the Modern Movement was decreed there was already a group of architects who believe that it needed to revise its dogmas. The 10th CIAM was prepared by some of those architects who joined forces to create the TEAM X. Led by Allison and Peter Smithson⁴, they considered Modernism decontextualized, Functionalism excessively mechanized and the International Style a loss of identity. The ‘genius loci’ (‘the spirit of the place’) was therefore considered as the project’s starting point, as opposed to previous theories that created the urban context upon the single living cell.

Le Corbusier’s ‘Unités d’Habitation’ were criticized as the perfect example of the previous excesses. The traditional urban life was defended, as the ‘Unités’ couldn’t support it: the shopping floor was a failure, the inner corridors were more like tunnels than streets and even the ground floor lacked the characteristics to support urban life. The counter-proposals tried to rethink these matters and fabulous utopias (like those of the Metabolists) were imagined in order to establish architectural discussion.

The ‘Park Hill Estate’, by Jack Lynn and Ivor Smith, was built in 1957-1961, despite being designed in 1945. The general concept was influenced by Le Corbusier, but also by the Smithson couple who designed a proposal for a competition in Golden Lane, London (won by Geoffry Chamberlin, Peter ‘Joe’ Powell and Christoph Bon⁵). They proposed ‘streets in the sky’, external galleries or corridors of great length and width destined to simulate a street. These corridors, despite being located in very high storeys, managed to allow the entrance of milk distributing cars trough the different floors.

³ **Sherwood, Roger** – *‘Modern Housing Prototypes’*, 7ª Edição, 2001, page 18, Harvard University Press, Cambridge e Londres, Inglaterra, ISBN: 0-674-57942-9

⁴ (1929-1993; 1923-2003)

⁵ (1920 – 1999; 1919 – 1978; 1919 – 1978)

Figure 8: ‘Park Hill Estate’

The organicism of the urban structure and streets was intended to be simulated by the building’s sinuosity and the facades’ dynamic treatment: ‘betón brut’ and orange, yellow and red brick were used to brighten up the continuity of the ‘streets’ (but time and smog turned its colours into a single shade of grey...). Initially a success, the resident’s economical situation and the robberies and violence that took place in the ‘streets in the sky’ (like in ‘Pruitt-Igoe’) made its living very hard. Finally the whole building was nicknamed ‘Saint Quentin’⁶, a famous American jail.

Figure 9: ‘Park Hill’s’ galleries by night, vandalized; facade.

Despite it all, it was recognized in 1988 as ‘Architectural Heritage’ and since then is being rehabilitated according to a project of ‘Grant Associates’ Studio⁷. The tallest blocks were entirely stripped, leaving only the concrete structure, and new social housing but also offices and expensive apartments were built.

We may ask ourselves if this kind of intervention respects the author’s initial intentions. The question is not merely formal, but also idealistic: as social housing, for the ‘poor’, the structure seemed to fail, but has high cost housing it is believed to be a success. Changing the type of residents is the way of making social architecture work, or just Modern high-rise architecture (despite the name they wish to call it)?

⁶ <http://www.guardian.co.uk/gall/0,,547763,00.html>, [02.2011]

⁷ <http://www.grant-associates.uk.com/index.aspx>, [02.2011]

Figure 10: 'Park Hill' being renovated.

At the same time the 'Pruitt-Igoe' was being demolished, the Smithsons 'inaugurate' the 'Robin Hood Gardens' building, that, as the previous example, stands for a model of English post-war Brutalism, whose investigation was based upon high-rise housing. The 'streets in the sky' were its main feature, since the sequence 'house/street/neighbourhood/city' substituted the mere functional differentiation made in the Athens's Chart: 'housing/work/leisure/circulation'.

The 'Robin Hood Gardens' were composed by two long buildings, with small obtuse angles in the middle. The outside gallery was, again, intended to be a street, as the housing units were organised in order for the gallery to have as many doors possible converging into it (a total of three floors had entrances to the same corridor). The doors were inserted in 'niches' in order to offer a small space between the 'street' and the 'house' where people could stop and talk.

Figure 10: 'Robin Hood Gardens'

But, as for the 'Park Hill' experiment, this was again a failure, since its ideological, physical and use characteristics were similar. The concrete facades (opposed to the pure white ones of the International Style) offered the buildings a decadent appearance, diluting at the same time any means of identification of 'their house', 'their street', 'their city' for the various dwellers.

Figure 12: 'Robin Hood Gardens' in its 'urban' context

The architectural community in general believes that the theories supported by the TEAM X failed to be seen in its projects, as the Modernism main faults were not solved. Le Corbusier, however, admired and supported this kind of proposals, himself revising at the moment his own dogmas and proposing the same 'béton brut' in his projects, like in the 'Unités d'Habitation'. Painting each balcony with a set of primary colours did little for the dweller's loss of identity in the whole building, and eventually Briey-la Fôret suffered from abandonment since 1973 and it was even intended to demolish it in 1984. Finally, today it's considered as 'National Monument' by the French authorities, and Marseilles, after being restored in 2010 waits for the title on World Heritage attributed by UNESCO.

Park Hill was also threatened by a demolition process, before the present recovery process, but the 'Robin Hood Gardens' are still under the same menace. The British authorities denied the building's classification as of 'general interest', that would have prevented its demolition. There is a group of organized people that is trying to stop it⁸, but the authorities bunged, for example, any investment in the building's conservation to 'invite' dwellers to leave it for another building...

As for similar structures, the 'Hyde Park Flats', nearby the 'Park Hill Flats, were already partially demolished in 1991 in order to adapt them to the 'World Student Games' (to lodged the athletes). Still in the city of Sheffield, the Kelvin Flats, also a Brutalism piece of architecture from the 1960's were completely demolished

⁸ <http://www.bdonline.co.uk/bd-launches-campaign-to-save-robin-hood-gardens/4000545.article>, [02.2011]

Figure 13: the ‘Hide Park Flats’, before its partial demolition (with the ‘Park Hill Flats’ behind them), and the already completely demolished ‘Kelvin Flats’, also in Sheffield.

The legacy of all these building is sometimes unfair, since its projects suffered from alterations that compromised the whole complex: the ‘Unités’ were never inserted in a full Modern urban settlement that would made them more ‘logical’, and, as it was said, the ‘Pruitt-Igoe’ complex was far from being close from its original plan.

Today’s suburbs tend to look closely to these ‘perverted’ settlements, as they are often composed by high-rise structures very densely build, without any kind of infrastructures whatsoever: leisure, commerce or even other kind of connection to the city they ‘serve’. And, in complete opposition with the idealisms that originated the first structures, these complexes are completely incapable of consisting in urban settlements for themselves, remaining architectural and social ghettos.

Figure 14: Social Housing scheme in Gaia, Portugal

New ‘patterns’ in ‘old fabrics’

As an urban proposal, Modernism shouldn’t be considered as a simple or fast solution for all city’s problems, although it tended to be that way for many years and for many architects, urban planners, and developers (with density and profit as a constant pressure).

As it was referred before, the Smithsons made an urban proposal for Golden Lane, a huge plot in the heart of London that was bombarded during the 2nd World War. As an open wound in the centre of the city, in the middle of a traditional urban fabric, a competition was created in order to round up proposal to solve the physical, urban and social gap created by the ‘blitz’.

Having faith in their own ideas and believing that they were solving the above mentioned Modernist dogmas, the Smithsons rounded up their theories of mega-structures supporting urban life in their ‘streets in the sky’ to propose a complex that would make a great influence in the ‘Park Hill Flats’.

Figure 15: The Smithsons proposal for the Golden Lane Estate

The winning proposal was much different from the above. In fact, the Smithsons never even made to the runners-up, but still they publicized their proposal intensively in the press. Chamberlin, Powell and Bon⁹ won with a proposal that, despite opposite to the one of the Smithsons, it was very faithful to Modernist believes. It was composed by a series of blocks not higher than 6 storeys, except for the tower implanted in the centre of the plot, disposed orthogonally among them, that didn't have any intention of relating to the traditional city's way of occupying plots or quarters. Still, a sort of transition between old and new fabric is given by the curved building facing southwest, and, of course, the fact that the tower sits in the middle of the quarter ‘protects’ passersby from the otherwise dissonant element in the context.

Figure 16: ‘Golden Lane Estate’, by Chamberlin, Powell and Bon (1952): urban context and site plan

⁹ 1920 – 1999 (Geoffry Chamberlin); 1919 – 1978 (Peter ‘Joe’ Powell); 1919 – 1978 (Christoph Bon)

The in-between space among the blocks had nothing to do with the typical private inner-blocks spaces, and it ‘belongs’ to all dwellers. Commerce, housing and pedestrian circulation are kept apart. Even the living cell was completely ‘modern’ and very similar with the ‘Unités d’Habitation’ apartment’s layout: maisonettes with a double-height front balcony (and in the inner staircase, like in Nantes), accessed by an outside gallery, which are completely modernist elements, as they try to create the idea of a ‘private house’ among a large housing estate (a compromise rarely achieved).

Figure 17: ‘Golden Lane Estate’: facades and maisonette’s floor plans

As a proof of the success of the whole housing complex, dwellers have an internet site¹⁰ where they invite everyone to publish their photo in order to recognize them as neighbours and discuss problems and solutions for the complex. A kind of pride also found in Ernst May’s (1886-1970) Praunheim (1927) where the author is acknowledge by its dwellers and is drawings published in their site¹¹. And Praunheim has for its main reference the English Garden Cities...

The ‘Brunswick Centre’ (1959-1972) was another structure that was created to ‘heal’ the thorn fabric of the traditional city, destroyed during the war. The Camden district housed a project by Patrick Hodgkinson (1930 - ...) that, for years was ‘one of the most miserable places in London - a rain-streaked, litter-strewn concrete bunker of empty shop units, whose ambitious, space-age design only accentuated its sense of failure’¹².

Figure 18: ‘Brunswick Centre’ before its recent intervention

The analysis of the project must take into account several problems that occurred during the 13 years that took to complete the whole structure. Initially it was intended to be a luxury estate (since it was located in Camden, a ‘posh’ neighbourhood), but after the promoter abandoned the

¹⁰ <http://www.goldenlaneestate.org/>, [09.2010]

¹¹ <http://www.siedlerverein.de/>, [09.2010]

¹² **Rose, Steve** – ‘*Scrubs up beautifully*’, architecture critique in the October 23 of 2006 edition of the paper ‘The Guardian’; <http://www.guardian.co.uk/artanddesign/2006/oct/23/architecture.communities>, [02.2011]

project the city hall converted the scheme for social housing purposes. At that time, Hodgkinson had already abandoned the project, due to the pressure he felt from the promoters to alter its use, density and appearance.

If we observe Brunswick we recognize a well-known urban structure where housing is set in the above floors and commerce stands in the ground floor. Here the buildings open to the surrounding streets as they intend to establish continuity among them and the ‘inner’ street that was created inside the complex. The entrance to the dwellings is made in the facades facing the older streets in order to maintain its character with mixed uses, a truly urban dynamic.

Figure 19: Camden before the bombardments and the ‘Brunswick Centre’ and how it was intended to connect to its surroundings

The chosen aesthetics seem to deny all this purposes, with its access system (the outside gallery), the higher density of the blocks or their shape as football benches, and the use of ‘betón brut’ for the finishing of the complex. The architect, even if he affiliated himself to the heritage of Le Corbusier and others, worked with Alvar Aalto, that he refers as one of main influences. As such, searching for a more integrated character for its buildings, he idealized them in red brick (like the surrounding ones), abandoning the idea because of the involved costs. So he turned to a Georgian influence proposing a painting in ‘Regency Stucco’, an idea again refused for reasons of cost and real estate speculation.

After becoming a ‘social housing ghetto’¹³ (the architect intended to mix uses and social stratus), a new private company proposed Hodgkinson to rehabilitate the complex, which he accepted,

¹³ **Patrick Hodgkinson**, quoted in the article: **Rose, Steve** – ‘*Scrubs up beautifully*’, <http://www.guardian.co.uk/artanddesign/2006/oct/23/architecture.communities>, [02.2011]

with the help of David Levitt (...-...) and David Bernstein (...-...). If the project recovered its intended painting job, it was also revised in its public spaces, reducing, for instance, the width of the inner commercial street ('scaled' according to the surroundings) and building a block at the top of the same street, that before ended facing a blind wall.

Figure 20: the 'Brunswick Centre' after its renovation process in 2006

Nowadays the 'Brunswick Centre' is a well-succeeded shopping area, as it stands close to the city centre and it's served by public transportation. And, of course, the 2006 renovation gave back its dignity but also changed its dwellers: David Levitt himself lives there and the 'ghetto' referred before has ended. And mainly because of a well made intervention in public space.

Conclusions and Questions

Despite the 'happy ending' there are a number of questions aroused that put into question the real success of this complex, and of all large housing estates. Despite 'Brunswick's' smaller scale, we must take into account that part of its failure was its exclusive use as social housing. And, of course, its success was due to the intervention of private investors that ended up changing its 'audience'.

As for 'Golden Lane Estate', its promoter was in fact the City Hall. But the housed city workers still tend to be financially above social dwellers, because as 'workers', they have a stable financial situation. And, at the end, the dwellers tended to be middle-classed and nowadays apartments in 'Golden Lane' are, at least, expensive... due to its success.

The 'Narkomfin' failure was due to its ambitious social intentions, but the British 'Isokon' building found its dwellers among well-read members, who knew how to adapt themselves to minimum areas and minimalist furniture...

Figure 21: 'Isokon Buildin', formerly known by 'Lawn Road Flats'

The solution founded for the ‘Park Hill Flats’ was its total reconversion, adding offices and luxury apartments to an originally exclusively social housing building. Still, mixing social stratus (like upscale dwellers with low income ones, as Hodgkinson also intended for ‘Brunswick’) it’s a solution yet to be proven efficient and it adds more doubts about the possibility of large housing estates for social uses being valid solutions.

The architectonic solutions they represent tend to promote decreasing ‘urban’ living quality, as they have a propensity to be located in the outskirts of the main cities, which is a consequence that we can point also to the developers (private or public) that promote the complexes: the lack of investment denies these intended cities the necessary elements to make them urban (like commerce, leisure areas, etc.) and creates ‘ghettos’, dorms for poor people that tend to promote violence (as a last resort), made easier in large housing estates access systems, for instance.

Nevertheless, for the same reasons, we probably can’t make a fully illustrated assessment of most of these proposals, since they never were completed as they were intended to be: the ‘Unités’ remained lonely buildings, and not part of the complex for which they were idealized (despite the shopping floors/streets in the middle of the building were a proven failure).

The anonymity promoted by these kinds of structures seems to be general nowadays, in any kind of housing buildings, where people hardly know any of their neighbours. And for some this is a valued characteristic, making the ‘streets in the sky’ useless. For others, it is a problem to be solved, like in ‘Golden Lane’ where neighbours want to get together... as they represent no ‘danger’ for the above reasons.

So, the questions remain: was Modern Architecture incapable of changing the world, or it never had the real chance to do so? Is it the scale or the dwellers that make huge structures ineffective? And if so, what lessons should we take from not so big complexes, built ‘inside’ the city, but that were successful according to their dwellers? Finally, are there any easy solutions?

Figures

Fig. 1: <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Phalanst%C3%A8re>, [01.2011]

Fig. 2: Google Earth, 49°53'59.02"N, 3°37'40.86"E, image taken in 01/01/2006;
<http://pt.wikipedia.org/wiki/Famelist%C3%A9rio>, [01.2011]

Fig. 3: <http://www.dearchitecturablog.com/?p=618>, [01.2011]

Fig. 4: Google Earth, 51°33'6.64"N, 0° 9'43.74"W, image taken in 01/01/2006, [01.2011]

Fig. 5: Google Earth, 47°11'18.55"N, 1°34'6.19"W, data da imagem: 15/03/2007
<http://www.panoramio.com/photo/33239870>, [01.2011]

Fig. 6 and 7: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pruitt%E2%80%93Igoe#cite_ref-5, [01.2011]

Fig. 8: Google Earth, 53°22'47.57"N, 1°27'29.48"W, image taken in 10/04/2010,: http://www.e-architect.co.uk/leeds/sheffield_building.htm, [01.2011]

Fig. 9: <http://www.flickr.com/photos/fictionalfuture/3938273865/in/faves-ellyoracle/>;
<http://www.parkhillflats.co.uk/redev.html>; <http://www.flickr.com/photos/paolomargari/451545773/>, [02.2011]

Fig. 10: <http://www.sublimephotography.co.uk/eastendphotos/isleofdogs/pages/robin.htm>, [01.2011]

Fig. 11: <http://www.sublimephotography.co.uk/eastendphotos/isleofdogs/pages/robin.htm>, [01.2011]

Fig. 12: Google Earth, 51°30'34.13"N, 0° 0'32.76"W, image taken in 05/04/2006, [01.2011]

Fig. 13: <http://www.parkhillflats.co.uk/history.html>, [01.2011]

Fig. 14: <http://maps.google.pt/maps?ll=41.096199,-8.591555&spn=0,0.005681&z=18&lc=com.google.webcams&layer=c&cbll=41.096129,-8.591502&panoid=MUjfpNac6QyBtfX73qnMrw&cbp=12,62.48,,0,4.83>, [02.2011]

Fig. 15: <http://archiflux.wordpress.com/2010/09/10/ap-smithson-golden-lane/>, [01.2011]

Fig. 16: Google Earth, 51°31'18.75"N, 0° 5'41.25"W, image taken in 27/06/2010;
http://housingprototypes.org/project?File_No=GB008, [05.2011]

Fig. 17: <http://www.flickr.com/photos/doctorcasino/2883343401/in/photostream/>, [05.2011]; author's drawing, based upon the model presented in: **French, Hilary** - *'Key Urban Housing of the Twentieth Century'*, 2008 Laurence King Publishing Ltd, ISBN-13: 978-1-85669-564-0

Fig. 18: <http://www.vlugt.co.uk/hetero08.html>, fig. 14, 10 e 12, [02.2011]

Fig. 19: <http://brunswickwcl.wordpress.com/2010/09/21/historic-maps-of-the-brunswick-site/>;
<http://www.vlugt.co.uk/hetero08.html>, fig. 13, [02.2011]

Fig. 20: <http://www.levittbernstein.co.uk/architecture/retail-offices/?image=1&page=1>, [02.2011]

Fig. 21: <http://www.stace.co.uk/projects/detail.cfm?item=97>, [05.2011]

References

- Baptista, Luís V.** – *'Cidade e Habitação Social, o Estado Novo e o Programa das Casas Económicas em Lisboa'*, 1999, Celta Editora, ISBN 972-774-044-8
- Benevolo, Leonardo** – *'História da Arquitectura Moderna'*, 2004, 3ª edição – segunda reimpressão, Editora Perspectiva S. A.
- Benevolo, Leonardo** – *"O último capítulo da Arquitectura Moderna – reimpressão"*, 2009 Coleção Arquitectura e Urbanismo, Edições 70, ISBN: 978 972 44 1402 7
- Caselli, Cristina Kanya** – *"100 anos de habitação mínima. Ênfase na Europa e no Japão"*, Dissertação de Mestrado em Arquitectura e Urbanismo, Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie, São Paulo, 2007, http://biblioteca.universia.net/html_bura/ficha/params/id/34292049.html, [08.2008]
- Frampton, Keneth** – *'Historia critica de la arquitectura moderna'* - Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A. 08029 Barcelona, 1996, ISBN 84-252-1628-1
- French, Hilary** - *'Key Urban Housing of the Twentieth Century'*, 2008 Laurence King Publishing Ltd, ISBN-13: 978 1 85669 564 0
- Lynch, Kevin** – *'A Imagem da Cidade'*, 1960, Lisboa, Edições 70, 2009, ISBN 978-972-44-1411-9
- Sherwood, Roger** – *'Modern Housing Prototypes'*, 7ª Edição, 2001, Harvard University Press, Cambridge e Londres, Inglaterra, ISBN: 0-674-57942-9
- Teige, Karel** – *"The Minimum Dwelling"*, 2002, The MIT Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts, ISBN 0-262-20136-4

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'The Minimum Cell as a House: ideas and forms in social housing in search of a Home'

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The Minimum Cell as a House: ideas and forms in social housing in search of a Home

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Abstract

Throughout the last century efforts have been made in order to correspond to a high demand of housing in Europe. From the high density of the traditional city, the consequences of the Industrial Revolution or the hardships of war(s), social housing has been a laboratory of experiences that include living space, shape, volume and urban solutions. The obtained results navigate through traditional answers to the most radical experiments, but at search for the same thing: a sense of belonging sustained in the idea of the 'house' in its various demonstrations, such as shape, association, internal space and ways of use.

The present analysis tries to search within the twentieth century this 'house' in various social or subsidize experiences, according to its various restrictions, of cost and effectiveness, for example. From the single houses of a garden city to the cells of Le Corbusier's Unités d'Habitation, each present an interpretation of the traditional house in its shape and use, in a more or less obvious manner.

We will take in to account different perspectives in the formalization and use of the housing cell, starting with the inner spatial solutions used in various case-studies, from the point of view of the dweller (according to its traditions 'versus' their idealized house) and the architect (who tries to substitute tradition for efficiency, or uses tradition as a basis for modernity). After that we will approach the house as a shape or single unit, and the way that its idea was formalized as single houses or the vertical sum of individual units, always taking into account their ideological and political backgrounds.

Keywords: Minimum, house, dwelling, home.

Introduction

Among the models of social housing, since the beginning of the use of the term, there has always been the need to balance the 'wanted house' and the 'feasible house'. The boundaries defined by cost always implied a compromise between the idealized house by the tenant (maintaining its customs) or by the architect (through the idealization of new spatial solutions, new ways of living)

Definition

What is intended with this paper is how the 'house', in its more elemental shape and idea, has always been manifested in the way dwellers wanted to live, or others idealize they should. This 'house' it's its most primeval shape, as an isolated building, maybe bucolic, that raises a sense of 'ownership' (opposed to the 'shared' urban dwelling, for instance).

It might sound strange to search such 'house' in social or subsidized housing, because the main ideas that occurs are those of density or stacking where an isolated element seems impossible to recognize. But this is an idea that is possible to demystify because, in between the dweller's dream home and the architect's ideal one, that 'house' was a frequent presence in the XX century housing projects.

The House as spatial definition: use and symbol

The dialectics established among the dreamed house and the proposed one were based on many factors, among them dweller and architect, cost and idea, available space and its use or symbolism. This latest item states for the more controversial one, since there is an encounter among the dweller's ancient living ways and its desire to reproduce his ideas of another social stratum. In the architect's point of view there is a need to respond to new realities, new ways of life (idealized or not), rejecting any reference to supposed inadequate models.

Popular aspirations

In the early XX's, worker's living conditions were rather bad, as the result of overcrowded cities where the poorer families only could afford a room, or at best, part of a shared house. However, since they were coming mostly from the countryside, they 'brought' with them their ancient lifestyles, based upon '(...) big rural kitchens, centered in the fireplace¹'. However, the city brings to their knowledge new models of housing, including the bourgeois house.

Figure 1: 'Popular' kitchens

Bourgeois Ambitions

So, opposed to the rural model, synonymous of poverty, the bourgeois model becomes an aspiration, in its shape, but also because of the social (and financial) statement it symbolizes.

There was, of course, the impossibility to offer each family a bourgeois house, but the goal is kept, even if 'translated' to small spaces that intended to be a symbol rather than something really useful. After the World War I the British government creates a panel of woman advisers in order to give a female perspective to the creation of new housing types. This was a way to acknowledge their part in home management but also to recognize their efforts during the war. Their solution referred a small room by the entrance used as a space for receiving guests, for example², but it didn't had much success, since the costs an area involved were unbearable and with no 'practical uses'.

¹ Nunes, João Pedro Silva - *Lisboa, arquitectura e urbanismo à escala humana: planeamento urbano e arquitectura de habitação em Olivais Sul, Lisboa 1959-1969*, 2007, Câmara Municipal de Lisboa, ISBN: 978-972-8543-08-2

² Swenarton, M.- *Building the New Jerusalem*, HIS BRE Press, 2008, pages 46-7

It must be said, however, that there is modest investigation, among the one consulted, that tried to deal with the ‘real’ use of the space in social housing, to perceive, for instance, if those aspirations were still ‘manifested’ in common spaces. Nevertheless there were some inquiries done in order to establish the population’s ‘dream house’, especially during the Italian Neo-realism, a movement that tried to make an approach to the ‘real’ populations (as opposed to the ‘ideal’ dweller of the Modern Movement). The INA-Casa process (INA: Istituto Nazionale Assicurazione; Casa: house) included the participation of the populations in the design of their new houses (part of their salary was retained voluntarily to build them), and the surveys revealed that 25% of the dwellers wanted a dinning space in the kitchen. This ‘hided’ the intention of having the living room as the single ‘domestic public’ space, where guests where received in an always ‘tidy’ area, while the kitchen was the really everyday living area. That led to the creation on the ‘lavoro’ (‘working room’), an in-between space amidst the kitchen and the living room where housework or hobbies could be carried out.

Figure 2: Nucleo Noncello, 1964 (Giulio Brunetta, 1906-1978)

In the Portuguese experience of ‘Olivais’ in the 1960’s, near Lisbon, the INA-Casa process had a great influence in the way the building process was methodically conceived (defining local materials and construction methods easily used and done). There was a level of austerity difficult to understand nowadays, like the absence of hot water (except in the tub) in the lower rent buildings, but, as in Italy, there was the explicit intention to offer as many square meters as possible. Sergio Fernandez, a Portuguese architect, refers the Italian ‘lavoro’³ in some buildings, but there also experiences similar to the ‘laboratory-kitchen’ or in-between solutions. That is why Nuno Portas classified the whole urban intervention as ‘experimental’⁴, although in its own proposal (with Bartolomeu Costa Cabral) he chose to offer a kitchen with enough space for the house tasks (while the ‘lounge’ maintained its own dining area for special occasions).

³ Nunes, João Pedro Silva - *‘Lisboa, arquitectura e urbanismo à escala humana: planeamento urbano e arquitectura de habitação em Olivais Sul, Lisboa 1959-1969’*, 2007, Câmara Municipal de Lisboa, page 137, ISBN: 978-972-8543-08-2

⁴ Idem, page 147

Figure 3: Housing building in Olivais, 1963 (Nuno Portas, 1934-... and Bartolomeu Costa Cabral, ...-...)

There was an inquiry to understand the dweller's reaction to their new homes, and there was a great deal of satisfaction, since their previous houses were, to say the least, shanty. But the internal solutions were not understood by them as a 'final proposal', as most of the dwellers adapted the existing spaces to reach their own expectations and ambitions. Sometimes the complete opposite of what the architect intended.

In the lowest rent buildings the kitchen opened to the lounge was considered intolerable, because it made impossible to keep private their house tasks. The 'modernist' hatch between the kitchen and the dining room was closed, but the most impressive change was the use of a bedroom as a 'proper dining room' (alluding to the bourgeois house), even if some of the family members had to renounce to their own privacy (by sharing their rooms or even sleeping in the living room).

Figure 4: Housing building in Olivais, category 1, 1963 (João Vasconcelos Esteves, ...-...)

Interestingly, in the higher categories of the subsidized program that consisted Olivais (and the previous Alvalade neighborhood) there was still some traces of the 'old' bourgeois house, with a maid's room with its own bathroom. Even if the external image of the building was undoubtedly Modern.

Figure 5: Housing Building in Alvalade, 1959 (nicknamed ‘Bairro das Estacas’: ‘Pole District’, because of the ‘pilotis’), with maid quarters (Ruy d’Athouguia, 1922-2004)

Proving that the shapes that manifest old habits can still be of use, this solution was mentioned as an important one for today’s households, where sons and daughters tend to stay at their parent’s house for much longer: this private ‘apartment’ would thereby be a solution for their need of independence⁵.

Plebeian Ambitions

Among the models gathered in this study, little are those who intend to make a direct reference to popular or vernacular roots, even if we can relate the Italian ‘lavoro’ with the desire to establish a ‘home’ around the ‘modern’ fire place: the kitchen. João Pedro Pena Lopes interprets this desire in a very clear way, putting the apartment’s fireplace in the kitchen, instead of the living room, keeping this space as an occasional one.

Figure 6: Housing Building in Meda, 2001 (João Pedro Pena Lopes, ...-...)

We can identify a phenomenon of transport of the ‘plebeian house’ by the future tenants. We must take into account that what a person desires is, in most situations, based upon on its own knowledge, in their own experience. The SAAL (‘Serviço de Apoio Ambulatório Local’ – ‘Local Support Service’) was a movement, as political as architectural, that intended to give people a decent home. Starting immediately after the 25th of April 1974 (when the Authoritarian Portuguese Regime ‘fell’), the idea was to promote

⁵ **Monteys, Xavier; Fuertes, Pere** – “*Casa Collage – un ensayo sobre la arquitectura de la casa*”, 4th edition, 2005, Editorial Gustavo Gili, SA, Barcelona, ISBN 84-252-1869-1

local and direct contact between architects and dwellers, which meant that the populations would participate actively in their own home's designs. In one of the inquiries a housewife demanded a stone floor for her kitchen in order to have a place to light a fire. Far from being amusing, this shows how decadent their previous life was, but also the ignorance of something as simple as a stove or even a fireplace. Therefore the desire to keep upon one's known models.

The architect's visions and predictions

Being a 'Modernist' ambition to start from a clean slate, where all the ancient housing types would be forgotten, some architects maintained for a long time the presence of the 'enfilade', where rooms with no specific use would succeed one another. Karl Ehn, in his 'Karl Marx Hof' (1926) chooses the traditional 'enfilade' in his one-bedroom apartments, while with the same 53 square meters Alexander Klein, in Bad Dürrenberg (1928) offered in his 'C2 Cell' a 2 bedroom apartment with a 'fully equipped' bathroom. The difference stands in the assumption that social housing couldn't be the mere adjustment of the bourgeois house to a smaller scale. A new Type in housing should be created in order to respond to the new needs of society, culturally and sanitarilly.

Figure 7: Karl Marx Hof, 1926 (Karl Ehn, 1884 – 1957) and Bad Dürrenberg, C2 Cell, 1928, Alexander Klein (1879-1961)

Modern living

The traditional scheme of 'reception-private-service' is therefore substituted by the modern 'public-private-service' sequence, where each spacial definition had a new meaning:

Reception > Public: to 'entertain' was understood as a ritual where a visit was prepared trough a special room where, for example, the family's valuables where exposed. Its use was occasional, remaining the family in a daily basis in the 'private' areas. When it becomes 'public', it still is a space where visitors had access in most occasions, but it loses its occasional status to become the household's gathering room (although still competing with the kitchen). In fact, Modern architects thought that would be illogical to try to offer 'representation' spaces when areas where so scarce.

Private > Private: in this context the house's private spaces is re-evaluated: the bedroom becomes bedrooms, plural, translating a need for privacy among the household, rather than the household and visitors or friends. The real 'revolution', however, occurs when children are separated according to their gender (creating the three bedroom house). Even if these rooms are minimum, privacy is still an important achievement, when comparing to the previous houses for the poor.

Service > Service: in the bourgeois house the service areas include a spacious kitchen, a pantry and even the maid's bedroom. In this context, 'service' included the staff, and not a mere definition of 'space'. Modernism abolished, obviously, the staff in their social housing models, and service areas became

‘practical’ ones, like a bathroom (another ‘achievement’) or a kitchen: its social aspect was denied and it was intended like a mere extension of the human body: like a laboratory to mix elements (like in the Frankfurt-kitchen, by Ernst May and Grete Schütte-Lihotsky).

Figure 8: Reception > Public; Private > Private; Service > Service

Moderate Modern

After the II World War Modernism started a revision process where its dogmas were reviewed, formal aspects included. The ‘New Nordic Empiricism’ was the starting point, followed by the Italian ‘Neo-realism’. In this specific example, as it was said, the future dwellers were listened, in order to try to understand their needs and dreams. The main difference between the INA-Casa process and the Olivais Portuguese experience was the order of the process itself, since the inquiries to the population were made after the houses have been built. The consequence was that in Portugal many dwellers revealed to be dissatisfied (making the above mentioned alterations), while in Italy, far from being a consensual process, there were some constants among projects that proved, partially, that there was some consensus (like the need of a ‘lavoro’).

Unmeasured Modern

A small reference here to the Russian Constructivism, where the entire notion of the traditional house was destroyed, starting with its occupants, the traditional family. The Individual would be the main unit of the ‘shelter’ since all was defined according to the inexistence of any family ties. Communal spaces substituted the kitchen, the bathrooms; bedroom would be bigger in order to offer a private lounge space to its occupant, when the apartment was shared, in the ‘transition’ model from the traditional house to the final Dom-kommuna.

Figure 9: Dom-kommuna Narkomfin, 1927 (Moisei Ginzburg, 1892 - 1946)

The ‘House’ as a Shape: signs and symbols

The development of the idea of ‘social housing’, even before it was called this way, was based upon the urgent need to solve housing problems in the big cities where the Industrial Revolution had a strong presence. The migrating population left their houses in the country and flew to the city, where the homes they could afford were shared rooms resulting from speculation.

A political instrument

The previous life of the populations was far from being ideal, since their houses had no comfort at all, and famine was common, as agriculture started to decline. Even so, a bucolic image of a little hut in the countryside was starting to being built, as the complete opposite of the contemporary city.

Garden-cities were hardly ‘social housing’, but they were the first models to explore the idea of an urban settlement in harmony with nature. In Letchworth (1905) Geoffrey Lucas (1872-1947) referred that the houses were design in order to look like cottages rather than small houses⁶. This was a posture denied by Modern architects, like Mies Van der Rohe (1886-1969) who headed the Weissenhof Colony (1927). Numerous architects participated in order to show healthy new homes⁷. Their image was white, pure, Modern, the opposite of the previous example, and once empowered, the Nazi regime considered it intolerable. It promotes the isolated house with a ‘traditional’ sloped roof, as in Rottweil, a settlement built far away from the city centres. The benefits were double for the regime: the poorer were kept out of sight and people were supposed to be happy with their cottages.

Figure 10: Weissenhof, 1927 (Mies van der Rohe, 1886-1969) and Rottweil, 1937-1940 (...)

The Portuguese totalitarian regime of the ‘Estado Novo’ (‘New Estate’) also tried this path in their own proposal of social housing, with the ‘Casas Económicas’ (Economical Houses) 1918 project. The urban structure was still the bourgeois one, and in 1928, trough the assumed influence of the Garden-Cities, single houses surrounded by a little garden typology was used to achieve that peaceful and bucolic character, proving that the process was ‘filled with a strong symbolism and an elaborate ideology’⁸.

The reference to an upraised social status is thus obvious in these experiments that we can assimilate, in most cases, to right-wing political thinking (Garden-cities excluded, of course). The basis of all these conceptions of a ‘single house for the poor’ was the traditional family, precisely what was put in to question by the Soviet Communists, who intended, as referred, a communitarian living in buildings conceived according to a beehive. Even so, the communist regime became suspicious of this ‘family revolution’, opting later for more ‘soothing’ solutions for the Russian dwellers. According to Bruno Zevi (quoted by Leonardo Benevolo) totalitarianism is always hostile to Modernism, since it admits free-will and self-determination, a menace to the established order or at least a question better not raised⁹.

⁶ www.tomorrowsgardencity.com/system/files/25_July_1905.pdf, [01.2009]

⁷ **Schoenauer, Norbert** – ‘6,000 Years of Housing, revised and expanded edition’, W. W. Norton & Company, New York, NY 10110, 2000; ISBN 0-393-73052-2

⁸ **Nunes, João Pedro Silva** - ‘Lisboa, arquitectura e urbanismo à escala humana: planeamento urbano e arquitectura de habitação em Olivais Sul, Lisboa 1959-1969’, 2007, Câmara Municipal de Lisboa, page 148, ISBN: 978-972-8543-08-2

⁹ **Benevolo, Leonardo** – ‘História da Arquitectura Moderna’, 2004, 3th edition – second reprint, Editora Perspectiva S. A.

Singular/Plural

We are used to think about the Modern Movement as a clean slate in architecture, and in its models we can hardly recognise the ‘house’ we’ve talking about. As this was considered inadequate, new types were proposed although nowadays we tend to think that the real dwellers (not as imagined by Modernists) were the real inadequate elements.

The house was the primal element of all Modernist Architecture, as there was a need to urgently respond to the housing shortage that derived into a stacking solution, instead of the isolated house. Efficiency and repetition become housing standards, neighbourhoods becoming a repetition of standardized cells. Ernst May (1886-1970), for instance, saw the city as a linear process based upon repetition¹⁰.

According to the ‘new’ city, that was idealized backwards (house > building > block > city), its growth was an inverse process, starting with the individual towards the collective. This was an attempt to overcome housing shortage, speculation and urgency.

However Modernist Architecture wasn’t that ‘cold’ or disconnected of the concept of the ‘primitive hut’, as the idea of the House was present in many proposal from Modernist Architects, even if disguised under their efficiency and novelty. Some extreme functionalists proposed a scientific approach that established almost mathematical proportions, in area, sunlight and air, according to the number of occupants of a determined cell. The most famous example was Alexander Klein (1879-1961), whose ‘cells’ for Bad Dürrenberg had variable area if one room was to be occupied by one or two dwellers.

Figure 11: Cells ‘C2’, ‘C7’, ‘C9’ and ‘C16’: for couples with one children, two children with separate rooms, two same sex children sharing a room and three or four children; the area of the lounge increases with the number of dwellers.

Unit/Multiple

The idea of repetition, even if the units were infinitely stacked or side-by-side, it can correspond to a definition of ‘house’, formal and anthropologically, where the dweller is able to recognize its ‘own’ house. Le Corbusier (1887-1965) produces an important investigation upon these principles, even if most of them remained pure experiments. The ‘Pavillon de l’Esprit Nouveau’ was conceived as temporary structure for the 1925 Paris’ Decorative Arts International Exhibition. Rather than a pavilion, it was a house, a duplex striped of ornament that served as well as manifest against the notion of ‘decorative arts’. Demolished after the exhibition, it served as a unit for the project, never built, of the ‘Immeuble-Villas’, where those duplex houses, with a private courtyard were stacked and joined side-by-side in order to compose a big housing building.

This project was no social housing building, but illustrates the house has a shape and a meaning in Corbusier’s thinking. In 1925 he finally manages to put together a neighbourhood destined to the workers of the Frugés Company, in Pessac. The ‘Quartier Moderne’ was composed by side-by-side houses (the

¹⁰ **Montaner, Josep Maria** – *‘Depois do Movimento Moderno: Arquitectura da segunda metade do séc. XX’* – Editorial Gustavo Gili, Barcelona, 2001, pág. 139, ISBN 84-252-1828-4

Modern compromise with House and Density), and it was based in a 5 by 5 meters cube upon which the traditional local houses were made. Besides his efforts, the use of a traditional construction process, rather than the idealized (but hard to put into practice) ‘projected’ concrete elevated the cost of the houses to a level that a worker hardly could sustain.

Figure 12: the ‘Pavillon de l’Esprit Nouveau’, the ‘Immeuble-Villas and the ‘Quartier Modern Frugés’

Street/House

The relation that is established between the street and the cell is something that cannot be set apart when thinking about a ‘house’. It’s a place for conviviality and community life, especially if the ‘inner cell’ is as small as it tends to be in social housing. The traditional European city, dense, vertical and clustered, wasn’t able to offer this kind of use of the street with quality or hygiene, but since the first planned city expansions a more open and useful outer space become part of the commission.

The Spangen Quarter (1919), from Michiel Brinkman (1873-1925), was one of the first examples to use the outside gallery not only as a mere entrance to the flats, but also as a space capable of supporting urban life. And, until today, remains one of the most successful. This ‘elevated street’ lies in the 2nd floor of the building, since the flats below have direct access to the ‘ground street’. The upper flats are duplexes so they can all have direct access to the gallery/street.

Over the time there have been many examples of these streets in the air, but their failure was due to a question of scale, that is mastered in Spangen: the gallery has a width between 2,2 and 3,3 meters and it’s only two floors away from the ground. Apart from this there were also elevators that made possible to the milkman and the baker to deliver milk and bread as in any ground floor. Therefore the identification of a ‘house’ occurs not only when each entrance accesses the flat directly from the street, but also because these ‘streets’, real or virtual, are defined as such by the kind of urban living it supports.

Figure 13: The Spangen Quarter: the galleries and the ‘cells’ (ground/first floor; second/third floor)

Although the top floors have duplexes, in the flats below Brinkman chooses to overlay single-floor flats, although the top one as a private stair directly from the ground. Despite being a miscellaneous solution between the traditional ‘horizontal street’ and the very Modern’ vertical street’, it proves wrong Keneth

Frampton when he states that vertical streets never were an effective solution compared to the ones in the ground¹¹.

House/Street

After the 2nd World War the urban solutions reviewed completely the traditional city, abandoning the elements that had been defining it throughout the centuries: the street, the plot or the block. Buildings became out of scale, as a result of an almost infinite stacking of individual cells served by communal daycares, washrooms or even stores. Even if the duplex and the gallery are inherited from previous experiments, the ‘house’ becomes undoubtedly the starting point of the ‘new’ settlements. Le Corbusier’s ‘Unités d’Habitation’ are known as the main example of this new urban attitude, mainly the one in Marseille (1947-1953), although there are others: Nantes (1955), Berlin (1958), Briey-la-Forêt (1963) or Firminy (1965), these being, perhaps, more interesting for us since their units were smaller, for example.

Figure 14: Unité d’Habitation in Briey-la-Forêt (1963): section, juxtaposition of cells and photo

As a result of the ‘L-shaped’ living cell, conceived as bottle supported by a cellaret (the structure) the street becomes an inner-corridor supposed to support urban life. As for the cell, the attempt was to recreate a house, a three-bedroom duplex for a ‘normal’ family. The living-room has a double-height ceiling (partially), with a balcony which was intended to be an outdoor extension of the cell, just like in a ‘house’: the façade of the flat was a two-storey residence...

House/Building

This kind of solution for the façade is very important for the identification of ‘my house’ among the other cells. In the previous example the cells remained rather anonymous, due to the whole scale of the building, but in 1952 Chamberlin, Powell e Bon¹² conceived a whole estate just in the middle of London that ‘solved the problem’. In an area devastated by war, a truly ‘Modern’ urban layout was juxtaposed to a traditional fabric, but in an attempt to dialogue with the surroundings, buildings were smaller, ‘shorter’, more human, if we prefer. The layout of the cell is very similar to the one in the ‘Unités d’Habitation’, despite occupying just one ‘side’ of the gallery (which became open). The living-room balcony was double-heightened so the above bedroom would lean over it. As the balcony was ‘closed’ sideways, the dweller, from his bedroom or lounge, only saw his house’s outer space. ‘My house’ became identifiable from the inside and the outside.

¹¹ Frampton, Kenneth – ‘Historia critica de la arquitectura moderna’ - Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A. 08029 Barcelona, 1996, pág. 273, ISBN 84-252-1628-1

¹² 1920 – 1999 (Geoffrey Chamberlin); 1919 – 1978 (Peter ‘Joe’ Powell); 1919 – 1978 (Christoph Bon)

Figure 15: Golden Lane Estate (1952): rear façade (gallery and bedrooms), front façade (with the double-height balcony) and typical cell.

As a proof of the success of the whole housing complex, dwellers have an internet site¹³ where they invite all dwellers to publish their photo in order to recognize them as neighbours and discuss problems and solutions for the complex. A kind of pride also found in Ernst May's (1886-1970) Praunheim (1927) where the author is recognized and his drawings published in their site¹⁴.

Building/Maze

The main element that differentiates the previous examples is thus the scale of the complex, as in the promotion of a 'sense of belonging' (and not as an evaluation of the whole architectural project). The use of solutions as the duplex, the open gallery and such cannot overcome reality, even if theory tries to defend any gallery as a 'street in the sky'. The 'Robin Hood Gardens' project (1972), from Alison (1928-1993) and Peter Smithson (1923-2003) tried to encourage a review of Modernism's urban dogmas, arguing that they promoted anonymous and sterile cities. The cells were one floor and two floors solutions (upwards and downwards) in an attempt to converge as many doors as possible to the gallery. The cell's entrances were positioned in 'niches' in the gallery so neighbours could meet at their doorsteps talking and saying their hellos.

Nevertheless, the anonymity of the whole building and its galleries, which all looked the same with no special features that qualified them as 'my street' where 'my house' is, condemned the architects' intentions: as a solution, it became not much different from another supposedly Modern buildings (plenty of proposals we see in our suburbs are mere misrepresentations of Modernism's intentions).

Figure 16: 'Robin Hood Gardens' (1972): the building and its galleries.

House/House

The fall of the totalitarian regime in Portugal creates the opportunity to express political alternatives to fascism, but also to try out architectural experiments that were forbidden by the 'Português Suave' ('Mild Portuguese Style') defended by the regime. In 1974 the references were no longer Modern ones, even less

¹³ <http://www.goldenlaneestate.org/>, [09.2010]

¹⁴ <http://www.siedlerverein.de/>, [09.2010]

the soviet Constructivism. The INA-Casa in Italy was taken into account, since its purposes fitted the Portuguese needs: suppress housing shortage, to promote construction and create jobs. The use of common labour to build with traditional techniques helped in every aspect, and in Portugal dwellers were even supposed to help to build their own homes.

The inquiries made to the population, inherited from the INA-Casa but also considered necessary after the partial success of Olivais, due to the ‘resistance’ to Modern solutions (kitchens, dining-rooms...). Nevertheless, between the north and the south of Portugal different aspirations were listened, according to the models that the future dwellers had, even if the political/practical program (the above mentioned SAAL) was the same.

The architects also played an important role in this process, and up North there was the consensus among designers that the traditional city needed mending, since the pre-existing spatial and social order seemed convenient: the attempt was to keep populations in their context, the city, not a suburb. The ‘house’ becomes the base-unit of the projects of, for example, Álvaro Siza, perhaps still a Modern idea, but that was adapted to the surrounding scale: the row-houses in ‘Bairro de São Victor’ (1976) reveals influences from the Modernist projects of Oud or Taut¹⁵ and corresponds to an economical way to give dwellers ‘a house’.

Figure 17: ‘São Victor’ neighbourhood, 1976

The need to establish a closer dialogue with its surroundings in the ‘Bairro da Bouça’, who were higher, for instance, than in ‘São Victor’, defines a four-storey building, but even here the main unit is still the cell, or the house: the building is like the overlap of two rows of houses, duplexes with a direct access to the ground floor or to a gallery in the upper row.

Figure 18: ‘Bouça’ neighbourhood: the 1977 project, revised internally in 2004 when the construction was completed.

¹⁵ Costa, Alexandre Alves quoted by **Bandeirinha, José António** – “O processo SAAL e a arquitectura no 25 de Abril de 1974”, 2007, Imprensa da Universidade de Coimbra, page 219, ISBN: 978-972-8704-76-6

Figure 19: 'Bouça' neighbourhood, 2004, after completion/renovation.

The upper gallery, very narrow, as no use as a cell's outdoor space, or even as a meeting spot. In one hand, we can consider that as a flaw, since offering more outside space, especially in social housing, is always a plus, as people are not obliged to make use of it. On the other hand, in 1977 Siza Vieira had already realized how utopian the 'streets in the sky' were, preferring to design a simple outside corridor. And again, in Portuguese culture, privacy is very dear to dwellers and the option was to offer patios inside the house's perimeter. This was one of the aspects that were redefined in 2004, since most dwellers closed those patios in search of some extra area. And their conversions were acknowledged and adapted to new blocks that completed the whole project.

Conclusion

The attempt to make any house a home has many different characters, since it derives from one's culture but also from the previous living experiences. Insalubrity and degradation don't define for themselves the desire for any kind of house, but in one which complies with the dwellers' expectations in social representation.

As architecture in general gave up trying to change the (whole) world and started to pay attention to actual needs and a changing society (rather than respond to an intended society), models started to be created taking into account social and sociability needs, rather than just being functional.

Nevertheless the previous efforts weren't inglorious, as the house as a unit was an explored theme in every type of dwelling. We must take into account that it is not always possible to build with low density, since a tight budget almost always means exactly that: density. And as we observe a mere duplex in a high rise building we must have in mind that this kind of 'homeliness' wasn't spontaneous but a result of an intense investigation and experiment.

Figures

Fig. 1: **Sindicato Nacional dos Arquitectos** – *'Arquitectura Popular em Portugal'*, 4ª edição, 2004, ISBN 972-97668-7-8

Fig. 2: Author's drawing, based upon the model presented in: **Cambi, Di Sivo, Steiner** – *'Viviendas en bloques alineados'*, 1992, Barcelona, Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A., ISBN: 968-887-186-9

Fig. 3: Author's drawing, based upon the model presented in: **Câmara Municipal de Lisboa**, Outubro 1967 – *'Habitação Social na cidade de Lisboa, 1959-1966'*

Fig. 4: Author's drawing, based upon the model presented in: **Câmara Municipal de Lisboa**, Outubro 1967 – *'Habitação Social na cidade de Lisboa, 1959-1966'*

Fig. 5: Author's drawing, based upon the model presented in: **Costa, João Pedro** – *'Bairro de Alvalade – um paradigma no urbanismo português'*, Livros Horizonte/Faculdade de Arquitectura da UTL, 2ª edição 2005, ISBN 972-24-1382-4;

Picture: http://premiosvalmor.blogspot.com/2005/11/19501959_20.html, [10.2010]

Fig. 6: Author's drawing, based upon the model presented in: **Coelho, António Baptista; Coelho, Pedro Baptista** – *'Habitação de Interesse Social em Portugal'*, 2009, Livros Horizonte, ISBN: 978 972 24 1655 9

Fig. 7: Author's drawing, based upon the model presented in: **French, Hilary** - *'Key Urban Housing of the Twentieth Century'*, 2008 Laurence King Publishing Ltd, ISBN-13: 978-1-85669-564-0; **Klein, Alexander** - *'Vivienda Mínima, 1906 – 1957'*, 1980, Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A.

Fig. 8: Author's drawings.

Fig. 9: Author's drawing, based upon the model presented in: **French, Hilary** - *'Key Urban Housing of the Twentieth Century'*, 2008 Laurence King Publishing Ltd, ISBN-13: 978-1-85669-564-0; <http://teoriarquitectura.blogspot.com/2009/06/bloco-como-paradigma-moderno.html>, [04.2010]

Fig. 10: **Roger Sherwood** – *'Modern Housing Prototypes'*, 2002 Harvard Paperbacks, ISBN-10: 0674579429, ISBN-13: 9780674579422; **Schoenauer, Norbert** – *'6,000 Years of Housing, revised and expanded edition'*, 2000, W. W. Norton & Company, New York, NY 10110, ISBN: 0-393-73052-2

Fig. 11: Author's drawing, based upon the models presented in: **Klein, Alexander** - *'Vivienda Mínima, 1906 – 1957'*, 1980, Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A.

Fig. 12: <http://factoidz.com/towards-a-new-architecture-le-corbusiers-modernist-manifesto/>; <http://www.retopolis.net/exposition/newsspirit.html>, [10.2010]; <http://dlhtms.net63.net/memoire%20A4.htm>; <http://soa.syr.edu/faculty/bcoleman/arc523/lectures/523.lecture.housing.packages.html>, [10.2010]; **Curtis, William J. R.**, 1986 – *'Le Corbusier, Ideas and Forms'* – Phaidon Press Limited, reprint 1997, pág. 60, ISBN 0 7148 2790 8

Fig. 13: <http://www.flickr.com/photos/doctorcasino/2883343401/in/photostream/>, [05.2011]; author's drawing, based upon the model presented in: **French, Hilary** - *'Key Urban Housing of the Twentieth Century'*, 2008 Laurence King Publishing Ltd, ISBN-13: 978-1-85669-564-0

Fig. 14: <http://blog.pressebook.fr/giulio/2009/01/23/contre-larchitecture/>; <http://www.bwk.tue.nl/architectuur/dmw/group4/le%20corbusier%20unite.htm>, [10.2010], <http://www.obiw.fr/voyage-decouvertes/carnets-de-route/86173-la-cite-radieuse-de-briey-en-lorraine>, [05.2011]

Fig. 15: <http://www.flickr.com/photos/trevira/2864614421/in/photostream/>, [10.2010]; author's drawing, based upon the model presented in: **French, Hilary** - *'Key Urban Housing of the Twentieth Century'*, 2008 Laurence King Publishing Ltd, ISBN-13: 978-1-85669-564-0

Fig. 16: <http://www.parameters.cc/blog/2008/05/15/robin-hood-gardens-ii/>, [10.2010]

Fig. 17: http://www.housingprototypes.org/project?File_No=POR002, [10.2010]

Fig 18: author's drawings, based upon the models presented in: **Santos, José Paulo dos** (ed.) – *'Álvaro Siza, Obras y Proyectos, 1954-1992'* – 1993, Gustavo Gili, ISBN: 84-252-1513-7.

Fig. 19: photographer: João Sousa, <http://www.mimoo.eu/projects/Portugal/Porto/Bou%E7a%20Housing%20Complex>, [10.2010]

References

- Afonso, Ana Isabel** (2008) - *'Grupo Doméstico e Mudança Social: abordagens quantitativas e qualitativas'*. http://ceas.iscte.pt/etnografica/docs/vol_04/N1/Vol_iv_N1_153-182.pdf, [10.2008]
- Aymonino, Carlo** (1973) – “La Vivienda Racional: ponencias de los congresos CIAM 1929-1930” - Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A. 08029 Barcelona, 1973
- Banham, Reyner** (1959) – *'Neoliberty: the italian retreat from modern architecture'*, in *The Architectural Review*, n.º 747, vol. 125, April 1959
- Frampton, Keneth** (1996) – *'Historia critica de la arquitectura moderna'* - Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A. 08029 Barcelona, 1996

Workshop 01 – Housing Finance and Regulation

Klein, Alexander – *‘Vivienda Mínima: 1906 - 1957’*, Editorial Gustavo Gili, 1980

Lynch, Patrick (2008) – *‘Aldo Rossi Knew all about the symbolic power of a kitchen table’*, AJ (The Architects’ Journal), Greater London House, Hampstead Road, London NW1 7EJ, 28.02.08, page 22, 2008

Montaner, Josep Maria (2001) – *‘Depois do Movimento Moderno: Arquitectura da segunda metade do séc. XX’* – Editorial Gustavo Gili, Barcelona, 2001

Monteys, Xavier; Fuertes, Pere – *‘Casa Collage – un ensayo sobre la arquitectura de la casa’*, 4ª edição, 2005, Editorial Gustavo Gili, SA, Barcelona

Nunes, João Pedro Silva - *‘Lisboa, arquitectura e urbanismo à escala humana: planeamento urbano e arquitectura de habitação em Olivais Sul, Lisboa 1959-1969’*, 2007, Câmara Municipal de Lisboa, ISBN: 978-972-8543-08-2

1.º CIHEL *Congresso Internacional (da) Habitação no Espaço Lusófono*

'O Mínimo como Dinâmico'

Lisboa, Portugal, Setembro de 2010

<http://cihel01.wordpress.com/about/>

Cod. C2: O MÍNIMO COMO DINÂMICO

Pedro Fonseca Jorge

Resumo

Os novos Tipos do habitar têm de fazer face a indefinição do Grupo Doméstico que deles farão uso. Urge por isso encontrar novas soluções que colmatem as incapacidades dos Tipos actuais em corresponder aos novos usos. Entende-se que a investigação encetada deve considerar a História da Arquitectura como operativa, em que as experiências passadas fornecem pistas sobre os aspectos qualitativos da 'nova' habitação. Procede-se por isso à recolha de modelos que façam uso de dispositivos de organização do espaço que permitam dinamizar áreas contidas, de modo a versatilizar o uso da casa a diversos níveis: adição de equipamentos que permitam usos simultâneos, esquemas de circulação que multiplicam acessos, relação entre público e privado doméstico, entradas e saídas, e carácter evolutivo da habitação. Executa-se deste modo a um levantamento que funciona igualmente como fonte de elementos para consulta que se pretende útil para a concepção de futuros Tipos de habitação que se adequem ao Grupo Doméstico contemporâneo, composto por diversos elementos em que a família nuclear é apenas um dos mesmos.

Abstract

New housing types have to face the contemporary undefined household. It's therefore urgent to find new solutions that can bridge the gaps of the Types in use in their inability to fulfill contemporary needs. The necessary investigation must consider Architectural History as something operative, where past experiences give us clues about qualitative features in new housing proposals. It is shown a collection of Dwelling Models that use various spacial solutions that can make more flexible restrained areas, in order to make a house more versatile: equipments that allow simultaneous activities, circulation schemes that permit various accesses, new relations between the domestic public and private, outside and inside areas, and the house's evolutionary devices. This recollection also works as an useful source of solutions for the creation of future Housing Types appropriate to the contemporary household where the nuclear family is just one of its elements.

Palavras-chave: habitação, família, grupo doméstico, tipologia.

1. CONCEITO

A definição de 'dinâmico' divide-se em vários métodos para diversificar um espaço que à partida é contido. A noção de 'mínimo' não se resume à restrição de área útil por motivos ideológicos ou de custo, mas quando o espaço é limitado, esforços foram feitos para que essa realidade fosse contornada. Neste contexto entende-se a dinamização do espaço como o conjunto de processos utilizados para dissimular a frieza da fita métrica, criando a ilusão de um espaço mais vasto através da sua versatilidade.

Procuram-se atitudes práticas no uso ou apropriação do espaço, para lá de esquemas sensitivos baseados na cor ou extensão das janelas.

Dentro dos elementos estudados podemos apontar três caminhos possíveis: conceber espaços onde se possam desempenhar várias funções, relacionar as diferentes áreas de modo a que tenham uma utilidade variável e oferecendo à célula a possibilidade de evoluir fisicamente consoante as necessidades dos utentes.

2. MÓVEL/IMÓVEL

O termo 'funcionalidade' não deve ser confundido com 'Funcionalismo'. Ao invés de procurarmos Tipos espaciais estanques no seu uso, pretendemos esquemas que tenham como objectivo sobrepor hábitos, contornando área ou volume em falta. O 'Funcionalismo' encontra-se ligado a uma escola de pensamento com um substrato ideológico que induz à redução da área e volume a valores mínimos como solução-base para problemas maiores.

2.1. UM HOTEL FLUTUANTE

Em 1929 Le Corbusier dá uma palestra que intitula 'Uma célula à escala humana', onde enumera o conjunto de experiências que foi efectuando no domínio da habitação mínima¹. Como ilustração do paradigma habitável pretendido, refere uma viagem de pacote que realizou de Bordéus a Buenos Aires, onde passou duas semanas num quarto onde se considerou 'instalado em casa'.

Em cerca de 15m² diz ter encontrado um espaço onde poderia exercer numerosas actividades, práticas e sociais, desde dormir e lavar-se, a descansar e receber amigos, dada a excelência no aproveitamento da área reduzida. Para o conforto atingido contribuíram os equipamentos colectivos que, divididos segundo os numerosos utentes, resultam económicos e suportáveis pelas camadas menos favorecidas da população.

Corbu vê na contenção das áreas a solução para um problema que consiste na falta de casas, procurando meios para as 'produzir' rapidamente. A pré-fabricação e o uso de sistemas modulares são soluções, e quanto menor for essa célula modular e pré-fabricada, mais rápida será a sua construção em série. Não vê neste processo uma cedência ou uma limitação, pois no quarto do pacote, com os seus 15m², sente-se 'no papel de um senhor que alugou uma pequena casa' ou num 'apartamento de luxo onde viajam comodamente senhores importantes'. Paralelamente à questão do tamanho, Corbu considera o modo ideal de evitar a vida burguesa, que pretende erradicada pelo Moderno. No entanto há que apontar que entre 1/20 de criado, 1/40 de cozinheiro e o restante 'exército de pessoas' encarregues da generalidade de tarefas, estaríamos perante um ordenado completo a encargo do utente dos 15m².

Enunciam-se aqui vários princípios que seriam usados nas suas Unidades de Habitação, constituídas por apartamentos servidos por serviços como lojas, hotel e infantário, e onde a ausência de frigoríficos (para controle de custos) é colmatada por um 'criado' que vai servindo os apartamentos de gelo por uma abertura especial, a partir das 'ruas elevadas' da unidade (galerias), que já são identificadas no pacote como espaços sociais.

2.1.1. Um Hotel atracado: este Tipo habitacional já tinha algumas demonstrações práticas nos Estados Unidos sob a forma de 'apartment ou catering hotels', onde, face ao apartamento de dimensões contidas, havia salas comuns, lavandarias, cozinhas e serviços de entrega de refeições nos apartamentos. Este é um Tipo que se encontra associado ao aluguer de espaços e não à sua propriedade, dado que a maneira de aumentar a rentabilidade de um edifício consistia em aumentar o número de apartamentos por piso, com os serviços em falta a ser executados noutras áreas.

Efficiency Apartments: este Tipo merece destaque pela génese que consistiu de Tipos posteriores, ainda que inseridos em contextos socioculturais diferentes. Schultze (1877-...) & Weaver (...-...), acostumados a hotéis de luxo, previam o desaparecimento da casa cidadina, concebendo para isso os 'Efficiency Apartments', idealizados para proporcionar alojamento barato.

O termo 'efficiency' já era usado desde o princípio do século para designar os Modelos com redução de áreas a um mínimo, e nesta proposta traduz-se na combinação de cozinha e sala

¹ Le Corbusier, 'Una célula a escala humana', <http://legislaciones.iespana.es/escalahumana.htm>, [02.2009]

de refeições na menor área possível e no uso de um único espaço para albergar duas funções: a sala de estar consistia também no quarto, propondo camas rebatíveis ('door-beds'²) que se recolhiam durante o dia no quarto de vestir adjacente. O aspecto prático é outra característica da proposta, pois um quarto de vestir é mais eficaz num espaço diminuto do que um roupeiro. Nas cozinhas concebidas para funcionarem sem ajuda externa (isto é, criados) os armários situavam-se na parede adjacente ao corredor para poder serem por aí reabastecidos (Figura 1A).

A proposta possui uma essência Moderna ao racionalizar o espaço através de dimensões mínimas, pelo engenho mecânico aplicado na duplicação funcional do espaço mas também pelo processo de mudança de hábitos que impõe aos seus habitantes, através do uso mais descomplexado do espaço.

Pertinências presentes/futuras: duvida-se da pertinência desta solução para uma família convencional, pois apenas suporta albergar indivíduos ou casais, não havendo espaço para restantes elementos. Podemos inseri-los na categoria de 'permanência temporária' e não de 'habitação permanente', pelo menos no contexto social em que foram idealizados, pois são incapazes de evoluir em conjunto com o grupo doméstico. A validade contemporânea desta célula manifesta-se nas necessidades de casais sem filhos, trabalhadores a tempo inteiro, ou idosos que beneficiariam dos serviços à disposição.

Não deixa de ser irónico que o Tipo de célula mínima associado a serviços centralizados se tenha convertido na expressão máxima das Dom-Komunas russas, e de um sistema político oposto àquele que esteve na sua génese. Mas os seus princípios de rentabilização de espaço, infra-estruturas e recursos, bem como de revisão da família tradicional, prestar-se-iam aos princípios ideológicos sobre os quais assentava o Construtivismo Russo e o Comunismo.

2.2. DOIS EM UM

As casas em banda da exposição de Viena da Werkbund (1932) de André Lurçat (1894-1970) poderão ser inseridas com alguma desconfiança no contexto de 'mínimo', pela área confortável mas também pelo conjunto de serviços que não têm lugar numa casa que pretende contrariar modos de vida burgueses: quarto de empregada, pátios, jardins, piscina infantil, lavandaria, depósito de madeira e carvão, tudo com mais sentido numa colectividade (Figura 1B).

2.2.1. Móveis imóveis: o recurso usado é semelhante ao referido nos 'Efficiency Apartments', mas ampliado a uma escala muito maior: dota-se a casa de todo o mobiliário necessário ao seu uso, mas rebatível ou encastrado para que se possa escolher a função de determinada área consoante as necessidades. A intenção era não aplicar mais mobiliário para além do embutido, de modo a que peças 'soltas' não interferissem no funcionamento da casa.

Também na Dom-komuna Narkomfin é aplicado o princípio da cama rebatível, muito embora se encontre associado a um princípio sociológico e político alicerçado na abolição da estrutura familiar convencional. Pretendia-se atribuir aos adultos privacidade, criando espaços de recepção e de descanso aparte da restante família. Com base nos mínimos necessários a nível de área, Moisei Ginzburg (1892-1946) faz partilhar esta área com os quartos, usando uma cama ocultável para ampliar o espaço de estar, sem chegar ao extremo de Karel Teige (1900-1951)³, que propunha um quarto para cada adulto e a abolição das zonas comuns (seriam oferecidas salas colectivas). Ginzburg apresenta uma cozinha mínima, mas também sala de estar comum e quarto de casal, embora o Narkomfin também se apoie em estruturas comuns complementares: refeitório, zonas de convívio, lavandarias, creches, etc. (Figura 1C).

² French, Hilary, *'Key Urban Housing of the Twentieth Century'*, Londres: Laurence King Publishing Ltd, 2008, pág. 38, ISBN-13: 978 1 85669 564 0

³ Teige, Karel, *'The Minimum Dwelling'*, Cambridge, Massachusetts: The MIT Press, 2002, ISBN 0-262-20136-4

2.2.2. Imóveis móveis: o mobiliário encastrado parece condicionador na apropriação do espaço, mas insere-se na lógica Funcionalista de dominar os movimentos do utente na direcção de um comportamento desejado. A apropriação era contrariada e funcionalmente cada divisão era definida ao milímetro para cumprir uma função específica. Mas Lurçat, através desta aparente condição, não realiza uma obra Funcionalista: as camas são rebatíveis precisamente porque um espaço de dormir não é exclusivamente para dormir, mas serve também para estudo ou descanso, oferecendo mesas encastradas. Do mesmo modo as zonas comuns rebatem as mesas para que uma cama encastrada possa 'adicionar' um quarto à casa existente. A casa 'possui' assim o dobro da área verificável pela fita métrica.

Desapropriação: este é um aspecto em que o móvel embutido é condenável, apesar da versatilidade demonstrada: limita a apropriação da casa pelos utentes ao impedir a escolha dos seus móveis e também a localização destes: o utente não tem hipótese de encostar uma cama à fachada, do mesmo modo que não pode aproximar um sofá da janela para a utilizar como recurso de leitura.

Este aspecto era muitas vezes intencional, pois encarando a obra de arquitectura como um todo, a localização do mobiliário era também alvo de estudo, de modo a conseguir um aproveitamento máximo do espaço e iluminação. Alexander Klein⁴ fá-lo, ao propor localizações exactas para as peças de mobiliário de acordo com a dimensão e função desempenhada: um louceiro de grandes dimensões não poderia assim estar junto de uma janela, para não projectar sombras, tal como as secretárias se localizariam defronte das janelas porque melhor iluminadas (Figura 1D).

Apropriação: paradoxalmente, o esquema apresentado induz também à apropriação dos espaços por deixar implantados os meios para o fazer, como camas, mesas e secretárias embutidas na mesma divisão induzindo o utente a pensar no espaço de forma menos estática. Ou seja, se não deixa em aberto o 'como se faz', já é mais flexível no 'onde se faz'. O condicionamento pelo Funcionalismo da vida doméstica de modo a desempenha-la de um determinado modo considerado como o mais eficiente muitas vezes entrou em colisão com a vida doméstica real, implantada á força em espaços inapropriados.

Figura 1

3. PERMANECER/CIRCULAR/ACEDER

A contenção de recursos no desenvolver de casas mínimas levou à procura de esquemas que contornassem aquilo que pareciam ser condicionantes intransponíveis. O factor custo leva à criação de sistemas de pré-fabricação e rapidez de execução, e à diminuição das áreas. Esta última não foi entendida como uma limitação, mas antes um processo de pesquisa de organizações alternativas sobre as diferentes zonas que compõem a célula e o modo como se circula ou acede nas e às mesmas.

3.1. USO/DESUSO/ABUSO

O modo como se associam as zonas numa célula determina o uso das mesmas, apesar deste condicionamento ter provado não mudar hábitos muito enraizados. As condições impostas acabaram por manifestar-se em apropriações incorrectas ou impositivas de espaços que não foram destinados para o efeito, mas por vezes também numa mudança de hábitos, uma vez descobertas as potencialidades dos novos espaços.

Existe também o modo como se lhes acede, o que pode consistir num enriquecimento da célula, pois ao propor acessos suplementares possibilitam-se usos complementares.

⁴ Klein, Alexander, '*Vivienda Mínima: 1906 - 1957*', Barcelona: Editorial Gustavo Gili, 1980

Chegamos assim a uma composição do percurso interno da célula que deixa de se assemelhar a um tronco central do qual derivam ramos como acessos únicos, mas a esquemas circulares permitindo múltiplos trajectos.

3.1.1. Antecedentes: Mies van der Rohe (1886-1969) pretendeu mostrar com o edifício em Weissenhof (1927) as potencialidades da planta livre (Figura 2A). Apresenta um espaço interno em que apenas dois pilares, bem como as canalizações, condicionam a sua distribuição. Com base numa banda edificada de três pisos e com oito apartamentos por piso, consegue 24 apartamentos diferentes, fazendo variar a disposição interna das paredes. Se a solução em 'open-space' produz uma circulação livre e usos liberais, nas soluções onde pretere esta solução não se escusa a investigar a flexibilização dos espaços sem pôr em causa a privacidade dos ocupantes.

Recorre a duas soluções: duas portas como acessos independentes ao mesmo espaço, ou um esquema de painéis de correr que permite abrir na totalidade um espaço para outro. Um quarto pode ser acedido a partir do hall de entrada, mas ao possuir uma parede ocultável, pode perfeitamente ser usado como extensão da sala comum.

Uma opção curiosa é os espaços de circulação transformados em locais com utilidade suplementar. Se adicionar armários num corredor é óbvio, transformar um espaço de passagem num espaço de permanência é mais invulgar, pois parece interferir no correcto desempenho de ambas actividades (passar/estar). Em 1970 Dan Alrod (...-...) fá-lo em Jerusalém em Katamon (Figura 2B), em parte porque precisa de contornar a reduzida área útil (48,2m² para um T2) mas também porque o esquema de associação das células permite 4 frentes: todos os espaços internos são naturalmente iluminados e ventilados, incluindo circulações. João Álvaro Rocha (1959-...) usa o mesmo recurso em Seara, Matosinhos (2004) (Figura 2C). A célula beneficia de uma profundidade reduzida que permite iluminar um espaço que pode ser acedido pela sala ou pela cozinha e que conduz ao corredor dos quartos e instalações sanitárias. Assumido como espaço 'sobrante', cria-se uma zona que tanto pode pertencer ao domínio do privado como do público. A sua função é deixada ao encargo do utente, que a pode usar para refeições ou para o tratamento da roupa.

3.1.2. 'Intermezzo': A possibilidade de comunicar e de alterar os diversos espaços da casa foi uma prática em desuso durante muitos anos. Mesmo os casos mencionados consistem em excepções, por versatilizarem o espaço e no modo como o fazem, sendo que a proposta de João Álvaro Rocha, datada de 2004, anuncia contudo uma prática que voltou a ser corrente actualmente. Muitos podem ser os factores que contribuíram para a imobilidade da investigação espacial.

Permanências: habitamo-nos a considerar Movimentos como Estilos, e a avaliar a permanência da Arquitectura e das Artes em geral através do seu aspecto superficial. Mas ao atentarmos no espaço doméstico percebemos que há um certo número de aspectos que se estendem no tempo. Um dos efeitos da perseverança do Funcionalismo foi a imagem da casa como estática, com cada um dos espaços assentes numa função pré-definida, com dimensões e localização na célula estabelecidas de acordo com esta. A rigidez deste esquema induziu à diminuição da investigação espacial dado considerar-se este como pertinente até há pouco tempo.

Família: a estrutura dos ocupantes da casa foi dada como um facto adquirido durante esse período. O utente permanece o grupo familiar, sem se considerarem outras hipóteses de relação entre os ocupantes da casa que não fossem os laços de sangue. O Construtivismo Russo tentou outro tipo de união entre os habitantes da célula mas, falhada esta concepção, retomaram-se os preceitos antigos de aceitar a família nuclear como base da ocupação da célula. Esta ideia é referenciada por Alexander Klein em 1927⁵, mas também por Nuno Portas

⁵ Klein, Alexander, '*Vivienda Mínima: 1906 - 1957*', Barcelona: Editorial Gustavo Gili, 1980

(1934-...) que em 1958⁶ esboça uma 'tipologia familiar baseada na relação classe/modo de vida'⁷ para estabelecer critérios na definição do utente da habitação social.

Mudança de paradigma: a própria arquitectura viu a sua atenção ser desviada do tema da habitação após o fulgor que este atingiu no Modernismo. Baseado no aforismo de Corbusier em que a casa estaria na génese de um processo que culminaria na cidade, a habitação foi tema principal do CIAM de 1927 e retomado no seguinte, ainda que inserido num contexto mais urbanístico⁸. Quando se começa a questionar o Moderno atenta-se nas matérias que se consideraram descuradas por este. O TEAM X adopta uma ênfase mais urbana, tentando retomar o espírito da rua como unidade de vizinhança, mas recuperando o espírito 'corbusiano' da 'rua elevada', uma galeria aberta apoiada numa edificação em altura e comprimento: 'Robin Hood Gardens' (1972), de Alison e Peter Smithson (1928-1993;1923-2003) é o exemplo mais emblemático (Figura 2D). Avaliada a impossibilidade de fazer evoluir o Moderno, aposta-se em suplantá-lo, 'reavivando o significado e o simbolismo'⁹, através de uma pesquisa formal baseada numa interpretação mais popular da imagem arquitectónica. A posterior dispersão de posturas busca respostas em diversas circunstâncias, que escusaram a inclusão do Homem no debate, e por conseguinte, a temática do habitar.

3.1.3. Contemporaneidade: a dessacralização do arquitecto acaba por ser uma das pedras de toque da actual postura adoptada na projectação do habitar. Assume-se ser impossível prever todos os usos e modos de vida desempenhados na casa, muito menos determinar esta de acordo com uma vivência idealizada. As experiências modernas neste campo revelaram a sua falência parcial ao longo do tempo: certas propostas seriam adoptadas, como a separação funcional, outras dificilmente foram aceites, como a cozinha-laboratório. As soluções traduziram-se numa certa rigidez no uso da casa cuja indefinição de um utilizador-tipo levou a por novamente em causa. Consequentemente, considerar o espaço como uma tela branca a ser 'pintada' pelo utilizador torna-se um princípio a seguir, afirmando Hilde Léon (1953 – ...) e Konrad Wohlhage (1953 – 2007) que 'só a indefinição e a ambiguidade tornam o espaço útil'¹⁰. No edifício de habitação de Schlesiesschtrasse, Berlim (1994), propõem espaços 'indefinidos' cuja função é intercambiável. Neste caso, entre quarto e sala, espaços de dimensões comparáveis que se diferenciam nas relações estabelecidas entre os outros espaços e o exterior. Se no T1 a opção passa por querer a sala ou o quarto com contacto com a varanda, no T3 pode-se optar entre uma relação mais próxima entre sala e cozinha, ou entre sala e varanda, localizada numa zona mais privada da célula. A opção passa também pelo carácter do espaço, com a sala a poder adquirir um aspecto mais recatado, junto dos quartos, em que as actividades aí desempenhadas adquirem mais privacidade (Figura 2E).

Figura 2

MVRDV e Blanca Lleò¹¹ retomam os temas das aberturas duplas ente espaços contíguos para permitirem uma apropriação personalizada. Nos apartamentos Mirador, em Madrid (2004) um quarto permite uma passagem ampla para a sala comum que torna o primeiro público ou semi-público: as novas possibilidades tecnológicas, como a internet, levam a considerar mais

⁶ Portas, Nuno, 'A Habitação Social: proposta para a metodologia da sua arquitectura', Porto: Edições FAUP, 1.ª edição, 2004, ISBN 972-9483-63-9

⁷ Família rural, operária e burguesa, idem, ibidem

⁸ Aymonino, Carlo, 'La Vivienda Racional: ponencias de los congresos CIAM 1929-1930', Barcelona: Editorial Gustavo Gili, 1973. ISBN 84-252-0755-X

⁹ Nesbitt, Kate (editor), 'Theorizing a new agenda for architecture: an anthology of architectural theory, 1965-1995', Nova Iorque: Princeton Architectural Press, 1996, ISBN 1-56898-054

¹⁰ 'The Construction Team Model',
<<http://www.leonwohlhagewernik.de/fileadmin/downloads/english/Texts.pdf>>, [10.2009]

¹¹ 1959-... (Viny Maas), 1964-... (Jacob van Rijs), 1965-... (Nathalie de Vries) + 1959-..., (Blanca Lleò)

frequente o trabalho em casa e um espaço a ele dedicado, ainda que sem um carácter fortemente marcado (Figura 3A).

O projecto de 1954 para Tapiola de Aulis Blomstedt (1906 – 1979) propõe um T2 (T3?) onde usa o duplo acesso aos diversos espaços para sugerir usos suplementares: uma sala de jantar acessível pela cozinha e pelo corredor adaptável a quarto, ou ainda um quarto que se abre para a sala, como uma extensão desta (Figura 3B).

A sugestão de diferentes ocupações consegue-se também através de esquemas mais sensíveis, como a localização ambígua dos espaços: Francisco Barata Fernandes (1950 - ...) em Massarelos, Porto (1994), coloca um quarto junto da entrada que sugere usos adicionais. Oferece-se também uma segunda entrada, a partir da cozinha, para um dos quartos, o que resulta num percurso circular do fogo que permite aceder ao privado sem passar pela sala: esta poderá adquirir outra função sem devassar a intimidade dos espaços anexos, ou muito simplesmente permitir entradas e saídas de algum habitante, com privacidade (Figura 3C).

Grupo Doméstico: esta independência no acesso/saída de casa encontra-se ligada a dois fenómenos diferentes, mas cada vez mais comuns: o abandono tardio da casa dos progenitores, e o facto de actualmente se constituir família mais tarde, o que também adia a independência. E também a coabitação de amigos ou mesmo desconhecidos, visando a divisão de despesas (fazendo cair em desuso a ‘família’ enquanto ocupante-tipo da casa, em prol do mais abrangente ‘grupo doméstico’¹²). Este tipo de coabitação baseia-se na manutenção de uma certa privacidade pessoal que não passa exclusivamente pelo encerramento da porta do quarto, mas também por um conjunto de movimentos que exigem independência, desde receber amigos pessoais a entrar e sair de casa ‘em segredo’.

Velhos tipos, novos usos: Se Barata Fernandes propõe um circuito interno independente, Tipos existem que recuperam soluções em desuso. Sendo o serviço doméstico realizado pelos moradores ou ainda por entidades exteriores, a tradicional entrada de serviço e o ‘quarto da criada’ tornam-se obsoletos. Mas estas duas soluções sugerem ‘um novo apartamento dentro de casa’¹³, pertinente para as actividades profissionais no lar, que ganham um acesso independente, ou para a privacidade dos filhos adultos que ainda moram com os pais.

Estes factores levaram Kazuyo Sejima (1956 - ...) e Ryue Nishizawa (1966 - ...) à concepção de um edifício de habitação colectiva baseado na repetição de unidades, que já não são os apartamentos, mas sim os quartos (Figura 3D). Em Kitagata, Japão (1994 – 1998) recupera-se a sala ‘tatami’, oferece-se um espaço comum de cozinha/refeições e adiciona-se um pátio que abrange ambas as fachadas, mas o verdadeiro cerne da célula é o quarto enquanto refúgio privado do ocupante, que inclusive possui a sua porta de entrada. Cada espaço possui a sua própria função, sem hipóteses de mutação: a ambiguidade reside na liberdade de movimentos que permite o ‘convívio de desconhecidos’ que fazem dos serviços unidades colectivas: a casa de banho separa sanita e banheira e o lavatório encontra-se no corredor, permitindo o uso simultâneo do conjunto (Figura 3E).

Micro-escala: é inevitável proceder a uma comparação com um tipo passado, ainda que utópico e mal sucedido. As Dom-kommunas do construtivismo russo pretendiam controlar os gastos na oferta de uma casa condigna ao mesmo tempo que punham em causa a estrutura familiar ‘burguesa’. Ofereciam-se pequenos núcleos privados em que cada membro da família possuía o seu espaço, enquanto a higiene e a alimentação eram realizadas em estruturas comuns. Finalmente, a Família resiste e o convívio e a higiene permanecem em família. Analisando Kitagata com alguma liberdade, podemos assumir que uma nova comuna é proposta, mas à escala da célula e não do edifício: dá-se primazia às unidades privadas do

¹² Afonso, Ana Isabel, ‘Grupo Doméstico e Mudança Social: abordagens quantitativas e qualitativas’. <http://ceas.iscte.pt/etnografica/docs/vol_04/N1/Vol_iv_N1_153-182.pdf>, [10.2008]

¹³ Monteys, Xavier; Fuertes, Pere, ‘Casa Collage – un ensayo sobre la arquitectura de la casa’, Barcelona: Editorial Gustavo Gili, pág. 72, 2005, 4ª edição, ISBN 84-252-1869-1

fogo (quartos) e fomenta-se o uso de estruturas comuns como sanitários e espaços de refeição (da casa). A grande diferença consiste do facto de aqui não se pretender 'moldar' um grupo doméstico tradicional a um modo de vida idealizado, mas adaptar a casa a tipos de ocupação que já existem, o que por si só pode ditar o sucesso futuro desta proposta.

1/4: atentando às diferentes possibilidades de ocupação dos 'quartos', questiona-se a pertinência desta designação para espaços que permitem mais do que apenas dormir. Como reduto de privacidade do indivíduo, este dorme, descansa, 'faz sala' e trabalha neste local. Os espaços da casa indiferenciados anteriormente ao Moderno, eram uma mera sucessão de módulos que pela sua descaracterização permitiam múltiplos usos. Actualmente procura-se esta versatilidade mas a casa está longe de ser uma mera agregação de módulos, sendo a implantação do 'quarto' estudada de modo a verbalizar a versatilidade atribuída.

Figura 3

4. PRIVAR/PRIVATIZAR/VERSATILIZAR

Um dos denominadores comuns das propostas avaliadas é a de possuírem espaço condicionado. Para além da área reduzida, esta condição implica na versatilidade com que se usa o espaço doméstico mas também no tipo de serviços oferecidos. É corrente vermos associadas certas utilidades a desafogo económico, mas que, sem ser luxos, são confortáveis por permitirem a não sobreposição de usos ou a simultaneidade dos mesmos. Uma lavandaria evitaria o uso da cozinha no processo de tratamento da roupa, uma casa de banho de serviço liberaria a principal de usos rápidos durante o período dos banhos, rentabilizando o espaço destinado a um número limitado de pessoas. Neste caso estamos não só a contabilizar área adicional, mas acabamentos e peças sanitárias adicionais, etc.

Ao longo do tempo foram sendo executadas algumas experiências que visavam contornar este óbice, tentando propor acessos, compartimentações e zonas que aumentassem a privacidade dos espaços. Trata-se de simular artificialmente uma área ou orçamento de que não se dispõe, sobrepondo funções num curto intervalo de tempo (ao invés de o fazer a médio ou longo prazo, como no ponto 3).

4.1. INSTALAÇÕES SANITÁRIAS

A casa de banho é das divisões da casa que obrigatoriamente todos os membros do grupo doméstico usam, na maior parte das vezes em horários similares. E nesta se sentirá mais facilmente a sobrepovoação da célula.

4.1.1. Individualização da sanita: um dos processos mais comuns para o uso simultâneo das instalações sanitárias consiste na separação da sanita das restantes peças. Assim pode-se fazer o uso da sanita enquanto noutro espaço se toma banho, faz a barba, etc.

Consiste, por exemplo, numa solução enraizada na cultura francófona, mesmo na habitação tradicional. Corbusier (1887 – 1965) faz uso desta na Unidade Habitacional de Marselha (1947 – 1952), ainda que as instalações sanitárias se dupliquem: a sanita e a banheira possuem um espaço próprio, mas existe ainda um chuveiro num espaço anexo e um lavatório em cada um dos quartos secundários. Na Unidade Habitacional de Nantes (1952 – 1953), de área bastante mais comedida, escusam-se a banheira e os lavatórios privados, permanecendo a sanita única (Figura 4A).

É uma solução que se encontra ligada à definição clara de espaços públicos e privados. A sanita é uma peça que pode ser usada por elementos estranhos ao grupo doméstico, enquanto a banheira e o lavatório consistem em espaços de uso exclusivo dos habitantes da célula. Não é por isso estranho que a primeira peça se associe à entrada, como em Grivegnée (1953): Charles Carlier (... - ...) coloca a sanita 'à disposição' do público, mas remete as restantes peças para a zona dos quartos, definida como área privada/nocturna.

4.1.2. Desconstrução: este processo de separação é levado mais além, sendo proposta por alguns a individualização de todas as peças sanitárias. Esta solução é usada por Van den Broek (1898 – 1978) e Bakema (1914 – 1981) em Overschie (1957), onde dispõem de cerca de metade da área bruta de Corbusier: 66m² face aos 126m² da Unidade Habitacional de Marselha. É um recurso utilizado como solução única e não um complemento de uma instalação sanitária adicional.

Embora tenham participado na revisão do Moderno são considerados 'expoente do Movimento Moderno'¹⁴, o que se manifesta no cuidado com que a planta é elaborada preservando o privado. A separação funcional está ligada à disposição das peças sanitárias, pois os quartos possuem dois lavatórios privados e um chuveiro apenas acessível por estes (permitindo um percurso circular da casa), estando apenas a sanita à disposição de família e convivas. Pouco importa que os quartos abram para o hall de entrada ou para a sala pois tudo o que é funções íntimas se realiza dentro dos mesmos.

¹⁴ <http://www.answers.com/topic/va-den-broek-bakema-2>, [10.2008]

Em 1968 Fábio Penteado (1928 - ...), Vilanova Artigas (1915 – 1985) e Paulo Mendes da Rocha (1928) apresentam no Complexo Zezinho Magalhães Prado, em São Paulo (Figura 4D), uma solução que consiste em separar o lavatório das restantes peças, colocando-o num espaço que as antecede. Não é encerrado, permitindo uma utilização livre e o acesso à sanita e chuveiro em qualquer circunstância. Em Kitagata (1994), o gabinete SANAA¹⁵ faz evoluir este conceito, tornando independentes a sanita e o chuveiro. O lavatório permanece na circulação e permite o seu acesso em qualquer altura (Figura 4E).

Van den Broek e Bakema resumem a melhor síntese do conjunto, ao proporem um espaço privado controlado, versátil e contido em área, evitando áreas de distribuição adicionais, o que se revela fundamental quando se dispõem de uma área útil de 57m² para albergar um T2.

4.2. ZONAS COMUNS

Uma das principais diferenças entre o espaço público e o privado de uma casa consiste no facto do segundo ser constituído por unidades privadas. Face ao público, em que as unidades que o constituem não se encerram e não têm um acesso limitado a um 'proprietário', os quartos da casa constituem um reduto íntimo em que a entrada é condicionada. Não é de estranhar que o espaço comum seja território de maior experimentação, porque é mais fácil unir espaços ou intercomunicá-los. No entanto, o tipo de trabalho efectuado sobre a sala/cozinha dependeu igualmente das características próprias de cada população, que se pretendeu rever nas propostas.

4.2.1. Passar pratos...: a mulher como operária, minimização do tempo passado em casa, refeições 'pré-fabricadas': pormenores que levaram à consideração da cozinha como um espaço menor, eliminando as suas características sociais de convívio entre grupo doméstico e outros. Esta postura encontra eco no Moderno, mas é em Alexander Klein que encontramos uma aplicação mais directa deste princípio: Bad Dürrenberg apresenta uma sucessão de Tipos que vão desde o T2 para 3 pessoas até ao T3 para 6 pessoas em que a cozinha é a mesma (aumentado apenas a área nesta última proposta). O princípio é o de que a cozinha apenas se destina a preparar as refeições, função desempenhada por uma única pessoa, independentemente do número de comensais. A Sala Comum é favorecida, pois o aumento da área verificado no Público beneficia esta: de acordo com o Tipo, a sala inicia-se como 19m², aumenta para 25m², 26m², culminando nos 34m² para, respectivamente T2/3, T2/4, T3/4 e T3/6¹⁶. O contacto entre a cozinha e a sala era realizado por um passa-pratos, reforçando o carácter laboratorial e oculto do espaço.

Cozinhar em Frankfurt: o expoente desta idealização foi a 'Cozinha de Frankfurt', desenvolvida a partir de 1926 por Margarete Schütte-Lihotzky (1897 – 2000) e usada por Ernst May (1886 – 1970) na 'Nova Frankfurt', conjunto de novos bairros nos quais foram utilizados os princípios do 'Existenzminimum'. Este seria o tema do segundo congresso dos CIAM, destinado a definir parâmetros mínimos de dignidade habitacional, focando aspectos práticos como a salubridade ou insolação, mas também psíquicos, do Homem. Científica, prática e depurada, a cozinha de Frankfurt consistia num modelo prefabricado destinado a sair da fábrica directamente para o canteiro da obra (Figura 4F).

Cozinhar em Marselha: Corbusier faz perdurar este Tipo nas suas unidades de habitação, mas interpretado de modo mais aberto: o balcão fronteiro à cozinha e à sala possui uma abertura confortável e a parte superior do mesmo consiste numa prateleira de fácil acesso. Melhora-se o contacto entre os convivas, no que consiste numa evolução da cozinha funcionalista: esta considera a preparação das refeições um acto único e intervalado, que antecede o consumo, enquanto Corbusier admite que a preparação faz parte do convívio, antes, durante e depois da refeição (figura 4G).

¹⁵ Kazuyo Sejima (1956 - ...) e Ryue Nishizawa (1966 - ...)

¹⁶ Tx/y, em que x é o número de quartos e y corresponde ao número de camas.

4.2.2. Passar pessoas...: o processo acima descrito tem ainda fortes raízes funcionalistas, postura que esquecia um pouco a humanidade do habitante. As suas necessidades de relacionamento eram descuradas num ideal de vida asséptico, em que o objectivo era o 'necessário', não o possível. Talvez como reacção, talvez como reflexo de um modo de vida enraizado, outros processos existem de tornar mais franca a relação entre cozinha e sala, ou seja, entre as pessoas.

O corredor garante na maior parte dos casos o acesso directo a todas as divisões da casa, mesmo que se desdobre em dois espaços de modo a controlar o acesso aos quartos. Casos há em que se incluem os espaços de circulação na zona da sala, o mais 'público' dos espaços e cuja área surge visualmente ampliada. Mas é sempre possível acesso adicional entre cozinha e sala, resultando num percurso circular em que se acede de diversas formas a estas: a sua função é a de tornar mais directo o acesso à sala ou ampliar sensorialmente o espaço através de uma abertura ampla. Não se trata de uma mera porta, pois pode ser pequena, ampla ou ausente, e também que tipo de sala liga a que tipo de cozinha, ou que espaço da sala liga a que espaço da cozinha. Cada uma destas soluções esconde uma raiz cultural que revela o tipo de relações que estabelecem familiarmente ou entre conhecidos e que ganharam o seu lugar após a tentativa de homogeneização do espaço à escala internacional. Não se trata da recuperação do modelo burguês de habitar, muito embora a mobília de sala de jantar para (raras) ocasiões especiais permaneça um hábito muito enraizado entre os países do sul da Europa (onde funciona como dispositivo de representação).

Após o apogeu do Moderno nos anos anteriores à Segunda Guerra Mundial, nos anos 50 começam a sentir-se algumas mudanças. No geral afectaram toda a concepção da arquitectura, mas, em particular, o espaço doméstico começa a ser mais sensível às pessoas e às suas raízes.

Comer a norte: diversos exemplos suportam a existência de diferenças entre os modos de vida a norte e a sul da Europa. Pode dizer-se que existe uma certa amenização dessas diferenças nas zonas centrais onde duas influências, mediterrânica (e atlântica) e nórdica tendem a confluir.

O modo de vida mais liberal dos nórdicos induziu a relações menos rígidas entre os espaços da casa. No espaço comum da célula, onde se procura interligar os espaços, começa a desenhar-se um Tipo que parece ser popular no final dos anos 1950: uma cozinha corredor, perpendicular á fachada, com uma zona para mesa junto desta, aberta para a sala de estar. Nuno Portas identifica este Tipo¹⁷, mas refere também que na Suécia é comum guardar este espaço para refeições correntes, adicionando uma mobília de jantar mais formal na sala comum¹⁸.

Exemplares são os apartamentos de Alvar Aalto (1898 – 1976) para a Interbau, em Hansaviertel, Berlim (1957), (Figura 4H). A proposta consiste numa cozinha estreita com uma bancada lateral, acessível desde o hall de entrada, e que culmina numa zona de refeições junto das janelas. Esta contacta com uma varanda grandes que também se abre para a sala comum. Ainda em 1957 Kaija e Heikki Siren (1920 – 2001; 1918 - ...) fazem uso do mesmo Tipo em Otaharju (Figura 4I), mas com um segundo balcão de cozinha aberto para a sala. A amplitude destas aberturas sublinha o aspecto convivial do espaço comum, mas também deriva do facto destes edifícios consistirem em alojamentos para professores universitários, temporários e menos circunspectos. E talvez por isso Nils Lonroth (... - ...) reduza as aberturas a uma porta em Forshagagatan (1959), mantendo contudo o duplo acesso à cozinha a partir do hall de entrada e da sala de estar (Figura 4J). Em nenhum destes casos se exclui a possibilidade de haver um espaço de refeições mais formal nas salas, dado que a dimensão destas o permite. O

¹⁷ Portas, Nuno, *'A Habitação Social: proposta para a metodologia da sua arquitectura'*, Porto: Edições FAUP, 2004, 1.ª edição, ISBN 972-9483-63-9

¹⁸ Portas, Nuno, *'Funções e Exigências de Áreas da Habitação, Informação Técnica: Edifícios'*, Lisboa, Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil, Fevereiro de 1969

mesmo se sucede em Leninova Trida (1974), de Joseph Polak (... - ...), na República Checa, onde apenas uma parede separa cozinha e sala (Figura 4K).

Figura 4

Aparentada a esta solução é a de Nyem, em Finspång, na Suécia (1970)¹⁹, onde a cozinha é central, situando a sala de estar na fachada oposta da zona de refeições. Parecendo apenas uma deslocalização da sala acaba por parecer uma sala de jantar assumida, apenas pertencendo à categoria acima porque não existe limite físico entre refeições e preparação (Figura 5A).

De referir que a solução em 'kitchenette' nunca foi encontrada nos Modelos recolhidos, sendo preterida a favor de soluções que resguardam a cozinha, mesmo que esta se veja reduzida ao espaço do balcão e um corredor paralelo, como em Comasina Nord (1957), Milão²⁰ (Figura 5B).

Comer a sul: no Pós-Guerra italiano o 'retorno' a modos de vida mais convencionais induziu à escolha de sistemas organizativos onde a cozinha surge como um local privado face a elementos externos. Outras derivações consistem no 'nicho' para a cozinha com uma zona de refeições anexa (Sorgane, Florença, 1968, por Leonardo Savioli, (1917 – 1981/82), (Figura 5C), ou ainda a cozinha espaçosa com espaço de refeições integrado, solução mais tradicional (Tiburtino Est, Roma, de Federico Gorio (...-...), datado de 1952 (Figura 5D).

Esta passa por ser a situação exemplar do período em causa, mas no entanto foi igualmente realizado um esforço para fazer evoluir este Tipo doméstico, que se caracterizava por definir limites precisos entre utilitarismo e formalidade. Se a cozinha era refúgio de muitos labores, pretendeu-se a determinado momento criar um espaço de uso indiferenciado onde se pudessem realizar actividades domésticas desligadas do acto de cozinhar. Cria-se o *lavoro*, 'espaço não convencional destinado às tarefas domésticas, que frequentemente se impunha como centro organizativo do fogo'²¹. Um exemplo o Núcleo Noncello, 1964, de Giulio Brunetta (1906 – 1978), onde no *lavoro* entre a cozinha e a sala comum seriam realizadas as tarefas domésticas, que não sendo do âmbito privado individual, permaneciam privados face às visitas e aos espaços de representação por estas acedidos: uma pequena mesa de trabalho, uma tábua de passar a ferro, e claro, a mesa de refeições diárias (Figura 5E).

4.2.3. Passar por...: Espaço de convívio entre família, grupo doméstico e elementos exteriores ao grupo, a sala permite não ser um espaço totalmente encerrado, adicionando circulações que permitem criar desafogo visual. A pertinência desta solução encontra-se ligada a modos de vida menos formais: Nuno Portas desaconselha esta solução, referindo-a mesmo como incompatível com a entrada da casa por não oferecer resguardo da vida privada da família²². Mas é possível contornar esta situação, oferecendo um hall de entrada, com possibilidades de encerramento, e o corredor integrado na sala, à semelhança da Cooperativa de Massarelos de Francisco Barata Fernandes (Figura 5F).

A nível das aspirações das populações, o desejo de uma casa burguesa nascia da comparação das suas vidas com a dos mais abastados. As casas operárias ou rurais consistiam num espaço único onde se desenvolviam todas as actividades, sem privacidade ou conforto, enquanto a casa burguesa, dividida em espaços consoante os usos, com espaços de aparato e zonas recatadas, se manifestava como um desejo legítimo.

Mas foi a planta livre que permitiu maior desenvolvimento, pois a distribuição da casa deixa de obedecer a uma ordem ritmada pelos elementos de suporte. O aproveitamento intencional

¹⁹ Bertil Engstrand (1922 - ...) e Hans Speek (1920 - ...)

²⁰ Attilio Mariano (... - ...) e Carlo Perogalli (1921 - ...)

²¹ Bandeirinha, José António, 'O processo SAAL e a arquitectura no 25 de Abril de 1974', Coimbra: Imprensa da Universidade de Coimbra, 2007, ISBN: 978-972-8704-76-6

²² Portas, Nuno, 'Funções e Exigências de Áreas da Habitação, Informação Técnica: Edifícios', Lisboa, Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil, Fevereiro de 1969

deste benefício foi demonstrado por Mies van der Rohe (1886 – 1969) em Weissenhof, exposição da Deutscher Werkbund (1927). Sem um cliente específico, serve-se desta valência para variar paredes, portas e espaços para produzir várias modalidades do espaço. A comunicação entre estes é favorecida, com cozinhas, salas ou quartos a terem mais do que uma entrada. A sala é espaço de circulação, em muitos casos, mas Mies amplia esse carácter também aos quartos, o que se revela numa solução possível num T1, mas improvável num T2.

Actualmente têm sido preferidos esquemas que favoreçam a independência da sala, porque a ambiguidade que na contemporaneidade se pretende atribuir aos espaços de permanência da casa assim o induz: para que uma sala se possa transformar num quarto, é necessário que a sala possa oferecer o nível de privacidade/conforto que oferece o quarto comum. Se deste se quiser fazer um escritório ou uma sala, não é necessário produzir alterações na sua estrutura, já o inverso não é verdade. Assim sendo, em prol dessa ambiguidade pretendida, a sala encerra-se, ainda que possuindo portas/paredes de correr, que ‘versatilizam’ o seu uso.

Florian Riegler e Roger Riewe (1954 -... ; 1959 - ...) concebem em Bahnhofstrasse uma planta modulada que sugere a livre apropriação dos espaços: a localização do balcão da cozinha define o espaço de refeições contíguo, mas a zona de estar pode encontrar-se contida neste espaço ou junto da fachada oposta. Este espaço pode ainda vir a ser um quarto porque existem dispositivos de encerramento que o tornam independente (Figura 5G).

Hilde Léon e Konrad Wohlhage defendem o mesmo, mas aplicam-no de forma menos evidente em Schlesischstrasse: no T3 é oferecida uma sala ‘encerrada’ que é de dimensões similares ao quarto no extremo oposto, o que significa que podem ser intercambiáveis (Figura 5H).

4.3. ESPAÇOS PRIVADOS

Como dispositivo de adição de funções ao espaço (mas não de substituição, como no ponto 3) podem estabelecer-se relações entre os quartos que compõem o fogo. São raros os modelos onde se pode dizer que existe esta intenção de providenciar mais um uso ao quarto, pois implica com o espaço privado do seu ocupante: alterar a função deste implica ‘expulsar’ o seu inquilino, para que se possa ocupar o seu espaço com outra actividade.

Há a possibilidade de complementar o uso do quarto através de actividades que possam ser exercidas por ambos (ou mais) ocupantes de dois quartos durante um período de tempo que não se sobreponha à função de dormir. Nuno portas fala da incompatibilidade entre ‘dormir/descanso pessoal’ e o ‘recreio das crianças’²³, mas o facto é que estas não têm de se realizar simultaneamente, e é também o próprio que afirma que os quartos deveriam ser dotados de uma zona de expansão ‘como na Unidade Habitacional de Marselha’²⁴ (Figura 5I).

Este exemplo oferece uma porta de correr que une os dois quartos secundários. Mais do que providenciar uma passagem pretende-se criar um espaço de brincar comum, mantendo o carácter recolhido da zona destinada à cama.

O já referido projecto de Bahnhofstrasse, de Riegler/Riewe usa duas portas de correr em todos os espaços da casa. Possuem a dimensão de uma porta normal, e estabelecem uma relação dinâmica entre espaços comuns e privados, e não apenas entre espaços privados. Este seria o caso se a sala de estar fosse usada como quarto, o que de resto é possível, pois a lógica que dita as propostas contemporâneas é precisamente a ambiguidade dos espaços.

Figura 5

²³ Portas, Nuno, *Funções e Exigências de Áreas da Habitação, Informação Técnica: Edifícios*, Lisboa, Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil, Fevereiro de 1969

²⁴ Portas, Nuno, *A Habitação Social: proposta para a metodologia da sua arquitectura*, Porto: Edições FAUP, 2004, 1.ª edição, ISBN 972-9483-63-9

5. ENTRAR/SAIR/ENTRAR

Um dos processos de verificação da dinâmica de percurso e uso de uma célula é através do desenho do seu esquema distributivo, onde são ilustrados os diferentes trajectos que se podem realizar ao aceder às diferentes funções. O esquema mais estático assemelha-se a uma árvore, caminhando-se de espaço para espaço sucessivamente, e em que no retorno se tem de voltar a percorrer os espaços precedentes. Neste capítulo são estudados os processos que alteram este percurso com o intuito de facilitar trajectos e de diversificar o uso do espaço, contornando a sua exiguidade. Chegamos assim a modelos cujo esquema distributivo é composto por 'círculos' que indicam que o 'retorno' pode ser efectuado por espaços diferenciados.

Mas permanece por explorar a relação da célula com o seu exterior, dado que nos exemplos acima o percurso tinha início num ponto único, o da porta de entrada. Referimo-nos à possibilidade de aceder do fogo através de mais de ponto, o que se traduz em diferentes hierarquias, usos e utilizadores. Em '3.1.3' foi abordado este tema, em que se propunha a reutilização da antiga entrada de serviço ligada ao quarto da 'criada' para se estabelecer um 'apartamento dentro do apartamento'. Quem o ocupasse veria a sua individualidade protegida ao entrar e sair do seu espaço. Semelhante solução é mais difícil quando associada a um imóvel de habitação colectiva, por isso mesmo em 'Kitagata' se teve de recorrer a outro tipo de acesso para se poder multiplicar os acessos à célula: uma galeria exterior comum para onde se orientam todos os espaços.

5.1. VELHOS HÁBITOS

Referíamos-nos a usos contemporâneos da casa, a um conjunto de indivíduos diferenciados entre si. Tal não significa que a solução de multiplicar acessos não tenha estado presente noutros modelos, mais afastados temporalmente e a nível do uso contemporâneo dedicado à casa.

A habitação unifamiliar é um bom exemplo, pois através da sua relação com o solo consegue sempre estar em contacto directo com a rua. Torna-se mais fácil oferecer múltiplos acessos, recurso que foi utilizado na habitação mais modesta, mas segundo um esquema de hierarquias bem estabelecido. Falamos das entradas nobre e de serviço da casa, ligadas a espaços de recepção (sala de visitas) e a utilitários (cozinha), associadas à típica casa rural. Este foi o modelo adquirido por José Veloso (... - ...) na realização dos seus projectos no âmbito do SAAL (Serviço de Apoio Ambulatório Local) que pretendeu formal e utilitariamente integrados localmente: em Aljezur (1976) as casas foram concebidas como uma aglomeração de volumes sobre uma cobertura inclinada, sugerindo um crescimento evolutivo que também permitiam. São diferenciados os espaços comuns de recepção ou da família através de um equilíbrio de área entre sala comum e cozinha, que possuem acessos distintos (Figura 6A).

Esta é uma marca de ruralidade, a formalização de um modo de vida ancestral em que a escassez de recursos não impedia a existência de um espaço de representação. Mas tal como no exemplo do 'quarto da criada', nada impede que o espaço assim definido e acedido não possa ser na actualidade apropriado como quarto ou escritório, uma vez que a casa possui um acesso suplementar.

5.2. NOVOS HÁBITOS

As facilidades de acesso permitidas por uma casa unifamiliar manifestam-se essencialmente nos espaços públicos do fogo, mas tal não implica que não possa haver também a possibilidade de aceder pelos quartos ou pela circulação privada.

5.2.1. Batateiro: esta facilidade é mais invulgar numa casa unifamiliar que se desenvolve em dois pisos, porque tem de ser uma circunstância prevista na concepção do fogo. Tem de haver uma intenção explícita de oferecer essa dinâmica à célula, porque a atitude não se resume à abertura de um vão numa parede. O Bairro do Batateiro (1976) no Seixal, de Fernando Bagulho (... - ...) apresenta uma escada que une a cota da rua ao piso superior do fogo, por intermédio da varanda de um dos quartos. A escada é partilhada por duas células, dispostas lado a lado, numa banda, o que contudo não lhe tira utilidade: poderá ser um artifício para fomentar a proximidade entre vizinhos (Figura 6B).

5.2.2. Bouça: Mais inequívoca é a atitude de Álvaro Siza Vieira (1933 - ...) no Bairro da Bouça no Porto (iniciado em 1977, concluído recentemente) onde a tipologia da 'casa' é recuperada para construir bandas acedidas por galerias. O edifício é entendido com um somatório e sobreposição de células unifamiliares, que têm de ser acedidas nos pisos superiores por uma galeria exterior. Deparamo-nos com duplexes sobrepostos, num total de 4 pisos, em que os inferiores se distinguem dos superiores: na galeria encontram-se fogos com disposições convencionais, onde o acesso é directo às zonas públicas do fogo, com quartos e casa de banho no piso superior. Ao nível do solo o fogo possui as zonas públicas no piso superior, às quais se acede por intermédio de uma escada individual exterior. Deste modo, os quartos do fogo encontram-se no piso 0, em estreito contacto com a rua, piso em que situa igualmente a entrada principal. Os quartos conseguem ser espaços de contacto com a vida exterior, situação que só é possível por que o bairro se encerra criando pátios entre as bandas para os moradores (Figura 6C).

Figura 6

6. SER/ESTAR/CRESCER

A noção de evolução deve ser encarada dentro de parâmetros muito latos, pois podemos definir 'crescimento' de várias formas: prende-se com os fenómenos de transformação que ocorrem na célula que a leva a adaptar-se a necessidades surgidas com o passar do tempo ou a desligar-se de usos entretanto abandonados. A evolução do fogo pode manifestar-se nos espaços vagos e 'inacabados' que são deixados à disposição do utente para que este possa proceder à adaptação do espaço consoante as suas necessidades particulares, tão particulares que são impossíveis de prever pelo autor do projecto.

Em nenhum dos exemplos citados se limita a evolução de uma casa ao crescimento da mesma, abrangendo-se também alterações internas realizadas dentro de um quadro previsto.

6.1. PREVISÃO/IMPREVISÃO

A capacidade de suporte de evoluções imprevistas da célula encontra-se ligada à implantação e associação que define o conjunto edificado, pois aqui se estabelecem os limites através dos quais uma casa pode 'crescer', no sentido físico e figurado. Uma casa isolada suporta melhor este tipo de evolução, pois dentro dos limites do terreno que se lhe encontra associado muito é possível. A todas as possibilidades de evolução encontramos associada uma noção de 'módulo' a partir da qual derivam as variantes. A definição desta palavra é lata, mas dentro das possibilidades encontramos algumas definições que se adaptam ao estudo em causa:

Módulo (latim *modulus*, medida pequena, ritmo, cadência):

(...) 'Unidade que serve de medida'; (...) 'Unidade de mobiliário ou marcenaria que se combina com outras, formando um conjunto homogéneo e funcional', ou ainda, associado a 'modulado': 'Harmonioso, melodioso'.²⁵

(...) 'medida que regula as proporções das partes de um edifício ou de qualquer peça arquitectónica'; 'unidade ou peça autónoma que pode ser combinada com outras para formar um todo'; (...) 'quantidade que se toma como unidade de qualquer medida' (...).²⁶

Aqui 'módulo' consiste na unidade-base a partir da qual derivam todas as variantes, mesmo que segundo directrizes diferentes: ou consiste numa 'peça autónoma combinável com outras' (sem que se faça referência a medidas ou proporções semelhantes) ou uma 'quantidade que se toma com unidade de qualquer outra medida' (aqui sim, estabelecendo essa peça autónoma como referência).

6.1.1. Erudito: seja sobre uma casa isolada ou sobre uma célula associada a outras em altura, a intervenção de um agente especializado (arquitecto) pressupõem uma característica adicional face ao exemplo precedente:

Previsão: quando durante o processo de concepção da célula se prevêem os modos de evolução desta, para que o processo se realize de forma coerente ou '(...) formando um conjunto homogéneo e funcional'. Salvaguarda-se a salubridade, utilidade e estética do projecto, seja individual ou inserido num conjunto mais lato, seja fazendo crescer fisicamente a casa ou alterando a organização espacial do espaço preexistente.

6.2. METAMORFOSE/ESTÁTICA

Dentro desta categoria não incluiremos espaços que, sendo modulares, não são evolutivos. Ou seja, células que se obtêm uma a partir da outra, mas que funcionam como entidades

²⁵ 'Dicionário Priberam da Língua Portuguesa'
<<http://www.priberam.pt/dlpo/default.aspx?pal=módulo>> [11.2009]

²⁶ 'Infopédia; enciclopédia e dicionários Porto Editora'
<<http://www.infopedia.pt/lingua-portuguesa/módulo>> [11.2009]

individuais, como por exemplo a concepção de diferentes tipos de acordo com a ocupação (T1, T2, T3 ou T4), em que a partir do módulo inicial com um quarto, se vão adicionando quartos de dimensões semelhantes na criação dos tipos sucessivos.

Podemos considerar duas facetas a partir das quais se produz a evolução da célula, dentro do registo em que se presume um técnico e uma intenção subjacente ao crescimento da casa. Consideraremos as propostas que se baseiam no crescimento físico da célula paralelamente àquelas que se debruçam apenas sobre alterações sobre o seu interior.

6.2.1. Aumento: este é um processo que se encontra associado a moradias unifamiliares isoladas. No entanto existem soluções onde as condicionantes são maiores, em que se prevêem adições sucessivas: casas geminadas, em banda ou até mesmo 'back-to-back', onde existe a oportunidade de acrescentar um piso. Opção que se esgota no tradicional bloco de apartamentos onde tal é inviável, espacial e tecnicamente, e também pelo carácter colectivo da propriedade.

Malagueira: o projecto de Siza Vieira corresponde ao mencionado 'back-to-back', onde a habitação possui apenas uma frente, por se encontrar encostada lateralmente a na traseira, a outros módulos semelhantes. Eventualmente pode apresentar mais do que uma frente se a forma da casa for dinamizada, como é o caso da Malagueira (1974 – 2000), onde o módulo possui a forma de um 'L' envolvendo um pátio.

As opções de crescimento passam pela adição de um piso, fazendo variar os tipos do T1 ao T5. A concepção é modular, pois cada tipo deriva do precedente, mas o que os torna realmente evolutivos é o facto dessa derivação poder ser realizada após a construção inicial: a base de todos os tipos é o T1 de piso único, que possui uma escada encerrada de acesso à cobertura plana, onde se encontram todas as infra-estruturas necessárias a posteriores adições a rede de águas e esgotos acede à cobertura de modo a possibilitar a implantação da casa de banho.

No piso superior podem existir dois, três ou quatro quartos, volumes exteriores que se vão adicionando (ao invés da subdivisão do espaço interno). Qualquer T1 pode acabar em T5, mas a casa pode 'nascer' como T3, T4 ou mesmo T5, em qualquer um dos casos havendo a possibilidade de evolução (Figura 7A).

6.2.2. Subdivisão: as alterações efectuadas sobre os espaços internos são as mais comuns, por serem as possíveis em edifícios colectivos, mas também por consistirem num investimento mais moderado.

Em exemplos precedentes foram expostas soluções que permitiam alterar ou multiplicar as funções dum espaço, seja por auxílio de mobiliário embutido, portas adicionais ou de correr, que podem ter associados inconvenientes, como isolamento acústico deficiente. Outros processos existem sem esse tipo de condicionantes, ainda que impliquem uma solução definitiva.

Campo di Marte: em 1985 Siza Vieira propõem um apartamento evolutivo onde dois quartos podiam dar lugar a três, através da subdivisão de um deles. Havia que adicionar uma parede perpendicular á fachada, mas a divisão estava preparada dado possuir duas janelas e duas portas de entrada. As novas divisões resultariam pequenas, mas os benefícios são maiores: deste modo a casa suporta evoluções do grupo doméstico sem o sacrifício de outras funções anexas ou a privacidade dos ocupantes. Opta-se por dar ao proprietário a responsabilidade das alterações a efectuar, criando apenas o dispositivo para que se possa realizá-lo (Figura 7B).

Massarelos: este projecto, já mencionado, permite a sua transformação interna, ainda que de forma radical. Faz uso duma estrutura de betão periférica com apenas um único pilar interno. Assim consegue-se que não hajam outros elementos que perturbem a demolição do interior do fogo para dar origem a uma solução diversa, respeitando as infra-estruturas existentes. Permite-se assim um vastíssimo leque de possibilidades em que a única intervenção por parte do autor original foi a previsão da sua possibilidade.

Figura 7

Referências:

Ábalos, Iñaki, '*A boa-vida, visita guiada às casas da modernidade*', 1ª edição, 2ª reimpressão, Barcelona. Editorial Gustavo Gili, 2008

ISBN: 978-84-252-1931-3

Aymonino, Carlo, '*La Vivienda Racional: ponencias de los congresos CIAM 1929-1930*', Barcelona: Editorial Gustavo Gili, 1973. ISBN 84-252-0755-X

Bandeirinha, José António, '*O processo SAAL e a arquitectura no 25 de Abril de 1974*', Coimbra: Imprensa da Universidade de Coimbra, 2007, ISBN: 978-972-8704-76-6

French, Hilary, '*Key Urban Housing of the Twentieth Century*', Londres: Laurence King Publishing Ltd, 2008, pág. 38, ISBN-13: 978 1 85669 564 0

Klein, Alexander, '*Vivienda Mínima: 1906 - 1957*', Barcelona: Editorial Gustavo Gili, 1980

Monteys, Xavier; Fuertes, Pere, '*Casa Collage – un ensayo sobre la arquitectura de la casa*', Barcelona: Editorial Gustavo Gili, pág. 72, 2005, 4ª edição, ISBN 84-252-1869-1

Portas, Nuno, '*Considerações sobre o organismo distributivo das habitações*', in '*Arquitetura(s) – Teoria e Desenho, Investigação e Projecto*', Série 2 – Argumentos, volume 3, Porto: FAUP Publicações, Faculdade de Arquitectura da Universidade do Porto, 2005, ISBN: 972 9483 71 X

Portas, Nuno, '*Funções e Exigências de Áreas da Habitação, Informação Técnica: Edifícios*', Lisboa, Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil, Fevereiro de 1969

Portas, Nuno, '*A Habitação Social: proposta para a metodologia da sua arquitectura*', Porto: Edições FAUP, 2004, 1.ª edição, ISBN 972-9483-63-9

Teige, Karel, '*The Minimum Dwelling*', Cambridge, Massachusetts: The MIT Press, 2002, ISBN 0-262-20136-4

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Figura 1

1A - planta e ilustração: desenho do autor;

1B - plantas: French, Hilary, *'Key Urban Housing of the Twentieth Century'*, Laurence King Publishing Ltd, 2008 [ISBN-13: 978 1 85669 564 0], imagem:

<http://www.artnet.de/magazine/reviews/sobich/sobich10-11-07_detail.asp?picnum=5>, [12.2009];

1C: Plantas: desenhos do autor; ilustração:

<<http://www.arch.mcgill.ca/prof/schoenauer/arch529/lecture09/htm9.htm>>, [12.2009];

1D: Klein, Alexander, *'Vivienda Mínima, 1906 – 1957'*, Editorial Gustavo Gili, 1980

Figura 2

2A - plantas: desenho do autor; imagem: <<http://www.artstamps.dk/images/989-Weissenhof.jpg>>, [02.2009];

2B - planta: desenho do autor; imagem: <<http://www.alrod.co.il/>>, [02.2009];

2C - planta: desenho do autor; imagem: <<http://cacifo200.blogspot.com/2007/07/recusa-afirmao-preferindo-sempre-o.html>>, [12.2009];

2D - <<http://www.treehugger.com/files/2008/02/save-robin-hood-gardens.php>>, [05.2009]

2E - plantas: desenho do autor; imagem:

<<http://www.leonwohlhagewernik.de/index.php?id=272>>, [10.2009]

Figura 3

3A – planta: desenho do autor; fotografia:

<<http://picasaweb.google.com/lh/photo/njNXkFu8LIJqM8653pljBA>>, [12.2009]

3B – planta: desenho do autor; fotografia: French, Hilary - *'Key Urban Housing of the Twentieth Century'*, 2008 Laurence King Publishing Ltd, [ISBN-13: 978 1 85669 564 0]

3C – planta: desenho do autor; fotografia: <<http://arkitectos.blogspot.com/2007/09/casa-om-ponte-da-barca-in-progress.html>>, [12.2009]

3D - plantas: desenho do autor; fotografias:

<http://www.egodesign.ca/en/article_print.php?article_id=90>, [12.2009] e

<<http://gifuprefecture.blogspot.com/>>, [12.2009]

Figura 4

4A - planta: desenho do autor; fotografia: <<http://www.an-architecture.com/2008/11/cloning-buildings.html>>, [03.2009]

4B - planta: desenho do autor

4C - planta: desenho do autor

4D - plantas: desenho do autor; imagem:

<<http://www.vitruvius.com.br/arquitextos/arq000/esp434.asp>>, [11.2008]

4E - plantas: desenho do autor; imagem:

<http://www.cse.polyu.edu.hk/~cecspon/lwbt/Case_Studies/Kitagata_Sejima/Kitagata_Sejima.htm>, [10.2009]

4F - <<http://www.uni-ak.ac.at/~p0004145/frankfurter.htm>>, [12.2009]

4G - <http://londonstroll.blogspot.com/2009_03_01_archive.html>, [12.2009]

4H a 4K - plantas: desenho do autor

Figura 5

5A a 5E - plantas: desenho do autor

5F - planta: desenho do autor; imagem: '*Páginas Brancas II*', Janeiro 1992, Porto: Departamento Páginas Brancas, AEFAUP

5G - plantas: desenho do autor; imagem: <http://www.rieglerriewe.co.at/projects/ho_esg/2.html>, [12.2009]

5H - plantas: desenho do autor; imagem: < http://www.murri-immobilien.de/seiten/mietshaeuser_taborstrasse.php?bild=5&#oben>, [10.2009]

5I - <<http://www.galinsky.com/buildings/marseille/index.htm>>, [03.2009]

Figura 6

6A e 6B - plantas: desenho do autor; imagens: Bandeirinha, José António, '*O processo SAAL e a arquitectura no 25 de Abril de 1974*', 2007, Coimbra: e|d|arq – Editorial do Departamento de Arquitectura da FCTUC, Imprensa da Universidade de Coimbra, [ISBN: 978-972-8704-76-6]

6C - plantas: desenho do autor; imagens: <<http://architecturalgrammar.blogspot.com/2008/11/saal-conjunto-habitacional-da-boua.html>>, [01.2010]

Figura 7

7A - plantas: desenho do autor; imagens: <<http://arquitecturafotos.blogspot.com/2007/02/outroira-importante-centro-militar.html>>, [09.2009]

7B - planta: desenho do autor; Dos Santos, José Paulo (ed.), '*Álvaro Siza, obras y proyectos 1954-1992*', 1993, Barcelona: Ed. Gustavo Gili, [ISBN: 84 252 1513 7]

1C - 'Dom-kumuna Narkomfin', Moscovo, 1928
Moisei Ginzburg (1892 - 1946)

1A - 'Efficiency Apartments', 1920s
Schultze (1877 - ...) & Weaver (... - ...)

1B - 'Casas em Banda', Viena, 1931-1932
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3E - Kitagata (1994 – 1998)
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e Ryue Nishizawa (1966 - ...)

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Fernando Bagulho (...-...)

Projecto revisto (2004)

Projecto original (1977)

6C - Bouça, Porto (1974 - 2004)
Álvaro Siza Vieira (1933 - ...)

7A - Malagueira, Évora (1974 – 2000)
 Álvaro Siza Vieira (1933 - ...)

7B - Campo di Marte, Venezia (1985)
 Álvaro Siza Vieira (1933 - ...)

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THE MINIMUM CELL

Family and households in new housing proposals

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Abstract

This study tries to reflect upon dwellers that will take part in recent and future housing proposals through new experiments under spatial and formal offers.

It is supported upon a reflection based in the so-called social housing that have been proposed mainly since the beginning of the 20th century, without ignoring the philanthropic experiments that were tried since the beginning of the industrial revolution.

From them aroused the questions of idealization or observation of the dwellers: in the first case through a conception of an idealistic family or household who would lead to a better society; in the second case, the attempt to respond to the existing dweller creating a proposal to better respond immediate needs for shelter and to identify himself with his own house.

Throughout past and present experiments, it will be offered the opportunity to prepare, rather than predict, our responses to future challenges in housing.

Keywords: Housing; Function; Family; Household

1. Concept: Minimum as Family

The idealization of minimum criteria in architecture has always been based in practical needs. The urgent response to a chronic shortage of housing for the poorest pressured the philanthropic and architectural community to devise ways of solving the lack of physical and psychological dignity in worker's houses. Therefore, it will be made an investigation about the way houses have been designed according to their intended dwellers. The concept of 'family' has been proven to be a fragile definition of the house's users, since there are other possibilities of residence other than those defined by blood-

ties. It will be sought in this chapter the identification of the domestic space with its dwellers, where several architectural theories try to formalize its models as a response to the household, rather than providing a mere practical shelter.

2. Inhabiting a Home: Uses and Symbols

As an evolutionary process, the architectural house was once the social manifestation of those with the possibilities to do so, before the adoption of some of its symbols by vernacular and popular architecture that tried to transform a house into something more than a physical protection.

2.1. Erudite Domestic Architecture

2.1.1. The 'Enfilade'

Figure 1: spatial sequence according to Alberti

Alberti (1404-1472) in his treatise 'De re Aedificatoria' describe the ideal house within the visitor's point of view: a course initiated in a square space, followed by circular one, a new polygon, ending at the heart of the house, a space defined by straight lines and curves. Although very generic, it's an example how the erudite house was define according to its symbolism.

Figure 2: spatial sequence according to D. Duarte

This sequenced spatial solution (the enfilade) was also referred later by D. Duarte in the aristocratic house from the XV century, where the successive spaces evolved from public to private: first, a welcoming area, then a space accessible to only some noble gentleman, a sleeping room, a dressing room and finally an oratory, the last resort of intimacy.

2.1.2. The Corridor

Figure 3: first apartments in previous multi-storey family town house

The first urban apartments were born from a single multi-storey family house, where several rooms formed an apartment that had to share a common staircase with all its neighbors. When the apartment started to be defined in one single floor, the 'enfilade' became a useful feature in the design of a scheme that started in a reception room, then the sleeping room, a 'cabinet', and finally the dressing room (always using the public/private sequence, where all the utilitarian rooms were excluded¹).

The 1755 earthquake in Lisbon, through the necessary reconstruction of the downtown city ('Baixa Pombalina'), gave the possibility to experiment some new spatial features in city planning, but also in

¹ Barreiros, Maria Helena, 2004, 'Casas em cima de casas: apontamentos sobre o espaço doméstico da baixa pombalina', in Revista Monumentos n.º 21, September 2004, Direcção Geral dos Edifícios e Monumentos Nacionais, Lisbon

new dwellings that offered a 'new' room, a hall-type space that consisted in a limit between the public staircase and the house². More important was the corridor, introduced sideways to the 'enfilade', allowing the access to each room without disturbing the previous one. This meant that now each space could be given a specific use independently from its position in a sequence.

Figure 4: 'Baixa Pombalina' building: ground-floor, entresol, first floor, second floor and above

Although distant from social housing, this example tries to make us understand the transformations among the house's character that would perspire to more modest dwells, but also that the criteria applied in the organization of the dwelling did not always considered the dwellers as an unique entity, like a family. Another point of view can be taken into consideration, this time trying to see the (master's) house as a physical manifestation of the family's DNA: being the layout of the house defined by the 'intensity' of privacy, it would be normal to join their activities according to their need for seclusion, as a group: the room where the parents slept, ate, rested and played with their children was the same, preceded by an 'apparatus room' for the visitors, but followed by a dressing room and an 'oratory/boudoir' where women started to write their diaries once they had access to literacy.

The distinction between public and private is still common in our houses but in the above examples the hierarchy is defined according to the paternal/maternal figures and not the family as a whole. Along in this hierarchy children did not have a specific space or a role, understood as single entity, making possible to declare that the entity that gave structure to the house was not the family but the couple.

3. Space and Hierarchy: Domestic Procedures

This brief itinerary trough erudite architecture seems taken out of context, but it precedes the first popular housing models. For instance, it is important to explain the meaning of 'Popular' in our present discussion.

² Loyer, François, 1987, *Paris XIXe siècle, l'immeuble et la rue*, Paris : Fernand Hazan [ISBN 2 85025 121 6]

In the present context we will use ‘Popular’ but something that is ‘made for the people’, contrary to the definition used in studies about Vernacular, Popular and Erudite architecture³ where it’s discussed unequivocally something that comes ‘from the people’.

3.1. Prelude 1

The Vernacular and Popular house always had some spontaneity, since there was no theoretical debate over them. In this particular context we are still away from nowadays, searching for the moment where the dweller became the basis of the architectural debate. But even in the more remote examples the vernacular house was more than a shelter, like in Skara Brae, a Neolithic village located in Scotland. The houses were circular structures with a central fireplace where a series of elements and furniture defined a precise circular path which culminated in a ‘stone cabinet’, a utilitarian space destined to the matriarch (the patriarch sat at the fireplace, in front of the entrance). So, just like in an erudite Model we can identify a Patriarchal organization defining space even without walls or doors.

Figure 5: typical house in Skara Brae

3.2. Prelude 2

The first philanthropic movements in England comprised mainly the rural house, since it occurred before the first migrations to the cities caused by the industrial revolution. There were created models of housing for rural workers, supposedly adapted to the needs of its idealized dwellers. John Plaw (1745-1820), for instance, is one of the few that manages to offer models with a real practical sense (rather than making a mere aesthetically romantic investigation), in its dimensions and materials.

³ **Jorge, Pedro Fonseca, 2006, ‘Tipos de Arquitectura’,** in ‘*A casa rural no Concelho de Alcobaça em 1961: da teorização Erudita à prática Popular*’, Thesis for the Master Degree in ‘Methods of Intervention in Architectural Heritage’, FAUP 2006, pages. 16 to 49.

Figure 6: proposed rural housing models, by John Plaw

Like in the previous examples we can still find a patriarchal/matriarchal solution where the parents' privacy is an emphasized feature: there is only one room, for them, while children still use the utilitarian spaces to sleep. The models also presented a series of annexes, like a pantry or a space for firewood that leads us to think that the main effort was applied in satisfying practical needs.

4. The First Popular Models: countryside/urban solutions

4.1. Being Popular in the Countryside

The beginning of the Industrial Revolution didn't occur in the cities, but in less centralized areas, where space and resources were available. But even in the countryside migration occurred and houses were needed for the once rural, now factory workers. One solution was the conversion of ancient farms, whose longitudinal buildings allowed the use of the row house typology. The models created from scratch had the same inconvenient, where houses were overlapped without any breathing areas or sunshine. So, like Schoenauer said⁴, there was a regression in one's life quality, since the rural model was a more spacious, isolated building, with extra room that prevented the use of the 'box-beds' offered by these models. This was the only resort of privacy in the entire house, where the same patriarchal family structure was applied.

4.1.1. Weaving against Horticulture

⁴ Schoenauer, Norbert, 2000, '6,000 Years of Housing, revised and expanded edition', New York: W. W. Norton & Company, [ISBN 0-393-73052-2]

Figure 7: Weaver's Tenements (1780) and Laborer's Cottage (1796)

Figure 8: Weaver's Tenements (1780) and Laborer's Cottage (1796); (Distribution schemes)

In the 1780 model destined to weaving factory workers we can recognize a building scheme with a central staircase that gives access to two apartments per floor. The inner spatial solution is the one mentioned above, where only 19 to 21m² serve the entire family with the referred 'box-bed' enclosed by a curtain. It doesn't sustain the comparison with the same period row houses for rural workers, who had 54m² distributed in three floors, but still one bedroom.

4.2. Being Popular in the City

4.2.1. Proposed Type

Among the studied models we must refer those proposed for a housing competition promoted by an American magazine by the end of the XVIII century. The briefing asked for Types of houses that could solve the lack of salubrity of the common New York apartment, born trough the internal division of town houses, with rooms without lighting or ventilation. The alternatives should consider very narrow and profound plots where light shafts would try to offer the necessary light and fresh air. In the selected proposals it's common the scheme were different rooms succeed, starting in the kitchen/dining room and ending in a more noble space, with windows facing the street. In some models there is another room between those two, sized to fit two beds. We can assume the biggest room as the resort of privacy for the parents, with the siblings staying in the small bedroom or even the kitchen.

Cell

Association of the Cell

Figure 9: Design Competition 2 (1879)

Being the more important space the bedroom (the only space facing the street), the above example sustains the existence of a 'linear family', that, as seen in erudite examples, it's not a question of area.

4.2.2. Existing Type

Although the inner 'course' of the house ends in the parents' room, it is still the masculine figure that dominates the family. The social distinction between man and woman was not obvious in the physical shape of the house, since the kitchen was attached to the 'dining room' without any kind of spatial hierarchy (although cooking and serving were tasks only a woman could perform).

In the late years of the XVIII century England was proposing small and simple housing models for factory workers, but in Holland there was a very common city apartment⁵ where the kitchen was an

⁵ French, Hilary, 2008, *'Key Urban Housing of the Twentieth Century'*, London: Laurence King Publishing Ltd, [ISBN-13: 978 1 85669 564 0]

independent space next to the façade with more than 20% of the apartment's total area (37m²), even if bedrooms were still 'box beds'. Was this a first step in women's emancipation (through a more qualified workspace)? Or was it another way of segregation by enclosing her and her functions in a closed space?

Floor plans

View

Figure 10: XIX Century Dutch Apartment

5. The Mirror of the Family: Father, Mother, Sons and Daughters

5.1 Two Bedrooms

Until now there was little thought about children and their accommodations, as they made use of other areas. Therefore, when a properly lightened and ventilated second bedroom is added to the structure of the house, it demonstrated the children's different status within the family.

5.1.1. Streatham

This might be considered the first (1848-1849) of 'social housing' buildings for many reasons. Its author, Henry Roberts (1803-1876) intended to provide a whole solution to the social problems of the poorer beyond a mere shelter. Therefore he proposed a second bedroom with practically the same qualities as the main bedroom, and that in a city building, usually more pressured by speculation and profitability.

Figure 11: Streatham Building (1848), Henry Roberts (1803-1876)

This is a very meaningful change, since other contemporary proposals, like the ‘bylaw houses’, designed to comply to new health regulation, who were double storey row houses, still didn’t have any evolutions according to this criteria. Like the Dutch model, Streatham has the same 37m², so area was not a motive for the inner cell differences. There is a different ideology that considered promiscuity a question of mental health, as important as physical. This lead to the transformation of the domestic space in a more profound way than an independent kitchen would do (Streatham proposes only a pantry that complements the living/dining/kitchen).

Floor Plans

View and association of the cells

Figure 12: ‘Bylaw Houses’ (1853)

5.1.2: Van Beuningstraat

In 1909 Van der Pek (1865-1919) proposed a Type with two rooms, lounge and kitchen, all of them correctly lightened through windows facing the street (there is variation of this Type in the first floor that still has box beds - requested by tenants – but they don't replace any bedroom). We must mention van der Pek's social activism in the achievement of this solution, since he thought that housing was one of the most important ways to obtain changes to the society. He considered the English models as mere reduced bourgeois houses, arguing that new housing proposals must correspond to worker's expectations and needs.

Floor plan (ground floor)

Outside view

Figure 13: Van Beuningenstraat (1909), Jans Ernst van der Pek (1865 – 1919)

5.2. Three Rooms

The need of the tenants of Van Beuningenstraat for the additional box beds in their flats was not only dictated by ancient ways of living, at least not entirely: at first, in these models they seem dispensable, since there were already two bedrooms. However, a truly absence of promiscuity, has the philanthropists intended, would only be achieved if it could be a separation according to the siblings genre. A three-bedroom apartment wouldn't be a luxury but the necessary evolution in order to provide true privacy.

5.2.1 Spangen

Ten years after Van Beuningenstraat, Michiel Brinkman designs the Spangen Quarter in Rotterdam, where he tries to strengthen society through the individual. The three-bedroom flat is therefore a conscientious choice, like a foundation for the development of the person. Brinkman only has 3 to 4m² more than van der Pek's apartments to design his three bedroom house, but still he manages to offer the additional room by diminishing the other rooms' areas, proving that for him even a 5,5m² bedroom was better than no bedroom at all. Also corridors and an entrance hall were provided in an attempt to promote privacy not only within the apartment but also for outside's prying eyes.

Floor plan (ground floor)

View from the pateo

Figure 14: Spangen (1919), Michiel Brinkman (1873 – 1925)

Trough the floor plan we can identify a Modern solution: a private or nighttime area, a dwellers' public or daytime area, and a service area (kitchen and bathroom, around the entrance hall). Because his architectural language had little to do with the Modern Movement, Brinkman is for some an 'empirical classicist'⁶, which already means some recognition of his effort in the conception of the inner spaces of the housing cell. But according to his premises of observing people's lives as a basis of his architecture, it would be more accurate to define him as a 'classical functionalist'.

5.2.2 Bad Dürrenberg

The period between the two World Wars was fertile in experiments in the field of social or subsidized housing. In three years four exemplar projects are concluded exhibiting four different approaches to domestic life, proving that was impossible to unit all architectural practice under the aegis of terminologies like Modernism, Functionalism or International Style.

Figure 15: Praunheim (1926); Karl Marx Hof (1926); Weissenhof (1927); Bad Dürrenberg (1928)

⁶ **Lambla, Ken**, 2009, – *Abstraction and theosophy: social housing in Rotterdam, The Netherlands*, <<http://corbu2.caed.kent.edu/architronic/v8n1/v8n104.pdf>> [01.2009]

Ernst May (Praunheim, 1926); Karl Ehn (Karl Marx Hof, 1926), Mies van der Rohe (Weissenhof Apartments, 1927) and Alexander Klein (Bad Dürrenberg, 1928) testify that diversity. Among them, Klein tries to mirror the existing family type in its proposal in a rather rigid manner with a severely functionalist solution, a result that would affiliate him in the European contemporary avant-garde movements, if only his language would be more 'Modern'. An entrance hall, a laboratory kitchen (strictly for cooking), a lounge with a dining area close to the kitchen, a corridor for the private spaces like bathroom and the 'children's' bedrooms' (in his own words). The master bedroom, according to the apartment modular solution was accessed through the lounge or even by one of the previous bedrooms.

His exaggerated functionalism makes him observe all the family types that were common in the period so he could create a unique and exclusive solution for each of them. His cells were 'static' in the sense that they would only fully adapt to its tenants at the moment of the 'observation', not being capable sustain future evolution (like the addition of one or more family members).

The C2 cell it's strictly conceived for only three occupants: father/mother and one child. The measurements of the children's bedroom were scientifically determined (with a method created by him) to accommodate one bed, one desk and one chair. If the couple had one more same-sex children, then they had to choose (or move to) the C9 cell, who had more 5m² in the bedroom for another bed, another desk and another chair. But if their children had different genres, then the solution would be the C7 cell with two of the C2 single bedroom. Finally, if the children were more than two, there was the C17 cell with two of the C9 double rooms... The lounge would evolve in each of these solutions but the laboratory-like kitchen would maintain its area.

Cell 'C2'

Cell 'C9'

Cell 'C7'

Cell 'C17'

Figure 16: Bad Dürrenberg (1928), Alexander Klein (1879 – 1961)

Nevertheless the addition of a third bedroom was a huge change, since the Karl Marx Hof, two years earlier, offered mainly one bedroom flats with the same floor area as the two bedroom C2 cell (53m²). Karl Ehn's solution was based in a more ancient conception of the house that still polarized the family structure in the parents (ignoring the children as individuals)

One bedroom apartment

Outside view

Figure 17: Karl Marx Hof (1926), Karl Ehn (1884 – 1957 or 1959)

Nevertheless, Klein's surgical proposals created typologies that are still common nowadays, like the functional separation that would be current for decades. However, the third room was already a big achievement: the single room for each son would have to wait some more years.

5.3. More Rooms

In the next examples we can find some models that offer supplemental spaces to the original structure of a two or three-bedroom apartment. This was not yet associated to the desire to offer each son a room, but it was born under the analysis of family structures that added more elements to the basic nuclear family (parents/sons).

5.3.1. Praunheim

Ernst May's 'New Frankfurt' is well known for many reasons, mainly for being a well executed series of small garden cities around Frankfurt. Unlike the original English garden-city, May conceives them closer to the city core, making it more plausible. As a functionalist, he works with Grete Schütte-Lihotsky (1897-2000) in order to conceive the 'Frankfurt Kitchen', a prefabricated structure based on a thorough analysis of the housewife's activities while cooking. This 'laboratory' would be included in all of the 'New Frankfurt' housing typologies, Praunheim included.

Figure 18: Praunheim (1926), Ernst May (1886 – 1970)

Intended to be one step forward in women's emancipation (since it would simplify their tasks, now that they were part of the family's working members), the 'Frankfurt Kitchen' was actually another way to segregate them. Cooking is still their exclusive task, an additional labor to the factory work already done during the day. And now, instead of cooking in a 'traditional' kitchen where all the family got together, they are now kept apart in a tiny cubicle with a small opening where dishes are passed through. Intended as a step forward, this was a regression where even the part of the woman as a designer is called in to question: she was still an accessory to the main architect's work, also like Charlotte Perriand, Corbusier's partner in furniture design and... the 'Unité d'Habitation' kitchens.

Nowadays' replica

Grete Schütte-Lihotsky

Figure 19: 'Frankfurt Kitchen'

The internal layout of the Praunheim cells was not something very innovative, somehow common in other functionalist proposals: parent's bedroom, children's bedroom (in his own words), without gender distinction. The master bedroom is always bigger than the children's (16m² for 8m² in the Type IIA), which remembers the above mentioned family structure defined by a couple and an amalgam of children. The master bedroom's additional area does not only define hierarchy but it allows the couple's private development as an entity by giving them additional private space for other activities in the bedroom (a need that is not acknowledged for the children or adolescents). In the above mentioned Type IIA there is a room defined as 'loft' in the upper floor of the house, with a huge balcony that actually is an extension of the master bedroom.

Figure 20: Type IIA cell, Praunheim

At a glance the Type VII looks similar to the previous one, but in fact its loft corresponds to a nuclear family that has been expanded: the loft is no longer an extension of a room, but a separate entity altogether, since it has an independent entrance, becoming a flat within the house. It has kitchen, bathroom and an open space for lounging and sleeping. Usually the floor plans have captions that identify the bedrooms as parent's and children's, but this loft has no precise user attached. So it is a space for multiple purposes than can accommodate grandparents, uncles or even a recently married son or daughter.

Figure 21: Type VII cell, Praunheim

This would be a breakthrough since usually the family was idealized as a static entity where the characters 'maintain the same age forever', forgetting those periods where the family's boundaries are toned down (and where the entity of a 'household' would be more pertinent than the conception of a 'family'). However this is an example of a very rigid initial module that has to repeat utilitarian spaces (like kitchen and bathroom) to become versatile, instead of promoting flexibility from the start.

5.4. Several Rooms

Even if it seems contradictory we may say that, through the analyzed models, Functionalism hadn't made the best of the technical potential that Modernism brought, like an independent structure from the outside walls. May used prefabricated façades applied in the construction site in the skeleton of the house, but that didn't prevent the design of very severe houses.

5.4.1. Weissenhof Apartments

Mies van der Rohe never intended to be a functionalist, although being known to say that every shape that did not come from its structure should be refused⁷. As the director of the German Werkbund he organizes the 'Weissenhofsiedlungen' exhibit where many modernist architects participate with their projects. His proposal is a linear block with inner staircases for two apartments each per floor, with a total of three floors and eight apartments per floor, where he manages to conceive twenty-four different apartments, allowed by the structure-free internal layout of the building. His inner space solutions don't correspond to a specific theory about family or living, but mainly to the need to expose the infinite possibilities permitted by a concrete structure and the absence of housing preconceptions (traditional or... functionalist).

Figure 22: Weissenhof (1927), Mies van der Rohe (1886 – 1969), Second Floor (above), Ground and First Floors (below)

⁷ <<http://www.vitruvio.ch/arc/masters/mies.php>>, [03.2009]

Mies proposals contemplate rigid layouts and open spaces, tiny kitchens (3m²) and livable ones (13m²); well defined nocturnal areas or bedrooms with sliding doors opened to the lounge. And finally, very common layouts and others more difficult to digest.

Figure 23: Weissenhof (1927), Mies van der Rohe (1886 – 1969), Second Floor (above), Ground and First Floors (below)

Mies probably didn't conceive this proposals as unalterable, like a catalogue in which the client would chose their preferred flat. As a display of possibilities, it would be also a demonstration of how the dweller could intervene in its own space, adapting it to changing circumstances as time went by.

Figure 24: Weissenhof (1927), Mies van der Rohe (1886 – 1969)

6. The Family Dismemberment

Functionalism believed in the development of the family structure according to a mechanical idea, where people would function within their homes with the same efficiency as in a factory. Nevertheless

they still believed that the basis of the society was the family, even if an idealized one. The Socialist revolution that occurred in the Soviet Union led to a new conception of society: all notions of classes would be eliminated, including the main expression of the bourgeoisie, the Family. Blood ties were considered inappropriate for the development of an egalitarian society where the only collective element would be a community made only by individuals. The couple was accounted as two independent elements, and their main function was to evolve physically and mentally, in which the family and its duties were an obstacle. From now on raising and educating children would be a social duty performed by trained educators and not the parents.

This inhumane proposal of social organization would reveal inadequate and far from the aspirations of the future dwellers who would live in future housing proposals conceived under these theories. In an inquiry made to the Russian population promoted by OSA (Contemporary Architects Association), which defended a less pragmatic posture than ASNOVA (New Architects Association), people said that they didn't want English 'cottages' to live, but even less 'apartment cages'. They still defended the family as the society and house basic element⁸.

6.1. The Social Condenser

Despite this enquiry, some models were designed according to this 'new' society. The model building would be made out of units composed by a lounge and a room for one person, where he could have his personal space. All the interaction with his colleagues, friends and family would be made in the canteen or the Worker's Club. Karel Teige defined the housing block as a sum of these cells, with a total occupation of 400 to 800 dwellers (100 to 125 traditional families) distributed through only five stories so they wouldn't have a lift and could be built traditionally.

6.1.1. The 'Dom-Kommuna' Narkomfin

This building is the best known expression of the new social order, destined to house the employees of the Ministry of Finance (Narkomfin). Its author, Moisei Ginzburg (1892-1946), conceived it as a transition for the new society, since the intended changes in people's habits would be too dramatic. There's still a canteen and a Worker's Club, but the base-unit of the cells would be the couple (with or without children) and not the individual. It had a little bathroom, a small kitchen counter (that would be removed once society had evolved to use only collective services) and it was it. As Teige, he also agreed that the 'Frankfurt Kitchen' was useless and degrading for women. We are still far from the beehive intended by Teige, but close to his idealized cell: a comfortably sized private space (bedroom: 21m²;

⁸ **Aymonino, Carlo**, 1973, *“La Vivienda Racional: ponencias de los congresos CIAM 1929-1930”*, Barcelona: Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A. 08029, 1973, [ISBN 84-252-0755-X]

lounge: 24m²) so there could be a personal area away from children. Its galleries and double height ceilings would inspire Corbusier (1887-1965), which according to him ‘respired Modernity’.

Figure 25: Dom-kommuna Narkomfin (1927), Moisei Ginzburg (1892 - 1946)

Even if Teige’s extremist ideas were not put into practice, the toned-down ‘Social Condenser’ wouldn’t be accepted. It consisted in the ‘cages’ dreaded by people, and it promoted an urban solution without a core or references. The Communist Regime would eventually prefer a classical image for its buildings in order to soothe Russians in the post-revolutionary period⁹.

Double bedroom apartment

Section

Figure 26: Dom-kommuna Narkomfin (1927), Moisei Ginzburg (1892 - 1946)

Although the ‘Dom-kommunas’ were a failure according to their main objective, its typology nowadays deserves a second outlook, since its studio-like apartments seem to fit the needs of new types of

⁹ **Teige, Karel** – “*The Minimum Dwelling*”, 2002, The MIT Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts [ISBN 0-262-20136-4]

households, like friends, bachelors or couples without children. These new characters would create the new 'household' figure, in which the family is just one of its components.

Figure 27: The 'Dom-kommuna' Narkomfin today

7. The Perseverance of the Family: shape and image

The post-II World War years were beneficial to the idea of the Family as the basis of the living cell. After the previous failed radical experiences, the minimum house investigation recovers some of the previous spatial solutions, even some brought by Modernism proved to be effective. But the hegemony that was intended by its authors was far from being attained and each country starts to search for new housing solutions within their frontiers. Instead of trying to do radical changes in the way of life, architects started to observe how people lived according to their own traditions, and trying to conceive the 'new house' starting from there. That would be one of the causes that would call Modernism into question.

7.1 Public over private

So, the liberty (from dogmas) allowed by the Modern revisionist movements permitted a greater attention to the surrounding reality. As a more visible consequence the International Style dilutes and the architecture general image becomes more humane. The internal space of the cell now makes references to local ways of life, which are still based on the Family, but impose different limits for their member's privacy according to the country they stand. Northern European countries reveal to be less complicated in the family's inner relationship, proposing bigger daytime areas, not as welcome areas, but in a way that considers intimate only the more personal activities (therefore with smaller bedrooms).

7.2 Private over Public

Southern Europe as a different understanding of privacy in which each member has the opportunity to get more in touch with their intimacy. The rooms are bigger, but also the family's activities are

maintained private from outside guests. A big kitchen with a dining table keeps more secluded meals and other activities performed within the family. So, the internal separation between daytime and nighttime areas proposed by Functionalism suited the Italian Neo-realism who esteemed their privacy.

7.3 Rethinking Modernism

Although some Modernist values were still valid, in the 60s some voices started to be heard defending the revision of its principles towards new ideas, shapes and image in architecture. However the themes that urgently needed debate were other than the Dweller, even if he still was indirectly affected by questions as urban planning or architectural heritage.

7.3.1 Urban Humanization

An anonymous urban image composed by isolated and identical housing blocks demanded new proposals that could once again transmit a sense of belonging. The relationship between shape and psychological needs becomes the theme of the last CIAM (Congrès Internationaux d'Architecture Moderne) in which the TEAM X intended to rethink some of the more simplistic Modern ideas. Allison and Peter Smithson were two of its members and their proposal took shape in the Robin Hood Gardens housing blocks, a three dimension critique to Corbusier's Ville Radieuse: the functional division among work/house/leisure was intended to be substituted by a sequence of house-street-district and city (the house being the primary unit of the process). The open galleries would represent those streets but they would reveal themselves inappropriate for communal living and a very weak alternative for courtyards, for instance.

Figure 28: Robin Hood Gardens (1966 - 1972), Allison e Peter Smithson (1928 - 1993; 1923 - 2003)

7.3.2 Aesthetical Humanization

From the 50s it became obvious that modernism had been an experience with little influence outside the architectural context, without making the changes it proposed. It remained as a style that managed to make everyplace look like anyplace¹⁰. The effort made over functionality and rationality forgot beauty, therefore Post-Modernism gives focus on the subject in order to hand back to architecture its symbols and context. The absence of new housing theories lead to the permanence of some Modernist types, even if revised. The more radical experiences were abandoned but a more softened Functionalism still remained.

Despite all its excesses Modernism accomplished a lot, by giving dignity to social housing, which became healthy, mentally and physically, not only through correct lighting and ventilation, but also throughout new spatial solutions, mainly spaces that promoted privacy. Although each culture started to recover some of its housing traditions, the bedroom was kept as an enclosed space.

8. New Characters in the Domestic Scene: the household

The modern nuclear family was the western idealization that determined the functional aspects of the house. It was linked to the family's means of subsistence and had evolved since the three generation family that took care of the crops before the industrial revolution. Such categorization was a simplistic one, since it excluded other agents that were not covered by the pre-establish model¹¹. The consequences were housing models that didn't fit the purposes of many households, like composed ones.

8.1 Identifying the Household

The 'household' appeared as a new categorization in which families, simple, composed or extended, are only part of the whole types of dwellers. In the United Kingdom in the 1971's Census there were already references to a Household, in which dwellers, family or not, should have some activities in common to be considered¹². Only in 1991 those activities were specified, like sharing a meal or the

¹⁰ **Frampton, Keneth**, (1996), *'Historia critica de la arquitectura moderna'*, Barcelona: Gustavo Gili, S.A. [ISBN 84-252-1628-1]

¹¹ *'Family in Anthropology since (1980) - New Directions For Family Studies'*, <<http://science.jrank.org/pages/9308/Family-in-Anthropology-since-1980-New-Directions-Family-Studies.html>>, [11.2008]

¹² *'Household definition on the census form'*, <<http://www.celsius.lshtm.ac.uk/modules/hhfam/hf020100.html>>, [11.2008]

lounge. Sylvia Yanagisako in a 1979¹³ article says that the Household is connected to residence, and not blood ties, in which the dweller's culture is reflected. Therefore a society's main domestic activities must be identified in order to define the criteria that will define the members of a household within that society. So, having meals together only is a criterion if in the corresponding society that is a habit.

8.1.1 Physical Preceding

Although recent, the household notion has always been present, even if it was an unintended and unwanted situation (like in the Industrial Revolution ages, where families had to share the same room with others).

8.1.2. Ideological Preceding

But even in the Modern Movement where the typical occupants of a house were the nuclear family, some architects seem to have based their proposals by observing real existing households, rather than creating an all-purpose type. Ernst May, being a functionalist, designs in Praunheim very 'restrict' cells, but also some that stand out for their spatial and functional features. The Type VII cell, already referred, has a loft in the upper floor that consists in an additional flat inside the house. Therefore a three generation enlarged household would find their place with additional privacy for an older or younger couple.

Figure 29: Type VII cell, **Praunheim** (1926), **Ernst May** (1886 – 1970)

8.2 Household's Evolution Elements

¹³ **Yanagisako, Sylvia**, 1979, "Family and Household: The Analysis of Domestic Groups", Annual Review of Anthropology, October 1979, Vol. 8, pages 161-205

We can admit that the alternative households would only account for a number of cases smaller than nowadays. The reasons that took to the creation of new households have to do with the evolving society in cultural terms (new kinds of relationship and privacy among dwellers) but also financially (for better or for worse). Therefore, the 'traditional' Modernist models start to show its frailty.

8.2.1 Economics as a Factor

After the II World War there was a huge reconstruction effort that made use of the Modernist spatial and constructive features. In countries where destruction was less acute, urgency was not an issue and there was the opportunity to experiment new housing solutions (like in the Nordic New Empiricism¹⁴). But the nuclear family stood as the used type, sometimes forgetting how difficult economics prevent one's independency, therefore creating additional household types trough enlarged families grown vertically (grandparents, parents, sons) or horizontally (parents, uncles, sons, nephews). If the house turns to be incapable of supporting a kind of use other than the one it was conceived to, the inter-relations among dwellers become fragile and less private. On the other hand, those who chose independency in the early years of their life can share the same house, therefore creating a household unrelated to blood-ties. Emigration is another factor that leads to coexistence among families in the same house, with the aggravating circumstance that the housing model, if strict in its physical use, is also culturally castrating.

8.2.2 Culture as a Factor

A swaying financial situation also leads to cultural changes within the household, as we seen above, and a beneficial economy has parallel consequences in the way we live. When college became more common, one of its consequences was to postpone young adults' independency. House sharing is a solution for displaced students, but for those close to home it means sharing a house with their parents. We must see beyond the family ties to understand that we are talking about adults from different age groups with a different cultural background, which makes coexistence more difficult. The functionalist model, severely divided in public, private and service, becomes obsolete since some 'services' become public (the kitchen), for example. In the composed households, with members in different group ages, it's created a gap, where we can identify visitors from each group that don't necessarily socialize among them.

¹⁴ **Fonseca Jorge, Pedro**, 2010, *'The Minimum Cell – minimum housing standards: Minimum as Maximum'*, International Journal of Arts and Sciences (as presented in the International Conference for Academic Disciplines, Orlando 1-4 March 2010)

9. Redefining Parts: fatherhood, motherhood and brotherhood

Another cultural factor that would influence the development of the house since the late 1970's would be the (real) women's emancipation from its traditional part. It was attempted previously in Modernism, but as a paternalistic attitude that would keep women subdued: the simplification of the domestic tasks still implied that those tasks were exclusively hers. There are two aspects to take into account: first, the kitchen becomes more humane, losing its laboratorial look and isolation, and second it becomes an extension of the lounge.

9.1. Up North

This phenomenon was more visible in Central and Northern Europe, since its cultural history had always defined a less rigid separation between public and private: down south the kitchen kept its very private character, as a space for the family's inter-relationship. It is no longer a cubicle, but a spacious room, even if properly enclosed.

9.1.1: Kitchen with a space for meals

The second generation Modernism had already proposed a small dining area located after a corridor-kitchen, like in Alvar Aalto's Hansaviertel Apartments in 1955. But gradually this solution progressed to less liberal countries, like France, where the Emile Aillaude's (1902-1988) 'Tour Nuage' (1975) offers the same kitchen type. The 'corridor-kitchen' and dinning space opens freely to the lounge but the rest of the house still maintains a very private nighttime area (with a private corridor).

Figure 30 : Tour Nuage (1975), Emile Aillaude (1902-1988)

A variation is offered in DKV's building in Kop St. Janshaven Street (1986-1988) that places the dining area opposite to the lounge, with the corridor-kitchen in the middle, which results in a more private area.

This kind of solutions would become very useful when the architect searches for more versatility in the way dwellers appropriate their space, as we can see in the following examples.

Figure 31: Kop St. Janshaven (1986-1988), DKV

The Admiralstrasse Street building (1986), from Nylund, Puttfarken and Stürzebecher goes further, proposing a 22m² cooking/dining area. Its location, as an entrance space, indicates a public use where visitors are welcomed. The living room becomes a more secluded space, closed by a door and holding the stairs to the upper floor, where the rooms are.

Figure 32: Admiralstrasse, 16 (1986), Nylund, Puttfarken e Stürzebecher

The K25 building (1988-1992), from Zaaijer, Christiaanse and van De Born defines a small hallway but with immediate access to the 48m² dining room/kitchen where only the counter offers some sort of a limit between eating and cooking. Opposed to the kitchen there is still a living room with 20m² that can be closed, making this the truly private space within the public domestic areas. Contrarily to the Italians that during the 1950's Neo-realism used the kitchen as a family space, the 'Dutch' seem to prefer a leisure-only area to connect with their household members. Notice that it's possible to use the living room as an additional bedroom since it can be closed, but also because the dining area has enough space to be used as a lounge.

Figure 33: K25 (1988-1992), Zaaijer, Christiaanse e van De Born

The more radical solution seems to be to unite living room, dining room and kitchen in a single space, as in Galgebakken (1969-1974), in Denmark, by Stogard, Orum-Nielsen and Marcussen. All the domestic public life becomes public to outside visitors, even if there is a hall that protects the lounge from the front door that filters some prying-eyes. The nearby bathroom and office/bedroom makes possible to have visitors without them entering the household's private space, proving that even here there must be some sort of limit between 'outside public' and 'domestic public'.

Figure 34: Galgebakken (1969-1974), Zaaijer, Christiaanse e van De Born

10. Beyond the Family: fraternity and privacy

The perception in architecture of the existence of households beyond the family is a relatively recent phenomenon. The above mentioned causes lead to consider new spatial needs, because there are many reasons that lead to the coexistence under the same roof of families, generations, friends and strangers. The notion that you can't predict the precise type of dwellers destroys the last of Modernism's dogmas: the need for versatility, in order to be able to adapt to any kind of household, determines that spaces and rooms with a precise uses become obsolete.

College students and young adults are a good example of a new kind of household that demands a lot from a house. Friends and strangers share a series of services and spaces but also need privacy: a bedroom that is also a living and a reception room for visitors. The location and proportion of the rooms in a house are revised in order to create a space that is homogenous and innocuous in the sense that dwellers can use rooms as they please. A smaller lounge and bigger kitchen and rooms fit the above purposes but also the ones of a family that only spends their time at home during meals, being the rooms a leisure area (specially for children with their electronic paraphernalia).

This is why fraternity and privacy are opposites that come close together when blood-ties are no longer important in a house. The types and models from pre-Modern architecture become an example, with their undifferentiated spaces and multiple accesses for each room, and influence contemporary housing cells.

10.1 Bahnhofstrasse (1992)

The house as a dynamic organism is the premise of Florian Riegler e Roger Riewe (1954 - ...; 1959 - ...), who manage to use the same cell as two-bedroom or a four-bedroom apartment, just changing the location of the kitchen (with the necessary plumbing in both spaces). The countless doors among rooms allow that, whatever the chosen use, access can still me made without disturbing others privacy. And, according to evolving needs, altering the apartment becomes viable.

Figure 35: Bahnhofstrasse, (1992), Florian Riegler (1954 - ...) e Roger Riewe (1959 - ...)

10.2 Campo di Marte (1985)

Álvaro Siza (1933-...) also manages to vary the number of rooms within the same apartment, with physical changes kept to a minimum, in this case the addition of a wall. The lounge (or the bigger of the bedrooms) is divided into two spaces, creating two bedrooms with 8m^2 each. However, since this is a Mediterranean project, the idealization of the spaces is more conservative, where the kitchen maintains always its enclosed character. As in the above previous example dwellers still maintain their autonomy, but still function as a group. That wouldn't be the case in the next example.

Figure 36: Campo di Marte, Venezia (1985), Álvaro Siza Vieira (1933 - ...)

10.3 Kitagata (1994-1998)

The more unconventional proposal must be the one from Kazuyo Sejima (1956 - ...) e Ryue Nishizawa (1966 - ...) that uses the bedroom as the module of the cell, not only in their measurements but also in their ideology. They have even their own outside entrance, making each dweller feel like they live in their own house inside a bigger one. The kitchen and the 'tatami' room are still the same for each one, but even so the household is composed like the sum of individual entities, like a group of persons living alone. The cell can still house a traditional family, but its range comprises all the household types.

Figure 36: Kitagata (1994 – 1998), Kazuyo Sejima (1956 - ...) e Ryue Nishizawa (1966 - ...)

Image References:

Figures 1, 2 and 3: author's drawing

Figure 5: <<http://www.orkneyjar.com/history/skarabrae/>>, [04.2010]

Figure 6: <<http://digital.library.wisc.edu/1711.dl/DLDecArts.CountHousePlaw>>, [04.2010]

Figures 7 to 12: author's drawing

Figure 13: floor plan: author's drawing; image: <<http://www.iisg.nl/volkshuisvesting/p10f2.html>> [04.2010]

Figure 14: floor plan: author's drawing; image: <<http://soa.syr.edu/faculty/bcoleman/arc523/images/housing/spangen/courtyard.sm.jpg/>>, [01.2009]

Figure 15: < <http://www.siedlerverein.de/>>, [01.2010] ;
<<http://weichensteller4.twoday.net/stories/4940821/>>, [02.2009] ;
< <http://soa.syr.edu/faculty/bcoleman/arc523/lectures/523.lecture.housing.packages.html>>, [02.2009] ;
Klein, Alexander, 1980, "Vivienda Mínima, 1906 - 1957", Editorial Gustavo Gili

Figure 16: floor plans: author's drawing

Figure 17: floor plans: author's drawing; image: <http://citywiki.ugr.es/wiki/Imagen:62Karl_Marx_Hof.JPG>, [02.2009]

Figure 18: <<http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Ebelfeld2.jpg>>, [01.2010]

Figure 19: < http://www.apartmenttherapy.com/ny/retrospect/the-frankfurt-kitchen-small-space-solution-circa-1926retrospect-113421?image_id=1316748>, [04.2010] ; <http://austria-lexikon.at/af/Wissenssammlungen/Biographien/Schütte-Lihotzky,_Margarete>, [04.2010]

Figures 20 and 21: floor plans: author's drawing

Figures 22 and 23: floor plans: author's drawing; images (floor plans): **Sherwood, Roger**, 2001, '*Modern Housing Prototypes*', Harvard University Press [ISBN: 0 674 57941 9]

Figure 24: <<http://www.flickr.com/photos/8mobili/3289330447/sizes/s/>>, [03.2009]

Figure 25 : <<http://teoriarquitectura.blogspot.com/2009/06/bloco-como-paradigma-moderno.html>>, [04.2010]

Figure 26: floor plans: author's drawing

Figure 27: <<http://www.panoramio.com/photo/10249790>>, [04.2010]

Figure 28: <<http://theurbanearth.wordpress.com/2008/03/03/arquitetura-modernamodern-architecture-robin-hood-gardens/>>, [04.2010]

Figure 29: floor plans: author's drawing

Figure 30: floor plans: author's drawing; image: <<http://eras.free.fr/html/archi/nuages.html>>, [04.2010]

Figure 31: floor plans: author's drawing; image:
<<http://www.xs4all.nl/~couvreur/ned/rdam/architectuur/100jaar/1988.htm>>, [04.2010]

Figure 32: floor plans: author's drawing; image:
<http://www.a.tu-berlin.de/GtE/galerie/seminar/seminareWS0304/Reader%20IBA_2.pdf>, [04.2010]

Figure 33: floor plans: author's drawing; image: **Gänshirt, Christian** (coordenador), 2007, – ‘*Floor Plan Manual: Housing: 3. Updated and Extended*’, Basel: Birkhäuser, pág. 178, [ISBN: 10 3764370351]

Figure 34: floor plans: author's drawing; image: **Gänshirt, Christian** (coordenador), 2007, – ‘*Floor Plan Manual: Housing: 3. Updated and Extended*’, Basel: Birkhäuser, pág. 279, [ISBN: 10 3764370351]

Figure 35: floor plans: author's drawing; image:
<http://www.rieglerriewe.co.at/projects/ho_esg/2.html>, [12.2009]

Figure 36: floor plans: author's drawing; image:
<http://www.egodesign.ca/en/article_print.php?article_id=90>, [12.2009]

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The Minimum Cell: criteria for minimum housing studies

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Abstract

The paper tries to define the necessary criteria to correctly analyze dwelling buildings with a social or subsidized background conceived during the XX century.

The defined criteria simultaneously allows the choice of the Housing Models, but also the definition of an 'Analysis Sheet' intended to give the necessary information about the Case-Studies' spatial distribution, areas, image and the author's intentions according to his current work and the Architectural Movement in which he operates.

The dweller is understood as an entity who as changed its aspirations and needs over time, thus becoming urgent the development of new housing proposals which allows the proper performance of the house's contemporary activities.

The obtained result throughout the Case-Studies analysis allows the determination of the validity or obsolescence of its formal, spacial and distributional contents during the specified period, in order to establish the basis of the design of new housing proposals which meet the needs on the common dweller.

Keywords: Housing; Dwelling; Space; Function; Criteria

1. Concept: the Minimum Cell

1.1 Definition

'The minimum volume of habitable space needed to implement all functional and social uses of their occupants'

1.1.1. Habitable Space

Defines the living space understood as 'home'. Inhabiting a space is not limited to the completion of practical tasks, but to the entire effort of ownership made by the occupant that manifest itself in many different fields. The 'culture' in which they operate determines the occupants use the space that becomes a Habitat. If eating is a basic human function, location, time and how it feeds the occupant is determined by cultural background. The habitat's 'container' – home – will express these cultural processes. Therefore being 'habitable' is not simply the ability to accommodate physical life, but also the capacity to support cultural and social life.

1.1.2. Minimum Volume

Defines the capacity of the three dimensional 'Habitable Space'. The notion of Minimum depends on many cultural factors. A family with a small income may arrange its smaller Habitable Space in a more rational way, but at the same time, its desire to create space for social parts may lead to the

adoption of inadequate furniture for the available area. A bourgeois family will connote a reduced ceiling height to 'social housing', preferring larger volumes, even if it does not pursue a real practical effect.

1.1.3. Functional Uses

Defines all the eminently practical activities that support physical life: eating, sleeping or using the toilet facilities. It should be noted that a merely functional activity is an abstraction: any human act, however unconscious it may seem, contains in itself a social and cultural meaning.

1.1.4. Social Uses

Defines all the socialization activities among dwellers (as a family or other) and also between dwellers and visitors, necessary activities to the development of the human mind.

- I. **Family:** Nuno Portas¹ refers the importance of the family's recognition based in the connection between class and way of life. He differentiates rural, worker and bourgeois backgrounds, in which the relationship among family members changes. The provider(s) vary according to his (her; their) background: just the father, father and mother and even the children. The private relationship among husband and wife, parents and their children and family and friends also varies according to their cultural origin. But the 'family' includes only part of the occupants of the home, since it implies kinship among inhabitants (even if we consider an extended family, with more members than those of the 'nuclear family'). Blood ties are not an exclusive for kinship definition, since it also implies by marriage and adopted relatives.
- II. **Household:** we must take in account other types of households, where 'housing cells', minimum or otherwise, are occupied with several people without any kind of kinship. 'Household' is a definition used in anthropological studies that contains a number of Types of dwellers, families included, that live in the same house. This is the basic criteria, but when there is more than one dweller it takes in account the activities that are performed in the same space, like meals. If cohabitation defines the Household, within this we can define multiple categories, where dwellers share the same age, occupation or financial status, none of this features necessarily simultaneous. Ana Isabel Afonso² prefers to use the definitions of 'nuclear, extended or composite households', instead of referring to 'family'. The variable need of intimacy manifest itself in a greater need to personalize the dwellers' private space(s).

1.2 Context

The 'cell' is intended as an abstract entity that is disconnected from its physical context. Consists in the set of relations among spaces destined to 'social and functional uses', according to the criteria defined by its author. It has a physical enclosure defined by outer walls, but limited to its immediate surroundings. It depends however on several other factors.

1.2.1 Building

The analysis of the 'cell' includes the study of external elements that participate on its definition. The way that those 'cells' associate themselves it's a factor that influences its accesses but also in the outer proportions of the 'cell' (and consequently, in the inner spaces distribution). So there will be some references made to certain characteristics that are motivated by accesses or construction techniques, although they won't be the object of a particular study

1.2.2 Urban Context

Pre-existences also determine the characterization of the 'cell', since they influence the building's configuration. Depth, height or shape of built of pre-existences are interfering situations that define the

¹ Portas, Nuno (2004) "*A Habitação Social: proposta para a metodologia da sua arquitectura*", 1st Edition, Porto: Edições FAUP
ISBN 972-9483-63-9

² Afonso, Ana Isabel (2004) "*Grupo Doméstico e Mudança Social: abordagens quantitativas e qualitativas*", viewed in October 2008

<http://ceas.iscte.pt/etnografica/docs/vol_04/N1/Vol_iv_N1_153-182.pdf>

dwelling, since they oblige the use of different types of 'cells' according to light and airing needs, for example.

2. Criteria used in the case-studies' choice

2.1 'Cell'

The choice of the case studies will be determined by the definition of 'cell'. Our attention will be focused in the unit that supports the live of the household. Even if inserted in a larger group, the notion of 'unit' or 'cell' will prevail over other types.

2.1.1 Private or Collective

The definition of 'Collective Housing' is not an influential factor in the 'cell's' choice. The study of minimum cells, especially during the Modern Movement, was also made through the creation of isolated prototypes, not inserted in a major building. To limit our search to collective housing building would impoverish our research, since many interesting proposals would have to be ignored.

2.1.2 Communitarian or Individual

In the 'Collective Housing's definition is included the sharing of some spaces (like the plot or the accesses) and technical services that may not influence directly the definition of 'cell', but have some power over its configuration and internal spaces. The type of association of the 'cell' does not determine its choice, but must be referenced in its analysis.

2.1.3 Culture and Geography

In order to maintain some coherence in the criteria used in the 'cell's' analysis, models that come from particular cultures defined by very precise cultural and practical uses must be excluded, although we will not restrict our study to the boundaries of Europe.

- I. However the intention is not to produce a mere functional analysis, without paying attention to any kind of symbolism. The 'Material Culture'³ can't be isolated from its semiotic dimension: the dwelling's function is to be inhabited, but the way it is made it's the expression of a social dimension that is beyond practical aspects. Shape and organization may differ among the collected 'cells' due to different social behaviors, since the established relations between parents and children, or dweller and visitors, are manifested in how the different spaces are conceived and organized. For example, privacy is more valued in Southern Europe, who determines a greater attention voted to private spaces, especially if compared with Northern Europe.
- II. One of the main used sources is a book untitled 'Floor Plan Manual'⁴ since it mainly uses plans and sections as its primary means of communication and comparison of the collected housing proposals. Its importance is even recognized by Hilary French⁵, also the author a similar project, but recognizes that the main aim of the quoted book is to offer a general overview of contemporary housing and not to portray a particular movement or a trend: the author voluntarily limits his study to a field where are only small differences between culture and climate, thus limiting his research to Europe.

2.2 Minimum

The concept of 'Minimum Cell' is necessarily vague in certain parameters. The idea of a 'Minimum' was an evolutionary definition and sometimes contradictory, attached to the dominant architectural

³ **Bucaille, Ricard, Pesez, Jean-Marie** (1989) "*Cultura Material*", in **Ruggiero, Romano** (dir.), Enciclopédia Einaudi, vol. 16, Lisboa: Imprensa Nacional - Casa da Moeda
ISBN 972-270080-4

⁴ **Gänshirt, Christian** (dir.) (2007) 4th edition, "*Floor Plan Manual: Housing: 3. Updated and Extended*", Basel: Birkhäuser
ISBN-10 3764370351

⁵ **French, Hilary** (dir) (2008) "*Key Urban Housing of the Twentieth Century*", London: Laurence King Publishing Ltd
ISBN-13: 978 1 85669 564 0

movement or those opposed to its hegemony. As a reflection or antithesis of the society in which they are included, the 'Minimum Cell' has different criteria. Therefore it was chosen not to define precise rules, since there was the risk of excluding some important case-studies.

- I. If during the Modern Movement it was crucial to reduced the area of the minimum standards, in the Italian Neo-realism Movement gave more emphasis on offering bigger areas at the expense of some equipment and finishing details of the cell. Therefore, area can't be a determinant factor in the choice of the case-studies, as the 'minimum acceptable to life' does not depend on size or volume.

2.3 Costs

The building cost is a feature that is more influential in the idea of a 'minimum cell', since its research is in most cases related to mass production housing destined to less privileged populations. In the 'Modern Movement' the rationality of construction techniques and use of materials was a general concept for all architectural production, although they were (and are) mainly applied in subsidized and social housing.

2.3.1 Promoter

The main promoter of this type of housing is the country's government, due to the character of social responsibility associated to the right to decent housing. Since area is not a determinant feature in the definition of a 'minimum cell', the State as a promoter substitutes, in general, this criteria in the choice of case-studies, since its housing projects are directly linked to the principles that define an efficient 'minimum cell'.

2.3.2 Investigation

This kind of promotion is often related to housing policies that endorse spatial and constructive experimentation laboratories, trough mass construction often linked to a specific architectural trend. As a reflection of the valid theories in a precise timeline, social housing programs are valid criteria in choosing case-studies.

2.4 Experimentation

The effort put in use in the investigation and experiment of innovative proposals of housing cells is also a used criteria. Architectural quality is a very broad definition, and its importance is also variable according to author and period of the project (assuming the co-relation established among creator and society, individual and collective).

2.4.1 Icons

The need for a consensual opinion about 'architectural quality' leads to the choice of architecture 'masters' (as defined by critics in general) whose work will be chosen as mirror of the Architectural Movement in which they operate.

2.4.2 Forgotten authors

Despite the attempts to unify theory and practice in some architectural movements, it is considered that hegemony was never achieved. Architects always applied in their work a personal touch that distinguished them from the trend to which they are commonly associated. That character was often the reason why some of them were often forgotten by the architectural critique and orthodox History. That doesn't indicate a lesser quality job, only that even the more important trend in architecture is also made of different types of gray. This is why lesser known architectures are also chosen to participate in this study.

2.5 Sources

It seems somewhat contradictory to research for Models of 'minimum cells' in documentary sources, since the publication of a project or an author implies it and his recognition by the architectural community. This recognition, however, was made in a precise moment that may not be our present time. And today that model and that author may be forgotten but still valid to Architecture History.

2.5.1 Date

The chosen source assumes its importance trough the date of publication versus the date of the project. From all the projects once published, present time only uses certain examples, in most cases from the

'Masters'. As far as possible, to search for models published in their own time reveals to be most important because it will symbolizes architectural practice in its time. Contemporary recollections will remain important because they also establish the importance of the included Models, comparatively to its predecessor's publications.

2.5.2 The Source's Author

The main responsible for a publication also indirectly defines the importance or oblivion of a Model or an Architect, since they applied their own personal criteria in the selection of the case-studies. So, the illustration of a particular time and space will also be the illustration of the author's time and space. A small investigation about the book authors will be made in order to understand what dictates or dictated his choices.

2.6 Typology

Some definitions must be made clear before we proceed, like the definition of 'Model', 'Type' and 'Typology'. Anthony Vidler⁶ tries to accomplish consensus in this matter. Using previous studies he achieves a definition of 'Type' that excludes merely physical aspects. The 'Type' is therefore a set of physical and ideological features through which we can group a whole range of 'case-studies', similar according to the predefined characteristics. The 'case-study' it is called 'Model' that, unlike the 'Type', is a concrete example. The study that groups the 'Models' according to their 'Type' it's called 'Typology'.

Therefore the 'Type' defined by the number of bedrooms (referred as T_x , being the x the variable corresponding to the number of rooms) also can determine the choice of different 'Models'. If we pretend to make a comparison among the collected 'cells' it's important that they have some elements in common, as it was explained before.

2.6.1 Bedrooms

For instance, the same number of rooms in different 'cells' allows comparisons among them, through the areas they spend in communal or private spaces. It's also necessary to focus our attention in the typologies that are more common, but also more interesting in spatial terms. However the proportion among 'Types' is also dictated by different demands: in post-catastrophe periods the preference goes to the 'Types' that allow its occupation by complete families, in times of prosperity Studios and T1's are preferred, given the (financial) opportunity to live alone. Therefore the selection of 'Models' also takes in account the social and economic context.

2.6.2 Capacity

Due to different 'spatial cultures' among countries, or even different regulations, it is avoided to use the designation T_x/y , where the y stands for the 'maximum capacity'⁷ of the 'cell', or the maximal number of tenants it allows. This classification consists already in an analysis, which will be avoided when choosing the 'case-studies'

- I. The maximum capacity of the 'cell' is, however, used by Alexander Klein⁸ as a criteria to define the quality of a dwelling: the '*betteffekt*' is the ratio between the number of beds and the floor area, meaning that for a better value, a bedroom for two beds had to be slightly bigger than one for just one bed.

⁶ Vidler, Anthony (1977) "*The Third Typology*", in *Architecture Theory since 1968* (1998), New York: Columbia Books of Architecture ISBN 0-262-58188-4

⁷ Pedro, João Branco (2001) 4th edition "*Programa Habitacional – Habitação, ICT Informação Técnica Arquitectura ITA5*", Lisbon: Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil ISBN 972-49-1812-2

⁸ Klein, Alexander (1980) "*Vivienda Mínima: 1906 – 1957*", Barcelona: Editorial Gustavo Gili, pp. 88

3. Case-studies' designing criteria

3.1 Reproduction

The 'cell' will be reproduced from the paper or digital source without changes, exceptions made under the following circumstances:

3.1.1 Measurement corrections

Some measurements seem incoherent, sometimes originated by the imprecision of the source. There will be no corrections made because it is fundamental to be faithful to one's source. These inaccuracies can arise from unknown or less obvious constraints of the project, for example:

- I. Peculiar plot dimensions.
- II. A particular geometrical system used by the architect or imposed by general legislation.
- III. The use of different measurement units.

3.1.2 Quality of the reproductions

The lack of quality of the reproductions present in some sources makes some drawings inaccurate, even if digitalized through a scanner and drawn with the help of CAD (Computer Assisted Design). The thickness and irregularity of the lines of the drawing is one example, which may misinform.

- I. Therefore there will be defined two midpoints at the beginning and at the end of the line, which will determine the location of the correct original line.
- II. The irregularity of the lines will not be incorporated in the final design, but major corrections will be avoided.

3.1.3 Exclusion criteria

The 'migration' of the (designed or constructed) original project to an architectural publication or other kind of source may lead to inconsistencies that are impossible to verify. If the selected model as a number of irregularities that call into question its credibility, the 'cell' will be excluded from the present study.

3.2 Design standardization

In order to make the models easier to compare, some amendments are necessary. The purpose is to facilitate the appreciation of the project without calling into question the integrity of the original design.

3.2.1 Bathroom/toilet ware

In some models the drawing that represents the toilet ware is an incoherent drawing in its representation or measurements. Therefore it will be adopted a number of symbols, representing toilet, bidet and washbasin that will become an empiric measurement method, common to all the designed models. The same will be applied in kitchen ware, where the stove and the washbasin will have the same symbol.

Exceptions will be made in the showers, bathtubs and, occasionally, the washbasin because they are often adapted to a space or a niche in particular, without standard measurements. Also, the models that are further apart in time (XVIII or XIX century) didn't have toilets or bathrooms in the way we are accustomed to imagine them.

3.2.2 Furniture

Some sources include in the design of the models some furniture symbols which seek to explain the use of a certain space or area, sometimes by the author's will, others by the publisher's will. Every so often these symbols try to explain additional uses, most likely included in the original drawings. The Voldparken project (1951), Husum, Denmark, by Kay Fisker (1893-1965) features a dashed line that converts a sofa into a bed. The rooms are not fit for a double bed, so it's possible that the architect intended the conversion of the living room into a bedroom by night. Hence the importance of the furniture symbols seen in the original drawings in explaining the envisioned uses of spaces.

Voldparken (1951), Kay Fisker (1893-1965)

Cambi, Di Sivo, Steiner, 1992, "*Viviendas en bloques alineados*", Barcelona: Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A., pp. 65
ISBN 968-887-186-9

The use of furniture symbols also offers the additional purpose of providing scale to the drawing, but it will be avoided the 'decoration' of the house plan with an unlimited set of pieces of furniture: there will be a limited number of symbols representing the more common pieces: sofas, dining table and beds, which provide an immediate caption of a room.

There are some specific Architectural Movements or authors that use these symbols with a more specific intention, like Alexander Klein (1879-1961) who defined the specific place for each piece of furniture in order to make the space more functional, even in terms of sun exposure.

When furniture is not originally represented, it will be included in the redesign of the 'cell', in order to unify and visually scale the drawing, using the above mentioned symbols.

3.2.3 House plan

According to the same effort to standardize the design of the 'cells' it was defined an overall image that will be repeated in each case studie. Apart from the above mentioned symbols, all the walls will be represented in gray, regardless of how it is presented in the source.

3.3 Captions

In order to maintain the same uniformity criteria, the use of captions aims the immediate recognition of the cell plan. Depending on the source and the principles adopted, the captions may be more or less generic: in some cases a living area and a dining area are indicated in the same space, in others the same space it is referred as a 'communal room'. In others situations there is an empirical recognition of the spaces and uses (without captions). Symbols as the ones adopted to indicate the entrance of the cell will also be uniformed.

Prototype (?), Alexander Klein (1879-1961)

Klein, Alexander, 1980, "*Vivienda Mínima, 1906 – 1957*", Barcelona, Gustavo Gili, pp. 149

3.3.1 Rule

Since it is intended to include the cell in a case-study file, where the analysis will be based, its drawing cannot consist itself in a comment or analysis. Therefore, the adopted captions must be 'harmless', in order not to interpret the referred spaces.

3.3.2 Exceptions

In 'cells' where rooms have no physical boundaries the captions have to be more specific. An open kitchen/dining/living room can cause some confusion: if we identify the dining area as a part of the kitchen, we are already making a judgement about the functional aspects of the house and its users. Also, in the Functionalist Movement these areas were defined, if not through walls, by the relation establish among rooms (dining areas near the kitchen, living spaces hereafter the dining room, etc.)

3.3.4 Examples of application of the parameters

Bad Dürrenberg, apartamento C2,(1930), Alexander Klein (1879-1961)

Klein, Alexander, 1980, "*Vivienda Mínima, 1906 – 1957*", Barcelona, Gustavo Gili, pp. 149

'Cell' in Brussels (undated; presented at CIAM II), unknown author
Aymonino, Carlo, 1973, *'La Vivienda Racional: ponencias de los congresos CIAM 1929-1930'* Barcelona: Gustavo Gili

Forte Quezzi,(1968), Luigi Carlo Daneri (1900-1972)
Cambi, Di Sivo, Steiner, 1992, *"Viviendas en bloques alineados"*, Barcelona: Gustavo Gili, pp. 149
ISBN 968-887-186-9

4 Case studies

Chamberlin, Powell and Bon GOLDEN LANE ESTATE 1952

CAPTIONS

T2 apartment

1 - Outside Gallery
2 - Hall
3 - Kitchen
4 - Living/Dining Room
5 - Balcony
6 - Corridor
7 - Bathroom
8 - Bedroom

Scale 1:200

Project	GOLDEN LANE ESTATE		
Location	London (United Kingdom)		
Author	Chamberlin, Powell & Bon		
Date	1952		
Proxifier	Public: St. City workers		
Accession of the cell	Free-standing structure		
Access	Outside Corridor		
Type	T2 & T3		
TYPE-APARTMENT			
	Area (m²)	Area	Total
Type	T2		
Total Area	72.9		
Usable Area	59.1		81.0%
Public Spaces			
Living/Dining Room	18.6	76.9%	31.5%
Kitchen	5.6	25.1%	9.5%
Balcony	2.4		3.2%
Corridor	1.1	19.8%	4.1%
Total	24.2	100.0%	40.2%
Private Spaces			
Bedroom	11.8	50.2%	20.0%
Bedroom	11.7	49.9%	19.9%
Bathroom	1.8	5.4%	2.2%
Total	23.5	100.0%	39.8%
Other Areas			
Bathroom	3.3		5.8%
Hall	2.1	25.9%	3.0%
Stair	3.2	60.2%	4.4%
Corridor	2.6	34.6%	3.7%
Total	8.1	100.0%	13.7%
Total (corridor/usable space)	3.2		5.3%
Total Usable Area	59.1		100.0%
Total (Balconies)	1.8		10.4%

original drawing

<http://www.building.co.uk/story.asp?storycode=100&storycode=3755903&c=3>
24/2005

<http://www.architecture.com>
2008-07-10 21:18
(04/2008)

accession of the cell

page 00 - 01 03.31

GOLDEN LANE ESTATE 1952

Yew Hall College, Cambridge
1960-68
http://www.yewhall.cam.ac.uk/academic/development/eng/07_01_01.htm
[04.2008]

Small areas, yet spacious-looking?
Double-height living room and elegant stairs
Window between the kitchen and living room
Also a double-height balcony
[Review excerpt of Le Corbusier's Housing Unit]

Common in duplexes, the distribution of area between public and private sectors comes from the disposition by floor
Rooms with generous areas with almost 12m²
Living room with only 19m² and a full-height kitchen with 5.6m²
Although open, the space over the stairs is not usable

Given the small areas, there is a concern with storage spaces:
Kitchen, corridor and bedrooms with closets

CHAMBERLIN, POWELL & BON

1920 – 1999 (Geoffrey Chamberlin); 1919 – 1979 (Peter 'Joe' Powell); 1919 – 1978 (Christopher Bon)

BRITANIAN BROS AND PARTNERS

Society created for development of the T² award-winning Golden Lane Estate project
They all individually competed, but had agreed to jointly develop the winning design

Regarded as the first representatives of British Modernism
Although they are also considered as 'localists'
[The use of concrete, present in the Fabian Social Scale, must have jointly contributed]

Very influenced by the ideas of Le Corbusier
Their urban planning concept was close to the 'Ville Radieuse'
[The Golden Lane planning, a urban intervention with all the necessary infrastructure, built in a non destroyed space, had a lot in common]
There are also comparisons between the Golden Lane duplexes and Le Corbusier's 'Unité d'habitation' cells
[The positioning of the entrance and high ceilings are similar to France]

The influence of Architectural Review magazine from the 40 / 50s is also strong
Conceived by a group of artists led by Gordon Cullen, a great proponent of the concept of 'Townscapes' through publishing
[In the act of making the mode of buildings, streets and spaces that make up the urban environment visually coherent and integrated.]

Architecture teachers at the Polytechnic of Kingston, later university

Townscapes 1962-78
<http://www.arch.com/photos/tds/index.html>
1978/1982
[04.2008]

¹ http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Golden_Lane_Estate [04.2008]
² http://www.architects.net/catalog/product_info.php?products_id=4425 [04.2008]

img 00 / 01 / 00.01

For each of the collected models it will be made a case-study sheet, intended to serve as basis for further analysis, gathering for this purpose as much information as possible.

4.1 Header

Project	FORSHAGAGATAN
Location	Farsta (Sweden)
Author	Nils Lonnroth
Data	1959
Promoter	unknown
Association of the cells	4 storey block
Accesses	Two apartments per floor
Type	T2

The header consists of various information which may be defined as technical data. The information is general, but influences, even if indirectly, the composition of the 'cell'.

4.1.1 Name of the project

The designation is selected according to the source, and fully reproduced. The criteria chosen by it to identify a project is not always the same: it may consist in the name of the street in which the building stands, the name of the promoting programme or even the name given by its author. In other cases, History itself is responsible for christening the building. However, if one favours one source to reproduce the plan of the 'cell', then he must use the applied designation.

4.1.2 Location

Defined by the district/village/town/city and country in which the building stands. The precision of this indication is variable according to the source.

4.1.3 Author

It refers author of the project. The use of the designation 'architect' would not be accurate since some authors don't have architectural training, and others have training in other disciplines.

4.1.4 Date

It is common to present only one reference (a year) without specifying a phase (design/construction/completion). Other sources present two dates according to the interval between the designing of the building and its completion.

When only one date is presented, it is assumed that it is referred to the beginning of the designing process. When two dates are present, only the first one is considered in order to establish a chronologic chart of all the collected 'cells'.

4.1.5 Promoter

The majority of the selected models makes part of a subsidized public program (one of the criteria defined for choosing the 'cells'). In some cases the source only indicates if it is 'public housing', but in others the 'program' is specified. However, private housing or from an unknown promoter are not excluded.

4.1.6 Association

Although it is not a fundamental parameter in the choice of the 'cell', it influences its shape and spatial contents. There are many designations who define the type of the association, sometimes the same type. So, the way the source defines the association of the 'cells' it is used as a reference: block, tower, row housing, etc.

4.1.7 Accesses

A block doesn't always imply the same type of access: it may be a stairway enclosure, an open gallery, etc. Other cases use more than one single way of access. Like the association, the access also determines the physical and spatial aspects of the 'cell', through the different relations that are established between outer and inner spaces, and the way these are distributed. Again, it is taken into account the way the source defines the access.

4.1.8 Typology

The above outlined criteria will be use, according to the formula Tx, where 'x' is the variable number of bedrooms. The number of occupants of each room will not be defined, since it depends of several factors, including regulations or the architect's ideology.

4.2 Technical elements

STANDARD CELL	Area (m2)	Zone	Total
Type	T3		
Gross Floor Area	97,3		
Floor Area	73,9		80,6%

The intention is to cross-reference information about the 'cell' relating, for instance, the area of each room to the total area of the house.

4.2.1 Elements of the 'Cell'

Here are included some items that do not fit in the header, which is referred to the building in general, and not to the 'cell'. By 'standard cell' it is identified that the case-studie refers to the more common cell in the building, but it may also indicate a special situation (gable, corner, etc.).

Gross Floor Area (cell): João Branco Pedro⁹ says that it 'is measured through the external contour of the exterior walls of the building and annexes, or through the axis of the walls that separate the house'. This definition does not take into account the communal areas of the total dwellers, including accesses. It is intended a comparison among the different spaces that organize the 'cell'. Including spaces that are not exclusive to it would be illogical. External private spaces are taken into account, according to the definition above, like balconies, verandas and patios.

Floor Area (cell): Nuno Portas¹⁰ defines it as 'the measurement by the inner perimeter of the interior walls (...)'. João Branco Pedro defines it as 'the floor area of a compartment, including closets, minus (...) the areas where the ceiling is lower than regulated'. As such, the usable area of the 'cell' will be the sum of the floor area of all its compartments.

Area (cell): the concept of 'Area' is different from 'Floor Area', which is defined by Nuno Portas as the 'sum of the floor area with the area of the balconies. The percentage expressed in the lower right corner (80,6%) refers to the proportion between 'area' and 'gross floor area', where, in the example above, the 'area' corresponds to 80,6% of the 'gross floor area': the remaining 19,4% consists on walls and other infrastructures.

Area of the balconies: according to Nuno Portas it is 'the not enclosed area in direct communication with house and for its exclusive use'. This will be accounted in accordance with the room that it serves (balcony of the kitchen, of the lounge, etc.).

⁹ **Pedro, João Branco** (2002) "*Programa Habitacional – Espaços e Compartimento, ICT Informação Técnica Arquitectura ITA4*", Lisbon: Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil, 3rd edition
ISBN 972-49-1811-4

¹⁰ **Portas, Nuno** (1969) "*Funções e Exigências de Áreas da Habitação, Informação Técnica: Edifícios*", Lisbon, Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil

4.2.2 Zone definition

When defining inner spaces with similar uses it was chosen to employ a generic definition. The spaces that are commonly used by the household (communal areas), are distinguished from those generally used by their specific occupants (private areas).

When trying to define the parameters that programmatic spaces must comply within the 'cell', Nuno Portas chooses to classify them through their functional aspects. He doesn't define a physical limit for a specific area, but determines several activities that take place in a house: 1) sleep, rest; 2) meal preparation; 3) casual and formal meals, among other categories. Nevertheless this kind of analysis does not suit to the present investigation. The inexistence of a physical boundary and the shared spaces of the various activities prevent a clear overview of the various 'cells'.

It is also avoided a differentiation like the one proposed by the CIAM (International Congress of Modern Architecture), in which the public and private areas were complemented with purely technical spaces, like the kitchen or the bathrooms¹¹. It is nowadays commonly accepted that a kitchen, for instance, has a very important socio-cultural aspect that allows its use as a space for social and leisure activities.

Therefore, the chosen categories will be the following: household's 'public areas', 'private areas' and 'other areas' (where are included spaces that do not belong in the previous categories and do not define new categories for themselves).

Within those categories the usages that may be performed in a physically defined space will be distinguished in a generalist way: living room, kitchen, bedroom, bathroom, etc. Sometimes it can also appear: office, multipurpose rooms or separated usages in the bathroom (like the toilet separated from the rest of the bathroom).

4.2.3 Household's public areas

It will be taken into account, partially, the definition given by João Branco Pedro: living/dining rooms, kitchen and sometimes a bathroom. He defines 'communal' a space which everybody has access for functional and emotional needs. The bathroom won't be considered a private area, because there are no user's intentional traces, like those left in a private bedroom. In some case-studies the kitchen, very small (sometimes for ideological reasons) doesn't allow a simultaneous use, so it can't be considered a real communal space. So it will be used the following definitions:

4.2.4 Private areas

João Branco Pedro uses the expression 'individual spaces' that comprises bedrooms and possibly a bathroom (in a suite bedroom, possibly, or when are two bathrooms). However classifying those as 'individual' seems to excuse a bedroom used by siblings, who appropriate space differently from a couple. It is therefore preferred the term 'private', since it doesn't imply a number of users.

Bedrooms: associated commonly only with sleeping (a very 'Modernist' definition), but also used as a play area or study. Changing lifestyles and increasing financial status imply nowadays the presence of computers, stereos or televisions.

An office also can be considered as a private space, but it can support a professional activity where guests are welcomed. Therefore, as the multipurpose areas, they are considered as public areas.

4.2.5 Another areas

There are several reasons why certain spaces are not included in the above categories. Some are purely functional, like a closet room or a corridor. Another reason is the analysis made in the case study charts, where the relation between public and private is very important: if the bathrooms were added to same category of living rooms and kitchens we would be led to believe that the household's public spaces were wider than they really are.

Bathrooms: there are some discussions about the inclusion of this space as public or private. It is true that dwellers don't use it as a living space, but all of them have access to it. The Existenzminimum

¹¹Aymonino, Carlo, 1973, "La Vivienda Racional: ponencias de los congresos CIAM 1929-1930", Barcelona: Gustavo Gili
ISBN 84-252-0755-X

considered them as technical spaces, Nuno Portas defines them as private and João Branco Pedro makes a distinction between public bathrooms and private in-suite bathrooms.

Lobby and corridors: these definitions and spaces sometimes overlap since both are neutral spaces that distribute the dwellers within the house. And also, corridors may serve as lobbies and vice versa. Therefore those designations will be used only when their characteristics are clear, so the more wide-ranging designation of 'distribution' will be used in other circumstances.

Dens: their existence sometimes depends on the organization of the 'cell', but there are also some cultural issues that determine their presence, like in the Italian Neo-realism.

4.3 Spread sheet

The spread sheet is organized in three columns that gather information on the areas described above, but also about other spaces on the dependence of those.

	Area (m2)	Zone	Total
Public areas			
Lounge	23,1	87,8%	31,3%
(balcony)	4,5		
Kitchen	3,2	12,2%	4,3%
(counter)	1,7	53,1%	
Total	26,3	100,0%	35,6%

4.3.1 Area (m²)

In here are reported the values of the floor area (in square meters) of each of the spaces that compose the 'cell'. Those are grouped by categories: 'public areas', 'private areas' and 'other areas'; in the last category the total sum of the areas of the rooms is not calculated, only on its subcategories.

In this parameter it is also made the sum of all the storage areas recorded during the process, including incorporated closets in bedrooms, lobby and dens.

At the bottom of the column it is showed the total floor area, or the sum of all the categories described.

Outras Zonas			
WC	2,2	25,0%	3,1%
Bathroom	6,6	75,0%	9,2%
Toilet Total	8,8	100,0%	12,2%
Lobby	2,6	63,4%	3,6%
(closet)	0,3	11,5%	
Corridor	1,5	36,6%	2,1%
Circulation Total	4,1	100,0%	5,7%
Den	1,3		1,8%
Storage Total	1,6		2,2%
Floor Area Total	72,0		100,0%

In each individual space it is noted the area of wardrobes, counters or other kind of built-in furniture. Its area is included in the floor area of the room. Balconies and patios are also taken in consideration, but this time their area is not included in the room (since they are outer spaces, not inner floor area)

		Area (m2)	Zone	Total
Public Areas				
Lounge		23,1	87,8%	31,3%
	(balcony)	4,5		
Kitchen		3,2	12,2%	4,3%
	(counter)	1,7	53,1%	
Total		26,3	100,0%	35,6%

4.3.2 Zone

These values are presented in percentage and correspond to the proportion between a room and the 'area' in which is included: 'private areas', 'public areas' or 'other areas' (in the following the area of the lounge corresponds to 75.9% of the 'public areas').

		Area (m2)	Zone	Total
Public Areas				
Lounge		20,2	75,9%	37,1%
	(balcony)	7,4		
Kitchen		6,4	24,1%	11,7%
	(counter)	1,6	25,0%	
Total		26,6	100,0%	48,8%

The sum of all the percentages of a certain 'area' must correspond to 100%. Wardrobes and counters are also presented in percentage, but now they estimate the proportion between their area and the area of the room (for instance, the kitchen counter corresponds to 25% of the floor area of the kitchen).

		Area (m2)	Zone	Total
Public Areas				
Lounge		20,2	75,9%	37,1%
	(balcony)	7,4		
Kitchen		6,4	24,1%	11,7%
	(counter)	1,6	25,0%	
Total		26,6	100,0%	48,8%

4.3.3 Total

This percentage corresponds to the relation between the area of a room and the floor area of the 'cell' (the area of the lounge corresponds to 37.1% of the total floor area, per example).

These percentages are also summed up, partially (per Zone) and totally: here their total has to be 100%.

All the storage space is also summed up and its percentage is also calculated (the storage space corresponds to 6.6% of the floor area of the 'cell').

	Area (m2)	Zone	Total
Other Areas			
Storage Total	4,2		6,6%

After the Floor Area total of the 'cell' appears the sum of all the balconies and patios. Based on this we calculate the percentage of the outdoor spaces in the Gross Floor Area of the 'cell'. Based on this value it is calculated the relation (in percentage) between Area and Gross Floor Area (the outer spaces account for 13.1% of the Gross Floor Area, and the sum of the Floor Area and Outer Areas corresponds for 79.6% of the Gross Floor Area).

TYPE APARTMENT	Area (m2)	Zone	Total
Type	T3		
Gross Floor Area	61,0		
Floor Area	40,6		79,6%
Total de Área Útil	40,6		100,0%
Outer Spaces Total	8,0		13,1%

4.4 Information Column

To the right of the spreadsheet and the header there is available a range of information destined to complement the previous. According to the available space, these elements can also arise under the captions. It is more general information, not referring to the 'cell' in particular, but to the building, its surroundings, etc.

4.4.1 Original Floor Plan Drawing

The intended uniformity among drawings it is useful and necessary, but it is important to present the original drawings, even if without a proper scale (most of the times smaller than the used 1/200).

As in a written source, the drawn elements also need references. That makes possible to verify the fidelity of the re-worked floor plan. Referring these drawings as 'originals' is avoided on purpose, since, for example, in book used as a source, they have been in most cases already redesigned. This is

the case of 'Viviendas en Bloques Alineados'¹² (drawn by hand) or 'Key Urban Housing'¹³ (drawn in CAD) but not of 'Floor Plan Manual'¹⁴ (reproducing integrally the original drawings, regardless if by hand or by CAD) or 'Modern Housing Prototypes'¹⁵ (reproducing the original handmade drawings).

In an additional file, designated as 'Extra Sources' are presented further bibliographic data or internet sites where the mentioned project can be consulted and used to cross-check information among different sources.

4.4.2 Photos of the project

Whenever possible it will be included some photos of the 'cell' or the building in which they belong. This is a variable parameter since in some case, due to the age of the project there are no photos or even drawings available.

4.4.3 Association of the 'Cells'

It will be made a small reference to the way the 'cells' are put together, in which the case studie will be marked.

4.4.4 Source abbreviation

The source/publication of the 'cell' is identified through an abbreviation of its name (two, three or four letters):

VBA: '*Viviendas en Bloques Alineados*', 1992, Barcelona, Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A. [ISBN 968-887-186-9]

6YH: '*6,000 Years of Housing, revised and expanded edition*', W. W. Norton & Company, New York, 2000 [ISBN 0-393-73052-2]

The decoding of these abbreviations is included in a file where some information is gathered about the authors.

With this code is presented the page where the project can be found. In some cases it is necessary to crosscheck more than one source, so both abbreviations and pages will be presented.

French, Hilary - Key Urban Housing of the Twentieth Century. 2008
Laurence King Publishing Ltd
ISBN-13: 978 1 85669 564 0

4.5 Distributive scheme

Using color schemes and arrows, it is tried to clarify the relationship established among the various spaces that compose the 'cell'.

4.5.1 Coloring

The 'private areas' and the 'public areas' are assigned a particular color each, but for 'other areas' the option was to separate bathrooms from halls and corridors. It is easier this way to get a more direct understanding of the connected spaces (public, private, and bathroom) and connecting spaces (hall and corridor). The balconies and patios also have a distinctive color.

4.5.2 Distribution

Through a system of arrows, information is added to the color scheme: it is now clarified the connection among the rooms of the 'cell', along with

Núcleo INA-Casa (1953),
Giancarlo De Carlo

¹² Cambi, Di Sivo, Steiner (1992) "*Viviendas en bloques alineados*", Barcelona: Gustavo Gili
ISBN: 968-887-186-9

¹³ French, Hilary (2008) "*Key Urban Housing of the Twentieth Century*", Laurence King Publishing
ISBN-13: 978 1 85669 564 0

¹⁴ Gänshirt, Christian (coordinator) (2007) "*Floor Plan Manual: Housing: 3. Updated and Extended*", Basel: Birkhäuser,
ISBN-10: 3764370351

¹⁵ Roger Sherwood (2002) "*Modern Housing Prototypes*", Harvard Paperbacks
ISBN-10: 0674579429; ISBN-13: 9780674579422

their relative line-up. The system starts at the main door entrance, and here it is a public route, since dwellers and visits both use it. The public route serves the 'public areas' but also the bathrooms, even if they stand among the bedrooms: once again, a visit could have access to it. The private route serves bedrooms and other possible private spaces. Finally, the external route gives access to balconies and patios. Sometimes rooms have more than one access, so the circulation scheme becomes circular. The orientation of the arrow is arbitrary and it doesn't mean a compulsory course.

Mannheimer Strasse
(1960), Oswald
Mathias Ungers

4.6 Preliminary analysis

Here are underlined some distinguishable features of the studied 'cell'. There will be made some brief notes, without a specific order or criteria about its common and exceptional features. Since there is already a space for pictures of the project, the left space of the 'preliminary analysis' is used to present some of the author's other projects or works.

VOLDPARKEN

1951

Vestersøhus, 1939

No apparent hierarchy

Public and private are not separated, physically and ideologically
One corridor serves both 'public areas' and 'private areas'

Spaces are easy to appropriate

The lounge can also be used as a master bedroom
The kitchen may have a dining area, if necessary
Bedroom by the entrance may have also a public function as an office

Imbalance in the distribution of areas between public and private

More than one half of the floor area is public space, so it can provide the double function lounge mentioned above
Very small bedroom, incapable of accommodate a double bed (another reason for the lounge/bedroom)
Distribution spaces account for 11% of the total floor area

4.7 Biography

Some knowledge about the author's ideas and artistic context is very important for the analysis of the 'cell'. Here it is made a review of his (hers) life and work, were the more important features will be stressed. Their age and the fact that they might not be the best known authors of their time can make the information gathering a very difficult task, sometimes without any results. However even a small reference in the corner of a page might be informative, so this cannot be considered a useless effort.

JOSEP EMILI DONATO 1932 – ...	
	Spanish painter, architect and urban planner
	<p>Studied Fine Arts, who influenced its perception of Architecture</p> <p>Made some travels in order to get to know the buildings mentioned in his architectural studies</p> <p>His architecture is manifested as the demand for a formal plasticity Its manifested trough the intelligent use of materials and technique</p> <p>Considers however that the 'drawing, more than a word, is like a caricature (...) of the final object'¹⁶</p> <p>His architecture is based on the expression of timeless forms and aesthetics</p> <p>'The novelty is not a novelty'¹⁷, which means that vanguard is not synonymous of quality Expresses monumentality in his works, which he considers inherent to its public nature His material of choice is red brick</p> <p>His choice, however, is dictated by the economic imperatives of the project: different circumstances leads to different materials</p>
	<p>Also works as architectural critic and teacher</p> <p>Commissioner of Culture at the College of Architects</p> <p>Professor at the Polytechnic University of Catalonia</p> <p>Mgazine director 'Cuadernos de Arquitectura y Urbanismo'</p> <p>Tries to understand the cultural and social fabric in which architecture is performed.</p>

References

- Aymonino, Carlo** (1973) *“La Vivienda Racional: ponencias de los congresos CIAM 1929-1930”*, Barcelona: Gustavo Gili, ISBN 84-252-0755-X
- Bucaille, Ricard, Pesez, Jean-Marie** (1989) *‘Cultura Material’*, in **Ruggiero, Romano** (dir.), Enciclopèdia Einaudi, vol. 16, Lisboa: Imprensa Nacional - Casa da Moeda, ISBN 972-270080-4
- Cambi, Di Sivo, Steiner** (1992), *‘Viviendas en bloques alineados’*, Barcelona: Gustavo Gili, ISBN: 968-887-186-9

¹⁶ <<http://www.vitruvius.com.br/resenhas/textos/resenha032.asp>>, accessed in October 2008

¹⁷ <<http://www.geocities.com/medit1976b/donato2.htm>>, accessed in October 2008

French, Hilary (dir) (2008) *'Key Urban Housing of the Twentieth Century'*, London: Laurence King Publishing Ltd, ISBN-13: 978 1 85669 564 0

Gänshirt, Christian (dir.) (2007) 4th edition, *'Floor Plan Manual: Housing: 3. Updated and Extended'*, Basel: Birkhäuser, ISBN-10 3764370351

Klein, Alexander (1980) *'Vivienda Mínima: 1906 - 1957'*, Barcelona: Editorial Gustavo Gili, pp. 88

Pedro, João Branco (2001) 4th edition *"Programa Habitacional – Habitação, ICT Informação Técnica Arquitectura ITA5"*, Lisbon: Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil, ISBN 972-49-1812-2

Pedro, João Branco (2002), *"Programa Habitacional – Espaços e Compartimento, ICT Informação Técnica Arquitectura ITA4"*, Lisbon: Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil, 3rd edition, ISBN 972-49-1811-4

Portas, Nuno (1969), *"Funções e Exigências de Áreas da Habitação, Informação Técnica: Edifícios"*, Lisbon, Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil

Portas, Nuno (2004) *"A Habitação Social: proposta para a metodologia da sua arquitectura"*, 1st Edition, Porto: Edições FAUP, ISBN 972-9483-63-9

Roger Sherwood, 2002, *'Modern Housing Prototypes'*, Harvard Paperbacks, ISBN-10: 0674579429; ISBN-13: 9780674579422

Vidler, Anthony (1977) *'The Third Typology'*, in *Architecture Theory since 1968* (1998), New York: Columbia Books of Architecture, ISBN 0-262-58188-4

Web Page:

Afonso, Ana Isabel (2004) *'Grupo Doméstico e Mudança Social: abordagens quantitativas e qualitativas'*, viewed in October 2008
<http://ceas.iscte.pt/etnografica/docs/vol_04/N1/Vol_iv_N1_153-182.pdf>

CAPTIONS

T2 apartment

- 1 - Staircase
- 2 - Hall
- 3 - Kitchen
- 4 - Balcony
- 5 - Toilet
- 6 - Shower
- 7 - Bedroom
- 8 - Lounge

Scale

1/200

Project **OVERSCHIE**

Location Rotterdam
 Author Jacob B. Bakema e Joahannes H. van den Broek
 Date 1957
 Promoter unmentioned

Association of the cell Aligned Block
 Acessos Common staircase
 Type T2

original drawing:

TYPE-APARTMENT	Area (m2)	Zone	Total
Type	T2		
Gross Floor Area	66,3		
Floor Area	53,0		83,0%
Public Spaces			
Lounge	18,6	79,8%	35,1%
(closet)	0,4	2,2%	
Kitchen	4,7	20,2%	8,9%
(balcony)	2,0		3,0%
(counter)	1,5	31,9%	
Total	23,3	100,0%	44,0%
Private Spaces			
Bedroom	8,7	42,6%	16,4%
Bedroom	11,7	57,4%	22,1%
Total	20,4 *	100,0%	38,5%
Other Areas			
Bedroom Sink	0,5	12,8%	0,9%
Bedroom Sink	0,5	12,8%	0,9%
Toilet	0,9	23,1%	1,7%
Shower	2,0	51,3%	3,8%
Total	3,9	100,0%	7,4%
Hall	5,4		10,2%
(closet)	1,6	29,6%	
Usable Area Total	53,0		100,0%

* the area occupied by the sink it is not taken into account

Cambi, Di Sivo, Steiner
 "Viviendas en bloques alineados", 1992,
 Barcelona, Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A.
 ISBN 968-887-186-9

association of the cell:

CAPTIONS

T2 apartment

- 1 - Staircase
- 2 - Hall
- 3 - Kitchen
- 4 - Balcony
- 5 - Toilet
- 6 - Shower
- 7 - Bedroom
- 8 - Lounge

- Public
- Private
- Bathroom
- Hall/Corridor
- Balcony/Courtyard
- Circulation (public)
- Circulation (private)
- Circulation (exterior)

Scale 1/200

OVERSCHIE

1957

Interbau Tower, Hansaviertel, Berlin, (1957)
http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Jo_van_den_Broek
 [10.2008]

'Housing cell' designed to be versatile

The bathroom is divided in toilet, shower and sink (one on each room) in order to allow simultaneous use of the facilities

The shower is accessible directly through the bedrooms

The toilet is accessible through the all so visitors can use it too

The master bedroom can be used as an extension of the living room

The entrance, trough a big sliding door, is made by the living room

The obtained circulation scheme allows to cross the entire apartment

The shower's double access makes possible this circular movement

It simultaneous reinforces and minimizes the apartment functionalist solution

Some practical aspects

Kitchen balcony

Big closet space in the hall, despite te apartment's small areas

VAN DEN BROEK + BAKEMA

1898 – 1978 (Jo van den Broek); 1914 – 1981 (Jaap Bakema)

Jaap Bakema and Jo van den Broek
<http://www.team10online.org/team10/bakema/index.html>
 [10.2008]

Dutch architects

Bakema is invited by van den Broek to work at 'Brinkman - van den Broek' in 1948

He had work before in Amsterdam's and Rotterdam's City Hall

First in Urban Development in Amsterdam

Then for Rotterdam's Housing Public Agency

They became 'van den Broek e Bakema' after Brinkman's death

They are considered Modern Movement' main characters ¹, but Bakema participated actively in its revision, trough his participation in the CIAM meetings

Belonged to CIAM's dutch delegation

Prepares the 10th Congress with those who would become members of the TEAM 10

He was the editor of the 'Forum' magazine, used as a platform of the group's ideas

Bakema defines architecture as a comprehensive discipline, called 'Architeturbanism'

Applies the idea of 'neighborhood scale' in the planning of urban functions

His television program 'From the chair to the city: a history of people and space' was a manifesto of his ideas

One of their most visible project was the housing tower in the 1957 Interbau, a 'punkthochhäuser', a low-rise buildings with 4 facades typical of Nordic postwar planning

They had earlier won projection with the Lijnbaan Shopping Center

Their biggest reference remains the Faculty of Architecture of Delft

Bakema would be a teacher there, as in Hamburg

¹ <http://www.answers.com/topic/van-den-broek-bakema-2>. [10.2008]

CAPTIONS

T3 apartment

- 1 - Public Gallery
- 2 - Hall
- 3 - Kitchen
- 4 - Lounge
- 5 - Balcony
- 6 - Corridor
- 7 - WC
- 8 - Bathroom
- 9 - Bedroom

Scale

1/200

Project **UNITÉ D'HABITATION DE NANTES**

Location Nantes (France)
 Author Le Corbusier
 Date 1952-1953
 Promoter Private - Housing Cooperative

original drawing:

Association of the cell Free-standing structure
 Access Inner Gallery
 Type T5, T3, T1, studio...

TYPE-APARTMENT	Area (m2)	Zone	Total
Type	T3		
Gross Floor Area	103,8		
Floor Area	74,8		82,9%
Public Spaces			
Lounge	13,0	76,5%	17,4%
(balcony)	5,4		5,2%
Kitchen	4,0	23,5%	5,3%
(counter)	2,5	62,5%	
Total	17,0	100,0%	22,7%
Private Spaces			
Bedroom	12,1	35,5%	16,2%
Bedroom	11,0	32,3%	14,7%
(balcony)	2,9		2,8%
Bedroom	11,0	32,3%	14,7%
(balcony)	2,9		2,8%
Total	34,1	100,0%	45,6%
Other Areas			
Bathroom	3,0	81,1%	4,0%
WC	0,7	18,9%	0,9%
Total	3,7	100,0%	4,9%
Hall	2,6	13,0%	3,5%
(closet)	0,3	11,5%	
Corridor	1,5	7,5%	2,0%
Stairs	2,0	10,0%	2,7%
Corridor	13,9	69,5%	18,6%
(armários)	2,3	16,5%	
Total	20,0	100,0%	26,7%
Total Floor Area	74,8		100,0%
Total (balconies)	11,2		10,8%

Typical Unité d'Habotation kitchen, designed by Charlotte Perriand

<http://homedesign.wordpress.com/2009/03/01/palladio-and-le-corbusier/>
 [03.2009]

<http://www.an-architecture.com/2008/11/cloning-buildings.html>
 [03.2009]

association of the cell:

CAPTIONS

T3 apartment

- 1 - Public Gallery
- 2 - Hall
- 3 - Kitchen
- 4 - Lounge
- 5 - Balcony
- 6 - Corridor
- 7 - WC
- 8 - Bathroom
- 9 - Bedroom

- Public
- Private
- Bathroom
- Hall/Corridor
- Balcony/Courtyard
- Circulation (public)
- Circulation (private)
- Circulation (exterior)

Scale 1/200

UNID. HAB. NANTES

1952 - 1953

'Maison Citrohan', 1922
<http://www.freewebs.com/b1223682/fascinatie.htm/>
 [03.2009]

Smaller area than in the Unité d'Habitation de Marseille: 104m²

The double-height living room is missing
 More area for the public areas...
 ...who are now in a single floor

Corridors have more area: 20m² (+3)
 Although the lower dept of the cell...
 ... manifested in the bedrooms' dept

The absence of the double-height makes the space more coherent
 The master bedroom is no longer open to the living room

According to a functionalist scheme the cell presents some deviations
 Bedrooms with a double function, through the sliding doors
 The corridor could accommodate a supplemental use?
 Presents a vaste area...
 ...possibly added to the bedrooms?

LE CORBUSIER

1887 - 1965

<http://www.worshipworthy.com/blog/2009/02/25/bad-ass-from-paris-raphael-young-by-cody-ross/>
 [03.2009]

'Chaise-long Le Corbusier'
<http://confluence.rave.ac.uk/confluence/pages/recentlyupdated.action?key=%7E95248306&maxRecentlyUpdatedPageCount=20>
 [03.2009]

Swiss architect, urban planner, painter, sculptor e writer, with French citizenship

Like many other contemporary architects (like Mies...) he has a rather reduced education
 Studies 'Arts and Crafts' in his hometown, with the architecture professor Charles L'Éplattenier, who influences his early work.

Advocated a nationalist romanticism ornate, supported by local cottage industry

Performs numerous trips abroad, collecting what he considered 'essential and timeless'

The Charterhouse of Ema, Italy, as an image of their socio-political concerns ...

... And the Greek temples, which praises the proportional system, reproduced in 'Modulor'

Works with Auguste Perret, a pioneer of the use of concrete in France ...

... And Peter Behrens, a representative of the German Werkbund

In his office works with Mies van der Rohe and Walter Gropius

By their influence, adopts a theory and a language based on industrial production

Corbusier and the painter Ozenfant nominate it 'purism'

Close to 'Cubism', simplifying its expressionist character

In the 'L'Esprit Nouveau' magazine publishes his opinions, grouped in 'Vers une Architecture'

Summarizes new architecture in 5 points, based on the technical possibilities of concrete

The Villa Savoye and the Housing Units are its ultimate expression, but had already been anticipated by the houses 'Dom-ino' and 'Maison Citrohan' ...

... Stilts, open plan, independent façade, big windows, roof gardens

After the 2nd World War abandons the industrial style, exploring the materials' expressiveness

It makes use of concrete marked with the wood of the frameworks in articulated structures

Uses vernacular materials and shapes, more sculptural

The Chapel of Ronchamp is a symbol of this period

In Urbanism reflects the need to rethink the traditional city

Considered unhealthy and inappropriate to the new requirements ...

... Including car traffic, whose influence is the first to recognize

His first urban project was the 'Contemporary City for 3,000,000 inhabitants'

Functional division between trade, housing and industry, separated by green areas

Applied to the 'Plan Voisin' for Paris, which included the demolition of part of the city center

More realistic was the 'Radiant City' of 1933-1935

Large blocks arranged in large venues, like the Housing Units

Has also recurring activity advertising Modern Architecture

Publishes numerous books, pamphlets, posters ...

He is a founding member of CIAM (International Congresses of Modern Architecture)

They tried to link the economic and political spheres to the field of architecture

The 1933 'Charter of Athens' debated the role of urban planning in society

CAPTIONS

T2 apartment

- 1 - Outside Gallery
- 2 - Hall
- 3 - Kitchen
- 4 - Living/Dining Room
- 5 - Balcony
- 6 - Corridor
- 7 - Bathroom
- 8 - Bedroom

Scala 1/200

Project	GOLDEN LANE ESTATE		
Location	London (United Kingdom)		
Author	Chanberlin, Powell e Bom		
Date	1952		
Promoter	Public (for City workers)		
Association of the cell	Free-standing structure		
Access	Outside Corridor		
Type	T2 e T3		
TYPE-APARTMENT	Area (m2)	Zone	Total
Type	T2		
Gross Floor Area	72,9		
Floor Area	59,1		91,5%
Public Spaces			
Lounge	18,6	76,9%	31,5%
(balcony)	5,8		8,0%
Kitchen	5,6	23,1%	9,5%
(cabinet)	1,1	19,6%	
(counter)	2,3	41,1%	
Total	24,2	100,0%	40,9%
Private Spaces			
Bedroom	11,8	50,2%	20,0%
(closet)	1,1	9,3%	
Bedroom	11,7	49,8%	19,8%
(balcony)	1,8		2,5%
(closet)	1,1	9,4%	
Total	23,5	100,0%	39,8%
Other Areas			
Bathroom	3,3		5,6%
Hall	2,1	25,9%	3,6%
Stairs	3,2	39,5%	5,4%
Corridor	2,8	34,6%	4,7%
(closet)	0,4	14,3%	
Total	8,1	100,0%	13,7%
Total (closet/cabinet space)	3,7		6,3%
Total Floor Area	59,1		100,0%
Total (balconies)	7,6		10,4%

original drawing:

<http://www.building.co.uk/story.asp?sectioncode=555&storycode=3133863&c=3>
[04.2009]

<http://www.exhibit-goldenlane.com/2008/07/10/259/>
[04.2009]

association of the cell:

CAPTIONS

T2 apartment

- 1 - Outside Gallery
- 2 - Hall
- 3 - Kitchen
- 4 - Living/Dining Room
- 5 - Balcony
- 6 - Corridor
- 7 - Bathroom
- 8 - Bedroom

- Public
- Private
- Bathroom
- Hall/Corridor
- Balcony/Courtyard
- Circulation (public)
- Circulation (private)
- Circulation (exterior)

Scala 1/200

GOLDEN LANE ESTATE 1952

'New Hall College, Cambridge'
1962-66

http://www.vitruvius.com.br/arquitextos/arq047/arq047_01_e.asp
[04.2009]

Small areas, yet 'spacious-looking'¹

Double-height living room and elegant stairs
Window between the kitchen and living room
Also a double-height balcony

Reminiscences of Le Corbusier's 'Housing Units'

Common in duplexes, the distribution of area between public and private sectors comes from the separation by floors

Rooms with generous areas with almost 12m²
Living room with 'only' 19m² and a 'functionalist' kitchen with 5,6m²
Although open, the space under the stairs is not usable

Given the small areas, there is a concern with storage spaces

Kitchen, corridor and bedrooms with closets

CHAMBERLIN, POWELL & BON

1920 – 1999 (Geoffrey Chamberlin); 1919 – 1978 (Peter 'Joe' Powell); 1919 – 1978 (Christoph Bom)

'Barbican Estate', 1965-76
<http://www.flickr.com/photos/suburban/1697819929/>
[04.2009]

British architects and teachers

Society created for development of the 1st award winning Golden Lane Estate project
They all individually competed, but had agreed to jointly develop the winning design

Regarded as the first representatives of British Modernism

Although they are also considered as 'brutalistas'

The use of concrete, present in the Barbican Estate, must have greatly contributed

Very influenced by the ideas of Le Corbusier

Their urban planning concept was close to the 'Ville Radieuse'

The Golden Lane planning, a urban microcosm with all the necessary infrastructures, born in a war destroyed space, has a lot in common

There are also comparisons between the Golden Lane 'duplexes' and Le Corbusier's 'Unité d'Habitation' cells

The positioning of the staircase and high ceilings are similar to Nantes

The influence of 'Architectural Review' magazine from the 40 / 50s is also strong

Dominated by a group of artists led by Gordon Cullen, a great proponent of the concept of 'Townscapes' through publishing

'Is the art of making the maze of buildings, streets and spaces that make up the urban environment visually coherent and organized'²

Architecture teachers at the Polytechnic of Kingston, later university

¹ http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Golden_Lane_Estate, [04.2009]

² http://www.almedina.net/catalog/product_info.php?products_id=4429, [04.2009]

CAPTIONS

Prototype

- 1 - Hall
- 2 - WC
- 3 - Corridor
- 4 - Stairs
- 5 - Closet
- 6 - Living/Dining Room
- 7 - Kitchen
- 8 - Corridor
- 9 - Bedroom
- 10 - Bathroom

Scale

1/200

original drawing:

Project	PROTOTYPE		
Location	(virtual project)		
Author	Alexander Klein		
Date	(no date)		
Promoter	(virtual project)		
Association of the cell	Row Houses		
Access	Direct		
Type	T3 (three-bedroom)		
Groundfloor	Area (m2)	Zone	Total
Type	T3		
Gross Floor Area	66,7		
Floor Area	52,8		79,2%
Public Sapces			
Lounge	17,3	86,5%	32,8%
Kitchen	2,7	13,5%	5,1%
(counter)	1,4	51,9%	
Total	20,0	100,0%	37,9%
Private Spaces			
Bedroom	13,0	61,9%	24,6%
Bedroom	4,0	19,0%	7,6%
Bedroom	4,0	19,0%	7,6%
Total	21,0	100,0%	39,8%
Oother Areas			
Bathroom	2,5	73,5%	4,7%
WC	0,9	26,5%	1,7%
Total	3,4	100,0%	6,4%
Hall	1,0	11,9%	1,9%
Corridor	2,6	31,0%	4,9%
Stairs	2,9	34,5%	5,5%
Corridor	1,9	22,6%	3,6%
(closet)	0,3	15,8%	
Total	8,4	100,0%	15,9%
Total Floor Area	52,8	100,0%	

Klein, Alexander
 "Vivienda Mínima, 1906 - 1957", 1980
 Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A.

association of the cell:

CAPTIONS

Prototype

- 1 - Hall
- 2 - WC
- 3 - Corridor
- 4 - Stairs
- 5 - Closet
- 6 - Living/Dining Room
- 7 - Kitchen
- 8 - Corridor
- 9 - Bedroom
- 10 - Bathroom

- Public
- Private
- Bathroom
- Hall/Corridor
- Balcony/Courtyard
- Circulation (public)
- Circulation (private)
- Circulation (exterior)

Scale 1/200

PROTOTYPE

(no date)

Kitchen inspired in models created by Alexander Klein
<http://www.maximainteriores.xl.pt/decor/interiores/1103/casas/a01-00-00.shtml>
 [10.2008]

Two storey row house prototype with only 53m² of usable area, with three bedrooms for three beds

Despite the minimum area, it is still capable of providing privacy for most rooms...

It has a first hall that protects the rest of the house from prying eyes

Gives access to the toilet, separated from the rest of the bathroom

...but in the upper floor, where it is tried to save area in corridors, it's used a compromise solution. One of the bedrooms is only accessible through the bathroom, while the contiguous one has its access in the corridor

Each of these bedrooms has only 4m²...
 ...while the master bedroom has 13m², about 62% of the private areas

ALEXANDER KLEIN

1879 – 1961

<http://www.ikg.uni-karlsruhe.de/projekte/exilarchitekten/architekten/klein.htm>
 [10.2008]

Russian Architect

Studies at the Institute of Engineering S. Petersburg, where he received a classical education

Arts, symmetry, balance and orthodoxy¹

His early works reveal a neo-classical 'opulent, almost ostentatious'²

The design of the Hospital S. Petersburg, design in collaboration, is an example

The type of research he undertakes is intellectually inserted into Modernism

However, it is ignored by the 'modesty of his works in the purely formal field'³

It was only in Berlin, in the 1920's, that he came in contact with the 'New Objectivity' (Neue Sachlichkeit)

His floor plans adopt a 'scientific' scheme, although the building's image was still vaguely neo-classical

His floor plans method of evaluation and development is published in 1927

Aimed at the design of new projects, but also possible for the evaluation of existing buildings. It is organized into three distinct phases:

Comparison of variables such as number of beds, floor area, private and public areas

Relates depth and size of the facade, and their effects on health and cost

Drawing circulation schemes, furniture-free areas, projection of shadows...

Publishes 'Das Einfamilienhaus – Stüttyp', The first volume of a never completed encyclopedia he intended to issue

In Israel, where lives from 1935, he works in various areas

Plan designer in the development of several cities, including a garden city

Counselor and planner for the 'Jewish National Fund for Construction'

Founder, in 1943, of the 'Research Institute of Construction and Planning Problems'

He taught at various institutions throughout his life

Professor in the Faculty of Architecture of S. Petersburg

Project supervision teacher in Berlin

Professor at the School of Charlottenburg

Professor and Director of the School of Architecture at the Technion, Haifa

¹ Rossari, Augusto – 'Os estudos de Alexander Klein e o movimento Racionalista', Klein, Alexander – 'Vivienda Mínima: 1906 - 1957', Editorial Gustavo Gili, 1980

² <http://www.answers.com/topic/alexander-klein-1>, [10.2008]

³ Rivolta, Matilde Baffa, - 'Alexander Klein e o problema da casa na Alemanha de Weimar', 'Vivienda Mínima: 1906 - 1957', Editorial Gustavo Gili, 1980

Heritage 2010 Greenlines Institute

'History is not just stories: a proposal for an operative use of popular architectural heritage'

Évora, Portugal, Junho de 2010

<http://heritage2010.greenlines-institute.org/H2010website/home.html>

(disponível em: Lira, Sérgio; Amoêda, Rogério; Pinheiro, Cristina (Editors); 2010, **'Heritage 2010 – Heritage and Sustainable Development – Vol. 2'**, pages 1373-1382, Green Lines Institute for Sustainable Development, ISBN 978-989-95671-3-9)

History is not just stories: a proposal for an operative use of popular architectural heritage.

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The current investigation tries to present Architectural Heritage as a source for today's practice in contemporary housing architecture. It's based on the analysis of popular architecture in the region of Alcobaça, Portugal, through existing housing models, but also across the archives of the City Hall of Alcobaça, and previous popular housing investigations. According to these sources it was defined for the gathered information a timeline around the 1960's in order to produce a Typological Study on formal and organizational schemes of the Popular dwelling architecture in the region.

A Type is therefore set according to its formal and spacial aspects, defining two kinds of approaches in the design of contemporary dwellings: Architectural Heritage as a shape, where architectural forms produce a feeling of belonging, and Architectural Heritage as a scheme, where ancient housing solutions respond to present needs.

1 INTRODUCTION

The search for references in architecture should not be seen as an obligation. Regarding Heritage, its usefulness is not limited to historical contexts, where the new buildings look for their immediate surroundings to achieve the desired anonymity required for its physical integration. In this context, History is sometimes considered as a necessary evil needed for legal and social requirements. So, when used, Architectural Heritage is limited to a vague aesthetical appreciation, in order to not compromise the contemporary "st'architecture" search for a statement.

We must try to validate our architectural heritage as a source of knowledge where answers can be found in order to solve a range of current practical problems, not only aesthetically. Heritage isn't a shape, a date or even an image. It consists in a path over a wide time range where different solutions were used, tested, reinvented, reused and even abandoned if necessary. To interpret History is to use an encyclopedia filled with valid solutions, directly or indirectly.

1.1 *A change of paradigm*

In the process of designing architecture we witness a change of attitude when Heritage, as a source, is not a resource to be studied only when History is referred, but also in different circumstances where answers are required. In other words, History is not presented as a category with well-defined closed borders inside of which problems are formulated and solved. Heritage is also a source to be consulted when issues related to contemporary dwellings arouse.

2RULE/EXCEPTION

Identifying a city, for example, cannot be done through its exceptional elements, like a church, a fire station or the city hall, but by a wider set of values that allows us to codify the elements of the urban space in two opposite meanings: the “rule” and the “exception”.

The identification of a "whole" is done by a succession of "rules" that allow us to combine a set of elements under the same name. The “city” is thus an ensemble where “something” is often repeated. Housing, by its use, shape and image, can be assumed as the “rule” that is constant. Public spaces (objects or voids), used for leisure, contemplation or work, are the elements of “exception” on the “traditional city”. As such, the use of different architectural languages agrees with the functional differences carried out by various programs.

The same logic can be applied in rural settings, where the “rule” is assumed, in a landscape more sparse, through Popular residential architecture (associated with other utilitarian buildings, supporting the population’s economic activities), and where the “exception”, even more diverse, states the existence of a “rule”.

In both settlements we usually associate “rule” to a less noble architecture, rarely associated to an architect, dominated perhaps only by practical purposes, but always supporting the basic activity of urban and rural life: to dwell. As such it is undeniable that it’s also our “Heritage”.

3LONG TERM MEMORY/SHORT TERM MEMORY

“Past is commonly considered as ‘what it was’, and, probably, ‘what won’t be again’. It’s static, with no possibilities of change, where events are assumed as facts and not as possibilities”.

This would be an ideal definition, in fact as idealistic as impossible. Past would only be static if we had an absolute knowledge of precedent events, but the truth is, in most cases, that we only know the Past and our Heritage through fragments that we have to make sense of through its analysis, decomposition and hypothesis confirmed or refused as we gather more fragments.

Nevertheless, Past is more static as it approaches the present time, because it stays within the spectrum of the observer’s memory, but also because, as time progresses, a greater effort is made in the protection of our memory.

This is way we must distinguish between two types of historical legacy: Past as a part of our Short Term Memory, or Past as part of our Long Term Memory, a fragmented memory because distant from our present time. In Architecture the major difference between them lies within the image we have of the past, were in the Short Term Memory we still have physically present Models, while as times passes, Models become scarce making our Long Term Memory blurred.

3.1 *Inexistent past/fake memories*

Figure 1. Hostel of Santa Maria do Bouro (1989-1997), Eduardo Souto Moura

Eduardo Souto Moura, in the Hostel of Santa Maria do Bouro (1989-1997) built over an old and ruined convent, made use of a memory that is still “ours”, precisely the one of a ruin. The building in its proper shape no longer belonged to our mind or even to the idea that we carry of its image: excavations made around the ruin revealed blood-red fragments of stucco and 1.20m green glazed tiles, very different from the pale walls and red roofs that, in Portugal, we are used to associate to our architectural heritage. So, the architect had three hypotheses: the Long Term Memory, strange to our reality; an Imaginary Memory, faked to correspond to our expectations; or the Short Term Memory, used in this case to create a new usable “ruin” from the old one, an attitude that has nothing in common with a restoration.

It’s undeniable that the landscape, rural or urban, is largely defined by the Rule and not the Exception (like a Convent or a Hostel). And the Rule, in a rural context, does not consist in an exceptional use/program (like a church) or in “signature” architecture (again, like most religious buildings). The Rule is, by definition, the most common thing that we can observe: the landscape. More common and perhaps more trivial than the human need of religiosity or culture: the simple need of a shelter. Therefore the House is what defines our landscape, also the more common house from the more common architecture: the Popular one.

Popular architecture belongs mainly to our Short Term Memory, because, as every manifestation of popular culture, it’s performed by an anonymous author, based on orally transmitted communal knowledge. The only record that we have of Popular Architecture, housing included, is in most cases the Model, or the actual building. It is more volatile than the Exceptional or Erudite Building, because it’s built with less durable materials, but also because people think less of it, precisely because it’s more common and simpler in appearance. With the disappearance of the Model, the Type also gets lost, as the memory that we have of it.

Popular Housing can’t be considered useless, as a memory, just because it dilutes itself in the landscape. Any project born of a desire of integration searches the Type that identifies its surroundings, and when conceiving a new house we must keep in mind the ones that define it.

4PRIOR STUDIES

Decades ago, aware of the volatility of Popular Architecture, a whole generation of architects offered to record for posterity its Models, preventing our memory from the oblivion that would occur with their disappearance. The book “Arquitectura Popular em Portugal” (“Popular Architecture in Portugal”¹) was conceived in the aftermath of the Modern Movement, born under the intention of proving to the Portuguese fascist regime that popular architecture was not all the same in Portugal, but as diversified as its climate, topography, culture and materials.

The collected items in the book, at the time of its completion (the 1960’s), corresponded to the Short Term Memory of those in charge of the investigation: the physically existing models in that date that corresponded to their idea of Past. But, at the same time the 1960’s ancient models were being collected, other contemporary Popular Architecture Models was being built. Their Architectural Type was another, already replacing the one collected in “Arquitectura Popular em Portugal”, making more urgent its need for documentation. The fact is that the Type and its Models, “new” 50 years ago, are nowadays part of the past and our Short Term Memory. So, the preceding Type, then close in time and shape, would be entirely forgotten if not collected and documented as part of our Long Term Memory.

This is even more relevant if we remember, as it was predicted by the authors of “Arquitectura Popular em Portugal”, that most of its Models (and their Types) are at the moment missing, which is also true in the region where the present investigation is based.

¹AAVV, 2004 (reprint), “*Arquitectura Popular em Portugal*”, Lisboa, Sindicato Nacional dos Arquitectos.

Figure 2. Models of the Type present in “Arquitectura Popular em Portugal”

4.1 *Pre-1960's type*

The ancient Type was characterized by a small porch at the entrance, with a small entrance between two lower walls, surrounded by the house. This would be its most striking feature, being the rest of the house a cluster of volumes with no apparent order, added individually according to the dweller needs and possibilities. Therefore, the resulting shape was not essential for the classification of the Type in question.

In present days this house is practically nonexistent, and its memory will only survive in the records done in the meantime. This does not mean the disappearance of Popular Architecture since, as was said, a Type generally replaces another.

5 PAST/ PRESENT

5.1 *Another sources*

The first way to get in contact to more recent Models is watching the landscape. Our curiosity is aroused by those apparent Types (since we still have no ground/information to define one) who emerge from the scenery. Here we watch history repeating: our present Rule is somehow ignored since it is well known, constantly in our background and even inhabited by “us”. We favor the Exception that was our previous Rule: our current Short Term Memory Models, absent in “Arquitectura Popular em Portugal”, because, for their authors, they were the Models of their Present. As before, their recollection was possible through a camera and a measuring tape.

Figure 3. Model from the 1960's collected by the author “in loco” in 2000

Figure 4. Models from 1961 collected from the archives of the City Hall of Alcobaça in 2005

Another way to get to know these Models was to use the existing records of the time in question (the 1960's). The City Hall of Alcobaça revealed itself as an essential source, since all buildings already needed a license to be built, with an application accompanied by drawings of the house. By coincidence, the oldest examples relate to the same period: the 1960's.

The information requested at that time was very different from now, where the drawings, all from an unidentified authors, were limited to plans and elevations of the house. No reference whatsoever was made to the building site, which we can observe "in loco" (only in the still existing Models), like the relations among house, roads, the site contours and annexes, very important to consider, since the main house worked has an initial module meant to be added.

However it was enough to confirm that the 1960's Present time was very different from its Past, being their Types complete opposites.

5.2 Our present past

The Popular House gained notoriety by adding some urban influences like a more regular shape of the building, symmetrical façade, ornate stonework, etc. Inside it was added regularity in the different spaces, with a symmetrical plan where there is no disparity in shape or size among areas. In fact only the kitchen can be identified through the presence of a chimney.

And this is the house that presently builds the rural landscape of Alcobaça, and that consists in "our present Past". Although the application processes only mention one single volume, this house belongs to a structure that involves additional buildings, more organic and simpler in their materials and building process, grouped around a patio with an utilitarian function. Also important, maybe this Type is no longer restricted to a small defined region, but spread over a wider space, as we can conclude by looking at a broader scope.

This is our "new Past" because it defines our landscape but also because it differs from the Popular Architecture that is produced presently. In Portugal, Popular Architecture still exists since architecture, by law, is not an exclusive of architects, but also from other technicians like engineers, who lack the necessary training to create architecture projects. And these are the circumstances that will define our "future Past" in times to come.

We can ask ourselves: formerly the author of Popular Architecture was also "anonymous", and models were also designed by people without "training". But, as a counter-argument, we can defend that the social situation has mostly changed. With three Types of rural housing identified (the first present in "Arquitetura Popular em Portugal", the second licensed in the 1960's, and the third being currently built) we can also identify three specific moments in Popular Culture. For the first Type we can still refer a Vernacular Architecture, as its influences are almost exclusively local, without any outer references: a shape defined by function and local materials and techniques.

In the 1960's we can identify several references that don't belong to a specific site, much less the place where the house stands. The Erudite leaves some marks, in regularity and ornament, in order to create an allusion of a lifestyle that probably had no place in its context.

Figure 5. Present day Models, collected by the author in 2000

5.3 *Our future past*

So, where can we fit today's Popular Architecture? How is it different from the previous examples? We are presently living in a time where a Symbol is more worthy than a Fact. The released image, real or imagined, dominates current attentions and determines choices, and in Architecture this is no different, since the House is the main vehicle of an alleged image.

Today's Popular House is an agglomerate of decorative signs juxtaposed over an architectural model otherwise trivial, which brings together eaves, porches, masonry, shutters, colors and other elements that never existed in local architecture from Alcobaça, even from Portugal. All these elements are put together according to the intention of creating an "old style Portuguese house", a designation that is doubly wrong.

In one hand, we can't consider Portuguese Architecture like a succession of similar models, repeated endlessly to the brink of political boundaries, since each region, unique in its climate and resources, always determines specificity in its architecture. On the other hand it is also wrong to create an idealized past based on the sum of decorative excesses over harmless Models, merely to correspond to one's expectations, like in the "Imaginary Past" solution mentioned above.

The 1960's rural Portugal's precarious living was reflected in their modest homes, in size and aspect, now "forgotten" in benefit of a well succeeded Past that's not ours or anyone else's, but built upon idealized references from more rich and noble environments.

This is also the genesis of the Portuguese Emigrant House, in which is tried to create an alternative reality through references to a substitute background (mainly France), where there was no poverty as the one left behind in Portugal.

Nevertheless, if the Emigrant's house shares with the today's popular house the will to become part of an Alternative History and an Imaginary Past, it remains an Exception in the landscape, and doesn't overlap the contemporary Popular House as a Rule.

Nowadays, with most of the recent Popular Buildings resorting to an "imaginary historical model", we can assume that in a not too distant future our landscape will be composed of those models made of false memories and delirious imagination.

At that point that house will be recognized as "typical", and even worse, it will be assumed that the model, as presented, was based in a real existing house, the "former Portuguese house". Given the volatility of Popular Architecture, can we trust the surviving models to testify its "real" existence? And even our Short Term Memory, based on those existing Models, can it be trusted to reconstruct a past that left no physical marks?

In the 1960's the survey done in "Arquitectura Popular em Portugal" was justified given the eminence of the physical disappearance of the collected models, which would undoubtedly lead to the disappearance of the Memory of the pre-1960's Popular House Type. Today, thanks to that work, memory is the only thing that remains from those homes, destroyed by time, neglect, but also inadequacy to modern living standards.

There is a place for a new survey, nowadays, since the 1960's Popular House is starting to erode, but mainly because the Type that will replace it consists in an imaginary fantasy that will materialize in our "new past".

6MODEL/TYPE

So far this Typological Study has been done without any specific purpose than knowledge itself. Even if part of a wider investigation (a Bachelor and a Master thesis) the Model survey and corresponding Type definition was linked to mere curiosity (in fact, the driving force behind all knowledge).

This might be considered somehow controversial, considering the most recent studies on the subject. Fernandes (1999) defends that “a Type, in architecture, is the conceptual framework, the matrix behind spatial organization that is present, even with different formal solutions, in a set of cases selected for a specific purpose”².

In the present study we can observe the absence of a specific purpose (beyond knowledge), while extending the meaning of Type to cases (Models) grouped under the same shape. Formal aspects are also capable of organizing outdoor spaces, and its study might be themed under “formal integration phenomena in the surroundings”, without involving the “matrix of spacial organization” of the Model. This definition is especially important if the typological study is unbiased with a precise purpose and intended as source for future applications.

7CONTEMPORARY DWELLING ISSUES

Although we are still living in the Modern Movement aftermath, contemporary architecture has been questioning the dogmas on which modernism was based. Today’s housing, whether in the city or in a more rarefied urban environment, has evolved slowly in its internal spacial organization, mainly because there is a preconception of a typified inhabitant family. Nowadays the family is being considered as part of a wider category, the Domestic Household, which still considers people united by family ties, but ads other actors.

Today we can observe that is common for friends, or even strangers, to share the same flat as a way to meet the expenses of the apartment, or just to have some company, in the absence of the family, alongside with the desire of independence from them. Afonso³ (2004) prefers to refer a nuclear, extended or composed Domestic Household, instead of designating a family. In practice, this ‘new’ type of use needs different domestic spaces from those proposed to the nuclear family (couple plus two children), since there are new requirements of privacy: a bedroom is a more individualized space, since the intimacy among household members is sometimes limited to meals. Even among family members, computers, stereos and televisions on each room have turned outdated the hierarchy between social and private areas in the common house. It’s therefore urgent to create new housing models in order to respond to new types of use.

New proposals have made more versatile the different rooms of a house, with expansion or interconnecting possibilities or even attempts to make space more ‘anonymous’, without assigning spaces with a specific function. The pre-Modern house offered already some of these solutions, shaped like an ‘enfilade’ of rooms with no specific function attached (later connected by a corridor). But we can also find even more suited Types, in rural housing, as in the Type described above.

² Fernandes, Francisco Barata. 1999. “*Transformação e Permanência na Habitação Portuense: as formas da casa na forma da cidade*”. Porto. FAUP Publicações

³ Afonso, Ana Isabel. 2004. “*Grupo Doméstico e Mudança Social: abordagens quantitativas e qualitativas*”. Centro de Estudos de Antropologia Social. ISCTE. Viewed 10.2008. <http://ceas.iscte.pt/etnografica/docs/vol_04/N1/Vol_iv_N1_153-182.pdf>.

Figure 6. Proposed Model, using as a scheme the rural house from the 1960's, 2003

7.1 Heritage as a scheme

In this concept we make a reference to the “*matrix of spacial organization*” referred by Fernandes. From the observed 1960's Rural Type it was possible to conceive a contemporary housing proposal that meets the Domestic Household's different needs.

Even if the proportions of the new scheme don't match the original ones (for obvious area needs), the double symmetry of the floor plan creates a series of identical spaces than can absorb a large number of activities, made easy by the multiple entrances connecting the different rooms. Intentionally the external appearance of the house is not based in the same Rural Type in order to make more obvious its real influence. The intention was never to produce a gratuitous revival, but to answer a question formulated in the context of contemporary dwelling where the previous typological study gave the solution: the ambiguity of areas and spaces.

7.2 Heritage as a scheme and a shape

Aside from the previous referred Domestic Household groups, there is still a type of occupation that can't be inserted in this category: the single dweller. A common phenomenon in the city, where the new adult pursues privacy rather than a new family. The variety of typologies offered by apartments makes easier to find the right one for the single dweller, but the single house suffers from the preconceived idea of a static object for a predetermined nuclear family. Wanting to live alone and wanting a house it's the challenge, and the answer can once more be found in the Rural House.

Figure 7. Proposed Model, using as an example the evolutionary rural house from the 1960's, 2003

Figure 8. House in 'Cruz de Oliveira', Alcobaça, a three-phased evolutionary house, 2005

The “*spatial matrix*” used is now another, and concerns the evolving nature of the rural house, born as a parallelepiped volume (with the above mentioned floor plan) to which were attached more irregular volumes according to the dweller’s needs. The adopted scheme is now the idea of an organic growth of the house (a possibility that the flat can’t offer) where the distinct volumes (with different construction methods) of the popular house are used as a symbol of its phased growth.

The proposal present in Figure 8 was used to respond to a precise commission from a single man who wanted a house. The above evolutionary house was therefore suggested, proposing in a first phase the fundamental elements of ‘life support’: kitchen, living room, bedroom and toilet. The second phase was a dining room (already built) and finally the third were extra bedrooms for a hypothetical family. Although there were no formal references to the traditional house (even if interpreted in a contemporary way, as in Figure 7, a prototype), all the three phases have their own volumes to highlight the evolutionary house concept.

7.3 Heritage as a shape

When talking about shape we are referring to a practical and even emotional factor that searches their solutions in existing references. According to the built and natural surroundings there are questions of scale, proportion and shape that are far from being solved though decorative items like eaves, columns or colored stripes.

If we conceive, in architecture, the integration of the new in the old as succession of scales, where the volume connects with the past, and detail assumes the contemporaneity of the object, then we must refer in our new proposals the growth process of the Popular House.

In the presented examples its modular conception is certainly a reference, but is primarily a mean of designing outdoor spaces endowed with privacy: the former initial parallelepiped module plays the role as a limit between public and private, and the remaining volumes involve organically the outside intimate space. Also the designing of the house as single volume with all the desired area would result in an out scale object, strange to its surroundings.

Figure 9. House in 'Figueiral', 2004, and house in 'Taveiro', 2007, both near Alcobaça,

8CONCLUSION

The use of Architectural Heritage as a decorative element, or a mere formal excuse for assimilation and respect for Historical Contexts, is consequently denied. History isn't epidermal. The use of Heritage/History doesn't have to be obvious, because, as a source, it can influence form, space, even the creative designing process or the appropriation of space. Getting to know our Architectural Heritage is therefore a way to produce real solutions for real problems that, by its quality, might become our future Heritage.

A Typological Study can thus have mere encyclopedic assumptions, as a structure of recollecting and organizing knowledge, besides pursuing a very specific purpose, like a pre-established particular question. In this paper the debate – contemporary domestic life – is conducted in a different context of Architectural Housing History, but it's in its background that we can find solutions for the contemporary dweller that does not have a typical and automated life.

9REFERENCES

- AAVV. 2004. (reprint). *“Arquitectura Popular em Portugal”*. Lisboa. Sindicato Nacional dos Arquitectos.
- Afonso, Ana Isabel. 2004. *“Grupo Doméstico e Mudança Social: abordagens quantitativas e qualitativas”*. Centro de Estudos de Antropologia Social. ISCTE. Viewed 10.2008. <http://ceas.iscte.pt/etnografica/docs/vol_04/N1/Vol_iv_N1_153-182.pdf>.
- Bandeirinha, José António Oliveira. 1996 (2nd edition). *“Quinas Vivas, memória descritiva de alguns episódios significativos do conflito entre fazer moderno e fazer nacional na arquitectura portuguesa dos anos 40”*. Porto. FAUP Publicações.
- Caldas, João Vieira. 1999. *“A Casa Rural dos Arredores de Lisboa no Século XVIII”*. Porto. FAUP Publicações.
- Fernandez, Sérgio. 1945. *“O Problema da Casa Portuguesa”*. Porto. FAUP Publicações.
- Henriques, Alexandra Simões. 2001. *“46 anos depois do Inquérito à Arquitectura Popular em Portugal”*, Final Exam for the obtainance of the Architectural Degree 2000/2001, Thesis advisor: Ach. António Luís Novais de Madureira. Porto. Faculdade de Arquitectura da Universidade do Porto (FAUP)
- Monteys, Xavier & Fuertes, Pere. 2005 (4th edition). *“Casa Collage – un ensayo sobre la arquitectura de la casa”*. Barcelona. Editorial Gustavo Gili.
- Pizza, Antonio. 2008. *“La construcción del pasado, reflexiones sobre história, arte y arquitectura”*. UP-Commons, Portal d'accés obert al coneixement da la Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya. Viewed 10.2008. <<http://upcommons.upc.edu/revistes/bitstream/2099/1932/1/10.pdf>>
- Rosenfeld, Myra Nan. 1989. *“Sesto Seminario Internazionale di Storia dell'Architettura, Vicenza 31 Agosto - 4 Settembre 1987”*. Centre Internazionale di Studi di Architettura “Andrea Palladio”, Vicenza. Milano. Electa
- Távora, Fernando. 1947. *“O Problema da Casa Portuguesa”* in Leal, Manuel João (ed.) *“Cadernos de Arquitectura n.º 1”*. 1947. Lisboa.
- Vidler, Anthony. 1977. *“The Third Typology”*, in Hays, K. Michael (ed.). 1998. *“Architecture Theory since 1968”*. Nova Iorque. Columbia Books of Architecture.
- de Villanova, Roselyne & Leite, Carolina & Raposo, Isabel. 1995. *“Casas de Sonhos, Emigrantes construtores no Norte de Portugal”*. Lisboa. Edições Salamandra.

10FIGURE REFERENCES

Figure 1: PhotoS by G. Schmoll, 2008, viewed 10.2009, used with the author's consent

<<http://www.flickr.com/photos/gschmoll/2195934633/in/photostream/>>

Figures 2 – 9: author's architectural projects, drawings and pictures

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***'The Minimum Cell – minimum housing standards:
Minimum as Maximum'***

(vencedor do 'Best Paper Award', atribuído pela entidade organizadora)

Orlando, Florida, Estados Unidos, Março de 2010

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The Minimum Cell – minimum housing standards: Minimum as Maximum

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Abstract: The present study aims to reflect on the house's minimum living space through its functional and spacial features, throughout architectural models of the so-called 'social housing', where budget restraints and the need to dignify the habitat coexist. Spacial and formal restrains are therefore defined as the main concerns in an architectural research, meaning that 'minimum' thinking does also apply to a daily architectural practice, where there's a need to balance the 'desired' house with the 'possible house'. Therefore, the importance of the present proposal is manifested in an evaluation of Architecture as a comprehensive practice, analyzed in its contemporary context and establishing parameters that will be applied in new housing proposals. The proposed paper therefore tries to define Architecture as a widespread benefit capable to define and apply criteria so it can accomplish its intentions. The main architectural movements will be mentioned through their practical and theoretical ideals who express the principles of spacial definition and its correlation with the individual and the surrounding environment. However, in this article, it will be made a special mention to the Neo-realism movement from the post-World War II period, where the admissible minimum was intended as the maximum possible.

Keywords: Neo-realism, Modernism, Housing.

1. Concept: Minimum as Maximum

In many investigations and research papers held in the past, 'minimum' has been assumed as a synonymous of 'reduction' or 'elementary'. In that order, we might question the relevance of associating 'minimum' to 'maximum' when their meaning is antagonistic. However, words are fragile, especially when they are intended to produce a classification or rating of something.

Classifying and rating is still a recurring practice in architecture and arts in general, where different practices are named the same way when they are similar to each other according to certain characteristics. It does turn easier the induction of knowledge and assimilation of its characteristics, but it depends on the 'features' defined in order to determine a Style or a Movement. Or, better even, a 'Type'. Categorizing a practice or a theory is equivalent to present a Typological Study, where a number of constants are listed to classify Models in order to define a Type.

Therefore, if we define 'form' or 'space' as the criteria used in a future study / classification, we will obtain different Models, even if we want to define a same meaning: sometimes we witness a clash of opinions when, for example, it is tried to determine the very first signs of

Modernism based only by a depuration of architectural shapes, even when these shapes are still ruled by neo-classical criteria.

1.1 Definition

In the present investigation, 'Minimum' is translated as '*the minimum amount of habitable space needed to implement all functional and social movements of their occupants*'. Admittedly, this may be an evasive definition, in the sense that 'minimum volume' suggests 'a' smaller volume, but never 'the' smallest volume. That is, once defined the functional and social needs of the inhabitants, depending on the used criteria, it can be defined that an acceptable minimum volume is simply the maximum possible, according to the available resources (which in most cases are defined by financial criteria; nevertheless those criteria can also have technical or political restrictions).

1.1.1 Consequence or Ideology

There are many contexts in which we can point out the willingness of providing the 'maximum' possible given the limited resources available. This is more common when the factors that will determine the development of theories and practices used to define 'various minimums' consist precisely in situations where immediate answers are demanded. In these cases, a search for the maximum volume, needed for the inhabitants' dignity, health or socialization, is usually expressed by a practical program, and not by a precise ideological substrate, which primary objective is area or volume 'per se'.

Fig. 1: **Streatham Building** (1848), Henry Roberts

Henry Roberts (1803-1876), considered the 'father of the English Collective Housing'¹ (a paternity as arbitrary as those usually set to define movements or styles) reacts to the unworthy conditions in which factory workers survived after their exodus from the country to the cities. In spite of this very well known consequence of the Industrial Revolution, a series of philanthropic processes aimed at those in need began. Given the total absence of infrastructures of all kinds, Roberts drew the 'Streatham Building', in 1848 that had been preceded by a prototype four years before. Despite the small areas of the cells, these consisted in the 'acceptable minimum' because they were also the 'possible maximum' (even taking into account that, as a political activist, he made possible a taxes reduction on

¹ http://www.ukbookworld.com/cgi-bin/search.pl?s_i_DLR_ID=stern&s_i_keywords=poverty&pg=1
[04.2008]

construction materials that decreased building costs, paving the way for more affordable housing). In this context, the compromise reached between area and commodities did not translate into a choice, but as the only available option.

1.1.2 Ideology or Consequence

Always having as a background the pressing need to provide housing, the most common attitude, when defining the 'minimum' criteria, has always been the providing of standards that define a level from which the house should be endowed with the qualities of dignity, health, sociability and the ability to promote human development, rather than repress it. Of all the different 'minimum' ideologies, in every each of them there is almost always an underlying idea of a 'prototype' that aims to respond to a multitude of different situations according to a predetermined solution. The investigation process is thus somehow abstract, avoiding specific limits at various levels. The budget is one of them, not in the sense that there is no limit of costs and spendings, but because this limit is unknown (perhaps variable) and therefore worked in a hypothetical minimum value: pre-fabrication, modularity, replication, minimal areas ... Another factor missing in this particular attitude can be seen in the real dweller or inhabitant, also idealized as an abstract entity, who will have a very hard time trying to identify himself with a standard house.

This short introduction to such a complex subject illustrates that making use of an aphorism like 'minimum as maximum' actually corresponds to a change of the paradigm underlying the practical result.

2. Provenances

An opposite theory to the 'minimum standards' could only be developed beyond an environment of pressure that requires urgent planning, solutions and action. In these circumstances, the need of typifying is crucial, because many problems require simultaneous responses, as a prompt answer to immediate disasters (war, natural phenomena) or cumulative ones (as it happened in England's Industrial Revolution).

2.1 Context

That is why the basis of a less rigid system was a society that was immune to the hardships of war, uncontrolled industrial growth, or even an obvious differentiation among classes and their income, which required immediate large-scale solutions. The Northern European Countries offered a less analytical architectural approach, known as the New Nordic Empiricism, which focused its attention on local characteristics of topography, landscape and climate in order to provide a sense of belonging to architecture. This was a calm and consecutive process, enlarged by the fact that countries such as Sweden were spared from the destruction of the Second World War.

2.1.1 A sense of belonging

This attitude began with a change of perception in the conception of Man, who was therefore considered an entity formed not only by his biological needs, but also shaped by specific regional characteristics, which defined his physical and mental growth. The humanity was now gifted with a strong cultural and physical background, defined by real and daily needs, and not designed by an architecture capable of changing the world. Therefore, now Man belongs to a particular place (being 'place' a definition far from political borders or nationalistic expressions). As such, in order for Man to recognize himself within his own surroundings, the characteristics that produce the sense of belonging must be searched in his own environment:

Shape: the building, being the result of a specific location, and not of an abstract situation, assumes its characteristics: the contours of the site are reflected on its sinuous shapes, the surrounding landscape acts as an extension of domesticity (more important than mere solar orientation), or simply gains movement and diversity in the features of the building in order to combat 'modern' or 'international' monotony.

Fig. 2: Rostamrådet, 1950

Fig. 3: Stjärnhusen, 1953 – 1955

Sven Backström (1903-1992) and Leif Reinius (1907-1995)

It was, probably, not only by chance that the paternity of the 'Y' building was given to Sven Backström (1903-1992) and Leif Reinius (1907-1995), in which the central access serves three apartments per floor. The intention was to take the maximum advantage of the stairs (elevators were absent in most cases, given the usual small scale of the buildings) without sacrificing ventilation and lighting through the façade (which happens in most of the buildings served by an inside gallery/corridor) or the privacy of the internal spaces of the house (where some internal spaces lead to outside galleries). We mustn't forget the Nordics' more liberal concept of privacy, even in the city (where galleries and large windows are common use). In this new context, very close to nature (which is intended to be the 'entrance' of the living cell), a corridor next to the windows of the house wouldn't be logical.

Scale: always having the human figure as a reference, opposed to the 'Modern' Universal Man, the new neo-empirical urban schemes recover a scale inherited from the English Garden Cities. Despite the critical point of view of more conventional 'modernists', who

define this attitude as 'neo-romantic', such judgment was based on a direct comparison with purely 'Modern' models from the period between wars (we can mention as an example the 'Bergpolder' building, 1934²). Nevertheless, the single house, typical of the English Garden City, was not the exclusive type of housing cell of the Neo-empiricism, being the collective housing the main type in use.

Fig. 4: 'Bergpolder' building, Rotterdam, Netherlands, 1934

Willem van Tijen (1894 – 1974), **Johannes Andreas Brinkman** (1902 – 1949)
and **Leendert van der Vlugt** (1894 – 1936)

In Sweden a new Type of building where the advantages of multiple solar orientation and building height are combined, creates a unique low-rise building usually called 'punkthus'³ or 'point-blocks'. The very often reproduced solution eventually manifested itself as a compromise, because there were only two apartments per floor (each one with three facades) that would only be profitable if the access was made only by stairs, limiting the height of the block to four floors. Beyond those, it would be required the use of an (expensive) elevator which in turn would dictate the existence of more apartments per floor, destroying the original intention of maximum sun exposure. Eventually this type would degenerate into very high towers, especially in the Anglo-Saxon countries, were the translation of 'punkthus' became 'vertical slums'...

Matter: the visual identification of the building was part of the ideology behind the neo-empiricism, in which the use of local building materials became part of the vocabulary used by the architects of this generation. It should be noted once again the fragility of the definitions of 'generation', 'movement' or 'style': the main character in the use and exploitation of traditional materials was the Nordic Alvar Aalto (1898-1976), whose categorization varies from 'second generation modernist'⁴ to 'organicism'⁵ (such as Frank

² **Willem van Tijen** (1894 – 1974), **Johannes Andreas Brinkman** (1902 – 1949) e **Leendert van der Vlugt** (1894 – 1936)

³ **Schoenauer, Norbert** – '6,000 Years of Housing, revised and expanded edition', W. W. Norton & Company, New York, NY 10110, 2000
ISBN 0-393-73052-2

⁴ **Montaner, Josep Maria** – "Depois do Movimento Moderno: Arquitectura da segunda metade do séc. XX" – Editorial Gustavo Gili, Barcelona, 2001
ISBN 84-252-1828-4

Lloyd Wright ?...). However, in a more conventional range, the practical character of the common building materials also influenced the choice of brick, wood or even a sloped roof, because the use of local resources would lead to greater cost-efficiency, when combined with prefabricated elements. Also, the assumption that the local climate must determine the choice of materials and shapes (such as a sloped roof in a harsh climate) lead them to different possible shapes and a sort of rustic image, that contributed to the classification of neo-empiricism as being humble, but also as a petty-bourgeois fantasy.

Fig. 5: 'Forshagagatan', Farsta , Sweden, 1959

Nils Lonnroth (...-...)

2.1.2 Spacial Affinity

We can consider the 'petty bourgeois' classification as unfair, because Modernism remained present on these proposals through space and organizational solutions that were still valid. This kind of statement, based on epidermal features, can be considered superficial, because Walter Gropius (1883-1959) had always insisted in Modernism as a method and not as a style. The truth is that neo-empiricism tried to reduce the abstract idealization of the Modern Imaginary Man, mixing it with local lifestyle traditions⁶. That didn't prevent the 'neo-rationalist cell' to maintain its Rationalist organization and functional features. Nothing in the (many) studied models indicates the presence of the old bourgeois ways of life, guided by the ritualization of common functions, or the presence of servants, for example. One of the key criticisms about the first modern models consisted in, precisely, the maintenance of certain practices, associated with the more privileged classes, that would have no place in modern life, even less in needy families, like access to servants. Even if those buildings, Modern in shape and appearance, suggested rational and functionalist features.

⁵ Frampton, Keneth – '*Historia critica de la arquitectura moderna*' - Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A. 08029 Barcelona, 1996
ISBN 84-252-1628-1

⁶ Portas, Nuno - '*Pioneiros de uma Renovação (3)*', in "*História e Crítica, Ensino e Profissão*", Série 2 – Argumentos, volume 23, Porto 2005, FAUP Publicações, Faculdade de Arquitectura da Universidade do Porto
ISBN: 972 9483 72 8

For example, André Lurçat (1894-1970), a modern architect par excellence, presented at the 1932 Vienna's Werkbund Exhibition a series of townhouses with a modern language and organization scheme: the contained areas included closets where beds could be hidden, allowing the use of the same space as a day or night area. Nevertheless, he still 'offered' a room for a housemaid, arguing that this space could have a different use. And by doing so he was criticized by Roger Sherwood⁷, who considered that 'ancient habits' were unacceptable in a Modern construction.

The above floor plans correspond to the scheme used during the day, where beds are closed in cabinets. The lower floor plans show how spaces adapt do nighttime use, with the beds outside the cabinets. The pink areas correspond to the maid's bedroom

Fig. 6: 'Row Houses', Vienna, Austria, 1931-1932
André Lurçat (1894-1970)

The Nordic post-World War II examples didn't try to offer rooms for servants, or bedrooms big enough to make sleeping a daily ritual (its use was purely functional, with the necessary area to be so). Likewise, it reflected a new family organization, formerly rural, now factory workers, where women are also providers and don't make use of kitchens for poultry or farming products. Without being a 'Modern Laboratory', they are contained spaces, attached to dining areas devoid of a pompous or bourgeois character. Without being a rural hut, it is not a reduced Parisian Hotel.

Site specificity: So, again referring Nuno Portas, it is a crossing between Modern proposals and direct assessments of the user's real needs. Therefore, by maintaining the characteristics described above, these are validated as relevant and related to actual uses, not just supposed ones, proving that Modernism was able to meet certain expectations of a mutating society. However, there's no place for a use of an uncritically modern archetype: beyond the 'real' requirements of the user, it's introduced the notion of the existence of a 'real' user. The introduction of new disciplines in the architectural debate, such as psychology or sociology, lead to an idealization of an architecture less capable to change

⁷ Sherwood, Roger – 'Modern Housing Prototypes', 7th edition, 2001, Harvard University Press, Cambridge and London, England
ISBN: 0-674-57942-9

society (through the anticipation of a New Individual), but able to better respond to the existing community. And as such, the ‘discovery’ of actual practical and mental needs introduced a ‘regional component’ in the Modern housing prototype.

‘Voldparken’, Husum (Denmark), 1951
Kay Fisker (1893-1965)

‘Forshagagatan’, Farsta (Sweden), 1959
Nils Lonnroth (...-...)

‘Puotila’, Helsinki (Finland) 1960
Markus Tavio (1911-1978)

‘Nyem’, Finspång (Sweden), 1970
Bertil Engstrand (1922-...) e **Hans Speek** (1920-...)

Fig. 7

Given the context in which we belong, in Southern Europe, it was always felt that people further north had a less rigid notion of the concept of 'private', including in this category less activities that we would in Portugal or Italy. There's a lack of a clear differentiation between a house's public and private spaces, not in a way that functions are shared in the same area, but in the sense of a lack of a limit to separate activities (physical or otherwise). This can be sensed not only by the occupants but also by those unrelated to the household. Thus, it is common practice to locate rooms near the entrance of the cell. Although not exposing the inside activities, it does facilitate the perception of those by strangers in the lobby, and exposes the trips to the bathroom, for example. This proves the preference for the ‘public’ space of the house, and the relations established between family, household and guests. One of the reasons may be the harsher climate, which prevents outside neighbor relations (unlike the south of Europe). Inside it is used a more direct (and open) relation of common spaces with the kitchen (still small, in area), and it is given to living and dining spaces the maximal area possible: while in 1958 Portugal used an area of 12 to 13m² for the house's living spaces⁸, Sweden was already making use of a minimum of 20m². The worn-out argument that northern countries have a greater economic power which allows them, even in subsidized housing, to have more resources, doesn't entirely explain this fact. Nor the

⁸*‘multiple activities: meetings around the dining table, for meals or not; reception, rest, chat, recreation, certain hobbies’*, **Portas, Nuno** – *‘A Habitação Social: proposta para a metodologia da sua arquitectura’*, Edições FAUP, 1st edition, 2004
ISBN 972-9483-63-9

argument of private spared area spent in living rooms. In reality what happens is a careful management of resources, which in this case is shown by savings made in the equipment of the house⁹.

Although referred by Nuno Portas, one can point the lack of built-in furniture in many models, as opposed to those in André Lurçat's housing scheme, that was functional only at the expense of dynamic (and expensive) furniture. We can mention the 'Unité d'Habitation de Marseille' (1945), for example, who didn't have a refrigerator (only an ice box where blocks of ice were dropped trough the gallery) in order to achieve a comfortable floor area of 92m² in a three-bedroom apartment.

As noted above in '1.1.2: Ideology or consequence ', this was perhaps the first reasoning about the change of paradigm in architectural theory: facing concrete situations leading to the idealization of different possible 'maximums' (as opposed to an effort based only in the lowest possible value, is response to questions that didn't existed). The real change is established in the definition of the status of 'real': a real situation, a real Man with real needs, whose response admits experiments and different answers, since they were no longer handling with (abstract) constants.

3. Sequels: the Italian neo-realism

Italy follows with interest the experiences developed in Northern Europe, which, as we have seen, progressed in very favorable circumstances, given the destruction felt in countries more affected by war. Although Italy was one of the main actors in the conflict, it still could meet a number of factors that made them capable of using the Nordic neo-empiricism as a reference. In fact, only 5% of its housing dwellings were destroyed in the conflict. So, the emergency situation that leads to the standardization, repetition and fast building did not occur.

3.1 Scope

The (relative) lack of urgency, however, was the only resemblance that might have existed. Italy is one of the conflict's defeated countries, and all its political structures had fallen as a result. With them, all its manifestations of power were equally destroyed, especially in architecture, where the fascist regime had chosen Neo-classicism for its brand image, as an allusion to past (and successful) civilizations, including Italy's own Roman ancestors. Ancient Rome easily alluded to world and cultural domination that Italian Fascists wanted to reach through their participation in World War II. Modernism was therefore previously epressed by the regime (consequently having a reduced visibility), and by the end of the war all the Italian masters of Modern Architecture 'were dead'¹⁰, creating a formal and

⁹ Idem

¹⁰ **Benevolo, Leonardo** – *'História da Arquitectura Moderna'*, 2004, 3rd edition – second reprint, Editora Perspectiva S. A.

ideological vacuum that forces the country to look around for new references for post-war architecture.

The existence of any 'Italian Modernism Masters' could be another parallel discussion, since, in general, the Italians always steered clear from extremists who wanted to delete any reference of the past. The 'Group 7', appeared in 1926, defended a correlation between form and function, however with a classical substrate: Giuseppe Terragni (1904-1943) created on the 1932's 'Casa del Fascio', in Como, a set of geometric relations (quadrangular plan, with a building height equal to half the measure of the square) that alluded to Classical Rationalism. It was also based on the urban Italian palace's Type, organized around a central

Photo mount, by Marcello Nizzoli, 1936

Fig. 8: 'Casa del Fascio', Como (Itália), 1932-1937

Giuseppe Terragni (1904-1943)

courtyard. Despite the formal purity, some monumental and tectonic expressions remained, who led to the existence of an Italian Rationalism, instead of an Italian Modernism.

Modernism arrived after the establishment of the Fascist Regime, so there was no relation between its imagery (adopted by Rationalism) and the previous democratic regime. Thus, before the adoption of an unambiguous historicist language, repression over Rationalism was tenuous, even allowing the construction of some 'Casas del Fascio' ('Houses of Fascism') according to their principles. Terragni is the most visible example, but Luigi Carlo Daneri (1900-1972) also created a similar programmatic building in Sturla, in 1936, near Genoa. Adding to the authorities Rationalism's rejection, intellectuals were also disappointed by the fascist political agenda, in practice very different from the popular unity proposed in theory.

Fig. 9: 'Casa del Fascio', Genoa, Italy, 1936 – 1938

Luigi Carlo Daneri, (1900-1972)

The search for new references in architecture achieved two different perspectives: in a first phase an approach is made around the 'Real or Common Man', simultaneously forgotten by Modernism and Fascism. Despite the unaffected housing, the populations' ethical, moral and pride disintegration remains unsolved, which lead to a rapprochement to the underprivileged residents and its forms of expression. After identifying the different problems and goals, an intervention method is searched in order to respond to the aroused questions. Implemented or in progress examples are investigated, like the Nordic New-empiricism, that stands out for its humbleness but mainly for its search for a national identity. Italy didn't have political stability and social equality or even the means available in Northern Europe, but had a blank sheet at all levels that served the same purpose.

3.1.1 'Existent' reality 'versus' intended reality

The fascist aesthetics, like any totalitarian regime, had relied on an idyllic vision of society based in rather optimistic ethical and moral assumptions. The classical architecture references were, as seen above, synonymous to an imperial past, also intended to be an imperial future. With the regime's fall a process takes place that demystifies that (intended) reality, and its maximum expression takes shape in Italian Cinema (from which became common the term 'Neo-realism').

Fig. 10: Image taken from the film '**Roma: città aperta**', 1945

Directed by **Roberto Rossellini** (1906-1977)

Far from the romanticized epic movies from the fascist regime, it is now tried to make cinema the symbol of a new aesthetics linked to a new left-wing political ideology. Neo-realistic cinema desires to get closer to what they believe to be the people's reality, filming in slums, fisherman's villages and turbulent city centers. The idea is to show a working class, deceived in their rights and always frustrated in their attempts to achieve a better life, almost in a documentary way where bare facts are shown. This was intended to be an exposure of the problems urged to be solved, and not an ideological withdrawal from an attempt to improve people's conditions.

Neo-realism, manifested also through writing and painting, acts as a social reminder that intends to create an optimistic reaction from the population. Architecture responds to the

challenge, creating housing solutions for the less privileged, inspired in their aesthetics and spatial solutions.

3.2 Process

The intervention method adopted by the Italians manifested itself, among other programs, in the INA-Casa, who was financed through a withheld contribution from the worker's payments. The obtained financial resources were therefore managed by a central institute, who would promote the construction of social housing all over the country. Architects affiliated with the Neo-realism were the main designers, but also those indirectly associated with the movement (whose unique affiliation was the participation on the process): Luigi Carlo Daneri wanted to keep some distance from the neo-realistic figures, but he recurred to the topography and landscape of the sites when designing his projects, like in the experiments made by neo-empiricism and applied in Italy. In order to solve the city (and rural) housing problem, there were two different approaches that stood out, not only by their practical results, but also by the contrast made with Modern method and imagery.

3.2.1 Definition of Reality

The intended proximity to Real People, already visible in cinema, led to a designing process held close to those, listening to their ambitions and aspirations, but also paying attention to the lifestyle held inside the house. This was the first 'cut' to be made with Modernism, already announced by northern experiments, where the main goal of the project is the Contemporary Man, with real and verifiable practical needs, and not a persona to be

Fig. 11

developed in a near future. In other words, one works with facts and not based in assumptions.

Inquiry: in order to determine ‘that’ Real Man, and his lifestyle, part of the research was made according to the data obtained through surveys conducted among the population. This process allowed identifying a number of factors ignored by the idealized conception of Modern Life, but also helped, as had happened in Northern Europe, to validate part of its inheritance. Despite the attention devoted to elements like topography, climate or building materials, related to a specific site, the models present in the current investigation still managed to bring up some similar details, in their spatial organization, regardless of the shape of the building or its aesthetic choice. Nuno Portas refers that, in the surveys conducted under the INA-Casa program, 25% of the respondents wanted a dining area in the kitchen, and this one served by a balcony. And the fact is that the kitchen’s balcony is almost present in all of the analyzed Italian models. It can be interpreted like a response to a local requirement, but also the result of the designer’s attention to the applicants’ needs. It’s also noticed more reluctance in offering the dining area in the kitchen (that would make the living room the only ‘living’ space). More interesting is that we are able to see in the proposals with a kitchen/dining area the architect’s clear affiliation to the Neo-realism, and in those who don’t precisely the opposite: Carlo Perogalli (1921 - ...) was clearly opposed to this ‘movement’ because he considered it politicized, and in Comasina Nord (sponsored by the GPA in Milan, in 1957), the kitchen is reduced to a small counter contained in 3,2m² (without a balcony...). Also, the dining space is contained in the living room (refused by 90% of the respondents). Federico Gorio (... - ...), an assumed neo-realistic, offers a kitchen with nearly 11m², in Tiburtino Est, where it can be easily placed a dining table or performed a series of house chores (the balcony as a ‘working’ place, for laundry, also contributes to its practical characteristics). There are also some ‘compromise’ solutions where the dining area, is kept safe from prying eyes but close to the kitchen, even if included in the living room.

Such kind of spatial organization, as Nuno Portas refers¹¹, reproduces a traditional way of life, where the kitchen was used as a more private living area, opposed to the living room, a mere reception and representation area before the appearance of television. So, there was no place in the Italian neo-realistic house for the laboratory type kitchens made famous by Margarete (Grete) Schuttle-Lihotzky’s Frankfurt Kitchen, exponent of a Modern Lifestyle.

A similar solution can be found in the southern countries of Europe, where even in Portugal the kitchen is commonly felt as a living space for the domestic household. We can mention, for example, the João Paulo Pena Lopes’ 2001 ‘Instituto Nacional de Habitação’ (National Housing Institute) award winning project, in Meda, where in a still recent housing building the architect introduces this ‘ancestral’ way of living: ‘a large and friendly kitchen, where the dining table could be in the middle, and where family reunion where possible with the comfort of a fireplace’¹². Therefore the kitchen centralizes the household’s main activities, instead of the living room where the fireplace is absent.

¹¹ Idem

¹² **Coelho, António Baptista; Coelho, Pedro Baptista** – *‘Habitação de Interesse Social em Portugal, 1988-2005’*, 2009, Livros Horizonte, pág. 189

Fig. 12: 'Housing in Meda', Portugal, 2001

João Paulo Pena Lopes (...-...)

One of the main presences in the Neo-realist projects is a clear distinction between night and day areas, where bedrooms and the bathroom have a very well define limit, as seen in the floor plans. Entrance is always made trough day areas, or daily household spaces, and bedrooms are located at the end of the internal course, often protected by a private hall. And this, regardless of the architect's 'artistic orientation'.

Fig. 13

How should we interpret this? It's true that functional separation was one of the main concerns of Modernist authors, because it corresponded to the attribution of a specific function to a specific space of the house. On the other side, the Italian bedrooms have very comfortable areas, with numbers that even today are rare in current buildings: rooms could have up to 20m² (even if it this value is proportional to the total area of the neo-realistic house, also very spacious). These spaces are clearly destined to more than just sleeping, since they can accommodate more than one bed, but also desks, tables or sofas, where a series of activities can be performed. In other circumstances (countries, cultures) those could be carried out in the household's common spaces: study, work, various interpersonal

relations. The appreciation of privacy remains a southern characteristic¹³, very obvious if we compare it to Nordic housing cells, where an increase of the living room areas does not necessary mean bigger bedrooms. However, we can't forget that the main Modernist theories were elaborated in Germany, a country that we easily define as more northern than southern.

Another small signs allow us to characterize the post-world war Italian housing plans, which became common even after this period: the 'social' balcony in the living room, or a small den which help to define this house as a very practical one. All of this in an area than even today is uncommon in some unsubsidized buildings, like 103m³ for a two-bedroom house (Tiburtino Est, 1952), but that was made possible in a country recovering from a war that was lost also by the Italians.

Giancarlo de Carlo (1919-2005): it must be made a special mention to this architect, who worked in close communion with the future dwellers. This was a Neo-realism common characteristic, but De Carlo took it further, making participatory this kind of relation: '(...) participation is a political process, but also the construction of a truthful aesthetics (...) the rediscovery of peoples' real taste (...)'¹⁴. He admitted to be a complex and tiring process, demanding 'youth'¹⁵. That didn't stop him to put it into practice in the Matteotti workers' neighborhood (1969-1974), in Terni, when he was already 50 years old.

Fig. 14: 'Matteotti neighborhood', Terni, Italy, 1969-1974

Giancarlo de Carlo (1919-2005)

3.2.2 Building reality

The search for a 'truthful aesthetics' was simultaneously a goal and a consequence of the neo-realistic methodology. If the 'Real Man' approach leads to an investigation concerning its practical needs and aspirations, it also considers their aesthetic sensibilities, since architecture was intended to be a reflection of those to whom it was addressed. But, before being a goal, it was a consequence: the truth that was sought in the nature of the project was

¹³ Idem

¹⁴ **Giancarlo De Carlo**, interviewed by **Piza, João** in: '*A experiência participativa de Giancarlo De Carlo*' <http://www.arquitextos.com.br/entrevista/decarlo/decarlo.asp> [08.2009]

¹⁵ Idem

initially understood as a constructive expression of the building, build according to local constructive methods. That didn't mean (yet) a nostalgic process where vernacular materials and language were intended like a return to an idyllic past lifestyle. It was a practical decision that made the project feasible since they were using less expensive local materials and resources, as they were abundant and close to the construction site. Also, the use of local labor force, very experienced in the use of common materials and techniques, didn't imply training or recurring to workers from across Italy, specialized, for example, in the use of new prefabricated or modular materials. Federico Gorio (...-...), self defined as a 'neo-empiricist'¹⁶, became renowned for the care dedicated to the design of constructive details, with the purpose of making the construction process feasible.

Fig. 15: 'Tiburtino Est', Rome, Italy, 1952

Federico Gorio (...-...)

Compendiums: but, if it was defended the use of local technique, it could be also defended that a local building, built with local resources by a local labor force would also require a... local architect. For that reason those techniques and resources were made available to architects who wanted to learn from them. According to this logic, knowledge about popular Italian construction methods was collected in books, becoming reference guides as useful as those who collected measurements, standards, etc (like Ernst Neufert, for example). Mário Ridolfi (1904-1984) was responsible for one of the best known compendiums, 'Manuale dell'Architetto' (1945-1946), an official commission from the responsible authorities, who gave it the political support necessary to its divulgation.

The analysis of this logic allow us to verify that this was a subversion of Modernist thinking, that consisted precisely in the maximization of the standardization in minimum housing, so that these building resources would be less and less expensive. Like in a Ford T model, that became cheaper as years went by. If we believe in Modernism as a method and not a style,

¹⁶ Federico Gorio's comentary in: Cagliostro, Rosa Maria; Libro, Antonino; Domenichini, Carla – "Federico Gorio, Esperienze, Ricerche, Progetti"
http://www.delucaeditori.com/scheda_volume.php?id=17
[07.2008]

as Gropius defended it, there was no reason why popular aesthetics should not be used. Nevertheless, for that dogma to become true, there were two necessary things: a national industrial infra-structure that supported the construction of modular and prefabricated elements... and its intensive use, in order to make profit from all the investment made in its investigation, planning and execution. Italy wasn't one of the more active countries during the Industrial Revolution; Modernism had been interrupted by the fascists, and its imagery was wrongly associated with the totalitarian regime. So, instead of choosing a medium-to-long term process (necessary to implement the necessary infrastructures), it was chosen the immediate construction of the much needed workers' housing, with cost reduction as consequent benefit.

Fig. 16: 'Manuale dell'Architetto' (1945-46)

Mario Ridolfi (1904-1984)

Matter vs. form vs. formalism: the use of common materials and their handling in a conventional (and more accessible) way, lead to a plastic expression very different from the image obtained through Modernist methods. Textures, colors, even unusual shapes would be used in consequence, rather than by a clear will to make popular references. However, from the late 40's onwards, formal investigation is intensified, in order to make 'erudite' architecture (made by school trained technicians, that is) closer to popular taste. Therefore, the interest devoted to the construction method was replaced by a search for the aesthetics resulting from that same process¹⁷. This period was defined by Leonardo Benevolo as post-neo-realism, but not in a negative way. He even praises the obtained result, as new buildings were very well integrated in historic contexts, although, in general, Italian urban thinking did not considered the city in a general fashion, but bit by bit (or building by building).

Others would criticize this process, like Bruno Reichlin, who said that Federico Gorio acquired some signs of a 'lesser roman baroque' and 'other vernacular temptations'¹⁸ in the Tiburtino Est district (1952), absent in previous projects, like in Viale Etiopia, Rome (1948).

¹⁷ **Benevolo, Leonardo** – '*História da Arquitectura Moderna*', 2004, 3rd edition – second reprint, Editora Perspectiva S. A., pág. 664

¹⁸ **Reichlin, Bruno**, "*Figures of Neorealism in Italian Architecture (part 2)*", 'Grey Room 6, Winter 2002, pp 110-133, <http://mc1litvip.jstor.org/pss/1262617> [07.2008]

A clear revival was assumed within the ‘neo-liberty’ movement (a term used the first time by Paolo Portoghesi in 1958), a posterior architectural theory that would not last in time.

Fig. 17: ‘Towers in Viale Etiopia’, Rome, 1948

Fig. 18: ‘Tiburtino Est’, Rome, 1952

Federico Gorio (...-...)

In this context, Reyner Banham (1922-1988) states the definitive withdrawal of Italian architects from Modernism¹⁹, especially when he considers that Modern architecture had always been ‘insipid’ in Italy: promoted only by private projects where the architect could work in total freedom. When commissioned by the regime the result was shallow, restrained and reduced to its mere image, like Terragni’s ‘Casa Del Fascio’ (according to Banham, who considered Terragni’s work Modernist, unlike the author, who saw himself like a Historicist Rationalist, apart from the Modern Movement). He recognizes merit in an architecture that recovers traditional domestic lifestyles (admitting a necessary revision of Modernism), but considers superfluous explicit references to a bourgeois architecture that no longer made sense in those days, much less to bridge the gaps that Modernism didn’t fulfill.

4. Conclusion

Polemics aside, the Italian experience manages to obtain tangible results through the joint effort of listening to people’s wishes and researching traditional building methods. Nuno Portas defends that, for the first time, there was achieved a concept that was not exclusively focused on the notion of a minimum housing, but also on the notion of a ‘popular’ housing: the single cost criteria is therefore replaced by the social aspects of the house²⁰. The inquiries made within the population lead to conclude that the envisioned Modern lifestyle,

¹⁹ **Banham, Reyner** – ‘Neoliberty: the italian retreat from modern architecture, in *The Architectural Review*, n.° 747, vol. 125, April 1959

http://ltha.epfl.ch/enseignement_lth/documents/b_marchand/polycopies/rapp_histoire_v1.pdf
[08.2009]

²⁰ **Portas, Nuno** – ‘*A Habitação Social: proposta para a metodologia da sua arquitectura*’, Edições FAUP, 1st edition, 2004

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clinical and functional, was not valid in every corners of the world, because locally people's functional specifications still determines the organization of the house. The 'traditional domestic values' that Banham used to refer (kitchen/dining room as common areas, bedrooms as private spaces and living room as public) can be analyzed according to a more scientific (and cynical) perspective: the living room is actually a space for visitors, closed to daily uses, corresponding to the rural or working family's bourgeois lifestyle aspirations: the utilitarian character of the vernacular and popular houses and the scarcity of resources didn't allow the existence of representation areas. We can therefore suggest that the more simple way of live as it was foresaw by the Modernists (perhaps associated with a less 'southern' lifestyle) was an unfounded aspiration, but so was the bourgeois refinement desired by the populations.

Fig. 19

Another requirement revealed by the conducted surveys (and, in fact, by any tenant) was the need for more space or area. Here is manifested the social criteria Nuno Portas mentioned, substituting the single economical criteria, while maintaining the same budget. In fact, what happened was that the budget was applied differently, in order to promote area augmentation, rather than technical experimentations or avant-garde aesthetics. The use of local resources was one of the solutions founded; another was the 'striping' of almost all interior finishing and equipments, in a rather radical way²¹. We can observe that in the referred case-studies there are few examples with built-in cupboards (substituted probably by the storage rooms, mere spaces closed by a door with no special finishes) or with a complete, ready to use, kitchen (unlike the Frankfurt-kitchen). However, the lack of finishing cannot be assume as a lack of building quality, but a solution as seen in the Nemausus building (Nimes, 1985-1988) by Jean Nouvel (1945 - ...), where apartments was delivered to their tenants without coating on the walls, which was reflected, obviously, in the final cost. More than in this more recent example, in the 1950's Italy the use of self-construction to complete the living cell would be a realistic possibility.

²¹ Idem

In the right photo it's pictured the kitchen as it was after the conclusion of the building, where only the plumbing are installed. All the finishes were the owner's responsibility

Fig. 20: '**Nemausus**' building, Nîmes, France, 1987-1994

Jean Nouvel (1945-...)

And this is why, according to these criteria, it was possible to build houses with areas that even today seem impossible in social housing, like 20m² bedrooms, 30m² living rooms or total areas of 120m² for a two-bedroom apartment, a result only achieved through the concept of 'a minimum as a maximum'. But to what extent can we say that this was due to the evolution of a previous concept and not to a total breakage with Modernism? If we understand this 'movement' as a method rather than a 'shape', it was not with Nordic-empiricism that a complete collapse with functional and spacial principles of the Modern Movement was achieved: the traditional colors, textures and shapes were introduced in building procedures that were still industrialized. And in spatial terms we can still observe a 'faded' functionalism where each room has a specific use: a kitchen to cook, a bedroom to sleep, a living room for the remaining activities: areas are still defined through the area they needed and not by the amount of space they could have. Italy pays attention to this phenomenon, and, although influenced by it, creates something different, according to its different prior political and social history. The exclusive use of 'common' building techniques (rather than 'traditional' techniques), and the recovery of the traditional domestic habits, in clear contradiction with Functionalist assumptions (where the separation between day and night areas is more a traditional domesticity feature than a Modern intent), are a few examples. And all of this with a more extensive formal vocabulary and a better integration in the surrounding environment, affiliated with the Nordic-empiricism, but whose similarities end there. It's through a spatial analysis that we can argue the Italians' Modernism abandonment, prior to Federico Gorio's 'vernacular temptations'. Although we cannot define the superiority of a 'method' over the other, it is possible to justify the legitimacy of the doubt about the existence of one single valid method.

References:

Ábalos, Iñaki – ‘*A boa-vida, visita guiada às casas da modernidade*’, 2008, 1st edition, second reprint, Editorial Gustavo Gili, SL, Barcelona.
ISBN: 978-84-252-1931-3

Aymonino, Carlo – “*La Vivienda Racional: ponencias de los congresos CIAM 1929-1930*” – 1973, Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A. 08029 Barcelona
ISBN 84-252-0755-X

Banham, Reyner – ‘*Neoliberty: the italian retreat from modern architecture*, in *The Architectural Review*, n.º 747, vol. 125, April 1959
http://ltha.epfl.ch/enseignement_lth/documents/b_marchand/polycopies/rapp_histoire_v1.pdf [08.2009]

Benevolo, Leonardo – ‘*História da Arquitectura Moderna*’, 2004, 3rd edition – second reprint, Editora Perspectiva S. A.

Frampton, Keneth – ‘*Historia critica de la arquitectura moderna*’ – 1996, Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A. 08029 Barcelona
ISBN 84-252-1628-1

French, Hilary - ‘*Key Urban Housing of the Twentieth Century*’, 2008 Laurence King Publishing Ltd
ISBN-13: 978 1 85669 564 0

Montaner, Josep Maria – “*Depois do Movimento Moderno: Arquitectura da segunda metade do séc. XX*” – Editorial Gustavo Gili, Barcelona, 2001
ISBN 84-252-1828-4

Monteys, Xavier; Fuertes, Pere – “*Casa Collage – un ensayo sobre la arquitectura de la casa*”, 4th edition, 2005, Editorial Gustavo Gili, SA, Barcelona
ISBN 84-252-1869-1

Nesbitt, Kate (editor) – ‘*Theorizing a new agenda for architecture: an anthology of architectural theory, 1965-1995*’, 1996, Princeton Architectural Press, New York
ISBN 1-56898-054

Portas, Nuno – ‘*A Habitação Social: proposta para a metodologia da sua arquitectura*’, 1st edition, 2004, Edições FAUP
ISBN 972-9483-63-9

Reichlin, Bruno, “*Figures of Neorealism in Italian Architecture (part 2)*”, ‘Grey Room 6’, Winter 2002, pp 110-133,

<http://mc1litvip.jstor.org/pss/1262617> [07.2008]

Schoenauer, Norbert – *‘6,000 Years of Housing, revised and expanded edition’*, W. W. Norton & Company, New York, NY 10110, 2000
ISBN 0-393-73052-2

Sherwood, Roger – *‘Modern Housing Prototypes’*, 7th Edition, 2001, Harvard University Press, Cambridge e London, England
ISBN: 0-674-57942-9

Teige, Karel – *“The Minimum Dwelling”*, 2002, The MIT Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts
ISBN 0-262-20136-4

Image References:

Fig. 1: <http://www.workhouses.org.uk/index.html?model/model.shtml> [10.2008]

Fig. 2: http://sv.wikipedia.org/wiki/Backstr%C3%B6m_%26_Reinius [08.2008]

Fig. 3: http://www.solna.se/templates/Page_solna_submenu____19758.aspx [09.2008]

Fig. 4: www.woonen.nl/woon_7/berg.htm [03.2009]

Fig. 5: <http://www.familjebostader.stockholm.se/menyer/nyttaonje/stadsvandra/pdf/farsta.pdf> [06.2008]

Fig. 6: http://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Andr%C3%A9_Lur%C3%A7at [07.2009]

Fig. 7: Floor plan drawings: author; Images: **Cambi, Di Sivo, Steiner** – *‘Viviendas en bloques alineados’*, 1992, Barcelona, Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A.
ISBN: 968-887-186-9

Fig. 8: http://www.flickr.com/photos/alexander_str/2479906699/ [08.2009];
http://www.archweb.it/dwg/arch_arredi_famosi/giuseppe_terragni/casa_fascio/casa_fascio_2d.htm [08.2009]

Fig. 9: <http://www.archi.fr/DOCOMOMO-FR/genes.htm> [07.2008]

Fig. 10: <http://euamoatirardecarabina.blogspot.com/2009/10/roma-cidade-aberta.html>
[08.2009]

Fig. 11: Floor plan drawings: author; Images: **Cambi, Di Sivo, Steiner** – *‘Viviendas en bloques alineados’*, 1992, Barcelona, Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A.

ISBN: 968-887-186-9

Fig. 12: Coelho, António Baptista; Coelho, Pedro Baptista – ‘Habitação de Interesse Social em Portugal, 1988-2005’, 2009, Livros Horizonte
ISBN: 978-972-24-1655-9

Fig. 13: Floor plan drawings: author

Fig. 14: <http://www.arquitextos.com.br/entrevista/decarlo/decarlo.asp> [08.2009]

Fig. 15: http://www.archinfo.it/home.php?_idnodo=192504&_archivio=1 [07.2008]

Fig. 16: <http://www.fondazionebrunozevi.it/19451954/frame2/pagine/manualearchitetto.htm>
[08.2009]

Fig. 17: <http://www.casadellarchitettura.it/monitor/d/progetto.asp?id=906> [08.2009]

Fig. 18: http://www.archinfo.it/home.php?_idnodo=192504&_archivio=1 [07.2008]

Fig. 19: Author's drawing

Fig. 20: <http://alluu.wordpress.com/> [08.2009]

THE MINIMUM CELL

Pedro F. Jorge

MINIMUM HOUSING STANDARDS

Interdisciplinary Themes

Interdisciplinary Themes

'The Minimum Cell – minimum housing standards: Minimum as Maximum'

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MENDING THE CITY FABRIC

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Identifying the City

Rule/Exception: The city defined by a constant that celebrates the difference: housing as its "rule". Void/Filling: The city as mass (rule), interrupted by its lack (exception); the "void" as a deviation of the "rule", but not of urbanity. Useful/Useless: "Rule" and "exception" as "useful" if they promote continuity in the urban fabric, and "useless" if they are opposed.

Past/Present

Continuous/Discontinuous: "continuity" as the transition between past and present; "Discontinuity" as the absence of transition. Typology/Model: To promote continuity is to use preexisting typologies; Typology as a search for a repertoire of solutions. General/Specific: New relationships with the street, new shapes, new housing cells, but not the total eradication of the original typology.

Utopia/Reality

Surroundings/Background: The object wants to be "city" and "rule": a gable or rafter, a urban typology. Shape/Content: In the "Gable Module" his longest facade is also the more important: it replaces a blind wall. It defines the "city" by its external image and everyday life that leads inside. Ethics/Cosmetics: The aesthetic solution as the Significant and Sign: their loss as Cosmetics with no Ethics.

Public Virtues/Private Vices

Feasibility: regulations, construction process and comfort factors; Private willingness and urban regulations.

Key words: city, housing, gable, typology.

Identifying the city

Debating the "city voids" implies, first of all, discussing the meaning of the term, in a multiple perspective: not only if a "void" should always be considered as an "absence", but also how it manifests itself in the city fabric. Being in its essence something empty, the "void" should not be seen as merely the absence of an "object", because the organism that we define as a "city" is not only made of tangible matter: it expands beyond the notion of "physical" and it implies values and perceptions that are not accounted in terms of

“matter”: the sign, the meaning and the significant, that, although projected in a physical medium, don’t result through a simple overlap of bricks.

The meaning of the “urban void” surpasses matter and shape, and includes a context that is also ideological and morphological, in a way that expresses its usefulness and it contributes to the creation of the “idea” that we have of the City:

- a. The void as “useful”, if it states the values of the city;
- b. The void as “useless” if it contradicts the logical sequence of the urban space, much beyond the mere use of physical space.

1. Rule/Exception

Identifying a city cannot be done through the exceptional elements that emerge, like the church, the fire station or the city hall, but by a wider set of values that allows us to codify the elements of the urban space in two opposite meanings: the “rule” and the “exception”.

The identification of a "whole" is done by a succession of "rules" that allow us to combine a set of elements under the same name. The “city” is thus an ensemble where “something” is often repeated, but it doesn’t exclude the

“Warped spaces”, plaster, 2007
Sérgio Vicente

The sequence of objects and the voids among them creates an urban scheme that is reinforced by the use of tiny human models that roam among the shapes, giving them scale but also significance. Thus the importance of the observer in the creation of an idea of “city”

presence of the "exception", highlighted by its unique character, but that wouldn’t be exceptional if the “rule” was absent.

Housing, in its use, shape and image, expressed in the most common typologies, can be assumed as the “rule” that is repeated. Public spaces (shapes or voids), used for leisure, contemplation or work, are the elements of “exception” of the “traditional city”. As such, the use of different architectural languages agrees with the functional differences carried out by various programs.

- a. As a mind puzzle, let’s refer to a practical example: Barcelona and Gaudi’s “Temple Expiatori de la Sagrada Família”. Is surely an exception, even more if we have a look on the Cerda’s city quarters, regular and ‘infinite’. But if the whole city of Barcelona was entirely constructed with sequences of the same temple, the “exception” would become a “rule”. In a common view, the city would still be an “exception”, although made uniquely of “rules”. But would it still be considered a “city”?

2. Void/Filling

Beside the functional types, we can also identify the "city" as a succession of built mass (the "rule"), and its absence (the "exception"). The "empty space" assumes a role of "rule deviation", but it can't be regarded as something of no value in the urban context.

Contextualizing it historically, the "European city" implies this perception: a nucleus defined by a defensive system, conditioned in growth, led to unregulated constructions (the "filling"), defining as "exceptional" the places where constructions are absent (the "void"), not only for its uniqueness (obtained with much sacrifice, since land was as expensive as it was rare) but also for its "useful" character (market places or parade ground) and symbolic virtues (a church's yard).

As such, in a city where the process of foundation and growth was different (sometimes, created from scratch, like Brasília) the assumption of "built" as the "rule" and "void" as the "exception" may be dubious as a principle. Such as in Modernist experiments, in which urban thinking were expressed as a reaction to the traditional city, or at least in its adaptability to the demands of contemporary use and enjoyment. In these cases, the power of the "void" is exceptionally higher, in comparison with the examples that we commonly have access in Europe, which grounded the criticism of the traditional city by thinkers of the above mentioned "movement".

"Rule/exception, filling/void", 2007
 Pedro Fonseca Jorge

Although these concepts of "filling" and "void" result of objective reasoning, they should not be considered as being merely rigid notions, quite

the contrary. Its occurrence as part of the city's definition does not mean that its presence (or absence) should be accepted uncritically. The constructed element and the absent one must be related to the city, in which they participate. A mere volume does not imply an immediate correlation to the other volumes that define the city, and open spaces must serve usefully its surroundings (for leisure, contemplation or sports). There are two parallel logics, and if an entity comes into contradiction by tampering the image, scale or implantation of other entities that define a "rule" of the city, we can say that the "usefulness" of that building or space is called into question because they are a "system" that is contrary to the urban space (and vice versa).

3. Useful/Useless

It's therefore understood that if "rule" and "exception" in "our" cities are defined as "filling" and "void", they do not always have a unique value. Meaning that the "filling", as well as the "void", fall into two categories, depending on their role in the establishment of an identifiable image of the "city": "useful", if they promote continuity, or "useless" if they establish themselves as interruptions.

As such, there's a new relation, in which "filling", far from a "rule", becomes the "exception" by its morphological futility: using a practical example, in a location where the "rule" is assumed by a row of buildings with a low density facing the street, a tower in the middle of that row, away from the street, won't be more than an "exception", "useless" in the design of the "city", although still a construction and so-called "filling". This is obviously an extreme example, as architectural and urban project involves a series of questions that sometimes need that controversial aspect to become functional.

In the consolidated city the "void" can be considered useful, born under precise circumstances that indicate the need for public activities, like markets, parks or playgrounds. They express their practical and at the same time playful character, a factor required for the mental health of the city residents. However the significance of "useful" is beyond the requirements of a physical activity. Certain "voids" in the consolidated city are intended to be "useless" as spaces of physical occupancy, assuming a character of representation, a memorial or urban art. The area takes its usefulness by the ideological meaning assigned to it, and the corporeal can't define this site as devoided of a specific function ... apart from being seen and sensed.

Thus, the real absence doesn't exist where there's lack of built volume, but when a logical sequence is interrupted by a flaw or a lack of a "tail-end".

Using again the previous example: a row of buildings, with an interruption, where the resulting empty space is just a glitch inserted between two warps or gables (some call it 'rafters'), without dignity or function. Not something useful in shaping the character of the area, not a square (or something similar) in which its nobility is manifested by its physical and functional utility, but also by a set of morphological characteristics, such as creating a dignifying elevation in close relationship with the public space. As a mere interruption, without the morphological care that is required, the "void", for its lack of "usefulness", will remain an "exception".

Past/present

*“Housing building in Barcelona”,
Spain*

Josep Llinás, 1992/1995

Photo by Bryan Boyer, 2007

<http://www.flickr.com/photos/bryan/1104727688/>

Llinás tries to solve here the same “gable” problem leaning two blocks against the blind façades of the contiguous buildings. It also features an indented third block in order to light the four meter wide street in old Barcelona

Ideally, the solution to the outcome of the shape contradiction between “useful”, “rule” and “exception” is a set of attitudes that, in general, are already in use.

Regarding the “filling”, legislation, properly conceived and properly implemented, is the largest example of control of construction in urban areas. Especially if has morphological features that suggest a legible “rule”, fully recognized and therefore whose maintenance is required. And, as the scale of this “problem”, if the general legislation is inadequate or poorly defined (a reference to rules based on very general situations and not in specific places), we must produce an approximation to the character of the concerned area, so that “that” place with “those features” will deliver continuity and not breakage.

By “useless emptiness”, at least in the example above, the passing time dictates what is, in most cases, the required solution. Meaning, in a very simplified version of the problem, the construction or reconstruction of something missing

using the legislated “rules” as described above.

However, it is curious how something that is a “rule” is likely to create so many “exceptions” and each more exceptional than others. Adding to the neglect of owners and legislators there are other causes, less controllable, but inexorable in the way it transforms the urban space: time, different eras that are marked by different types, which succeed and replace, not always in an harmonic way.

1. Continuous/Discontinuous

Ideally, the “city” (European, at least) grows in circular shape, where different times come in turn. A medieval heart, dense and intricate, expands its tentacles out of its “walls”, in a less densified way with more “breathable” area. In general, different characteristics which correspond, “roughly”, to different possibilities and different ideas related to town planning.

Ideally, it is so, but in practice the changes that are executed “in loco” are often not made in blank sheets, alias, they never are. If indeed the city grows to where it is possible to do so, in the direction of the “emptiness” that is still not urban, there are numerous experiments performed on places that are “inappropriate” to modern rules of salubrity, functionality and urban living.

Here we must distinguish between the different attitudes that try to adequate existing infrastructure to modern assumptions, or, by the contrary, try to undo these by promoting a total replacement in which the legacy of the preexisting shapes is the place of settlement. It is not denied the existence of intermediate ideologies, arising from, or adapted to specific situations (and not of general idealisms) but, extremism is necessary to illustrate what we want to communicate. "Time", for instance, heals a lot of things, especially extreme idealisms, where the most obvious examples are certain principles dear to Modern Architecture who did not admit the existence of traces of the past: they dictated the intention of scrapping the Oporto riverside (who was partially demolished but now rebuilt and classified as "World Heritage").

Old fabric is ripped up to create new crossings, open spaces are created for respite and recreation, based on the existing urban forms, but the result of these actions will be determined by the choice of one of the ideas above described, which will promote the continuation / transition between preexistences and new proposals, or, conversely, a clear break, formal and ideological, as a statement of a particular design (note that in "continuity" it is not intended any reference to formal and typological "pastiche").

2. Contiguity/Obliteration

"From rule to exception to rule", 2007
Pedro Fonseca Jorge

In these two words is summed up the principles above, always assuming that in any case, an intervention is essential to adapt old typologies to modern purposes.

Here we should make a parenthesis to explain what is meant by Type, which in this context is a definition of contents that group together similar Models. The Typology is not a form, a picture, something very specific. It was

born of the need to select and rank models for a particular study. Thus, the fact that certain types of buildings still have some validity in respect to their location, volume and aesthetic solution (here a typology based on formal rules), does not imply that the solutions used in the living cell still fit contemporary living in the same way. It concerns the living area, its functional distribution, the health of space through lighting and ventilation, etc., etc.. (an assessment based on typological functional aspects).

On the contrary, if the internal spaces of an house designed long ago can still be relevant (because although created for other purposes, it fits new purposes), the relationship between the building and the street, or the city in general, can be called into question by several reasons.

In the concept of "full / empty," what interests us are the relations established with the observer / user, in which the "public space" is what the eye can see. Thus, as already mentioned, the street is part of his journey throughout the city, of its field of vision, and as such, the user learns and assimilates the formal typologies based on principles of location, volume, configuration and aesthetics. From now on the term "Type" will be restricted to this meaning.

Different times require the use of different types that, ideally, would be built on a continuous, progressive, circular growth, and so on. But replacement happens, it's required and therefore the "problem" exists when two types coexist contiguously and they are adverse in the values that define them: misalignment, different heights, diverse formal solutions. If a typology is replacing another over time, it can be said that this "time" is the "cure" for this evil, in which a new Type obliterates the other. But this does not imply that the extinct typology is completely inappropriate or, equally important, that was not important in the design of an "old city", whose memory must be preserved. It's hypothetical functional mismatch is anuled by it's adequacy to a broader context in which memory is important (without implying melancholy). The building in extinction, whith a new "exceptional" character when before it had been a "rule", can accommodate new uses, new programs, new facilities.

3. General/Specific

"Blind gables/useless voids", Porto, 2005
Pedro Fonseca Jorge

Therefore, and because all this reasoning implies a development of scale that evolves from something large and general for a particular situation, we are already in a field in which we see before us a concrete situation of "survival of the species" in the traditional city. Take the single houses of privileged classes: once throughout the city, in areas that were in the past largely suburban, and presently in the heart of the city, as a result of growth and increased scale of built area, in density, and finally by the appropriation of space by "lesser" privileged classes.

To this process corresponds, of course, a replacement of the Types at all levels. New relationships with the street are experienced, different shapes are applied, and more functional solutions consistent with the new "tenants" are used rather than the previous types.

To the single isolated houses (typological similar to each other) with four facades, away from the street and exposing an image crafted according to the social standing of his owner, succeeds a multifamily home, developed in height, facing the street, with a different image enabled by the available smaller financial resources and by their tenants different status.

If there is a gradual replacement, more profitable in the exploitation of the available area, this does not mean that the "obliteration" of "original" Type is total: some models can survive, as was said above, and the previous "rule" turns to an "exception". However, in the adjacency of these different types, the real problem is not installed by the alleged typological inadequacy, but because the "contiguity" of species is assumed without a "shot" or a "tail end" that produces a transition between two very different types.

Examine the following situation: a street of reasonable size and with a certain nobility, crosses and separate these two types. You can even say that on both sides of this street there are two different "rules": on the left side the housing building, willing to face street and developed in height. On the other side, the single house, of contained height and separated from the street

"Blind gables/useless voids", Porto, 2005
Pedro Fonseca Jorge

through a wall and a garden area. In this situation the "contiguity" is resolved because there is a shot, a solution between the different types that you can often find in many urban contexts. It doesn't consist in mere "distance", personified here by a "street" (which has been classified as "useful void" when personifies the image of the city in general), where an absence is reflected in "transition".

The real punch line is produced in the presence of "elevations" or facades (and not a gable) on the opposed faces of the street whose confrontation is resolved through the use of the traditional vocabulary of the city. This vocabulary is not the presence of "windows", per se, but because both the "filling" and "void" find their justification in urban situations by communicating among themselves.

This "communication" is defined as a set of physical elements, sensory enjoyment and do not exhaust in the "elevation" as a formal element. As a mirror of "urban life", the facade offers the experience inside the house, and commerce shows the relationship between the "street" as a "perambulation" and a "useful void". The elevation, with all it implies, involves all areas of the city like a skin that justifies the presence and absence of form.

In comparison, adjacency between two contradictory types is the real lack: a blind gable, a lack of elevation that is manifested in the "absence of city". Being an absence, is a "void" and does nothing for the image of the city, its "useless." And its condition of "useless", requires solution.

Utopia/Reality

*“Rua do Teatro building”, Porto, Portugal
Eduardo Souto de Moura, 1992/1995*

*Photo by R. Silva, 2009
<http://www.flickr.com/photos/rsa150429/3730376705/>*

Souto Moura uses in is “own” building a typical solution taken from old downtown Porto, with shield-like black slates. The cosmetic quality of this solution is obvious... but was it always so? Was this in the past an ugly wall, like modern gables are? Is “Time” all forgiving?

they should be many. If we proceed to a more comprehensive monitoring of the scheme in which is included, his interest is diluted in its context: plot, street, city, and its obliteration will be consistent if a solution to the gable of the building does not exist (the same way that a wound is diluted).

1. Surroundings/Background

The architect, however he tries to verbalize, needs to express himself in shapes, where the "solution" becomes matter, and processes into an object. This excludes the immediate bonding of a "false façade or elevation" that mimics but doesn't replace, despite having been common practice throughout the history of architecture in the composition of various urban spaces (Michelangelo did it in the Capitol Square searching for a symmetry that however didn't deny urban values).

The object proposed will be the "summit" of a building row, which is a known urban typology, but that may not belong in the context of the "traditional city": here, the "street", as opposed to the "building", induces the shaping of a block as a form closed in itself. As such, the most common type of occupation of the plot is made in depth, with two elevations respectively

The gable, blind and ugly, which only time might add some quality (noting the slate escutcheon of the typical gable in Oporto, well employed in the Rua do Teatro building by Eduardo Souto de Moura) has a solution that seems obvious: constructing contiguously, filling with a new building the empty space between meant to be hidden gables. The reverse process, to replace the most recent Type with the most ancient, now the “exception”, it is more difficult and less consistent...

We cannot however deny that the “new exception” is devoided of interest: it consisted in a "rule", has consisted in the “city”, and had a striking presence. It is a memory, and important one to those who consider memory essential. And

oriented to the street and into the inner courtyard. One exception is the block corner, with two elevations to the street, and an interior solution which varies depending on the depth of the plot: the facade may be absent or may be multiplied in several plans (seeking solutions to overcome the construction depth). Even when, by whims of growth and development of the traditional city, a building offers a "gable" who wants to be a block "summit", it produces it a "light legged" solution, because, according to some, it was never created a solution for this situation (for its rarity), or, as others believe, because the traditional constructive supporting walls system made necessary a minimal intervention in a separating wall who now is a facade.

There are other situations of exception, but, truth be told, the "top" appears to us more clearly when the city begins a process of change based on the application of principles of Modernism. The isolated block (from other buildings, streets, corners, etc...) "creates" four elevations in (housing) buildings that, traditionally, only had two. The isolated house maintains its four elevations, while the traditional collective housing building slope their shoulders on its partners. Formalities aside, where the parallelepiped volume is devoid of judgments about its relationship with its surroundings, the block demands a "punch line", because their "less important facades" are also elevations: they move towards public space, even if the "street" is not the closest "void"

*“Santa Maria do Bouro Inn”, Bouro, Portugal
Eduardo Souto de Moura, 1992/1995*

Photo by G. Schmoll, 2008

<http://www.flickr.com/photos/gschmoll/2195934633/in/photostream/>

The reconstruction of the old ruined monastery was made under the intention of keeping the ruin, as this belonged to the present memory that everyone had of the building. Window frames were hidden, the roof is flat with plants on top to keep its ruin-look, etc. In fact, the original building, as excavations revealed, was blood red, and covered with 1,2 meters long glazed green tiles ... so, a short term memory was used, instead of a long term memory, in an absolute contrast with the general idea of local heritage (white stucco and small red tiles), who, if used, would produce a fake memory.

Thus, giving the fabric of a “traditional town” a solution brought from the “modern city” seems counter-intuitive, since there is a need to produce a relationship between the “subject” and “context”.

However, the “problem”, as pointed, is born in the traditional city, who is still a contemporary one: born of the confrontation of two “eras”, we can’t indicate which one is more correct. Some scholars advocate the use of “short term memory”, or shapes that are still present, even if distant in their creation.

Others use the “long term memory”, where research focuses memories hidden in disappeared architectural models.

The use of “typological study” should not be idealized as an assignment to an uncritical historicism. In essence, we search for solutions, investigate situations that correspond to a problem formulated by us: a solution to a wound in the urban fabric, by the search for "models" in similar contexts. Once the study is carried out, we are in the possession of various timeless solutions, in which we will find something to adapt to our problem. For example, in the current production of domestic architecture, some authors investigate the versatility of space, which can be occupied in various ways, as opposed to the legacy of modern functional utilitarianism. This "new" spatial solution is, in some cases, the pre-Modernist house, whose divisions were devoid of a specific function: public or private, day or night. A "traditional" solution solves a "contemporary" problem.

A "shot, summit or tail-end" is a "contemporary" solution, but it solves a "traditional" problem in the traditional city. As such, the typological study or more simply, the knowledge of History can be seen equally important in the architectural composition of the object, because the process is encyclopedic.

Shape/Content

This object must be “filled” with "city", manifesting itself as inhabited one.

And because “shape” requires “content”, the object which completes the gable is a building, something beyond a mere sculpture, by the need to experience space as it is required by architecture. The building asks for a "program", and the city requires functions that are in strict relation to the type of experience that, for example, describes the "street" as a "useful void": trade and housing.

This program, common in the city, will thus be applied to

something that is morphologically different: it is not a façade and not a block. It is a building, the narrowest possible, which fulfills the "gap" without overlapping the contiguous "exception".

Based in this assumptions (and the regulations in force at the time), it was created this "Top Module", a building with 3.90 meters in front of the street, but with about 17 meters deep, where the more extensive elevation is the most important. Precisely the one who opens into the lot, and replaces the gable, creating a space experienced by movements generate in the interior and transmitted to the exterior throughout its openings: light / shadow, open or closed, presence / absence.

These are the main principles: to deal with a "slice" of thin space. Everything else has to be changeable, adaptable to different circumstances because to different gables correspond different volumetries.

The building, although it is presented here as a finished project, is actually an abstract design based on a superposition of different modules designed according to a specific program. In this case, the ground floor is a commercial space that is oriented to the street and into the lot where the entrance to the housing floors is also made. Maintaining this pattern of entry, we can obliterate the commercial module, if the character of the street requires so.

The ground floor, for commerce, and hypothetically omitted, is composed by an open space store, developed in one, two, three floors, according to need and the street characteristics.

The proposed housing modules, conditioned by the compact dimensions of the building, follow the possibilities offered by them. Thus, it proposes a Studio with 36m², with the entrance made through the living/bedroom, giving access to an area of distribution / closet accessing bathroom and kitchen, directed into the lot and to the street: the contact between livable spaces and the public space must be preferential

Having opted for an "open space", probably the most profitable use of space, this solution also had an ideological root as it was sought to use a modular scheme adaptable in the organization of future schemes, while ensuring some privacy in the simultaneously use of the house by its tenants.

The second module are two One Bedroom apartments, who complement themselves, by sharing one floor for bedrooms and bathrooms, while the upper and lower floors stand for the common spaces of the individual T1s.

Thus, the third model is a Two Bedroom module, with two floors, with the public areas in the lower floor - living room and kitchen, with dimensions and distribution similar to the previous example. On the second floor are the bedrooms, interspersed by the bathroom. Obviously, one of the rooms complements the "street", the other "creates" a one within the plot. The dimensions remain contained, 72m², obtained by the sum of two modules of 36m².

A fourth module is a Three Bedroom which is characterized by the use of three floors, being the entrance a reproduction of the previous ones, occupied by a dining room, the kitchen, but adding a washing space. The lower level adds a small extra bathroom. It seems a curious option locating the dining room in the entrance area, but it allows the future use of the living

room as a fourth bedroom with minor adjustments. Finally the top floor reproduces the one present in the T2. The area is still contained, with a total of 108m².

These “small” areas reflect a kind of clientele who demands affordability and is willing to live in city cores, where the reported situations are. In fact, users referred to this type of proposal are important because they have to be consistent with the space proposed and the limitations to which it is subjected. Currently it has been made an effort to attract younger populations to the historic city centers (not exclusively the urban spaces referred), to fight housing desertification and aging population, and it is assumed that the same logic can be applied here: that the younger population, limited in budget, is willing to live with some restrains in terms of space in order to make the best of the dynamics of the city centers.

There is, no doubt, the possibility of creating new types, combining

different modules, but the basic idea remains: to create a set of circumstances that allow different overlaps. On the one hand, to adapt the building to the program conditions, on the other to respond to concrete situations, like the size of the contiguous building. So, the building can be composed by a series of similar modules, or with different ones, combining them in order to respond to demand and shape.

The attempt to make a realistic proposal meant that from the beginning it was considered a consistent constructive solution, as shown in the attached detail. Although there may be structural variants not covered, connected to the greater physical demands of a high building, the geological features of the land, the

*“Band-aid Building”,
section, 2005
Pedro Fonseca Jorge*

techniques and materials in use in the location, or the requirements of insulation, those exposed were designed for the possible making of this building. The composition of the walls had in mind the common thickness of a concrete structure, a simple brick wall covered in insulation and synthetic plaster (“economical” in terms of area, and consequently the width of the building). Internally, the carpentry applied, although simple in form and execution (extremely important to keep values within the proposed acquisition of restraint), were also the target of attention, and detail...

This did not mean that the formal solution was neglected, since space and aesthetics are closely connected in Architecture. If the depth of the building was designed in order to conciliate external dimensions and a quality interior space (plus the constructive system), this was never a deterrent to perform parallel search at the level of formal pleasantness. If the staircase meets the common rules that exist for size, number of steps in a flight of stairs and the existence of empty space in the middle (a fire department requirement), it was still possible to conceive a design in which the staircase is equally viewed from above or from low, because it has "steps" in the “ceiling” of the flights. That is, and referring us to something that covers all the architectural composition, “detail” is a quality factor for architecture in general, and not only in more "noble" projects (with all the subtlety that the use this term implies).

2. Ethics/Cosmetics

Therefore the formal solution to the presented building is a mere hypothesis, in the midst of other possibilities, as the combination of modules (multiplied by the number of floors) allows.

The aesthetics of the presented elevations meets the same criteria, meaning they are not rigid solutions and can be worked according to the surroundings (within the possibilities offered by the internal distribution). The example used, the "urban wound" (the gable), was based on a hypothetical relationship between two different types with equal importance within the historical surroundings. It is assumed that the reference to this aesthetic solution is the contemporary block, but in fact there are other situations where history will have more weight on the appearance of the building.

The question of intervening in "architectural heritage" has held several ideas, at the same time or separated by a period of time caused by the diversity of dominant architectural theories. However, the contemporary consensus identifies the need to make the differentiation of interventions distant in time, in the sense that each one is the result of his era, although integrating the new

with the old. It is denied therefore a reproduction of an original building, because it would be a historical untruth.

However, this approach is a “Pandora’s box” to many very personal opinions, so many as the authors charged with architectural heritage intervention. We can identify two extreme theories in order to facilitate reasoning: there are cases where the distinction is minor, although existing, as tile, stone or plaster resources are still used today, or, by contrast, a greater distinction is made, were the relationship between the old and the new is done by smaller elements, such as deployment or volume.

*“Gable Building”, Sevilla, Spain
2009*

Photo by Sebastiano Rossi

How utopian is this proposal? Isn't it present in other ancient and modern solutions in order to solve similar/different problems? And isn't it Typology an investigation process as any other? Does it have to be a mere “pastiche” of an ancient building?

capable to identify the qualitative aspects of a work of art.

And maybe here is showed the true virtuosity of the artist, but the fact is that it also makes way to the replacement of a pictorial art by orality or writing: the work itself is supported only in speech, not in its intrinsic value. And speech, reversing the process of "idealization / composition", may in fact be an attempt to justify a form born of a purely aesthetic and static appreciation (not using the dynamics of the environment in their manufacture), which we can't identify because we do not have the elements that allow us to recognize and classify "art".

As far as we are concerned, this relates to the attitude of "our" building: integrated with respect to form and image, or assuming its opposition, strengthening the character of the contemporary element that solves the problem expressed, irrespective of the location to which it is intended.

Far from being obvious this question deeper roots, it is based on something I call as the "art defining" elements, or in other words, the elements we can trust to define a particular object or action as art: Virtuosity, Sign and Meaning.

One of the first items to "fall" was the technical and expressive virtuosity in the sense that rigor and reality were dominant themes on the represented subject. Abstraccionism, perhaps based on the possibilities offered by other ways of capturing reality (like photography) has introduced another dynamic to art, but continued to emphasize Sign, or the referred object.

Contemporary art uses other resources to make more or less obvious allusions to the "Sign". To the observer only “Meaning” remains as something

This is a “simplistic” argument, because its exploitation would require another presentation, but it defends the return of art to more figurative ways, as opposed to “total abstraction”, unachievable for most observers.

Therefore, and because architecture remains an art, and its observers are widespread, it is intended that this building, far from being a unique landmark, easily identifiable, regardless of their location (whether in Lisbon or in Oporto, whether in Portugal or France), should therefore “fit in” within the surrounding reality, because its purpose is to mend the urban fabric and not adding another dissonant element. The identification with the image for other buildings that surround it (as they constitute a “rule”) is necessary, thus reinforcing the idea that the “finished” building, as presented in the attached proposal, is only one possibility among many others. You may ask about the relevance of diversity based on “epidermis”, and many may nickname this proposal as mere “elevation imagery”. But typological research does not necessarily mean investigating “Space” or “Form”, as aesthetics is also an architectural theme. At a time that certain types of buildings become obsolete, for present living requirements, one cannot deny the possibility that, once inserted into a well-defined mesh, the building will integrate in to the surrounding imagery, just because it does not in its internal space.

Public Virtues/Private Vices

*“Band-aid Building”, as it was presents in the “Unbuilt Architecture” contest, promoted by the “Boston Society of Architects, 2005
Pedro Fonseca Jorge*

Though abstract, this building was designed based on regulations, construction details and real factors of comfort. That is, something that you can build without any major dramas. The main obstacle to its application is therefore not the object, but the urban regulations requiring the use of this solution and the willingness of the owner to use it.

We are aware that there are ways of making a more profitable use of land, including opting for a long and high building, instead of just proposing

clogging blind gables in the surrounding buildings. Part of the solution involves the identification of heritage buildings, something that is already done in urban planning, and requires the "reuse" of preexisting historic buildings or spaces. The construction of the gables is offered as something more relevant, although conditioning the construction of the whole front. Also, rationally speaking, a building with one apartment per floor served by a stairwell and an elevator is not the most profitable type.

The desire to "mend" the city is not only expressed in public will, as the private has to have a say, since it is its domain that is involved in most cases. Regulating, identifying places where this typology can be applied, as architectural heritage is identified, is a complex and difficult process, given the particularity of each "exception". Here resides, probably, the real utopia.

Panel conceived for the "**Unbuilt Architecture**" contest, promoted by the Boston Society of Architects, 2005
Pedro Fonseca Jorge

Contrary to the current debate over the city and ways of intervening in it, here is offered a "surgical procedure" that it cannot be done without intervening in a larger scale, as it was said above. We can include in this procedure interventions made locally in public spaces like gardens or town squares, but, for once, the force behind this proposal is to consider private space as public, not only in a "skin deep" process (like regulating or recuperating facades), but also in space inside the plot, as long it is visible to the spectator.